

**Intra-organisational communication challenges in the automobile
industry: the case of atlas Honda, Pakistan**

A thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland as part of the Doctor of Business
Administration degree requirements.

By

Muhammad Shoaib

B00321542

Date of Submission

14/06/2021

Declaration

I, hereby, make the declaration that this research is a piece of my own work and I have properly referenced any other sources of work that I have used in this research. I also declare that the sources, published, unpublished or online, from which this research took reference or quoted, have been properly cited within the work and a full-text reference for these sources has also been added in the research.

Signature.....

Personal details withheld.

Date.....14/06/2021.

Acknowledgement

I begin by extending my deepest gratitude to my supervisor, without whose supervision and support this research would not have been possible. I would also like to thank all my friends and colleagues who were with me at every step of this research. These are the people who made it possible for me to understand this program better and put my best foot forward while conducting this research.

Last but not the least, wholesome gratitude to my family. Thank you for supporting me and for being by my side all along this journey. I cannot imagine myself completing this piece of research without your understanding and encouragement.

ABSTRACT

The main aim of the research under consideration is the identification and assessment of the main intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan. This involves a detailed discussion and elaboration of factors that are involved in intra-organisational communication. The automotive sector occupies a critical role in the economy of any region. Its significant contributions to the economy involve the generation of income, exports and employment, which all contribute to economic stability. Such significance of the automotive sector has led towards extensive research on policies, issues, practices and development (with the aim of improving operational effectiveness). One of the key factors that add to the effectiveness of the automotive sector, as seen from the developed economies, is the presence of effective intra-organisational communication structures.

To attain the aim in the proposed study, the research relies on quantitative methods based on the positivism philosophy to analyse the major intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan. Data collection has involved the selection of a sample, based on 350 individuals from Atlas Honda, an automotive sector organisation based in Pakistan. Additionally, even though Atlas Honda is headquartered in Karachi, it has operations across the country, with manufacturing and assembly taking place in other areas like Sheikhpura. Since workers from both these locations have been targeted, a decent representation of the entire workforce is ensured. Quantitative information to support data analysis and hypothesis testing is obtained with the help of a research questionnaire. Analysis of the information has been collected using IBM SPSS Multiple techniques is used, with regression and correlation forming the basis of hypothesis testing, while descriptive statistics and reliability testing contribute to the robustness of the analytical model used. The research has used secondary qualitative information for supporting, explaining and elaborating the results of primary analysis and helping in the synthesis of findings

The gaps present in the existing literature about intra-organisational communication, as well as its significance intra-organisational to a firm's performance, makes it necessary to evaluate it in the context of the automotive sector of Pakistan. The findings of this study indicated that intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan is faced with a number of challenges. These challenges stem from the industry characteristics and their relationships with intra-organisational communication. In addition, broader factors, like the generalised lack of resources in Pakistan or the impacts of the country's culture on managerial practices, often signify the challenges at hand.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Declaration.....	ii
Acknowledgement.....	iii
Abstract.....	iv
List of tables.....	xii
List of figures.....	xiv
Chapter One: Introduction	1
1.0. Introduction to the Study	1
1.1. Background to the Study	3
1.2. Problem Statement.....	6
1.3. The Aims and Objectives of the Study	8
1.4. Research Questions.....	9
1.5. Significance of the Study.....	9
1.6. Approaches to the Study	10
1.6.1. Theoretical Approach	10
1.6.2. Methodological Approach	11
1.7. Definitions of Key Concepts Used	11
1.8. Structure of the Thesis	12
1.9. Summary.....	13
Chapter Two: Literature Review	14
2.1. Introduction	14
2.2. Communication- An Overview	14
2.3. Intra-organisational Communication	16
2.4. Theories and Modern Practices in Intra-organisational Communication...	16
2.4.1. Rational Choice Theory.....	17
2.4.2. Social Exchange Theory	17
2.4.3. The Strategic Theory	18
2.4.4. Theories of Motivation	18

2.4.5.	New media.....	20
2.5.	Need for Intra-organisational Communication.....	24
2.5.1.	Intra-organisational Communication and Firm Performance.....	27
2.5.2.	Intra-organisational Communication and Employee Performance/ Engagement	29
2.5.3.	Intra-organisational Communication and Integration.....	31
2.6.	Automobile Industry of Pakistan.....	32
2.6.1.	Pakistan’s automobile sector- an overview	33
2.6.2.	The sector- structure, changes and modifications	34
2.6.3.	Major organisations operating in the sector	37
2.7.	Comparison between intra-organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan and other Economies of the World	38
2.8.	Intra-organisational Communication in International Automobile Sector .	47
2.8.1.	Germany	51
2.8.2.	United Kingdom	53
2.8.3.	United States of America.....	54
2.8.4.	India.....	55
2.8.5.	South Africa.....	55
2.8.6.	Italy.....	57
2.8.7.	Japan	58
2.8.9	Pakistan.....	59
2.9.	Key Challenges of Intra-Organisational Communication	60
2.9.1.	The complexity of Big Data Analytics	60
2.9.2.	Lack of Focus on the Personal Goals of Workers	62
2.9.3.	Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	65
2.9.4.	Lack of Innovative Mechanisms.....	69
2.9.5.	Low Levels of Internal Branding.....	73

2.9.6.	Lack of Technology.....	78
2.9.7.	Ineffective Payment and Reward Systems	82
2.10.	Research Gap.....	86
2.11.	Conceptual Framework.....	91
2.12.	Chapter Summary	93
Chapter Three: Research Methodology.....		95
3.1.	Chapter Introduction.....	95
3.2.	Research Philosophy.....	96
3.2.1.	Theory.....	96
3.2.2.	Chosen Research Philosophy.....	97
3.3.	Research Approach.....	98
3.3.1.	Theory.....	98
3.3.2.	Chosen Research approach.....	99
3.3.3.	Rationale.....	99
3.4.	Research Design	101
3.4.1.	Theory.....	101
3.4.2.	Chosen Research Design	101
3.4.3.	Rationale.....	103
3.5.	Research Strategy	104
3.5.1.	Theory.....	104
3.5.2.	Chosen Research Strategy	104
3.5.3.	Rationale.....	105
3.6.	Research methods.....	107
3.7.	Pilot Study	109
3.8.	Population of the research	110
3.8.1.	Selection of sampling technique.....	110
3.8.2.	Sampling size.....	114

3.8.3.	Random Sampling in the Current Study.....	115
3.9.	Data Collection Methods and Procedures	115
3.9.1.	Validity and Reliability	115
3.9.2.	Primary Sources of Data Gathering.....	116
3.9.3.	Responses	117
3.10.	Data analysis techniques.....	118
3.11.	Ethics Approval	119
3.12	Summary.....	119
Chapter Four: Data Analysis.....		120
4.1.	Overview of the Chapter.....	120
4.2.	Reliability Analysis	121
4.3.	Descriptive Analysis – Frequency Distribution.....	121
4.3.1.	Gender of the Respondents.....	121
4.3.2.	Age of the Respondents.....	122
4.3.3.	Education of the Respondents	122
4.3.4.	Department of the Respondents.....	123
4.3.5.	Employment Status of the Respondents	123
4.3.6.	The company confronts no issues in the management of large amounts of employee related data	124
4.3.7.	The company has the technology that can allow for the facilitation of data management	124
4.3.8.	Complexity of Data Analysis	125
4.3.9.	The company consults the employees at the time of creation of job descriptions	125
4.3.10.	There are ample opportunities for effective training and development of the employees	126
4.3.11.	The company has a rigorous and prompt system for the management of employee grievances.....	126

4.3.12.	Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	127
4.3.13.	I have sufficient levels of liberty and autonomy when it comes to performing my job	127
4.3.14.	Each employee has the responsibility of ensuring the quality of his job .	127
4.3.15.	I have sufficient information about the processes for communicating across the overall organisation.....	128
4.3.16.	Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	128
4.3.17.	The company has online portal that connects all the employees.....	129
4.3.18.	The company arranges events that allow for the socialization of the employees	129
4.3.19.	Lack of Innovative Mechanisms.....	130
4.3.20.	The company allows for the development of career aspirations of the employees	130
4.3.21.	The company has a sound and satisfactory internal environment	130
4.3.22.	I am always recognized for my performance and hard work	131
4.3.23.	Low Levels of Internal Branding.....	131
4.3.24.	The company is well equipped with the modern-day cloud technology ..	132
4.3.25.	The company has expertise in the advanced communication software....	132
4.3.26.	The company keeps itself updated on the modern technologies used for internal organisational communication.....	133
4.3.27.	Lack of Technology.....	133
4.3.28.	I am provided with market competitive pay rates	134
4.3.29.	My bonuses are satisfactory and performance based	134
4.3.30.	Good performance is always recognized through promotions	135
4.3.31.	Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	135
4.3.32.	The company has an exhaustive communication system in place.....	136
4.3.33.	All the information is transmitted to all the employees in a timely manner	136

4.3.34.	The cross functional teams are provided with effective platforms of communications.....	137
4.3.35.	Overall, I know how to reach each and every relevant member of the company	137
4.3.36.	We have effective formal as well as informal chains of internal communication.....	137
4.3.37.	Communication System.....	138
4.4.	Descriptive Analysis - Descriptive	138
4.5.	Correlation Analysis	140
4.6.	Regression Analysis	143
4.7.	Hypothesis Summary Table.....	146
4.7	Summary.....	148
Chapter Five: Discussion.....		151
5.1.	Chapter Introduction.....	151
5.2.	Key Factors Affecting Intra-Organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan	151
5.3.	Barriers and Challenges Associated with Intra-organisational Communication.....	157
5.3.1.	Complexity of Big Data Analytics	158
5.3.2.	Lack of Focus on the Personal Goals of Workers	167
5.3.3.	Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	171
5.3.4.	Lack of Innovative Mechanisms.....	179
5.3.5.	Low Levels of Internal Branding.....	187
5.3.6.	Lack of Technology.....	193
5.3.7.	Ineffective Payment and Reward Structures	200
5.4.	Chapter Summary	206
Chapter Six: Conclusion, Recommendations, and Contributions.....		208
6.1.	Chapter Introduction.....	208

6.2.	Overview of the Research.....	208
6.3.	Outcomes of Hypotheses Tested	210
6.4.	Contributions of the Study.....	213
6.4.1.	Theoretical Contributions	213
6.4.2.	Practical Contributions.....	214
6.4.3.	Policy Contributions	215
6.5.	Recommendations of the Study	216
6.5.1.	Recommendations for Atlas Honda Pakistan and Other Automotive Sector Companies.....	216
6.5.2.	Recommendations for Policy-Making Authorities in Pakistan	217
6.6.	Limitations of the Study	217
6.7.	Recommendations for Future Research.....	218
6.8.	Managerial Implications	219
	References.....	221
	Appendix A.....	254
	Intra-Organisational Communication Challenges IN THE Automobile Industry: THE CASE of Atlas Honda, Pakistan	254
	Appendix B	257
	Intra-Organisational Communication Challenges IN THE Automobile Industry: THE CASE of Atlas Honda, Pakistan	257
	Appendix C	258
	Appendix D.....	262
	Pilot Testing Results	262
	Reliability Test.....	262
	Correlations.....	263
	Summary of the Pilot Testing	265

List of tables

Table 1.1: Structure of the Study

Table 2.1: Tools for integrated communications

Table 2.2: Models of the Communicative Constitution of the Organisation

Table 2.3: Key Players in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Table 2.4: Summary of Themes Observed Across the Literature

Table 4.1: Case Processing Summary

Table 4.2: Reliability Analysis- Cronbach's Alpha

Table 4.3: Gender of the Respondents

Table 4.4: Age of the Respondents

Table 4.5: Education of the respondents

Table 4.6: Department of the respondents

Table 4.7: Employment status of the respondents

Table 4.8: The company confronts no issues in the management of large amounts of employee-related data

Table 4.9: The company has the technology that can allow for the facilitation of data management

Table 4.10: Complexity of Data Analysis

Table 4.11: The company consults the employees at the time of the creation of job descriptions

Table 4.12: There are ample opportunities for effective training and development of the employees

Table 4.13: The company has a rigorous and prompt system for the management of employee grievances

Table 4.14: Lack of Focus on Personal Goals

Table 4.15: I have sufficient levels of liberty and autonomy when it comes to performing my job

Table 4.16: Each employee has the responsibility of ensuring the quality of his job

Table 4.17: I have sufficient information about the processes for communicating across the overall organisation

Table 4.18: Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement

Table 4.19: The company has an online portal that connects all the employees

Table 4.20: The company arranges events that allow for the socialization of the employees

Table 4.21: Lack of Innovative Mechanisms

Table 4.22: The company allows for the development of career aspirations of the employees

Table 4.23: The company has a sound and satisfactory internal environment

Table 4.24: I am always recognized for my performance and hard work

Table 4.25: Low Levels of Internal Branding

Table 4.26: The company is well equipped with the modern-day cloud technology

Table 4.27: The company has expertise in the advanced communication software

Table 4.28: The company keeps itself updated on the modern technologies used for internal organisational communication

Table 4.29: Lack of Technology

Table 4.30: I am provided with market competitive pay rates

Table 4.31: My bonuses are satisfactory and performance-based

Table 4.32: Good performance is always recognized through promotions

Table 4.33: Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure

Table 4.34: The company has an exhaustive communication system in place

Table 4.35: All the information is transmitted to all the employees in a timely manner

Table 4.36: The cross-functional teams are provided with effective platforms of communications

Table 4.37: Overall I know how to reach each and every relevant member of the company

Table 4.38: We have effective formal as well as informal chains of internal communication

Table 4.39: Communication System

Table 4.40: Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.41: Correlation analysis

Table 4.42: Coefficients of correlation and significance level for the independent variables

Table 4.43: Model summary for regression analysis – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

Table 4.44: ANOVA table for regression analysis – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

Table 4.45: Coefficients of regression analysis – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

Table 4.46: Hypothesis summary table – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

List of figures

- Figure 2.1: Trends in Automobile Sales in Pakistan
- Figure 2.2: Trends in Profitability of Automotive Sector Companies in Pakistan
- Figure 2.3: Changes to Level of Difficulty in the Loan Process for Purchasing Automobiles in Pakistan
- Figure 2.4: Challenges in the Development of Big Data in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan
- Figure 2.5: Two-Way Communication that Underpins Efficacy of Intra-Organisational Communication
- Figure 2.6: Intra-organisational Communication and Personal Development Goals
- Figure 2.7: Managerial Emphasis and Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.8: Intra-organisational Communication and Employee Engagement
- Figure 2.9: Employee Engagement and Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.10: The Need for Innovation in Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.11: The Impacts of Low Innovation on Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.12: The Impacts of Intra-organisational Communication on Innovation in Companies
- Figure 2.13: Lack of Innovative Mechanisms and Challenges to Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.14: The Relationship between Intra-organisational Communication and Internal Branding
- Figure 2.15: Emphasis on Internal Branding and its Impact on Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.16: The Challenge Emerging from Low Levels of Internal Branding
- Figure 2.17: The Impacts of Technology on Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 2.18: Intra-organisational Communication and its Role in Payment and Reward Systems
- Figure 2.19: The Intra-organisational Communication Issues Stemming from Low Significance of Employee Engagement
- Figure 2.20: Conceptual Framework
- Figure 5.1: Resources, Culture and Challenges to Intra-organisational Communication
- Figure 5.2: Lack of Resources and Ineffectiveness of Communication
- Figure 5.3: The Role of Cultural Factors in Challenges to Intra-organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Figure 5.4: The factors underpinning barriers and challenges associated with intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Figure 5.5: The major issues surrounding big data analytics in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Figure 5.6: Big data analytics and challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Figure 5.7: Complexity of big data analytics and challenges to intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.8: Complexity of big data analytics and ineffective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Figure 5.9: Big Data Analytics and Pressure on the Intra-organisational Communication System

Figure 5.10: Two-way communication between workers and the management in an organisation

Figure 5.11: The role of intra-organisational communication in fulfillment of personal goals

Figure 5.12: The role of training and performance evaluation in fulfillment of personal goals

Figure 5.13: Focus on employee engagement and the need for stronger intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.14: Lack of focus on employee engagement and its negative impact on the need for intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.15: The lack of focus on employee engagement and challenges to intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.16: The bi-directional relationship between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.17: Lack of focus on employee engagement and ineffective intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.18: The Interplay between employee engagement, intra-organisational communication and cultural considerations in Pakistan

Figure 5.19: The Impact of Innovative Mechanism on Effectiveness of Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.20: The Three Facets of Innovative Mechanisms' Impact upon Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.21: The Negative Influence of a Lack of Innovative Mechanisms on Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.22: The Impacts of Intra-organisational Communication on Innovation within the Company

Figure 5.23: Intra-organisational communication, knowledge transfer and innovation in the company

Figure 5.24: The Two-Way Impact of a Lack of Innovative Mechanisms on Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.25: The Negative Impacts of Lack of Innovative Mechanisms on Intra-organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Figure 5.26: The Relationship between Internal Branding and Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.27: The Varying Roles of Intra-organisational Communication in Internal Branding

Figure 5.28: The Factors Linking Low Levels of Internal Branding with Ineffective Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.29: Lack of Technology and Ineffective Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.30: Lack of Technology and Low Quality of Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.31: Supportive technology and the effects of intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.32: Supportive technology and the improvement of intra-organisational communication

Figure 5.33: Ineffective Payment and Reward Structures and Ineffective Intra-organisational Communication

Figure 5.34: The Negative Impacts of Ineffective Payment and Reward Structures on Intra-organisational Communication

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.0. Introduction to the Study

The proposed study has been entitled Intra-organisational communication challenges in the automobile industry: the case of atlas Honda, Pakistan. With reference to Meyer (2018) study, it is found that intra-organisational communication is a method of face-to-face communication that can lead to a better understanding of robust processes developed for individual customers and to a greater diffusion of these new processes to other clients. Rather than disconnecting customers who would like to have employees implanted, these implants can be a valuable source of information and process improvement that can have a positive impact on a company's customer network. It relates to formal communication in organisations that take place among members of an organisation for the sake of attaining quality results. In addition, intra-organisation assists in making all steps and procedures clear. The likelihood of ambiguities, risks, and uncertainties are on a minimal level. Hence, intra-organisational communication means that the connection, collaboration, coordination, and collocation within the organisation so that aim, objectives, mission, vision can be obtained adequately. For example, amid diverse teams, or among levels in the hierarchy.

The automotive sector is among the most important industries across the globe. Not only have vehicle ownership and the automotive culture gained ground over the past 100 years across the world, but the automotive sector has also become significant from an economic perspective too (Mohr et al., 2013). In various countries and regions, the importance of the automotive sector has been demonstrated by researchers. In the European Union (EU), for instance, the automobile industry has been found to account for a 7% share in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), 5% share in total employment generation and a substantial proportion of exports (Vošta and Kocourek, 2017). Similarly, in the United States, the automotive sector has been considered to be one of the most developed industries, as well as chief contributors to economic growth, employment and GDP (Naeem, 2017). Even though the significance of the automotive industry is widely accepted by researchers and institutions alike, emphasis has been placed largely on developed economies. The automotive sector of the United States remains the most widely studied because the first mass-production automotive companies originated in the country (Jacobides, MacDuffie and Tae, 2016).

The disparity in research regarding automotive sectors implies that the Pakistani industry has not been subject to extensive study and exploration. In Khan (2011), it is revealed that specific details of the automotive sector are sparsely studied in the existing literature, supporting the notion being made here. The lack of formal research on the automotive sector in Pakistan, therefore, presents a need for focusing on the country. The sector does have the potential to occupy an important position in the country. According to Mustafa et al. (2018), Pakistan's automotive sector is a moderate contributor to the country's GDP and employment at present, but because of the presence of barriers to growth, it has stagnated the development of the industry. In addition to that, Naeem (2017) reveals that the current contribution of the automotive sector to Pakistan's GDP is 2.8%, which is expected to increase to 5.6% by 2022. Obviously, this shows that the importance of the automotive sector is certainly increasing in Pakistan, presenting another reason for research work to be focused on it.

Communication is an extremely important aspect of the business world. In Coffelt, Baker and Corey (2016), communication skills— whether oral, written or electronic—have been termed important by employers, demonstrating the significance given to communication in the business environment. Zerfass and Viertmann (2017) also state that corporate communication plays an important role in value generation in organisations, since the potential of ventures, projects, or activities cannot be impressed upon decision-makers or stakeholders without effective communication. Even more specifically, Ahmet (2015) points out that intra-organisational communication is an important factor affecting business success, such that the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication is directly and positively tied with a firm's success. Such notions illustrate the significance of communication—and more specifically, intra-organisational communication—for *all* businesses, not just organisations in the automotive sector (or the automobile industry of Pakistan, which is targeted in the current study). It can, therefore, be argued that intra-organisational communication is an important construct in business and challenges relevant to it could slow down performance in organisations. With this topic not being explored in detail for the automotive sector, particularly that of Pakistan (and keeping in view the importance of the sector from an economic viewpoint, as well as its future potential), there are visible and important gaps in the literature that are to be targeted in this study.

In this chapter, the context of this research is discussed further, with emphasis on its aims, objectives, and significance. The structure of this study and the approach used is also outlined in this chapter, with a focus on how research objectives will be met.

1.1. Background to the Study

Maintaining high performance in the automotive sector has become a daunting prospect, owing to the challenges that have emerged in the external environment. Companies are faced with a wide variety of challenges ranging from climate change (Gopal and Thakkar, 2016) and deviation in consumer behaviour (De Stefano, Montes-Sancho and Busch, 2016) to overall volatility, uncertainty, and competitiveness in the industry (Bolman and Deal, 2015; Sarkar, 2016). In particular, changing preferences of consumers in the automotive sector have led to negative impacts on sales and the popularity of conventional products, resulting in threats to organisational performance, as well as survival (Buerke et al., 2017; Cojuharenco, Cornelissen and Karelaia, 2016).

Under continuous pressure to preserve performance in these challenging conditions, organisations have been pushed to look for a means of enhancing operational effectiveness. Among other factors, intra-organisational communication has emerged as a key factor for increasing the performance of companies. Ahmet (2015) suggested that intra-organisational communication positively impacts company performance, while Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa (2019) link it with knowledge management. Knowledge management, on the other hand, is associated positively with innovation and performance (as pointed out by Kianto (2011), Taherparvar, Esmaeilpour and Dostar (2014) and López-Nicolás and Meroño-Cerdán (2011)).

Even though the improvement of intra-organisational communication could result in improved performance, the use of this strategy remains limited because of the presence of important barriers. Freitag and Trebecki (2012) reveal that efforts to improve communication in the automotive sector are rebuked by the presence of diversity in the workforce, as well as deficiencies in communication skills. Moreover, given Duthler and Dhanesh (2018)'s idea that diversity management is tied with the engagement of workers (which itself is key to internal communication), it is evident that diversity in the workforce and the absence of strong communication skills lead towards barriers to effective intra-organisational communication.

As intra-organisational communication is positively associated with organisational performance (Ahmet, 2015), and challenges to intra-organisational communication limit its

efficacy, it could be argued that such challenges can have negative impacts on the performance of companies. This assertion is valid for the automotive sector of Pakistan, owing to the presence of additional challenges to intra-organisational communication. Saleem (2015) shows that the automotive sector of Pakistan is far less developed than those in more developed parts of the world, such as in Japan. Any access, therefore, to tools, systems, or infrastructures of communication that encourage intra-organisational communication is minimal. This creates challenges for automotive sector companies in the country as they set out to improve intra-organisational communication. Nevertheless, it is incorrect to assume that automotive companies in the developed world do not face intra-organisational communication challenges merely due to the availability of resources.

Moreover, Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014), Dremel et al. (2017) and Mani, Agrawal and Sharma (2015) shed light on the inability of automotive sector organisations in developed countries to make the most of information systems and communication technology. This means that even after the availability of resources and information systems, automotive companies in developed countries struggle to improve their intra-organisational communication frameworks. From this, it follows that with an automotive sector that lags behind the more developed nations, these challenges are more amplified for Pakistan.

In addition to that, cultural factors in Pakistan create barriers to effective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector. This factor has not been discussed by researchers indirect relevance to the automotive industry, but implications can be drawn from other sectors and related disciplines. Taken together, the works of Mazzei (2018) and Quratulain et al. (2018) show that power distance is a defining factor in the Pakistani culture, which means that hierarchies are strong and clearly defined. It is, therefore, difficult for workers separated by their posts or roles to share two-way communication channels that allow for a seamless exchange of information. Obviously, this is a limiting factor for intra-organisational communication in the automotive industry.

In addition to that, Saleem (2015) is of the opinion that automotive companies in Pakistan do not emphasize rewarding workers and acknowledging their performance. The consequence of this deficiency is that the engagement of workers remains low, which also contributes to the low quality of intra-organisational communication in the country's automotive sector. This

view is supported in the work of Verčič and Vokić (2017), as well as Verčič, Verčič and Sriramesh (2012) who demonstrate employee engagement to be closely associated with the quality of intra-organisational communication. Obviously, this implies that the culture of companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan hinders intra-organisational communication, presenting a significant challenge in this regard. Furthermore, Sarwar et al. (2012) point out that the automotive sector of Pakistan does not rely on innovative channels of communication or technology to support the transmission of information. Studies such as McGrattan (2015) and Welch (2011) show that in developed nations, like the United Kingdom (UK) and the United States of America (USA), blogs, dedicated platforms, and social media are relied upon to support intra-organisational communication. The absence of these tools in the Pakistani industry implies that the barriers to intra-organisational communication are particularly high.

From the aforementioned discussion, it is clear that the automotive sector of Pakistan is shrouded in challenges associated with intra-organisational communication, ranging from the absence of resources to develop multi-modal communication systems to cultural barriers and low emphasis on employee engagement/ career development. In addition, Abdullah Kader and Johannesson (2019) has defined the term multi-modal communication that Multi-Modal Communication has been considered as a simple terminology that is used for the sake of describing all the diverse ways that can be used and are considered beneficial for sake of communicating with each other, every day. This may be via texting, spoken language, emailing, tweeting, body language, handwriting, as well as gesturing, or by using a communication device. When individuals have difficulty and issues in communicating orally, use alternative methods, it is classified as Augmented and Alternative Communication (AAC) usually, which includes all the above modalities as well as a few other methods. Multimodal approach, therefore, is considered an effective technique, which assists the cohorts to communicate with each other with the help of alternatives so that ambiguity, risk, issues, and uncertainties that could affect the business courses and procedures may not get affected and quality outcomes such as success, competitive edge, productivity, and similar other facets can be obtained easily.

A key observation here is that the existing literature on the topic does not pay attention to the specific challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. While a few researchers have certainly pointed out factors like the lack of innovation, absence

of resources, cultural barriers or poor emphasis on employee engagement, they have not been discussed specifically in the context of the automotive sector. Moreover, the studies that do focus on the automotive sector of Pakistan do not provide a holistic review and analysis of challenges that are present in the industry. With the absence of research that outlines and elaborates factors that can hinder intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector, there exists ample room for studies focusing on the topic. Thus, the research under consideration focuses on providing a holistic assessment and discussion of the intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan.

1.2.Problem Statement

The main problem that is addressed by the research under consideration is the problems that the Pakistani automotive sector faces with respect to intra-organisational communication, their origin, and any possible means to tackle them in the future.

Intra-organisational communication has been deemed as a beneficial, if not a necessary element for organisational productivity, knowledge management and even innovation by Ahmet (2015) and Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa (2019). Also, the absence of proper intra-organisational communication, thus, can deprive an organisation of these benefits, putting its performance, productivity and innovativeness at risk. Given the pressure on automotive sector organisations to adapt to change (Law, 2017), the lack of intra-organisational communication and these downstream benefits present a serious concern. In addition, Chasanidou et al., (2018) have stated that the importance of inter-organisational communication in the process of accomplishing the aim, mission, and vision of the organisation is considered an active and essential factor and it is recommended by the professionals such as Evtimova et al., (2017) and Williams et al., (2019) that organisations must adopt some active means and methods that support in ensuring the effective intra-organisation communication if the firm is objected to attain success and sustainability. Furthermore, intra-organisational communication refers to communication through the organisation, including dyadic and small group communication. Intra-organisational communication covers all aspects dealing with operating the organisation. In organisations, there is a constant exchange of ideas, messages, emotions, information and stories which play an integral part in daily activities. Communications within firms or intra-organisational communication can be transported or distributed through email, phone calls and meetings (Zhao and Ismail 2019).

In addition to this, without communication among individuals, an organisation cannot exist. Communication is what keeps the organisation together creating a bridge between departments and their activities. Moreover, Clegg et al, (2016) write that communication is what connects the organisational activities together. In addition to this, Jonathan (2020) has described communication as dynamic and complex, and through which people exchange meanings. Further, intra-organisational communication is a process where different types of information are transmitted from a sender at one point to a receiver at another. Further, in an intra-organisational communication context, the sender and receiver could be a person, group or organisation. As mentioned above, in the setting of an organisation, employees collect, send and interpret information that is relevant to them. This process is commonly referred to as organisational communication (Clegg et al, 2016; Hargie and Tourish, 2019), intra organisational communication (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016;) or internal business communication (Stevanovic and Gmitrović, 2015). Hence, that there is a connection between performance and communication in organisations. It is vital for organisations to have or create effective intra-communication. Well-structured communication enables information to be distributed and presented in a manner that achieves new levels of performance and satisfaction among employees (Oppenlaende et al., 2018).

Only sparse literary emphasis on the topic under consideration has been observed. Saleem (2015) is an example of a study that focuses on communication in the Pakistani automotive sector, deeming the automotive sector in the country to be ‘backwards’ in terms of technology and innovativeness. Similarly, another study is Sarwar et al. (2012), which reports low reliance on innovative methods of communication as causes of concerns for automotive sector organisations. Such studies show that external factors (like changing preferences of consumers and growing competition in the market) and internal weaknesses (such as the lack of resources, the prevalence of workplace practices that do not give importance to workers and cultural barriers to communication) place Pakistani automotive sector companies at a suboptimal position with respect to intra-organisational communication and consequently impacts their performance.

The aforementioned background of the issue at hand shows that there is a distinct lack of research regarding intra-organisational communication challenges and their impacts on automobile sector organisations in Pakistan. While the stagnated nature of the industry has

been acknowledged by Mustafa et al. (2018) and the significance of intra-organisational communication has been appreciated, on separate occasions, by other researchers, the latter's involvement in the Pakistani industry has not been appreciated. This is important because it presents a gap in the existing literature that can be targeted by the current work, adding to the research problem. In addition to that, given the significance of intra-organisational communication towards organisational performance, it could be a factor that explains the performance deficits in the automotive sector of Pakistan (and hence, help draft a strategy for improvement). This also adds to the research problem (that intra-organisational communication, despite being a potent factor affecting performance in the automotive sector, has not been studied extensively and evaluating challenges that companies face in association with it could provide a way for improving performance too).

The exact extent of the problem, however, cannot be known by drawing on literature from related sectors or disciplines. The paucity of studies that directly target the notion of intra-organisational communication challenges in the automotive sector of Pakistan, conditions limiting performance, and the general importance of intra-organisational communication to company performance add to the need for directly conducting research on this topic. A detailed study that focused on intra-organisational communication challenges in the Pakistani automotive sector, therefore, is essential.

1.3. The Aims and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of the research under consideration is the identification and assessment of the main intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan. This involves a detailed discussion and elaboration of factors that are involved in intra-organisational communication. To help attain this key aim, the research targets attainment of the following specific research objectives:

- ⇒ To identify the key barriers to intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan
- ⇒ To identify strategies that can facilitate effective intra-organisational communication sector within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

1.4. Research Questions

The main research question targeted in this study is:

“What are the intra-organisational communication challenges faced by organisations in the Pakistani automotive sector and to what extent do they disrupt performance?”

To help answer this main question, the research is subdivided into more specific questions:

- ⇒ RQ1: What are the intra-organisational challenges of communication in the automobile industry of Pakistan?
- ⇒ RQ2: How does such communication challenges impact performance in the automobile industry of Pakistan?
- ⇒ RQ3: What exhaustive and holistic framework can enhance intra-organisational communication within the automobile sector of Pakistan?
- ⇒ RQ4: How can the challenges in intra-organisational communication within the automobile industry in Pakistan be minimized in order to help improve the overall performance?

1.5. Significance of the Study

The research under consideration seeks to identify intra-organisational communication challenges in the automotive sector of Pakistan, as well as their negative impacts on companies. In addition to that, the current mechanisms in place to improve intra-organisational communication, as well as possible measures for improvement are also part of the research goals. Current research that is relevant to this topic shows that intra-organisational communication is in fact an important factor affecting a firm’s performance and innovation (Ahmet, 2015). Its associations with areas of importance for an organisation, such as knowledge management (Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa, 2019) and employee engagement (Verčič and Vokić, 2017), have been reported in studies, albeit not in relation to the automotive sector.

Therefore, the significance of this study draws from the factor that it is targeting an area that is important for organisations but has not been explored in relation to a specific sector. The significance of this factor is increased further by the fact that the automotive sector is often an important contributor to economic growth and development in regions (Mohr et al., 2013). This

latter notion implies that the study is significant because of its potential to improve the state of affairs in the automotive sector.

More specifically, the study targets the automotive sector of Pakistan. The sector is currently an important contributor to the economy of Pakistan (accounts for about 2.8% of the GDP) and is expected to grow in importance (to account for about 5.6% of the GDP) in the next five years, as per Naeem (2017). Current sales data, however, show that sales performance across all product categories in the automotive sector has fallen in the country (PAMA, 2020), showing that there is a dire need for strategic intervention and improvement. Separate research in this regard has shown that the automotive sector is not technology-intensive, unlike those from developed countries (Saleem, 2015). Furthermore, the sector is plagued with communication issues, often marked by a lack of emphasis and innovation and possibly also a resistance to change (Sarwar et al., 2012). These challenges coupled with the importance of the automotive sector and problems it has been facing imply that this study could allow automotive sector organisations to improve the caliber of intra-organisational communication and rely on it to bolster productivity. Over time, this could potentially play a significant role in enabling the automotive sector of Pakistan to play the role that it is expected to in support economic growth in the country.

1.6. Approaches to the Study

1.6.1. Theoretical Approach

Intra-organisational communications are a construct associated with multiple theories and, therefore, its study needs to be based on a mix of traditional and contemporary theories that draw from company practices, psychology and business dynamics. Respecting the complexity of the notion of intra-organisational communication, the current study has focused on important theories of communication, including the Rational Choice Theory, Strategic Theory, Social Exchange Theory, Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) i.e., internal IMC and the theories of motivation like Alderfer's ERG theory, Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and Theories X and Y. Therefore, these theories and models are considered to be best practices proposed by experts and professionals, which are cross validated, testified, verified, and effective means as well as methods that support in the process of obtaining quality results with nominal risk and issues. Thus, incorporation in the projected study assists in answering the research questions as well as in accomplishing the aim, objectives, and questions passably. Hence, these models

and theories also support in developing relevant insights and knowledge of the readers in an in-depth, active, and profound manner.

1.6.2. Methodological Approach

The research under consideration relies on quantitative methods based on the philosophy of positivism to analyze the major intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan. Existing literature on the topic has been used to develop a series of hypotheses, which have then been subject to testing in this study. As quantitative research creates room for use of statistical analysis, which supports hypothesis testing (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Data collection has involved the selection of a sample, based on 350 individuals from Atlas Honda, an automotive sector organisation based in Pakistan. Quantitative information to support data analysis and hypothesis testing has been obtained with the help of a research questionnaire. Analysis of the information has been collected using IBM SPSS Multiple techniques have been used, with regression and correlation forming the basis of hypothesis testing, while descriptive statistics and reliability testing contribute to the robustness of the analytical model used. Other than quantitative data and analysis, the research has used secondary qualitative information for supporting, explaining and elaborating the results of primary analysis and helping in the synthesis of findings. This information, collected from relevant books, reports, journals and other academic sources has not been used for the main portion of the analysis, but served purposes in the discussion, whereby the results of this study were compared with existing theory/literature and concepts to develop findings and conclusions.

1.7. Definitions of Key Concepts Used

Intra-organisational communication, in this study, is taken to be equivalent to the concept of internal communication, which can be readily found in studies like Verčič and Vokić (2017). It includes all modes and forms of communication that are concerned with participants within the organisation. Therefore, intra-organisational communication is a concept that is related to interactions involving internal stakeholders, such as the management and employees. For larger groups, this term is also taken to mean communication between subsidiaries or group entities, as it has been used in this manner in the work of Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa (2019). Nevertheless, it is worth noting that in this study, intra-organisational communication and internal communication have been used interchangeably and are taken to mean the same thing.

Another important concept that needs to be clarified here is the extent of the automotive sector. Some studies restrict the automotive sector to the manufacture and sales of cars. An ideal example is Mohr et al. (2013), where the term car culture has been used to demonstrate growth in the extent of automotive sector operations, as well as productivity. In this study, this limited meaning of automotive sector organisation has not been used. Instead, the automotive sector has been taken to include companies that manufacture motor vehicles, not only cars. This can include cars, trucks, buses, light vehicles and 2/3 wheelers (PAMA, 2020). In using the broader version of this definition, this research considers companies that manufacture road vehicles, such as cars, buses, trucks or 2/3 wheelers to be automotive sector organisations.

1.8. Structure of the Thesis

The research under consideration has been divided into six main chapters. Brief descriptions of each of the six chapters are illustrated below:

Table 1.1: Structure of the Study

Chapter	Description
Chapter One: Introduction	This chapter; presents an overview of the research topic, its goals, deliverables and significance. Emphasis on what is being sought, how it will be sought and why is it necessary.
Chapter Two: Literature Review	Existing literature on the topic has been studied and major themes identified and discussed. Particularly, studies and academic work on intra-organisational communication or relevant challenges in the automotive sector (with an emphasis on that of Pakistan) have been reviewed. The chapter includes a discussion on the gaps that are present in the existing literature (which have to be targeted here), as well as the conceptual framework to be used here.
Chapter Three: Research Methodology	The chapter is concerned with a provision of methodological details regarding the research under consideration. Paradigms, philosophies and approaches to the study have been outlined, with a clear discussion of the methods that have been used to fulfil the research purpose (such as the collection of data techniques or its analysis). Important constraints like validity

	and reliability or ethical concerns have also been discussed in this chapter, along with the measures taken to combat them.
Chapter Four: Data Analysis	Results of the analysis conducted in the study have been depicted here. The chapter provides descriptive statistics regarding the respondent body, while simultaneously illustrating results of correlation and regression analysis conducted on collected data. Acceptance and rejection of hypotheses developed for the study have been clearly demonstrated at the close of this chapter.
Chapter Five: Discussion and Findings	In this chapter, the results obtained via data analysis are discussed, often in conjunction with the existing literature to explain them and draw out the study's findings. Answers to the research questions raised in the first chapter have been developed using these findings.
Chapter Six: Conclusion and Recommendations	This chapter provides a summary of the entire research, recapping its objectives, questions and methods, detailing answers obtained and highlighting any recommendations for organisations in the automotive sector of Pakistan- with respect to intra-organisational communication- based on the findings of this study. Also, the limitations of the current study, coupled with recommendations for future research on the topic have also been provided.

1.9. Summary

The purpose of this chapter was to create a platform for the rest of the study to build on. It presented an overview of the concept of intra-organisational communication and the significance of the automotive industry across the globe and in Pakistan. The disparity in current research work regarding intra-organisational communication and its challenges in the automotive sector was discussed, with a presentation of the problem being pursued in this study. This was followed by research aims, objectives and questions, as well as a layout to be followed in this study. Also, major concepts and the study's significance were outlined.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction

The following chapter aims to assess the different arguments that have been put forward by previous research in relation to the current topic. It assesses the arguments and compares them with each other to provide the readers with a clear understanding of the topic. This chapter also develops the theoretical framework for the research under consideration and aids in the development of the hypothesis that has been tested under this study.

2.2. Communication- An Overview

A productive discussion of the challenges that can arise in intra-organisational communication is not possible without understanding the notion of communication, its importance and mechanisms underpinning effective organisational communication. For this reason, the notion of communication, as discussed across classic and contemporary studies, has been discussed in this subsection. Apart from these theoretical approaches, some communication models are also used in the anticipated study, mentioned and discussed below.

#	Communication Models	Explanation
1	Aristotle Model of Communication	According to this model, the speaker plays a key role in communication. He is the one who takes complete charge of the communication. The sender first prepares a content which he does by carefully putting his thoughts in words with an objective of influencing the listeners or the recipients, who would then respond in the sender's desired way. No points in guessing that the content has to be very impressive in this model for the audience or the receivers to get convinced. The model says that the speaker communicates in such a way that the listeners get influenced and respond accordingly.
2	Berlo's Model of Communication	While the Aristotle model of communication puts the speaker in the central position and suggests that the speaker is the one who drives the entire communication, the Berlo's model of communication takes into account the emotional aspect of the message. Berlo's model of communication operates on the SMCR model; S - Stands for Source M - Message C - Channel R - Receiver
3	Shannon and Weaver Model of Communication	This model is specially designed to develop the effective communication between sender and receiver. Also, they find factors which affecting the communication process called "Noise". At first the model was developed to improve the technical communication. Later it's widely applied in the field of Communication. The model deals with various concepts like Information source, transmitter, Noise, channel, message, receiver, channel, information destination, encode and decode.
4	Schramm's Model of Communication	The Schramm model views communication as a process that takes place between a sender (transmitter) and a receiver: there will be also a message, and a medium through which the message can be transmitted
5	Helical Model of Communication	The Helical Model of Communication, or Dance's Helix Model, is a communication model in which communication is explained by means of a helix. To this end, he used the shape of a helix. This shape describes the communication process, and visualises communication as a spiral-shaped model.

The term communication refers to the flow of information between two or more entities that can either be individual or groups. In other words, the communication process deals with the transmission of ideas, feelings, and information between a receiver and a sender (Vander Elst et al., 2010). According to the Ruck and Welch (2012), communication can be defined as an exchange or transmission of information, messages, data, and signals between receiver and sender through a communication channel such as radio, telephone, telegraph, talking or writing. Communication is a complicated process that combines the soft and hard elements of the organisation to manage and support the flow of information (Spaho, 2013). Soft elements such as the communication skill set of employees and the managers' plan to implement communication strategies in the organisational structure are combined with hard elements that contain notice boards, electronic media, meetings, and organisational publications to create the hierarchal channels of communication (Verčič, Verčič and Sriramesh, 2012).

Communication is used everywhere and every day. It is used at home, in school and within organisations. Clegg et al (2016) bring forward three different ways communication can be carried out, namely verbally, non-verbally and visually. They further explain that it can be carried out through email, telephone, the internet or face-to-face communication. In a manufacturing organisation, there are many processes that are operating simultaneously and must be controlled and managed to function well. Further, in an automobile organisation, there are many types of communication that are carried out on daily basis, e.g., decision making among employees, external communication concerning customers and consumers, and communication with stakeholders. Thus, communication plays a very important and central role in daily activities and must be a focus within automotive automobile organisations.

However, these elements support each other's functionality; therefore, failure to manage any particular attribute can affect the functionality of other elements (Aula, and Siira, 2010). Similarly, Miller et al. (2011) state that the communication process deals with the flow of information between sender and receiver; therefore, clarity of message is essential to convey accurate information, and to achieve effective communication. The ambiguous or unclear messages often convey different than intended meanings that directly contribute to the failure of organisational plans and strategies (Yildirim, 2014). It is, therefore, necessary for the organisations to ensure that the employees and the management understand the core meaning

of communication and incorporate it in the intra-organisational communication strategies so as to ensure that the maximum benefits of these strategies can be attained by the organisations.

2.3. Intra-organisational Communication

In order to further improve our understanding of the notion of intra-organisational communications, which lies at the core of this research and its objectives, it is critical to assess findings across the existing literature. It has been revealed that the existing literature and publications of previous researchers often utilize alternative terminologies such as organisational communication, inter-organisational communication, internal relationships, internal public relationships, and employee communication to refer to internal communication (Borca and Baesu, 2014; Cooren et al., 2011; Verčič, Verčič and Sriramesh, 2012; Viqar and Welch, 2013). The terms are extensively used to denote the internal communication between the management and employees of the organisation; therefore, this particular study combines their concepts under “internal communication (Karanges et al., 2015). Ruck and Welch (2012) suggested that management should adopt a flexible approach to implementing internal communication, so it could be modified according to the ever-changing organisational environment and changes that occur at employees’ workplaces. The aforementioned discussion shows that the concept of intra-organisational communications has remained ambiguous and intensely debated upon, with researchers using ideas pertaining to relationships, communication with workers and flexibility in internal communication to approach it. It is, therefore, essential to probe the topic directly. This gap seems to align with the aims and objectives of this research, which are concerned with a thorough discussion and evaluation of the concept of intra-organisational communication, as well as challenges associated with it.

2.4. Theories and Modern Practices in Intra-organisational Communication

The purpose and aims of this report are very specific; it intends to probe the concept of intra-organisational communication in the present-day automotive sector of Pakistan. In order to do so, there is a need to clearly understand the way organisations tackle intra-organisational communication. Moreover, having insights regarding best practices in intra-organisational communication can also facilitate the provision of recommended measures of action, which is another important objective of this research. For this reason, the theories and contemporary practices in intra-organisational communication have been discussed here.

The 21st century witnessed the introduction of a number of changes in the corporate world, altering the ways in which companies used to perform their daily activities. Like other business functions and activities, internal communication has also been strongly influenced by changes of the modern era, particularly technological innovations, giving rise to new concepts, theories and ideas in the field (García-Morales, Matías-Reche, and Verdú-Jover, 2011).

2.4.1. Rational Choice Theory

The rational choice theory can be used to explain internal communication here, as it has been used for this purpose across other similar studies. According to Iannaccone (2016), the rational choice theory states that net social behaviour within a community or organisation is the result of choices made by individuals. As per Paternoster, Jaynes and Wilson (2017), this applies to organisational communication, as the overall communicational effectiveness of a company is the outcome of individual efforts in relation to communication. This idea is further extended by Razmerita, Kirchner and Nielsen (2016), who claim that individual communicational prowess is strongly associated with the quality of intra-organisational communication, which further boosts performance in the organisational context.

Therefore, the rational choice theory establishes a link between the choices made by individual workers in an organisation and the overall quality of intra-organisational communication. Since the research under consideration aims to study the challenges associated with intra-organisational communication, as well as potential avenues for improvement, the rational choice theory provides an excellent directive by suggesting that the behavior of workers and their openness or eagerness to communicate could be investigated to get to the root of the issue at hand.

2.4.2. Social Exchange Theory

The social exchange theory claims that interactions between individuals provide the basis for social change. It is another important theory that can be used to explain intra-organisational communication. This idea is supported by the work of Mortensen (2017), which indicates that social exchange theory connects interaction and communication with widespread social changes. In the organisational context, the social exchange theory can be used to explain the impacts of interactions and intra-organisational communication on company performance and the smoothness of operations (Thibaut, 2017). Furthermore, Yan et al. (2016) comment that

the rational choice theory and social exchange theory govern internal communication, stating that effective communication and interactions within an organisation are essential prerequisites for organisational learning and innovation, illustrating the importance of internal communication in the maintenance of optimal performance.

Again, the social exchange theory is relevant to this research because it links interactions between workers in an organisation with the quality of communication (using the construct of social change). It even links these interactions and social change with organisational learning, innovation and long-term performance, as highlighted by Yan et al. (2016). From this, it follows that the social exchange theory can be useful in studying interactions between workers and social change as factors that influence the quality of intra-organisational communication. Also, the lack of healthy interactions between workers can be viewed as a barrier to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector, further depicting the relevance of this theory to the research under consideration.

2.4.3. The Strategic Theory

The strategic theory is also important in this regard as it links two important concepts—organisational learning and intra-organisational communication—pertaining to the concerned topic. According to van Ruler (2018), the strategic theory states that internal communication is associated with organisational learning, as well as performance. This, in turn, implies that companies can improve their internal communication in order to enhance performance (Kanyurhi and Bugandwa Mungu Akonkwa, 2016). Furthermore, considering the fact that in accordance with the social exchange and rational choice theories, internal communication is influential on both factors, the strategic theory can be extended to cover broader aspects of organisational performance (García-Morales, Matias-Rache and Verdu-Jover, 2011). Therefore, in the current era, the strategic theory can be extended to link internal communication with organisational learning; internal communication promotes innovativeness, which, in turn, can enhance organisational learning, thereby allowing organisations to gain competitive edges over their rivals (Neto, da Silva and Ferreira, 2018).

2.4.4. Theories of Motivation

Theories of motivation provide insights regarding the factors that determine the motivation of workers and have been discussed by some researchers in this regard (because motivation is closely related to engagement, which itself is related to communication and organisational

learning). Even though multiple theories of motivation exist, those pertaining to the traits and behaviours of workers are relevant here, as they can be used to explain the choices that workers make in the context of organisational communication.

For example, Theories X and Y outline different (opposite) assumptions regarding workers, allowing managers to employ the right management tools to keep them motivated and get them to perform their tasks (Şahin, 2012). In the case of internal communications, the characteristics put forward by these theories can be used to derive strategies for internal communication. For instance, ‘Theory X’ workers, who do not want to work and are motivated by a sustainable income can be dealt with using monetary incentives and strict orders, an approach which cannot be employed against their Y-counterparts who are internally motivated and seek knowledge and a sense of achievement (Soliman, 2013).

Other than that, as communication is a two-way process—as discussed earlier—managerial traits and practices are critical components of intra-organisational communication-related theory and practice. This necessitates discussion of Theory Z, which claims that workers’ behaviours are determined by managerial actions and strategies, which dictates, in this case, that internal communication measures need to be designed in accordance with characteristics and requirements of workers; optimum strategies and measures will be able to bring the best out of workers by keeping them satisfied and motivated (Lunenburg, 2011). On the other hand, using strategies that do not align with workers’ requirements can demotivate/ disengage them, reducing their effectiveness.

While characteristics, traits and preferences are important factors in determining employee behaviour and motivation- in the context of intra-organisational communication- needs and demands also play an important role. This implies that the discussion need-based theories of motivation can add to the understanding of intra-organisational communication here. For instance, Alderfer’s ERG theory, which is yet another theory of employee motivation, classifies Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs into three categories, namely existence, relatedness and growth (Lazaroiu, 2015). The existence category consists of the basic requirements necessary for existence and survival and the growth category consists of the inherent human desire to achieve personal growth and development. The ‘relatedness’ category consists of the social and communicative needs of employees.

Moreover, according to Mangi, Kanasro and Burdi (2015), all individuals have ‘relatedness’ needs to be proposed by Alderfer’s theory and in the organisational context, these needs add to the importance of a solid internal communication framework. Furthermore, this idea is extended by Nicoleta and Badshah (2016), who suggest that since a strong internal communication framework can satisfy the ‘relatedness’ needs of workers, it can keep them motivated, thereby adding to organisational performance, as well as innovation.

Therefore, it can be argued that intra-organisational communication is a concept that closely relates to motivation and engagement. Being a two-way process, communication is influenced by behaviours, characteristics and needs of workers, as well as practices employed by the managerial staff. This interplay of variables may underpin some of the challenges and complications associated with intra-organisational communication, making the theories of motivation relevant to the objectives of the current research.

2.4.5. New media

Even though the theories pertaining to intra-organisational communication have been discussed earlier in an attempt to improve an understanding of the topic, the attainment of research objectives requires knowledge and assessment of current techniques, practices and technology used for intra-organisational communication. A review of the literature in this regard reveals that advancements in information technology have revolutionized communication in the business world, with new tools such as social media, mobile applications, online portals and blogs finding their way into the internal communication systems of organisations (Coombs et al., 2015).

The existing literature comments on the feasibility and effectiveness of these tools, suggesting that, collectively, a new means of internal communication adds to the level of innovativeness, while simultaneously boosting effectiveness (Men, 2014). However, these tools can have a number of adverse effects too, such as the introduction of extra expenses, change-related issues, conflicts and, lastly, disruption of integrated communication channels within an organisation (Davison, Ou and Martinsons, 2013). A discussion of the four aforementioned tools is presented in the following tables:

Table 2.1: Tools for integrated communications

Social Media
<p>Social media is one of the most popular developments of the current era. The major driver behind its usage in corporate settings is the sheer number of people who use it. Social media networks like Facebook, Twitter and Instagram continue to grow in terms of the number of users as more and more people across the world are gaining access to the internet (Friedl and Vercic, 2011; Meshi, Tamir and Heekeren, 2015). Also, the fact that social media networks have extremely wide ‘coverage’, means they can reach a wide number of individuals regardless of geographic barriers. Considering these facts, social media can be quite instrumental for both internal and external communication (Ali, Jimenez-Zarco and Bicho, 2015; Estell and Davidson, 2019).</p> <p>In the case of internal communication, social media can be used to improve connectivity between and within different organisational departments, by forming groups of relevant workers who can communicate with one another as per requirements. In addition to that, creating company accounts or pages has also been observed to be a beneficial option that allows companies to communicate plans or instructions to employees (Friedl and Vercic, 2011). Not only does this boost employee engagement, but it can also allow for different departments to achieve greater integration, enhancing the net effectiveness of organisational operations. However, social media, like other digital technologies, has been viewed sceptically in terms of security and privacy. This idea is supported by Gritzalis et al. (2014), Zhang and Gupta (2018), Maule-ffinch (2015) and Abomhara (2015) who claim that social media networks and accounts are susceptible to cyber-attacks, making information discussed over them vulnerable to theft.</p>
Mobile Application
<p>According to Stieglitz and Brockmann (2012), the development of dedicated mobile applications for internal communication can improve the distribution of information across organisations, while simultaneously increasing employee involvement and engagement (Rodriquez et al., 2018). In addition to that, being available on smartphones and personal devices, apps have the added benefit of accessibility, meaning that employees can communicate with one another, as well as the management regardless of their location. This notion is further explained by Nayebi, Desharnais and Abran (2012), who states that mobile applications facilitate remote accessibility, thus enhancing connectivity.</p>

In the internal communication context, the development of a dedicated mobile application that allows employees to chat, share ideas, file complaints and view company news can improve their relationship with the company, while simultaneously motivating them (Stieglitz and Brockmann, 2012). Also, some studies state that such systems connect internal communication with internal branding, whereby an organisation targets its own workers with its branding efforts to improve retention.

However, some researchers argue that developing a dedicated mobile application is not a universal option for supplementing internal communication due to high development and maintenance costs. Indeed, Delia et al. (2018), Kim, Kankanhalli and Lee (2016) and Werth, Guhr and Breitner (2019) discuss challenges created by high costs in mobile application development. Also, others comment that the effectiveness of such a move can be cut down by resistance from workers (due to a major shift in means of communication) (Almaiah and Al Mulem, 2019).

Online Portals

The creation of online portals has been discussed by a number of studies across the existing literature. This tool is quite similar to mobile applications, except that the accessibility factor is reduced (Rodriquez et al., 2018). Online portals, dashboards or discussion platforms enable various workers and managerial staff of an organisation to discuss ideas and look for solutions over the internet. These virtual meetings are usually conducted via personal computers but may also be joined using smartphones. Mazzei (2010) states that the main feasibility of such systems lies in their ability to connect people from different departments and even branches at a single platform where they may discuss ideas. This view is supplemented by Kupritz and Cowell (2011), who claim that online discussion platforms can revolutionize internal communication, allowing workers at all levels to express themselves and share ideas (facilitating growth in organisational innovativeness). Also, it is further suggested that such tools can be instrumental in increasing employee engagement, thereby adding to the motivation and satisfaction of workers (hence increasing performance and effectiveness).

On the other hand, Gao et al. (2011) claim that online discussion platforms, like other internet-based systems, are prone to data loss, cyber-attacks or loss of service; all these events can be disastrous for internal communication, as well as overall organisational operations. In addition to that, researchers consider the lack of convenience another major issue with these systems; in the case of in-house networks, the platform can only be accessed

from within the organisation. This lack of remote access facilities can reduce employee convenience.

Blogs

Blogs and company websites have also come under scrutiny as potential tools for communication. In the external context, these instruments have been successfully utilized to facilitate communication with customers in the automobile sector. Internally, however, their application remains a relatively new area. According to Quirke (2017), one of the central aims of internal communication is to increase workers' awareness regarding organisational operations and brand, allowing for the establishment of a strong relationship between the two parties. The work of Ruck and Welch (2012) claims that websites and blogs can be used by companies to disclose information regarding their activities of brands. Therefore, workers can view such blogs to 'get in touch with their organisation.

While such means can allow for engagement and satisfaction of workers, if one-way blogs are employed (where employees can gain information but not share their ideas), the purpose of internal communication will not be achieved (Quirke, 2017). Also, blogs and websites also present minor security threats, which may culminate in a loss of sensitive information regarding organisational plans.

In light of the aforementioned discussion, it can be said that social media, online portals, blogs and mobile applications have been cited as the most popular 'new' techniques used by organisations to boost the quality of internal communication. Researchers have provided numerous pros and cons associated with the use of each technique in intra-organisational communication, making it difficult to point out a single most effective technique. However, considering the fact that the feasibility of using any one of these communication tools depends on the nature and complexity of organisational operations, it can be said that no single intra-organisational communication technique is universally suitable; organisations need to select a technique or blend of techniques that suit their requirements to boost the quality of internal communication and, therefore, performance.

In addition to that, a large number of studies focused on new tools and techniques pertaining to intra-organisational communication do not comment on their applicability in specific sectors; therefore, many ideas and concepts discussed in the existing literature are broad. A considerable gap in the literature in this regard is that the feasibility of using these intra-

organisational communication tools has not been evaluated for organisations belonging to the automobile sector, opening up room for researchers to explore this aspect.

2.5. Need for Intra-organisational Communication

The concept of intra-organisational communication, as well as theories and practices relevant to it, has been discussed thoroughly in the aforementioned sections. Here, the aim is to outline the major factors that underpin the need for intra-organisational communication (as this can help reveal why intra-organisational communication is important and hence, why companies need to focus on dealing with challenges pertaining to it).

A literature review conducted in this regard reveals that internal communication in the organisational context has been discussed extensively by researchers. The concept of Communicative Constitution of Organisations (CCO) has been discussed frequently in this regard, with researchers arguing that communication constitutes and influences the organisations, rather than the latter influencing the former (Schoeneborn and Vasquez, 2017). This idea is supported by the work of Schoeneborn, Kuhn and Karreman (2018), who clearly indicate that organisations are constituted via communication; they cannot exist without proper communication (this is the core concept proposed by CCO).

With time, various models of Communicative Constitution of Organisation have been proposed, including McPhee and Zaug's Four Flows and Luhman's Social Systems (Schoeneborn et al., 2014). These models have been chosen for discussion for the main reason that they elaborate the need for internal communication within an organisation. As these models shed light on the ways in which internal communication is important to an organisation, they can add towards understanding regarding the need for it, while simultaneously forming the basis for further discussion of the challenges and prospects associated with it.

Keeping the aforementioned notion under consideration, both these models have been illustrated in the following table, followed by critical discussion:

Table 2.2: Models of the Communicative Constitution of the Organisation

(Schoeneborn and Vasquez, 2017)

The above figure illustrates that the social structure within an organisation consists of four distinct communicational flows, namely ‘membership negotiation’, ‘institutional positioning’, ‘self-structuring and ‘activity coordination’ (Schoeneborn and Vasquez, 2017).

Self-Structuring	Membership Negotiation
<p>Self-Structuring is a communication flow unique to organisations and separates them from unorganized gatherings of individuals. According to Schoeneborn, Kuhn and Karreman (2018), organisations have a tendency to self-structure themselves, reflexively, giving rise to proper organisational structures and charts, which allow all individuals to play their parts effectively.</p>	<p>On the other hand, membership negotiation is a special flow of communication that allows an organisation to develop and maintain strong relationships with its members. Dobusch and Schoeneborn (2015) state that individuals cannot be identified as a member of a company until their position has been negotiated and a proper relationship has been developed between them and the company.</p>

Activity Coordination	Institutional Positioning
<p>Cooren and Martine (2016) link this flow with self-structuring, and state that once the latter outlines roles and responsibilities for all workers, the former comes into action to ensure that all individual efforts are targeting the achievement of organisational goals. Similarly, Dobusch and Schoeneborn (2015) claim that activity coordination consists of all communicative flows that are responsible for integrating individual activities and efforts and ensuring that they converge at the achievement of organisational objectives.</p>	<p>Institutional positioning is more to do with external, rather than internal communication. Nevertheless, it forms a critical element of the model and has been discussed here. According to Cooren and Martine (2016), institutional positioning consists of external communication and ways in which a company negotiates with suppliers, competitors and customers, among others. Schoeneborn, Kuhn and Karreman (2018) further claim that negotiation with external parties is essential for developing and maintaining a strong market position, as well as image (factors that can influence the smoothness and outcomes of organisational operations).</p>

Luhman's Social Systems

Luhman's social systems theory consists of three distinct elements, namely:

- Societal element
- Communication element
- Evolutionary element

According to Cooren and Martine (2016), the communication element forms the core of this theory, as social systems and structure are formed via communication. This idea is supplemented by the work of Dobusch and Schoeneborn (2015), which reveals that communication allows for the development of relationships, as well as negotiation with other parties; these factors, in turn, facilitate the formation of effective and functional social structures and systems, thereby making communication the key element of societies and social systems (Schoeneborn and Vasquez, 2017). This model can be extended to the organisational context as well. Since a company consists of many individuals tied into a functional social system, communication is quite important for maintaining normal operations and enhancing performance. Schoeneborn, Kuhn and Karreman (2018) support

this idea, claiming that internal communication is the chief element impacting organisational performance since it lies at the core of social systems and an organisational cannot function without the presence of effective social systems.

2.5.1. Intra-organisational Communication and Firm Performance

Both these models place internal communication central to the normal functioning, as well as the successful operation of an organisation. Regardless of the differences in their approach to the issue, both models are remarkably similar in that they point out that intra-organisational communication lies at the center of the organisational operational web and, hence, improvements can be extremely helpful in enhancing organisational performance.

Keeping under consideration the fact that an enhancement of organisational performance is desirable for all companies and that this research aims to assist companies to boost their performance by improving intra-organisational performance (and dealing with challenges pertaining to it), this revelation is of immense value. Moreover, this factor directly relates to the prevalence of challenges associated with intra-organisational communication, such as cultural barriers or misunderstandings (Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa, 2019). In all, this shows that even though intra-organisational communication is central to performance (Vermeir et al. (2018) mentions Hamilton's view that intra-organisational communication has potent impacts on employee commitment and satisfaction which go on to influence organisational performance), inability to acknowledge this fact manifests as the main barrier in improving communication and, hence, performance (Dwyer and Hopwood, 2019).

Verčič, Verčič and Sriramesh (2012) have identified the five key roles of internal communication to be “communication, change agent, organisational strategist, communication consultant, and education”. On the other hand, Mazzei and Ravazzani (2017) have identified that management can utilize internal communication to communicate with their employees about work, news, policies and control, change process, and organisational culture. This can improve the degree of integration between different organisational operations and departments, thereby boosting performance (Mazzei and Ravazzani, 2015). This creates an impression that the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication, which underlies its importance in a

company, is determined by the extent to which information disseminates within the organisation.

However, another group of researchers argue that providing extra information to employees increases the number of worker-worker interactions. While this is considered a beneficial outcome by many, Wright (2016) states that a higher number of interactions increases the likelihood of conflicts. Moreover, Lee (2010) further adds that the occurrence of conflicts between workers can prove to be disastrous. Such conflicts can disrupt the flow of information (hence, it can violate the purpose of internal communication). Moreover, completion of organisational activities, as well as team-based tasks, can also be hindered by conflicts among workers (Liebel et al., 2018). The net result, therefore, can be decreased organisational productivity (rather than improved performance, which is usually associated with internal communication).

Problems with intra-organisational communication have been a topic that many researchers (Wheelwright and Clark, 2021) have found interesting. If the intra-organisational communication is not good it can affect the overall organisational efficiency and effectiveness (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016; Eunson, 2012; Bergman and Klefsjö, 2010). Additionally, poor intra-organisational communication can lead to financial problems for the organisation (Bergman and Klefsjö, 2015; Wheelwright and Clark, 2018). There are many ways to communicate and thus there are many ways to fail to communicate correctly. Those ways of communication are many when discussing intra-organisational communication and therefore it is important for all organisations to consider the ways they communicate. A common and occurring problem in the automobile organisation studied in this thesis is communication. The perception among employees in the automobile organisation is that communication problems are leading to inefficient and ineffective problem solving and project closure. Additionally, there have been indications of insufficient and ineffective that communication problems lay between different departments, e.g., one department is not made aware when another department uses or scraps materials. This lack of communication can lead to information not being provided at the correct time or not in enough detail. When the information provided does not have enough detail the receiver of the information will have a hard time reacting to the information given, thus leading to difficulties in communication. Bergman and Klefsjö (2016) and Nadler and Tushman (2017) state that problems with cooperation can result in poor morale

amongst employees, which in turn decreases the likelihood of producing products with the required quality level and at the time requested by the customers. Due to the Just-in-Time relationship with their customers, the communication inside the organisation must work well. This means, enabling information to be delivered to the right personnel at the right time. A clear example of that this is not working at the automobile organisation in this thesis was brought forward by an employee, commenting, that a material planner had not been given the correct information regarding scrapped materials. Which resulted in shortages of materials and stoppage on the production floor. A situation like this usually has a domino effect, thus affecting other operations, e.g., there will be a need for logistical solutions which will be more expensive and less sustainable, there will be rush orders made to the suppliers, this is also more expensive and at its worst, it can cause the customer's production to stop. Although these problems are occurring and have been doing so for years, it is not known if they are due to the cultural behaviour of the employees, insufficient knowledge, insufficient systems knowledge, inadequate training, missing process maps, or inadequate channeling of information.

The result is a dilemma: whether or not intra-organisational communication is important to the success and improved productivity remains questionable. Indeed, as different researchers approach the problem from different scenarios, they arrive at different conclusions regarding the benefits or, alternatively, limitations of intra-organisational communication. Conversely, it may also be argued that it is the effectiveness with which intra-organisational communication is utilized within an organisational that determines its effectiveness and importance.

2.5.2. Intra-organisational Communication and Employee Performance/ Engagement

Further review of existing studies reveals that one of the most prominent characteristics of internal communication is that it directly affects the organisation's influence upon the employees, which allows them to increase employees' engagement (Ruck and Welch, 2012). This is one of the multiple factors that underpin the importance of intra-organisational communication in any company.

On the other hand, yet another positive influence of intra-organisational communication is that it enhances the communication between the leadership, management and employees of the organisation (Ruck and Welch, 2012). This is crucial, particularly in light of the two models outlined earlier that place communication central to organisational performance. Furthermore,

Verčič, Verčič and Sriramesh (2012) have been very supportive of the argument that effective internal communication enhances employee engagement and directly contributes to increased productivity. Similarly, De Araujo, Simanski and de Quevedo (2012) argue that effective internal communication allows the management to streamline the productive efforts of their employees, which makes it easier to achieve the organisational objectives. According to Karanges et al (2015), effective internal communication fortifies the existing bond between the employees and employer.

However, Leonardi, Huysman and Steinfield (2013) argue that depending upon the internal communication methods and strategies used by an organisation, internal communication may bring about certain disadvantages. Most importantly, as internal communication can promote transparency, workers may become worried about what they discuss with or tell others (due to the risk of the information spreading to parties who are not concerned) (Mazzei and Ravazzani, 2015). Also referred to as the 'leaky pipe' phenomenon, this can reduce the confidence of workers in internal communication, stopping them from expressing ideas rather than encouraging them to do so.

Apart from that, flaws in the internal communication system may also lead towards segmentation of the workforce into small groups, thus limiting effectiveness. Leonardi, Huysman and Steinfield (2013) comment on this concept, referring to it as the 'echo chamber' phenomenon. They suggest that the internal communication techniques that enable all parties to voice their opinions may lead towards the consolidation of individuals having similar opinions into smaller groups.

If such a situation persists, friction may develop between members of different groups, thus hindering teamwork and communication (Liebel et al., 2018). This, in turn, can limit organisational performance rather than boost it. Furthermore, Lee (2010) also comments on this notion, stating that depending on the media used for internal communication, it may have certain negative outcomes too. It is stated that face-to-face and computer-based communication media are the most commonly used options. While the former is associated with increased time, as well as the potential for errors in decision-making, the latter is concerned with high expenditure, as well as resistance from workers (due to the introduction of change in the form of new communication techniques).

These limitations or pitfalls of intra-organisational communication are quite important, particularly in the context of this study. As the focus remains on challenges of intra-organisational communication, the identification of pitfalls and risks is essential, as they often manifest as risks. Therefore, potential loopholes and threats of intra-organisational communication deserve further attention in the overall discussion of this concept, as they may limit the potential benefits that may be drawn from it in the practical arena.

Hence, while discussing the challenges of intra-organisational communication and ways in which they may be dealt with, it is critical to comment on this interplay of factors that might determine its final outcomes and effectiveness. For instance, the extent to which communication is open needs to be limited. Too much or too little may result in negative outcomes for the organisation.

2.5.3. Intra-organisational Communication and Integration

Integration is another factor that determines the importance of intra-organisational communication. As described before, Ruck and Welch (2012) related internal communication to integrated corporate communication; however, their research explored how internal corporate communication is also a sub-branch of internal communication, and it can be used to enhance employees' loyalty towards the organisation, which will help the organisation to achieve their goals and objectives. This is supported by others, such as Mazzei and Ravazzani (2017), who added that the level of integration allows companies to optimize operations, reduce wastage and make the most out of their workforce. In all, this indicates that effective internal communication is an important prerequisite to the development of a motivated and committed workforce, as well as optimization of internal operations.

However, another point of view is put forward by a different group of researchers. Leonardi, Huysman and Steinfield (2013), as mentioned earlier, claim that internal communication may cause division of the workforce into different groups rather than its unification (which is necessary for the accomplishment of integrated operations). Furthermore, the work of Wright (2016) claims that if internal communication strategies backfire and lead to conflicts, they can prove to be costly for companies. This is because the onset of conflicts can hamper the normal completion of tasks, or flow of information, especially if the conflicted parties have to join hands for performing the said task. Moreover, conflict management measures can introduce

extra expenses, increasing overall operational costs (Turner et al., 2012). Again, this can reduce efficiency rather than increase it, thereby violating the purpose of internal communication. Such studies frequently state that organisations should consider both positive, as well as negative impacts of internal communication methods and strategies before implementing them. Again, the aforementioned review clearly reveals that there is almost unanimous agreement between scholars and researchers when it comes to the importance of internal communication within a company and its impact on performance. Studies frequently term it as one of the most important factors influencing organisational operations and effectiveness. However, there are differences in the views of researchers when it comes to the ways in which these effects are imparted. While some researchers use the Communicative Constitution of Organisations to explain the importance of internal communication, others resort to different ideas, such as workforce integration and management effectiveness (linking the efficiency of these factors with the presence of strong internal communication) achieve this purpose.

Regardless of the differences between ideas presented by different studies, a generally positive relationship has been demonstrated between the status of internal communication and organisational performance. However, these studies are broad; they do not focus on specific sectors and organisations. Since communication techniques used by companies differ according to their industries and outcomes, this is a significant gap in the existing literature. In this case, the absence of significant research regarding the application of CCO models or other theories pertaining to internal communication for enhancement of performance in the automobile sector opens up room for researchers to investigate this topic.

The automobile industry in Pakistan is one of the main contributors to economic growth and is also a core focus of the research under consideration. With a large number of organisational functions, the need for effective intra-organisational communication within this industry is paramount. The following section makes an assessment of the nature and development of the automobile industry of Pakistan.

2.6. Automobile Industry of Pakistan

In this subsection, insights have been provided regarding the automobile industry of Pakistan. The significance of this lies in the fact that the importance and challenges of intra-

organisational communication are influenced by an interplay of factors. While some factors are related to the concept itself—such as integration, provision of information and relationships—others are industry and culture specific. The impacts of these factors also need to be considered to provide a better, more thorough understanding of the topic at hand. For this reason, the significance and structure of the industry, as well as cultures and values prevalent within it have been discussed below.

2.6.1. Pakistan's automobile sector- an overview

Up to 2018, the automobile sector of Pakistan had been experiencing consistent growth. The reduction of foreign investment, particularly from China, meant that the automotive sector started struggling in 2019 (Karachi Chamber of Commerce & Industry, 2019). Total sales of cars decreased from 216,786 units in 2018 to 207,630 units in 2019. Similarly, the sales of trucks and jeeps declined from 9,331 units and 12,870 units in 2018 to 5,828 units and 7,654 units in 2019 (PAMA, 2020). This clearly contradicts the views of researchers, such as Karamat (2017), who suggested that the country's automobile sector is expecting further growth.

However, it must be highlighted that the government has removed restrictions on the automotive sector, allowing non-filers to make purchases to bolster growth (Karachi Chamber of Commerce & Industry, 2019). Eventually, this could re-initiate the trend of growth that the sector had been experiencing previously. The possibility of growth in the automotive sector is attributable to two factors; the population continues to exhibit growth (Afzal and Awais, 2014) thereby increasing demand for automobiles and, secondly, Pakistan's GDP per capita has been increasing significantly since 2015 (World Bank Group, 2020), improving disposable income and purchasing power of customers.

The fact that Pakistan's automobile sector has managed to exhibit growth in sales volumes despite the country's miserable economic performance in recent years represents a positive situation for the sector. Moreover, statistics from this sector show an increase not only in sales volumes but also in vehicle-financing programs; total amounts recorded on account of vehicle-financing plans were 20 billion rupees in 2014 and by 2017 this value had increased to 40 billion rupees (about 191 million GBP). While these increments are mostly accounted for by growth in population and purchasing power of the population, increased business and employment opportunities also occurred in the transportation sector (Karamat, 2017). The

entrance of Uber and Careem in the transportation sector, for instance, has pushed people into purchasing vehicles and then registering with these organisations; this has led towards growth in sales of automobiles in the country.

2.6.2. The sector- structure, changes and modifications

The automobile sector of Pakistan consists of three major players, namely Toyota Indus Motors, Pak Suzuki Motors Company (PSMC) and Honda Cars. These players dominate the entire market, with very little opportunity for local players and new entrants. Toyota Indus Motors, Honda Cars and Pak Suzuki Motors Company (PSMC) dominate the automobile sector, with Toyota enjoying the highest margins. Toyota leads with the highest market share (at 35%), providing tough competition to Suzuki (29% market share) and Honda (27% market share) (Khan, 2019). Both Suzuki and Honda trail behind Toyota in terms of market share and profit margins (Next Capital Limited, 2015). As discussed earlier, these organisations have faced growth in sales in recent years, owing to a number of factors ranging from increased demand for cars, reduced maintenance costs and a reduction in interest rate.

All three organisations have made the most out of the growth in the automobile sector of Pakistan. Toyota Indus Motors, for instance, has been operating at full production capacities in recent years, producing and selling 4,000 units a month. This has been observed since the launch of the new Corolla model in 2014, which led towards a ‘boom’ in sales. However, Honda Cars followed suit, introducing its new model for City; the new model increased demand for Honda City, increasing its sales and reducing those of Corolla (Next Capital Limited, 2015). In contrast, Pak Suzuki Motors Company (PSMC) has benefitted immensely from the government’s ‘Rozgar’ scheme; this introduced demand for 25,000 units each of Suzuki Bolan and Ravi in 2015 and 2016, respectively, allowing the company to experience a boost in sales. However, the scheme ended in 2016, thereby discontinuing this privilege. Resultantly, sales for the organisation are expected to return to normal values in upcoming years.

Figure 2 - FY15 & FY16 will see an increase in demand due to new Corolla Model and launch of Rozgar Scheme; thereafter sales growth will normalize (No.of Cars)

Source: PAMA, Next Research

Figure 2.1: Trends in Automobile Sales in Pakistan

It can be stated after analysing Figure 2.1 that the company's gross margins show that INDU has higher margins compared to PSMC and HCAR. PSMC has lower margins due to the price-sensitive nature of its customers and HCAR, while serving consumers in the premium segment, has operated under 50% capacity utilization as INDU holds a larger market share in the 1,300cc segment. Looking ahead (after 2015), we expect margins to decline as the curves show that steel prices will gradually rise and the JPY will rise as well.

In addition to that, a comparison of the gross profit margins for PSMC, Toyota and Honda Cars reveals that Toyota's margins are higher than the other two players, thus supplementing the idea presented earlier. The other two organisations have lower margins than Toyota; in the case of PSMC, this can be explained by the price-conscious sector targeted by its products (as customers are highly sensitive to small variations in the price and do not allow the organisation to raise prices and subsequently margins). Honda, on the other hand, does not operate on its full production capacity due to strong competition from Toyota (Next Capital Limited, 2015). Particularly, Toyota is quite strong in the 1300cc cars market, hurting Honda's margins. However, profit margins for all organisations are expected to fall in the years to come despite expected growth in sales. This can be explained by projected hikes in the prices of raw materials, particularly steel.

Figure 3 – Gross margins will increase in the near term but taper off going forward..

Source: Company Financials, Next Research, Bloomberg

Figure 4 – ..as JPY is expected to appreciate and steel prices (\$/ton) are expected to increase

Figure 2.2: Trends in Profitability of Automotive Sector Companies in Pakistan

After analysing Figure 2.2, it can be stated that a reduction in the discount rate in the coming months will benefit auto sales, especially for PSMC, which caters to a price-sensitive consumer. A drop in gasoline prices also lowers the cost of car use and creates demand. However, lending is not expected to reach the golden year's levels between fiscal years 2005 and 2008 as banking policies on auto lending have tightened. However, we assume that the Mehran numbers in the CY15-CY16 will increase as car finance rates decrease as the discount rates decrease.

Apart from that, studies and projections regarding sales of motor vehicles in the country are indicative of imminent growth prospects. While general decreases in oil prices and maintenance costs act as drivers of sales growth, decreased interest rates can also be impactful. In Suzuki's case, for example, the target market is sensitive to price and therefore, decreased interest rates and prices are likely to promote sales (Next Capital Limited, 2015). There are a number of factors, however, that can cut down sales; most important among these is the introduction of difficulties in loan processes, making it tough for individuals to secure loans for purchasing vehicles. This factor, however, is expected to be outweighed by others listed earlier, thereby resulting in greater demand and sales of automobiles in the future:

Particulars	FY07	FY14
Upfront Payment	10%	20%
Spread	3%	5%
Documentation	Simple	Detailed

Source: Next Research

Figure 2.3: Changes to Level of Difficulty in the Loan Process for Purchasing Automobiles in Pakistan

From figure 2.3, it can be seen that the upfront cost has been increased in the 2014 fiscal year compared to 2007 where it was 10%. Similarly, the spread has also been augmented in 2014, which is 5% compared to 2007 where it was 3%. Therefore, the impact can also be seen in the context of documentation where the fiscal year 2007 shows that the documentation was simple, the fiscal year 2014 shows that there is the necessity of detailed documentation.

2.6.3. Major organisations operating in the sector

As mentioned earlier, Pakistan’s automobile sector is dominated by three major organisations, namely Honda Cars, PSMC and Toyota Indus Motors. Brief details regarding the three key players are as follows:

Table 2.3: Key Players in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Honda Cars
The organisation operates in ‘1300cc and above’ sectors, where City and Civic are its major models. In this regard, the organisation has experienced growth in sales, selling nearly 2,500 more units than it did last year.
Toyota Indus Motors
With approximately 8,700 Corolla cars produced and nearly 8,500 of them being sold, Toyota leads the way in the 1300cc sector. Its sales have remained fairly constant over the years, showing small signs of growth.
Pak Suzuki Motors Company
Suzuki’s operations bloom in smaller cars, with the organisation dominating 1000cc and below sectors with Mehran, Wagon R and Bolan. Sales of the aforementioned models have experienced considerable net growth in the past few years, representing the organisation’s stronghold in this market segment. However, in the case of 1300cc cars and above, the

organisation has lagged behind its counterparts. With fewer than 1,000 units being produced and sold in 2016, Suzuki Swift has not been quite so successful in penetrating the said market segment.

(Goraya, 2017)

2.7. Comparison between intra-organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan and other Economies of the World

The fact that the Pakistani automobile industry differs from those across the world is a significant factor in this study because most studies have been conducted in relation to large, multinational corporations in developed countries. This has created a gap in the existing literature, as communication depends on the culture and region-specific factors. Those studies fail to capture all variables that exert their influence on intra-organisational communication—and therefore, induce challenges—making it essential for factors specific to the Pakistani automotive industry to be highlighted, in comparison with international values and practices.

In Pakistani organisations, employees generally believe that companies pay them only for their jobs and any extra activities, such as 5S-related (sort, set in order, shine, standardize and sustain) (Veres et al., 2018) tasks are not a part of their jobs. This explains why organisations with experience of operating abroad or any involvement in international activities are more successful in applying 5S than solely local Pakistani organisations (Japan International Cooperation Agency and UNICO International Corporation, 2011). Overseas training has similar impacts on organisations allowing them to implement such strategies much easier than exclusively Pakistan based organisations (Sarwar et al., 2012). Apart from that, integrated communication systems are crucial for the normal functioning of companies, particularly in the automobiles sector.

While global standards intend to promote strong communication and ties within organisations (between employees and different departments), Pakistani organisations have failed to imitate such frameworks (Butt and Katuse, 2017). Since integrated communication between managerial staff and employees has been shown to improve motivation and performance, while simultaneously aiding in the promotion of ‘kaizen’ activities, Pakistani companies struggle when it comes to the implementation of these systems (Sarwar et al., 2012). Furthermore,

despite obtaining and learning about international quality and safety standards like ISO900, QS9000 and ISO14000, they take few, if any, steps to ensure the implementation of such standards. The quality of management and reporting within organisations clearly illustrates that these standards have not been implemented well enough (Japan International Cooperation Agency and UNICO International Corporation, 2011).

Moreover, the component manufacture and sales function of this sector is lagging behind its international counterparts as well (Butt and Katuse, 2017). In Japan, for example, informal business groups dominate the component manufacture and sales segments, but it remains up to date and is based on concrete relationships between buyers and suppliers. In Pakistan, however, the situation is quite different; suppliers rarely tend to form relationships with their customers and are always keen to strike deals with the most profitable option (Sarwar et al., 2012). Moreover, obsolete parts are still utilized in products, limiting their effectiveness; in some cases, the part which has been discontinued for 30 to 40 years in other countries are still utilized here, presenting an abysmal situation in the component manufacture and sales market (Qadir, 2016).

Pakistani automotive organisations have remained slow in terms of innovation and acceptance of technology. It has been indicated by the research of Dweiri et al (2016) that a potential solution to this issue lies in Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), who can develop new and up-to-date components for the automotive sector. However, the role of individual organisations is quite important too; these firms need to ensure that component manufacturers are provided with accurate designs, make use of up-to-date technological and quality-related standards and do not make use of or supply obsolete parts (Qadir, 2016). Playing this part efficiently requires companies to improve the quality of communication, so that information can be transmitted seamlessly within and outside the organisation (Butt and Katuse, 2017). Therefore, the development of strong communication systems as per international standards is another challenge that is important in this regard and needs to be overcome by automotive companies and component manufacturers together (Japan International Cooperation Agency and UNICO International Corporation, 2011).

In contrast, developed economies make use of technology to enhance organisational communication so as to exploit the benefits associated with effective communication (Erez et

al., 2013). For example, automobile companies across the world make the use of ‘global virtual teams, which are composed of:

- A global team
- A virtual team (Erez et al., 2013)

These teams are connected to each other via a web of communication networks based on electronic systems and information technology. Commonly used tools in this regard include Intranet (web 2.0), which allows organisations to develop communication between workers, while simultaneously allowing authorized personnel to access company data (Pongolini, Lundin and Svensson, 2011). In addition to that, the intranet can be helpful in the following:

- Development of knowledge hubs and discussion platforms, which can allow workers and other relevant individuals to interact with one another and come up with innovative ideas and solutions to problems (Erez et al., 2013).
- Bolster organisational communication by introducing new and interactive means of communication, such as video calls and video conferences. These tools, accompanied by the platforms and portals discussed earlier can be crucial in developing integrated organisational communication (Pongolini, Lundin and Svensson, 2011).
- Promote the development of strong mutual ties governed by positive feelings and professional integrity. The creation of such links between team members can improve the productivity of teams, bringing about a stream of benefits for companies (Erez et al., 2013).

The use of virtual teams had been observed excessively in automobile sectors of different countries across the world. For example, the Team-based European Automotive Manufacturer (TEAM) program made use of virtual teams (Szmelter, 2015). The said program intended to identify and discuss the part played by information systems and technology in facilitating normal functioning of organisational supply chains, as well as promoting strong ties (based on cooperation) between its different elements (Marlow, Lacerenza and Salas, 2017). In accordance with the requirements of involved parties and clients, the development of integrated communication software was initiated, with the software combining a number of communication tools such as discussion platforms and video meetings, as well as cooperative virtual workspaces like computer-based cooperative working systems (Charlier et al., 2016).

The aforementioned project consisted of virtual teams having a total of 40 engineers belonging to countries and working with a variety of component suppliers and manufacturers. The presence of such teams allowed for dramatic reductions in costs, as well as the time required to introduce new products in markets (Szmelter, 2015). It is suggested that the implementation of innovative solutions can cut down ‘time to market’ by as much as 50 per cent, streamlining the supply chains of automotive organisations. However, the implementation of such solutions is not easy; preset organisational roles and responsibilities may have to be modified, followed by the introduction of a number of alterations in the supply chain to make the most out of these tools (Marlow, Lacerenza and Salas, 2017).

Another example of effective use of internal communication is the use of self-steering technology in the automotive sector (Szymańska, Adamczak and Cyplik, 2017). Self-steering technology is entirely dependent on devices that can control and regulate activities on the basis of information and algorithms fed to them (information systems) (Ruesch et al., 2017). The key purpose of self-steering systems is to promote automation across organisational supply chains, particularly in relation to production and logistics; this implies that these systems intend to automate the process to an extremely high degree, allowing them to control their actions (Meier, 2016).

Employment of self-steering logistics in automobile organisations can allow for optimization of transport and logistics functions (Pryke et al., 2018). For example, the ILIPT (Intelligent Logistics for Innovative Product Technologies) program made use of self-steering technology. Alternatively referred to as the “5-day” vehicle project, ILIPT was designed to develop an integrated and smooth supply chain that could tackle orders within five days of receipt (Szmelter, 2015). The said project consisted of a number of participants, including:

- Component suppliers
- OEMs
- Comité de Liaison de la Construction d'Equipements et de Pièces d'Automobiles (CLEPA) or the European Association of Automotive Suppliers (CLEPA, Comité de Liaison de la Construction d'Equipements et de Pièces d'Automobiles) (Szmelter, 2015).

In addition to its primary aim of cutting down order-delivery time, ILIPT also intended to improve the quality of operations incorporated in the supply chain, thereby enabling

organisations to adhere strongly to consumers' requirements when developing and delivering products (Meier, 2016).

Apart from that, it has been observed that improving the degree of integration within the supply chain, as well as the quality of communication across it can be helpful in cutting down costs and improving the management of processes (Tatoglu et al., 2016). Throughout the course of history, supply chains in the automobile sector have been dominated by relationships with local and regional suppliers. Moreover, supply chains have remained complex in this sector, with special emphasis being placed on procuring the most appropriate parts from the most suitable suppliers (Luthra, Garg and Haleem, 2015). While such preferences have given rise to prolonged waiting times, modern-day organisations try to focus on the reduction of lead times. This has led towards progressive simplification of supply chains by elimination of unnecessary elements, as well as integration of appropriate technological advancements (Luthra, Garg and Haleem, 2016).

In addition to this, organisations unable to create a good environment for communication are likely to meet difficulties in conducting daily activities (Kanbul 2019). Examples of ways of communication are body language, speech, actions, signs, writings or signals (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016; Clegg et al, 2016; Stevanovic and Gmitrović 2015). For the organisation to reach objectives, there is a need for effective communication between departments, as well as between individuals within each department and individuals communicating with other departments (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016). For the individual within the organisation to work efficiently the information also needs to be communicated efficiently. The information communicated needs to be up to date, it needs to be delivered as soon as possible and the information also needs to be brief and valid. For this information to be useful for the receiver, the information needs to be precise, complete, understandable and with all facts presented (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016). In stressful situations, the receiver of the information can completely misunderstand the information given or even not receive it at all due to the anxiety level that gives more ground for the information to be simple and understandable for the receiver.

Moreover, the concept of internal communication is very straightforward to most people, it is something we are doing every day in almost all our everyday activities. According to Clegg et al (2016), internal communication in an organisation involves face-to-face interactions between individuals. Eunson (2012) identifies internal communication as a unique and

selective process of message transaction, allowing the opportunity for improved individual knowledge and a stimulus for personal contact with others. Littlejohn and Foss (2010) identify the criteria for internal communication as:

- When it is two or more people interacting with each other.
- It includes an interdependency between those communicating and interacting.
- It includes the exchange of information or message.
- The information or message exchanged is coded in a variety of ways verbally and non-verbally

According to Shannon and Weaver model of communication model, it can be stated with the support of Zwerin et al., (2020) study that internal communication inside the organisation functions in a structured form. First, the sender has a piece of information or idea he or she wants to exchange. Second, the sender creates a message according to a certain code, which has its roots in the experience, age, gender or environment of the sender. Third, the sender selects the appropriate channel for distributing and communicating the information or messages created. Fourth, in this phase, the recipient decodes the communicated information. The degree of decoding and understanding depends on the receiver’s knowledge regarding the communicated subject. Fifth, the receiver has interpreted the information and come to an understanding based on his or her degree of knowledge. Therefore, the final step feedback ensures if the receiver has understood the information communicated by the sender correctly. This phase is paramount because effective communication in organisations occurs only if the receiver has understood the information correctly or as it was intended to be understood.

Shannon Model

Internal communication tries to promote effective communication among individuals within an organisation. It includes the production and delivery of campaigns and messages on behalf of management, as well as promoting dialogue with employees in the organisation

(Butkouskaya 2021). In addition, in the organisation, internal communication has some channels and types. Moreover, workforce demographics are changing constantly that underscores the need for different communication channels. Wherever employees work and whatever they do, internal communication in the office and from a distance is an advantage. The exchange of information can take place verbally or electronically via systems such as the company's intranet. The nice thing about the intranet is that it is available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week and accessible to employees from anywhere with an internet connection. There are five main internal communication sources of such as;

- Face-to-face – briefing people on situations and tasks.
- Management – who dispense information such as company results, strategies, external and internal information, and other vital general information.
- Peer – informal chats amid contemporaries to segment information.
- Resources – the intranet, social media, email, video calls, messaging, telephone.
- Team – between contemporaries who work together to accomplish the same end goal.

The development of strong communication frameworks, especially on the internal aspect of organisations, can be extremely helpful in achieving this purpose. This idea is supported in the work of Gopal and Thakkar (2016), who claim that supply chains involve relationships, negotiation and interaction between many parties present within an organisation, as well as outside it. The presence of an effective communication framework to tackle both external and internal communication requirements is imperative for the smooth conduction of organisational operations and optimal functioning of its supply chain (Luthra, Garg and Haleem, 2015). More specifically, effective internal communication is necessary to ascertain those internal operations proceed in harmony and are directed towards the achievement of organisational goals. This notion is further expanded upon in Jacob, Yu and Chavez (2016)'s study, which reveals that good communication within an organisation can harmonize operations, improving the effectiveness of its supply chain. Furthermore, owing to the complex nature of supply chains in the automotive industry, it is even more important for organisations in this sector to harmonize and integrate operations, thereby illustrating the importance of internal communication in the automotive sector (Luthra, Garg and Haleem, 2016).

Moreover, it is further suggested by the World Economic Forum (2016) that digital revolutionization of supply chains in the automotive sector is likely to have far-reaching impacts going beyond cost and time; most importantly, it is expected to improve transparency

in supply chains, adding to management effectiveness (World Economic Forum, 2016). Szmelter, (2015), on the other hand, indicated that another positive outcome of supply chain decentralization lies in the fact that they may offer some immunity to hostile import duties and regulations. This can allow organisations to operate widespread supply chains with different components in different countries (as per feasibility). In addition to that, supply chain decentralization can play an important role in branding and marketing (Luthra and Haleem, 2015). For instance, in markets where consumers are loyal to local products, a locally placed supply chain can be valuable in brand development.

Other than that, the use of modern data collection and processing systems can also introduce a series of positive changes in the concerned sector. For example, modern information analytics can speed up organisational processes, thereby reducing lag and lead times (Dubey et al., 2016). In addition to that, another benefit of digital analytics lies in the reduction of errors (Yin and Kaynak, 2015). This implies that tasks can be performed more accurately and in greater accordance with customers' requirements than in the absence of such systems (Schoenherr and Speier-Pero, 2015). In addition to that, implementation of cloud technology, coupled with sensory mechanisms in the supply chain can allow automotive companies to ensure that all relevant departments have access to the same up-to-date data, improving accuracy of operations (Wang et al., 2016). For example, Bosch has planned a project that aims to install sensors across all its production facilities and logistics sites. Transmission of operations data from these sensors can allow the company to integrate functions of different departments while maintaining high levels of accountability (World Economic Forum, 2016).

While supporting this point, Bloom et al. (2014) indicated that such data management and analysis tools continue to increase in importance with the rise of social media and the internet of things, which provide large volumes of data to companies. The analysis of this information can be helpful in improving operation, as well as identifying potential loopholes in the supply chain (Dubey et al., 2016). For instance, information from these sources can be instrumental in pointing out whether a faulty component has been introduced into the supply chain at the assembly level or supplier level, thereby allowing companies to eliminate the root cause behind the issue (World Economic Forum, 2016).

Similarly, modern technologies like 3D printing continue to find their way in the corporate world, particular in manufacture-intensive sectors like automobiles (Bassi, 2017). It is expected that 3D printing will replace traditional printing in manufacturing industries (in upcoming years), allowing organisations to design parts and products with greater details and then communicate these intricacies to relevant component manufacturers and production facilities so that the final product is closer to specifications outlined earlier (Rehnberg and Ponte, 2018). Effective internal communication has also allowed Western economies to capitalize upon the high-tech research and development, thereby enhancing the overall quality and functionality of their products (Law, 2017). Germany is renowned for its R&D intensive organisations, particularly in the automobiles sector.

By boosting inter-and intra-institutional communications, the country has managed to promote research in industrial contexts, thereby imbibing innovation in its organisations (making them quite efficient) (Grigoriou and Rothaermel, 2017). In addition, German research institutions such as Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft and Leibniz Association hold partnerships with organisations and industrial unions, allowing companies to interact with researchers and experts from these institutions (Comin et al., 2018). Not only does this allow companies to benefit from a technological viewpoint, but it also provides a series of economic benefits which may be realized with the passage of time (Obeidat et al., 2016). In this regard, an automobile sector-specific information and communication technology (ICT) development program has been initiated by Fraunhofer Institute for Communication Systems ESK, which provides organisations with up-to-date tools and software for modelling, planning, simulation and communication in the said sector (German Trade and Invest, 2018).

As can be seen from the above-mentioned analysis, a wide range of differences exists between the manner in which intra-organisational communication exists in the automobile industry of Pakistan and other regions of the world. The international practices can act as a benchmark for the Pakistan Automobile industry. In addition to that, the assessment of the challenges confronted by these economies can highlight how the Pakistan Automobile sector can streamline its intra-organisational communication strategies. The following section, therefore, provides detailed insights into the research conducted in relation to the intra-organisational communication strategies within various international economies.

2.8. Intra-organisational Communication in International Automobile Sector

Communication is used everywhere and every day. It is used at home, in school and within organisations. Clegg et al (2016) bring forward three different ways communication can be carried out, namely verbally, non-verbally and visually. They further explain that it can be carried out through email, telephone, the internet or face-to-face communication. In an automobile organisation, there are many processes that are operating simultaneously and must be controlled and managed to function well. Further, in an automobile organisation, there are many types of communication that are carried out on daily basis, e.g., decision making among employees, external communication concerning customers and consumers, and communication with stakeholders. Therefore, communication plays a very important and central role in daily activities and must be a focus within automobile organisations (Littlejohn, 2019; Littlejohn and Foss, 2015). Organisations unable to create a good environment for communication are likely to meet difficulties in conducting daily activities (Littlejohn, 2019). Examples of ways of communication are body language, speech, actions, signs, writings or signals (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016; Clegg et al, 2016; Stevanovic and Gmitrović 2015). For the organisation to reach objectives, there is a need for effective communication between departments, as well as between individuals within each department and individuals communicating with other departments (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016). For the individual within the organisation to work efficiently the information also needs to be communicated efficiently. The information communicated needs to be up to date, it needs to be delivered as soon as possible and the information also needs to be brief and valid. For this information to be useful for the receiver, the information needs to be precise, complete, understandable and with all facts presented (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016). Nadler and Tushman (2017) discuss that in stressful situations, the receiver of the information can completely misunderstand the information given or even not receive it at all due to the anxiety level, which gives more ground for the information to be simple and understandable for the receiver.

A wide range of definitions explains the concept of internal communication and various studies have identified it as a multi-disciplinary perspective (Men, 2014). According to Welch (2012); Zhang et al. (2016), internal communication is also recognized as employee relations, organisational communication and internal marketing. Similarly, Jacobs, Yu and Chavez (2016) stated the internal communication as communication with management, cross-

department communication and internal media medium as well. It is also known as corporate or business communication, integrated internal communication and strategic communication. In the 21st century, a wide range of studies have been conducted related to internal communication; diverse terminologies can be used for internal communication practically for different scholarly approaches that rely on the organisational perspective (Wright, 2016). However, Welch (2012) defined a simple concept of internal communication as the sharing of ideas and information within an entire firm. Along with this, Zhang et al. (2016) defined internal communication as communication including informal and formal communication carried out across different levels of a company. Similarly, Viqar and Welch (2013) examined the concept of internal communication as per the perspective of a stakeholder and defined it as a constant interaction among various stakeholders for strategic management within the firms. For the purpose of this study, the definition provided by Zhang et al. (2016) has been preferred.

In this advanced technological era, organisations have enhanced internal communication with the help of the latest technology (Grant and Meadows, 2016). These technological developments include the use of intranet and video conferencing for meetings and information sharing purposes (Ruck and Welch, 2012). Consequently, these methods have resulted in a low number of communication problems faced by organisations (Zhang et al., 2016). Intra-Organisational communication refers to communication through the organisation, including the dyadic and small group communication presented by Clegg et al (2016). Moreover, communication within organisational communication covers all aspects dealing with operating the organisations (Littlejohn and Foss, 2015). In organisations, there is a constant exchange of ideas, messages, emotions, information and stories which play an integral part in daily activities. Communications within organisations can be transported or distributed through email, phone calls and meetings (Clegg et al, 2016; Eunson, 2012; Rogala and Bialowas, 2016). Without communication among individuals, an organisation cannot exist. Communication is what keeps the organisation together creating a bridge between departments and their activities. Clegg et al, (2016) write that communication is what connects the organizational activities together. Adler (2016) describes communication as dynamic and complex, and through which we exchange meanings. Further, Greenberg and Baron (2018), describe communication as a process where different types of information are transmitted from a sender at one point to a receiver at another. Further, Greenberg and Baron (2017) describe that the sender and receiver could be a person, group or organisation. As mentioned above, in the setting of an organisation,

employees collect, send and interpret information that is relevant to them. This process is commonly referred to as organisational communication (Kreps, 2020; Clegg et al, 2016; Hargie and Tourish, 2019), intra organisational communication (Rogala and Bialowas, 2016;) or internal business communication (Stevanovic and Gmitrović, 2015). Eunson (2012), Littlejohn (2019), Hargie and Tourish (2019), Rogala and Bialowas (2016), Greenberg and Baron (2018) have established that there is a connection between performance and communication in organisations. According to Hargie and Tourish (2019), it is vital for the organisation to have or create effective communication. They state that well-structured communication enables information to be distributed and presented in a manner that achieves new levels of performance and satisfaction among employees.

Good communication will result in a positive atmosphere amongst the employees, this positive atmosphere will result in motivated and loyal employees (Stevanovic and Gmitrović, 2015). Motivated employees who are loyal to the organization are ready to work hard so that the organisation can reach the organisational objectives. This claim is supported by Hargie and Tourish (2019) which suggests that good organisational communication between departments enhances morale, heighten employees' productivity and promotes a sense of engagement, thus helping the organisation to compete in the market more successfully. Well, working organisational communication does not only result in a positive atmosphere it also improves the cooperation and thus the efficiency of the organisation (Kreps, 1990). This is supported by Kujala, Lehtimäki and Pučėtėitė (2016), stating that good communication results in a high level of trust among employees in the organisation, which in turn lead to positive and productive relationships inside the organisation. Tjosvold (2014) finds that when employees work together on a task by combining their energy, perspectives and ideas, they can solve the most complex tasks faster and more effectively than if the task would be solved by individuals. Tjosvold (2014) goes into the possible barriers of cooperation, one of them is that individuals within the group that is to cooperate do not see the mutual benefit of the group succeeding or do not understand the goal aimed for. These individuals then start competing with other group members to prove that they are more competent or more independent than the rest of the group, instead, they should be competing together for a mutual goal.

According to Elving et al (2015), the use of the intranet has resulted in smooth internal communication with different branches. Organisations receive direct information from internal

stakeholders related to the administrative services and strengthen the organisational communication processes (Grant and Meadows, 2016). As per the positive outcomes of the use of the intranet within organisations, various studies have examined the impact of intranet on the performance and productivity of companies (Angouri and Miglbauer, 2013). The research study conducted by Palttala et al. (2012) determined that the use of the intranet improves the overall productivity of the organisation, enhances the quality of work and ensures smooth internal communication. Similarly, another research study conducted by Cornelissen (2016), determined that internal communication is dependent on a wide range of factors including the size of the organisation, the structure of the firm, the industry in which a company operates, managerial style and organisational culture as well.

As stated by De Araujo et al. (2012), previously internal communication was used to confront various challenges due to budget restrictions and it was limited by management's style. As per the past studies, internal communication has received limited consideration by the management and company owners. They mostly neglected the perception of stakeholders and focused less on the understanding of the message. Similarly, Welch (2012) examined that in past organisations, communication mostly used the help of reports, publications and other conventional models.

On contrary, in this contemporary era, internal communication is the major function that is comprised of organisational achievements, goals, personal contributions, formation of strategic visionary messages and new developments (Men, 2014). According to Zhang et al. (2016), there are four key dimensions of internal communication: internal corporate communication, internal project-peer communication, internal team peer communication and internal line management.

Internal communication has been the focus of considerable development by automotive organisations across different countries in the world. In order to further gain access to best practices in intra-organisational communication, as well as differences that are present in these practices as per regions and cultures, examples from specific countries have been brought to light. Examples have been taken from both developed and developing countries. The rationale behind using examples from Germany, Japan, the United States, UK and Italy (developed nations) is to explore the notion of resources and infrastructure influencing intra-organisational

communication (or, more accurately, the point that lack of resources can act as a challenge to intra-organisational communication). Moreover, since the automotive sector in these countries is developed, using examples from them provides access to best practices in intra-organisational communication, further aiding the evaluation being conducted here. In contrast, examples from developing nations like India and South Africa have been used to shed light on challenges other than the lack of resources, such as the absence of strategic emphasis or poor innovation. Schalk and Curseu (2011) say that the quality of the cooperation is what can distinguish successful organisations from those less successful. And thus, the management in each organisation needs to ensure good cooperation because then the organisation achieves more flexibility in production and can then in turn change easily if needed. Deutsch (2016) goes into that cooperation will lead to better productivity as well as improved psychological health. Deutsch (2016) discusses the theory of cooperation and competition. There he goes into the goal interdependence, that there are two ways of goal interdependence. A positive one, e.g., you swim together you sink together. A negative one, e.g., you swim even if the other sinks. A positive interdependence can be e.g., individuals that have the same goal, are on the same mission, relying on each other due to not being able to finish certain tasks without each other and even that the reward is distributed evenly between them if the goal is achieved. A negative interdependence can thus be related to that the reward is distributed unevenly depending on the result of everyone.

2.8.1. Germany

Organisations in the German automobile sector have taken a number of steps to improve internal communications (Caluschi, 2013). Audi, a renowned German automobile manufacturer, has revolutionized internal communications via the incorporation of digital mobile technology (Lockley, 2018). By developing a mobile application for internal communication, the organisation has managed to increase standards of communication with workers, while simultaneously enhancing transparency within the organisation. The said application also opens up room for internal marketing, which allows Audi to create positive impressions regarding itself in the workers' minds.

In addition to that, the concerned 'employee experience app' consists of a number of features like news, chat and a tool that allows workers to indicate what they feel like. According to the

organisation, the said application has been critical in the promotion of worker engagement and has facilitated their retention (Lockley, 2018). Moreover, this system has enabled the company to gather ideas from all relevant people in the organisation, allowing for the identification of innovative solutions. Lastly, Audi claims that the development of this mobile application has played a critical role in improving employee performance, allowing it to make the most out of its workforce. The automobile sector of Pakistan can focus on developing technologically advanced internal communication techniques to enhance internal communication and benefit from it (Welch, 2011).

Apart from that, Volkswagen Group, a German multinational automotive organisation, has made use of a different approach to facilitate internal communications across the entire group. It has developed the Volkswagen Language Portal, which allows workers across the group to gain more information regarding different languages and gain access to translations, as well as interpretations (Porsiel, 2008). The development of a machine translation tool has allowed Volkswagen to combat any hindrances that may be introduced by language barriers as it operates in different regions, so people belonging to different backgrounds can work together (Karanges et al., 2015). In either case, the machine translation tool has been instrumental in enhancing internal communication in the organisation, as employees can express their ideas or understand others' views regardless of the presence of any language barriers.

While the automotive sector of Germany is far more developed and mature than that of Pakistan, the aforementioned example has key implications for the latter (Mahmood, Ilyas and Rehman, 2014). German automotive companies have expanded greatly and operate all over the world, necessitating the presence of a translation tool; this is not the case with their Pakistani counterparts but the presence of such a tool can improve internal communications in case of mergers or acquisitions with foreign players.

Lastly, BMW AG is yet another German automobile corporation. The organisation has developed intricate internal communication mechanisms to facilitate operations and bolster effectiveness. However, BMW also relies on internal communication to achieve its Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) objectives (Papasolomou and Kitchen, 2011). The organisation focuses on increasing awareness internally so that employees act in a socially responsible manner, thereby creating positive CSR associations regarding the brand in consumers' minds

(Mishra, Boynton and Mishra, 2014). Also, BMW's internal communication measures also centre around internal marketing and employee engagement, whereby the company seeks to involve customers and keep them satisfied so that they continue to perform at peak levels.

The aforementioned examples reveal that in Germany, technology and information systems have remained at the forefront in driving intra-organisational communication in the automobile sector. Moreover, innovativeness has also played a part. Since the Pakistani automobile industry experiences a lack of these factors, this can prove to be a severe challenge for them.

2.8.2. United Kingdom

Rolls-Royce, an English organisation, has also worked on improving its internal communication infrastructure using technological advancements. Based on a worker survey, the organisation identified loopholes in its internal communication infrastructure and then developed an innovation portal, which allowed workers to communicate with one another, ask questions and share ideas. Moreover, by making this platform global, the company was able to ensure that its communication infrastructure cannot be impaired by geographic barriers (McGrattan, 2015). Also, the system boosted innovativeness, a factor that is critical for success in the automobile sector. The said portal also consisted of a 'voting feature', which allowed workers to cast votes in situations that necessitated it.

Furthermore, the organisation also focused on altering the language used for internal communication. It opted for a friendlier tone and kinder language to issue instructions or deal with workers. This allowed the company to develop strong relationships with workers, motivate them and enhance their commitment towards the achievement of strategic goals and objectives (Dulye, 2008). This coupled with general automation and integration brought about by advancements in internal communication allowed the organisation to optimize its operations while creating a positive image in front of its workers (Mishra, Boynton and Mishra, 2014). Again, the internal communication techniques employed by Rolls Royce can serve as best practices for automotive companies in Pakistan as they look to improve employee relationships and seek efficiency in internal processes.

2.8.3. United States of America

The use of social media and blogs in internal communication is illustrated by General Motors Corporation, the United States-based multinational vehicle manufacturer (Ruck and Welch, 2012). These measures add a touch of innovativeness to the internal communication framework. Moreover, by increasing employee engagement and involvement, such measures increase the motivation and contentment of workers, adding to their performance (Singh, Veron-Jackson and Cullinane, 2008). Also, these measures make workers feel ‘important’, adding an element of internal marketing and branding to the communication framework. This improves employee retention.

The automotive sector of Pakistan, in contrast to that of the USA, lacks innovation and the use of modern technologies. Social media and blogs, therefore, are not used for internal communication purposes in the said sector (Welch, 2011). Hence, the development and utilization of such systems seem to be the way forward for companies looking to develop an effective internal communication infrastructure.

Apart from that, another example of internal communication in the automotive sector can be observed in Tesla Motor’s case. The organisation’s Chief Executive Officer, Elon Musk, places great value on workers. This fact is illustrated in the internal communication measures introduced by Tesla, which focus on engaging employees and providing them with necessary information regarding the current nature of organisational operations, as well as future directions (Bučko, 2018). Moreover, Musk has been known to communicate directly with his subordinates, insisting that all workers report any issues or queries directly to him. Such practices enhance the quality of internal communication, while simultaneously improving employee engagement within the company. The result is obvious: organisational operations start becoming more streamlined and effective.

The aforementioned discussion provides another example of the status of internal communication and employee engagement in the automotive sector of the USA (Bučko, 2018). As compared to their Pakistani counterparts, automotive organisations in the USA have a number of internal communication strategies and practices in place to improve employee engagement, as well as the quality of internal operations (Saleem, 2015). Tesla’s example

clearly shows the value it places in its workers, as well as the benefits of such measures on organisational effectiveness.

2.8.4. India

Internal communication techniques are a topic of concern in the Indian automotive sector too. This is illustrated in the example of Tata Motors, which is one of the largest players in the Indian automobile sector (Srivastava, Ramachandran and Suresh, 2014). The organisation has recently worked on developing a new brand identity ‘connecting aspirations’, whereby it defines itself as a set of interlinked mobility solutions aimed at generating maximum value for customers. While the company has focused on popularizing this brand identity in front of external stakeholders, Tata has been intent upon communicating the nature of its new brand identity, its values and future to employees (Tata Motors, 2018).

This is beneficial for several reasons; firstly, since workers are often considered as ambassadors of brand identity, this prepares them so that they may act in ways that depict the morals and values of the brand. In addition to that, this step increases workers’ confidence and commitment in relation to their organisation, ultimately resulting in improved performance (Karanges et al., 2015). Again, this contains important lessons for automotive organisations across the world, including those in Pakistan. Most importantly, organisations should understand the need for a proper internal communication system and focus on developing one so that they may reap its benefits and increase the net performance of their workforce.

2.8.5. South Africa

With the support of the Daimler Chrysler South Africa case, which provides insights regarding internal communication in another region (Steyn, Steyn and Rooyen, 2011). The rationale to incorporate and discuss the aforesaid case is to highlight the importance of intra-organisational communication in the automobile sector and how via training and education it can be improved so that quality results can be obtained. In addition to this, it is found from the respective case that subsidiary of Daimler AG, a German automobile firm has faced significant challenges in adjusting its operations in a different culture. Their intra-organisational communication was not effective, which have been considered as the key reason behind the chaos and disputes (Benish 2015). Some studies such as Cornett et al., (2015) and Bolay et al., (2019) in this regard

have stated that the condescending nature of the workers and peers in the Daimler Chrysler case is considered another cause behind the issues they have faced while functioning in different countries such as Germany. On such statement, Straub (2018) has stated that in Daimler Chrysler initially there was a lack of education and training, which might support them to excel and thrive with the nominal likelihood of risks and issues. This argument has also been supported by Denker (2014) where the author has quoted that education and training practices in the organisation either automobile or others support the employees and employers in the process of setting up the best and effective means and methods that eventually had a reflection on the intra-organisational communication, relation, and rapport, supported by (AG 2018). This adequately aids in attaining the quality results with the nominal prospect of issues that could affect the entire organisation procedure to attain quality results such as sustainability, competitive edge, success, productivity, and profitability, supported by the findings of (Beenish 2015).

In continuation, studies such as Ell (2016) and AG (2018) has addressed that collaboration, cordialness, as well as communication in automobile companies are considered to work simultaneously. If any of such traits are affected, the possibility of adverse results in the context of fragile intra-organisational communication, understanding, as well as poor employee engagement is occurred, supported by Daimler (2013). On such aspect, Martin (2015) has depicted that if in the organisation, for example, automobile sector, if communication, understanding, and employee engagement is affected, it can be stated that sooner or later the consequences would be reflected on intra-organisation aspect and therefore, organisation success and efforts to attain quality results as mentioned above would get affected, supported by Beenish (2015). Moreover, sometimes firms need to maximize open and frank conversations between employers and employees. Improving a company's collaboration and communication efforts is not difficult, but it does require a more rigorous tactic (Hanigan 2014). Therefore, Zamora (2014) has defined some tactics such as transparency, codification of all vivacious discussions, appraisals, and appreciation. In addition to this, the similar author has further stated that if such means and tactics were integrated into Daimler Chrysler under training and education, the possibility to attain their mission and vision in Germany and similar other countries would be easy as these tactics help in setting up best methods and approaches, which assists to strengthen up the intra-organisation communication and collaboration along with employee engagement, also backed up by AG (2018) findings.

Internal communication at the organisation closely follows but does not completely adhere to the two-way symmetrical communication model. This implies that the organisation focuses on transparency, maintaining the flow of information amid management and workers, providing feedback, maintaining the availability of abundant information and effective communication between different departments of the company (Welch, 2011). The result is an effective internal communication system, which improves the quality and effectiveness of operations, as suggested by the research of Steyn, Steyn and Rooyen (2011). The study indicated that the company saw a decrease in the duplication of efforts as well as resource wastage as a result of integrated information sharing within the organisation. This, therefore, also increased the overall corporate efficiency. However, the said company has been found to be lagging when it comes to employee engagement and some workers have complained regarding a lack of attention provided to them. This limits the efficacy of internal communication techniques.

However, despite all issues, the South African automobile company have integrated some practices under the umbrella of training and education that were envisaged to train and develop the relevant insights and knowledge of their personnel in the process of effective intra-organisational communication, collaboration, and employee engagement that have supported them in the process of obtaining high-quality results (Masondo 2018). Therefore, the internal communication framework utilized by Daimler Chrysler South Africa has a number of positive aspects which facilitate the smooth performance of organisational activities (Mishra, Boynton and Mishra, 2014). If implemented in the Pakistani automobile sector, these practices can allow organisations to optimise operations and performance that eventually reflects on their intra-organisational facets and as a result, the possibility of obtaining high-quality results such as competitive edge, success, profitability, productivity, global recognition, and sustainability for automobile sector of Pakistan such as Honda and others would be easier and on higher-level.

2.8.6. Italy

Fiat Automobiles, an Italian organisation, has also made use of internal communications to redesign its operations and win the support of its workers. In an attempted corporate renewal, the organisation launched a project known as “Avanti e Veloci”, which provided the workers with insights regarding the organisation’s vision, as well as plans for future activities. In addition to that, the project also aimed to enlighten workers with the rationale and reasoning behind the step the company proposed (Invernizzi, Biraghi and Romenti, 2012). A series of

internal communication and marketing initiatives were brought into action, allowing the organisation to develop a vast body of workers who supported its new cause. The project initially targeted senior executives, and then progressed in a ‘top-down’ fashion to target subordinates and junior workers, eventually planning to cover the entire workforce.

The aforementioned developments allowed Fiat to back its activities with support from its workers, which is the aim of any successful internal communications strategy (Karanges et al., 2015). Such moves can be utilized by automotive organisations across the world, including those in Pakistan, to develop strong bonds with their workers, encourage and motivate them and direct them towards strategic goals (ultimately enhancing performance).

2.8.7. Japan

Toyota, a Japanese automobile giant, has also placed special emphasis on internal communications to improve alignment and harmony between different organisational operations, as well as benefitting from the concept of internal marketing. ‘The Toyota Way’, an innovative system introduced by Toyota which ensures that staff at all levels communicate and coordinate with one another to sustain organisational operations (Burton, Grates and Learch, 2013). Also, Toyota has worked on a number of aspects, including communication skills of supervisors, the trust placed in managerial staff and transparency in internal communications to ensure that its lean processes are backed by motivated and committed employees.

Also, internal marketing and communications at Toyota are backed by its reward and recognition system, which ensures that workers’ efforts are acknowledged and appreciated. Not only does this promote employee engagement, but it also creates positive brand associations in workers’ minds. The net outcome can be observed in the form of high retention of workers (as well as transmission of positive information via word-of-mouth) (Lubin and Esty, 2010; Terglav, 2017). Again, automotive sector companies in Pakistan can work on developing effective reward, recognition and communication systems that engage and acknowledge workers, while simultaneously allowing them to express their views (Saleem, 2015). This can be helpful in improving the quality of internal communications, as well as operations.

A clear contrast of a well working communication in both direction and a bad one can be seen when comparing the Japanese car manufacturers with the American car manufacturers during most of the 20th century (Liker and Choi, 2014). In the former, employees are to a high degree involved in the organisation's improvement work regarding the different processes, where discussion is going back and forth between employees and top management (Liker and Choi, 2014). While in the latter, communication is one-way road, where decisions are made by the top executives and the employees must carry them out (Liker and Choi, 2016). The result favoured the Japanese car manufacturer who was a more dominant force in performance, job satisfaction and productivity during the 20th century (Liker and Choi, 2015). However, several authors bring forward different aspects to improve and form a more effective upward communication. Keyton (2011) suggest that organisations should try an open-door policy, meaning that the door is always open for employees to go and talk to management about problems or suggestions for improvements. Bergman and Klefsjö (2010) and Stevanovic and Gmitrović (2015) states that management should take a walk around the organisation building, this will according to him signal openness and enable employees to initiate upward communication. Rogala and Bialowas (2016) which also add that upward communication can be improved through regular group discussion with management involved. In addition, Hargie and Tourish (2019) suggest that to create a well function upward communication, top management should share their perspective, feelings and difficulties to subordinates, creating an environment of trust and hopefully break the ice to enable greater upward communication.

2.8.9 Pakistan

The Pakistani automotive industry has been effectively contributing to its GDP that is around 3.0% and 30 billion rupees to the state treasury in the form of taxes and tariffs. Pakistan has the sixth-largest population in the world with a growing middle class. In 2018 there are around 17 million middle-class households and 102 million middle-class people. Pakistan's automotive industry is growing rapidly in Asia. In addition, sales and production have been increased to 171% and 172.5% respectively (2014 and 2018), all driven by the automotive development policy introduced in 2016 (Juska 2017). Moreover, on March 18, 2016, the Economic Coordination Committee (ECC) adopted the “Automotive Development Policy 2016-21” that tenders to tariffs incentives for new automobile manufacturers to set up production facilities in Pakistan. In response, several automakers have expressed interest in entering the market,

including Renault, Kia, Nissan, Volkswagen, SsangYong, and Hyundai (Hassan 2021). Pakistan is the 35th largest automobile manufacturer. Its contribution to the treasury is nearly \$310 million. Pakistan's auto market is one of the smallest but fastest mountings in Asia. In 2018, 269k+ cars were sold, but in 2019 they fell to 186,716 due to the austerity measures (Tahir 2020).

2.9. Key Challenges of Intra-Organisational Communication

The following section identifies the key challenges confronted by the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan:

2.9.1. The complexity of Big Data Analytics

While the aforementioned examples illustrated positive aspects and initiatives pertaining to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sectors of various countries, there are certain areas in which organisations struggle. For example, big data has become one of the leading innovations in the modern world, allowing organisations to collect, store and analyze large volumes of data (Yin and Kaynak, 2015). This can improve the quality of decision making. However, making the most out of this innovation requires effective communication and information handling systems (Dremel et al., 2017). As leading automotive organisations such as Audi and Volkswagen (Germany), Rolls-Royce (UK), Tesla and General Motors (USA), Toyota (Japan) and Fiat (Italy) continue to design connected vehicles that use navigation systems and connectivity to communicate with other vehicles and the surroundings. Due to the emphasis on such vehicles, it has become important for them to improve their internal communication and information dispersal and handling abilities (Dremel et al., 2017). Since connected vehicles can act as beacons of information for big data and analytics, organisations are likely to face challenges in communicating and transferring this data. According to one study, data generated from connected cars globally will increase by 186 per cent from 2013-2020, causing mass communication challenges for companies (IHS Market Ltd., 2014).

Another interesting aspect of this issue is that the development of data analytics capabilities and infrastructure needed to handle big data is a resource-intensive activity. Mazzei and Noble (2017), for instance, point out that a company's digital readiness is particularly critical when it

comes to the development of big data analytics capabilities. Among other factors, this readiness includes the availability of necessary technical and financial resources, as well as human capital. The need for technical, financial and human resources for the development of an effective big data analytics system (one that can handle the complexity associated with it) is supported further in the works of Dubey et al. (2019) and Niebel, Rasel and Viète (2019).

From this, it follows that the complexity of data analytics presents a much more significant challenge in conditions where the tangible (financial, infrastructure) and intangible (commitment, knowledge, skill) resources needed for the development of an effective big data system are absent. This assertion is backed by the fact that big data generated by organisations has high volume and variety (Debattista et al., 2015; Ghasemaghaei and Calic, 2019; Plale, 2013; Yin and Kaynak, 2015). Pokorný (2015) comments that improvements to database technology are critical for the adoption and effective use of big data in organisations. Similarly, the significance of human capital is illustrated in Erevelles, Fukawa and Swayne (2016), who reveals that the training of workers is critical for the effective functioning of a big-data system. In addition, Gardiner et al. (2018) reveal that recruitment drives at organisations are often modified to suit specific skills requirements (such as awareness or expertise of working with complex systems). Again, the fact that human and material resources are critical to deal with the complexity of a big data system extends support to the notion that the absence of said resources can make the complexity a major challenge.

In the automotive sector of Pakistan, there is a dire lack of these tangible, as well as intangible resources. Qadir (2017) reveals that companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan have lagged behind those in India (a developing country with similar resource constraints as Pakistan) in terms of organisational learning with respect to technology. This means that human resource is not developed enough to cope with advanced technology and so the pace of acquisition remains low. Khan, Masood and Qureshi (2019) also comment on the poor knowledge and skill level in the Pakistani automotive sector workforce. When applied in the case of big data analytics and the complexity associated with it, these limitations place Pakistani automotive sector companies in a weaker position than their counterparts in India (or other countries, such as Germany and USA discussed above). This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 2.4: Challenges in the Development of Big Data in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by Author

The fact that automotive sector organisations in Pakistan cannot deal with the complexity of big data analytics, when coupled with the need for analytics in the automotive sector, can create barriers to intra-organisational communication. This is primarily attributable to the fact that the infrastructure within organisations may not allow for handling multiple streams of data. Dremel et al. (2017)'s view that the rise in the volume of information available to companies has increased because the popularity of connected vehicles is important here. The inflow of a significant volume of information makes dissemination and handling extremely complicated (Fuller, 2012). Since the dissemination of information within an organisation is a critical aspect of intra-organisational communication, complexity originating from big data is an important challenge for intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies of Pakistan.

Based on the aforementioned discussion, the following hypothesis has been drawn out:

H1: The complexity of big data analysis has a negative impact on intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.9.2. Lack of Focus on the Personal Goals of Workers

Complexity and the costly nature of information systems or data analytics are not the only factors that underpin challenges associated with intra-organisational communication. This is evident from the example of Tata Motors, where the connecting aspirations program has emphasized the communication of values, goals and objectives internally (Tata Motors, 2018).

Tata's example shows that apart from emphasising technology and the use of information systems to improve intra-organisational communication, companies consciously focus on the communication of goals and values. This is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.5: Two-Way Communication that Underpins Efficacy of Intra-Organisational Communication

Source: (Dwyer and Hopwood, 2019)

The figure illustrated above shows that if an organisation focuses on the sharing of information regarding values and goals within it, it can bolster the quality of intra-organisational communication. Since this research is concerned with the challenges faced by automotive sector organisations in establishing sound intra-organisational communication, a lack of such focus on goals and objectives may be considered a challenge. This viewpoint is particularly relevant for automotive companies in Pakistan because of the power-distance prevalent in the country's culture (Mazzei, 2018; Quratulain et al., 2018). The presence of well-defined hierarchies implies that the management may not be concerned with two-way communication of goals in the first place, resulting in compromised intra-organisational communication.

In addition to that, it is integral to pay attention to the role that intra-organisational communication plays in the clarification of goals and objectives, as well as career development. Femi (2014) claims that effective intra-organisational communication is critical for clear communication of goals and objectives (between managers and workers; this is an example of peer-management communication, rather than peer-peer communication). Markaki, Sakas and Chadjipantelis (2013) clearly propose a link between communication within the organisation (peer to management) and professional development (attainment of personal targets) of workers. Similarly, Hrehova (2010) comments that communication skills are critical for the personal development of workers (this is explained by the fact that these skills allow them to engage in two-way communication with the management, as evident from the work of Markaki, Sakas and Chadjipantelis (2013)). This notion is extended further in the work of Buzzenell and Lucas (2013), who link communication with the notions of respect, dignity and

choice in relation to career development. The significance of intra-organisational communication in career development is summarized in the following figure:

Figure 2.6: Intra-organisational Communication and Personal Development Goals

Source: (DeCenzo, Robbins and Verhulst, 2016)

It is evident from the above figure that intra-organisational communication shares an important association with career development and fulfilment of personal goals at an organisation. Companies choose to focus on these latter aspects because of their influence on employee motivation and performance. Rizwan et al. (2014), Merchant Jr (2010) and Becker, Hartmann and Miller (2014) reveal that organisational interest in career and employee development stems mainly from their positive impacts on performance and organisational effectiveness. Considering the fact that intra-organisational communication supports personal development and career progression, it can be stated that a company that focuses on the personal goals of workers is likely to invest in intra-organisational communication (as compared to one that is not) (Mannan, 2013). This point is important here because the absence of emphasis on employees' personal goals and their development reduces organisational focus on the improvement of internal communication too (DeCenzo, Robbins and Verhulst, 2016). As a result, a lack of focus on personal goals can be termed as a barrier to effective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis has been drawn out:

H2: Lack of focus on the personal goals of the employees has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.9.3. Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement

In addition to that, employee engagement remains yet another challenge for some organisations in the global automotive sector. Daimler Chrysler South Africa, a key player in the South African automobile sector, has an intra-organisational communication model which lacks focus on employee engagement (Mishra, Boynton and Mishra, 2014). Since keeping workers engaged is essential for developing two-way internal communication, this can prove to be a major communication challenge for the company, as the power distance within the culture of Pakistan is very high. As a result, hierarchical boundaries between the employees are very strong, which can hinder the development of two-way communication challenges as a whole (Mazzei, 2018; Quratulain et al., 2018).

Employee engagement is directly associated with the notion of internal communication within organisations, marking its significance for this study. Indeed, Karanges et al. (2015) and Kang and Sung (2017) point out that sound intra-organisational communication creates a platform for employee engagement. From this, it follows that in an organisation with a low focus on employee engagement, the resources and efforts devoted to intra-organisational communication are bound to be low too. Thus, low emphasis on employee engagement creates barriers to the development of strong intra-organisational communication.

Furthermore, Balakrishnan and Masthan (2013) support the idea that intra-organisational communication improves employee engagement within an organisation. In addition to that, the study goes on to state that managerial staff in an organisation consider communication as the foremost factor that needs to be adjusted to improve employee engagement. As a result, it can be argued that as an organisation chooses to emphasize employee engagement, it will automatically turn towards intra-organisational communication. This is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.7: Managerial Emphasis and Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by Author

From the above figure, it is very clear that focus on employee engagement contributes to the improvement of intra-organisational communication in a company too, because the management considers communication to be an important driver of employee engagement in the first place (this has been mentioned in the work of Balakrishnan and Masthan (2013)). As a lack of emphasis on employee engagement will disrupt this pathway of improvement of intra-organisational communication, it can be considered as a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

On the other hand, another notion is presented in the work of Verčič and Vokić (2017), where employee engagement and intra-organisational communication have been termed as interrelated aspects that are connected in a loop. The figure illustrated below demonstrates this idea:

Figure 2.8: Intra-organisational Communication and Employee Engagement

Source: Verčič and Vokić (2017)

A clear implication that can be drawn from this figure is that a unidirectional relationship does not exist between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication. While many authors have acknowledged intra-organisational communication to be critical to employee engagement (Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014), Karanges et al. (2015), Ruck and Welch (2012) and Kang and Sung (2017)), the opposite dimension of this relationship remains less recognized. Nevertheless, it implies that as intra-organisational communication is improved, it leads towards enhancements in employee engagement, which further contribute to improvements in communication. From this, it follows that a lack of focus on employee engagement can disrupt the constructive loop (even if an organisation does work on improving intra-organisational communication, the benefits associated with employee engagement will be ignored) (Mannan, 2013).

To this point, two major ways in which a lack of emphasis on employee engagement can act as a barrier to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan have been identified. Firstly, the ideas of researchers like Karanges et al. (2015), Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014), Balakrishnan and Masthan (2013) and Ruck and Welch (2012) have been used to imply that companies consider intra-organisational communication as a means of

improving employee engagement. Thus, focusing on the latter ultimately results in improvements being made to the former.

On the other hand, based on the two-way relationship proposed by Verčič and Vokić (2017), it has been argued that not only does the lack of focus on employee engagement limit improvements being made to employee engagement, it also deprives the latter of positive influences offered by the former. Again, this creates a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. The following figure illustrates both ‘pathways’ involved in this relationship between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication:

Figure 2.9: Employee Engagement and Intra-organisational Communication

Source: (DeCenzo, Robbins and Verhulst, 2016; Mamman, 2013)

As evident from the aforementioned figure, a lack of focus on employee engagement can have both direct and indirect impacts on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. On one hand, a lack of focus on employee engagement translates to low focus on intra-organisational communication from the management, which prevents improvement. Resultantly, intra-organisational communication remains underdeveloped (Mello, 2014). On the other hand, the lack of focus on employee engagement can result in low employee engagement in companies. Considering the two-way relationship between the two variables at hand, this can have direct negative impacts on intra-organisational communication. Consequently, this can weaken intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies in the country (Chaturvedi, 2011).

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis has been drawn out:

H3: Lack of focus on employee engagement has a negative impact on intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.9.4. Lack of Innovative Mechanisms

All of the examples discussed earlier provide insights regarding internal communication frameworks and the part played by them in keeping employees engaged and satisfied, providing considerable lessons for the automobile sector of Pakistan, which is fairly under-developed at present (Saleem, 2015). Organisations around the world continue to integrate technology and innovations within their internal communication systems. This is evident in Audi's mobile applications or General Motors's use of social media and blogs to facilitate internal communication. Studies conducted on the Pakistani automobile sector reveal that the use of such tools remains limited in automobile companies operating in the country (Sarwar et al., 2012).

The nature of this challenge is firmly associated with the notion of innovation. According to De Medeiros, Ribeiro and Cortimiglia (2014), innovation is equivalent to change or novelty. From this perspective, innovation in communication can be considered as the use of unconventional media to support communication. As evident from General Motors' use of social media and blogs, the use of unconventional means to support intra-organisational communication is critical in the current era. Sarwar et al. (2012)'s revelation that the Pakistani automotive sector lags behind in terms of innovation shows that companies in the country are likely to face challenges in attaining high-quality intra-organisational communication.

Indeed, this notion can be extended further using the role of innovation in communication systems within organisations. Zerfass et al. (2018), in their study, point out that innovation-driven communication strategies and systems are critical for businesses in the contemporary world because of the nature of requirements at hand. As companies have to deal with various requirements associated with their communication system (among other things, intra-organisational communication is related to employee engagement (Karanges et al., 2015; Verčič and Vokić, 2017), knowledge transfer and product development (Jacobsen et al., 2014)

and fulfilment of organisational goals (Hume and Leonard, 2014), innovation-driven communication becomes quite critical, as illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 2.10: The Need for Innovation in Intra-organisational Communication

Source: (Quirke, 2012)

The above figure shows that innovation is critical for efficient intra-organisational communication in contemporary organisations. Establishing the significance of innovation to intra-organisational communication is necessary here, because the identified challenge is “lack of innovative mechanisms”. Simply put, given the importance of innovation driven strategy and innovative mechanisms to intra-organisational communication, their absence can be presented as a challenge (Chaturvedi, 2011). This is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.11: The Impacts of Low Innovation on Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by Author

The figure illustrated above shows that lack of focus on innovative mechanisms can render the communication frameworks in a company to be weak. In this way, intra-organisational communication within a company may not be able to cope with the multifaceted requirements associated with it. As a consequence, a lack of focus on innovative mechanisms and the absence of an innovation driven strategy can weaken intra-organisational communication (Chaturvedi, 2011). Even more so, Sarwar et al. (2012) have revealed the abysmal status of Pakistani companies with respect to innovation, further highlighting the significance of the issue at hand. For this reason, it may be considered as a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

In addition to that, another line of reasoning may also be used to highlight the significance of the challenge posed by a lack of innovation to intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies of Pakistan. In contrast to the positive impacts of innovation on the quality of communication within the organisation, this relies on the need of high-quality communication to innovation and firm performance (Quirke, 2012). From this perspective, it can be argued that communication serves to boost innovation in an organisation. This further implies that in order to improve innovation, a company will resort to the enhancement of its intra-organisational communication competence. In this way, focusing on innovation could result in effective intra-organisational communication (while the converse also holds true, making a lack of innovation a challenge for intra-organisational communication) (Mannan, 2013).

The notion presented earlier can be ascertained using works of numerous researchers. For instance, Walker, Damanpour and Devece (2011), Jiménez-Jiménez and Sanz-Valle (2011), García-Morales, Jimenez-Barrionuevo and Gutierrez-Gutierrez (2012) and Ali, Kan and Sarstedt (2016) all link innovation in organisational practices with organisational performance. Given this relationship between innovation and firm performance, it may be implied that organisations can target intra-organisational communication to enhance innovation and, hence, enhance their performance. A focus on innovative mechanisms and performance, hence, drives corporate interest and devotion to improvement of intra-organisational communication.

Indeed, the significance of intra-organisational communication to innovation in organisations is acknowledged by a number of studies. Bruhn and Ahlers (2017) and Suh, Harrington and

Goodman (2018) both argue that intra-organisational communication is extremely important for innovation within an organisation. Moreover, Verčič and Vokić (2017) state that intra-organisational communication is the *cause* of innovation in an organisation. Furthermore, this notion can be supported using ideas from knowledge management too. Lee et al. (2016), Mahdi, Nassar and Almsafir (2019) and Torres, Ferraz and Santos-Rodrigues (2018) all identify knowledge management as an approach that considers knowledge to be the source of innovation and competitive advantage in an organisation. As knowledge transfer is dependent upon the quality of intra-organisational communication, its value to innovation becomes quite clear (Quirke, 2012). This is illustrated below:

Figure 2.12: The Impacts of Intra-organisational Communication on Innovation in Companies

Source: (Pfeffermann, Minshall and Mortara, 2013)

In the above figure, the influence of intra-organisational communication on innovation has been clearly illustrated. From this, it follows that if a company focuses on innovation, it has to enhance intra-organisational communication. In this way, the focus on innovation and innovative mechanisms drives improvements in intra-organisational communication (and presence of innovative mechanisms is evidence of effective intra-organisational communication) (Pfeffermann, Minshall and Mortar, 2013). Alternatively, the absence of innovative mechanisms or a focus on innovation reflects absence of effective intra-organisational communication (or emphasis on it). Either way, a lack of innovative mechanisms is another challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

So far, the relationship between intra-organisational communication has been found to be two-faceted (in synonymy to the one between intra-organisational communication and employee engagement). Given this close relationship between the two variables, the lack of innovative

mechanisms can create challenges for intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. This is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.13: Lack of Innovative Mechanisms and Challenges to Intra-organisational

Source: (Pfeffermann, Minshall and Mortara, 2013)

The above figure clearly shows that a lack of innovative mechanisms reflects low emphasis on intra-organisational communication and further restricts communication in a company too. Therefore, it posits two-faceted challenges to intra-organisational communication.

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis has been drawn out:

H4: Lack of innovative mechanisms has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.9.5. Low Levels of Internal Branding

In addition to that, organisations around the world have made use of other techniques, such as internal marketing and branding (BMW, for example), rebranding (Tata Motors) and utilization of soft/respectable language when dealing with workers (Rolls-Royce) to improve internal communication. Again, Pakistani organisations lag behind their international counterparts when it comes to the use of such techniques. The highly bureaucratic structure of the organisations, coupled with high levels of change resistance, makes it difficult for the organisations within Pakistan to resort to the internal branding strategy, as the perspective of

the employee being customers is not yet prevalent within the industry (Butt and Katuse, 2017). It is clear that intra-organisational communication and internal branding are closely tied concepts. Indeed, Lee, Kim and Kim (2014) identify intra-organisational communication as an important component of internal branding. This means that a low level of internal branding is equivalent to poor intra-organisational communication. It must further be pointed out that as companies face challenges in developing internal branding frameworks, their attention to intra-organisational communication suffers too, making the low levels of internal branding a challenge for intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector.

This notion is supported further in the work of Punjaisri and Wilson (2017), who point out that the presence of effective intra-organisational communication is necessary for the success of internal branding tactics deployed by an organisation. It is further stated that communicating brand characteristics internally is necessary for internal branding and this process depends on effective intra-organisational communication. Effectively, this implies that in the absence of strong intra-organisational communication, internal branding cannot function at all. Liu, Ko and Chapleo (2017) provide further support for this idea, stating that inter-functional communication increases the efficacy of internal branding in companies. Inter-functional communication refers to the transfer of information and interactions between workers from different departments within a company (which is a specific example of intra-organisational communication).

In contrast, Matanda and Ndubisi (2013) do not consider intra-organisational communication to be a factor that affects internal branding. Rather, the authors posit it as a component of internal branding. Similarly, Dryl (2017) identifies communication to be a part of internal branding, extending support for this notion. Under this viewpoint, intra-organisational communication can be deemed *essential* rather than *beneficial* for internal branding. This means that while intra-organisational communication was supposed to be a factor that improved internal branding, this viewpoint implies that internal branding cannot happen without effective intra-organisational communication. The different views regarding internal branding and intra-organisational communication are illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.14: The Relationship between Intra-organisational Communication and Internal Branding

Source: Developed by Author

Regardless of the exact nature that intra-organisational communication shares with internal branding, the above figure (and preceding discussion) firmly establish the fact that researchers have expressed near unanimous agreement regarding its existence. This means that intra-organisational communication is important for internal branding and contributes to it. Such a relationship has important implications for this research, because low levels of internal branding may be indicative of ‘decreased need for intra-organisational communication’ (Verghese, 2012). Thus, companies may stop investing in intra-organisational communication, causing weakness. In this way, low levels of internal branding may be a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. The following figure sheds light on this notion:

Figure 2.15: Emphasis on Internal Branding and its Impact on Intra-organisational

Source: Developed by Author

It is clearly illustrated in the above figure that low levels of internal branding are illustrative of negligible managerial attention being devoted to intra-organisational communication. This is attributable to the fact that had intra-organisational communication been on the management's agenda, measures would have been taken to improve it. Such improvement would have resulted in enhanced internal branding (Piehler, Hanisch and Burmann (2015), Merrilees and Frazer (2013) and Dhawan and Prior (2017) all suggest that improving intra-organisational communication facilitates the internal flow of information, which has positive impacts on internal branding. In a situation where organisations do not provide significance to internal branding and low levels of internal branding prevail, the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication is negatively influenced too (Verghese, 2012).

A mention of Pakistani culture and managerial practices in Pakistani companies may also shed light on the issue at hand. Inderyas et al. (2015) reveal that the Pakistani culture has been

observed to be one that has high power distance score on Hofstede’s cultural dimensions model. In cultures with high power distance, managerial practices tend to be supportive of hierarchical structures and high levels of control. Gul et al. (2018) comment that high power-distance facilitates the creation of companies with hierarchical structures and limited employee freedom. In such a situation, the value given to workers’ preferences or awareness regarding the brand is limited. Consequently, the need for internal branding is not felt (Merrilees and Frazer (2013) have identified internal branding to be a process that involves top-down transfer of information regarding the brand within an organisation).

Given the prevalence of power distance in Pakistan, low levels of internal branding are not unheard of. Again, the reason behind this remains same. Internal branding focuses on improving employee performance and commitment by enhancing communication and flow of information regarding the brand (Iyer, Davari and Paswan, 2018; Dhawan and Prior, 2017). In a culture that does not value employees’ attention and preferences, internal branding is not considered to be necessary. As a result, intra-organisational communication is not developed to the extent that it would be when internal branding is considered to be important. The reason remains here too. Intra-organisational communication is used to support internal branding in organisations (Merrilees and Frazer, 2013; Piehler, Hanisch and Burmann, 2015). These factors are summarized in the figure below:

Figure 2.16: The Challenge Emerging from Low Levels of Internal Branding

Source: Developed by Author

Simply put, the levels of internal branding in Pakistani companies remains low because of the country's culture and this limits the extent to which intra-organisational communication is worked upon. Therefore, low levels of internal branding also constitute an important challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis has been drawn out:

H5: Low levels of internal branding have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.9.6. Lack of Technology

The importance of technology to communication in the realm of business is a widely discussed theme. While a significant proportion of such studies focus on business-business and other forms of external communications (business-customers, for instance)- Nguyen, Newby and Macaulay (2015), Jussila, Karkkainen and Aramo-Immonen (2014) and Agnihotri et al. (2016) are examples of such studies-, studies that link intra-organisational communication with technological advancements can also be found. Such studies may be broad or specific. For instance, Conrad and Newberry (2012) state that information technology competence is a critical communication-related skill in business. Business communication involves both internal and external forms of communication within organisations (Guffey and Loewy, 2020). From this, it follows that the need for information technology competence in business implies that technology plays a significant role in business communications and since it also involves intra-organisational communication, a link between the two concerned variables (technology and intra-organisational communication may be implied).

The new media theory, as suggested by the research of Friedl and Vercic (2011); Meshi, Tamir and Heekeren (2015) can be used here to better highlight the weaknesses of intra-communication within Pakistan. The case study organisation showed that the company lacks the technological and innovative measures that can be used to enhance the communication. In addition to that, there is also an absence of the infrastructure that is needed to support such innovative measures. As the company as a whole does not deploy new media to boost the overall effectiveness of intra-organisational communication, the weakness prevails, which can have a negative impact on the overall learning and performance within the organisation. This

can be backed up by the strategic theory, which clearly states that a strong link exists between the intra-organisational communication and organisational performance and learning (García-Morales, Matias-Rache and Verdu-Jover, 2011; Kanyurhi and Bugandwa Mungu Akonkwa, 2016).

Even though broad studies such as Conrad and Newberry (2012) can be used to implicate a strong link between technology and intra-organisational communication, specific research can also be found. In Young and Hinesly (2014), the use of social media for promotion of intra-organisational communication is discussed. It is stated that contemporary organisations are relying on social media for intra-organisational communication and the successful implementation of this measure tends to enhance performance, coordination, collaboration and innovation. Furthermore, Men (2014) discusses the various 'novel' channels of intra-organisational communication too, stating that social media allows for two-way exchange of information between employees (peer-peer communication) and hence, serves as an excellent conduit for intra-organisational communication. On the other hand, online chat platforms, embedded video/ audio and webcams have all been identified as possible channels to supplement intra-organisational communication in organisations.

Apart from that, Lipiäinen, Karjaluoto and Nevalainen (2014) support the idea that digital technologies can be deployed for intra-organisational communication, but also identifies those unique skills may be needed for their use, creating some challenges in their adoption. Despite this, blogs, communities and social media are used by organisations for intra-organisational communication (apart from serving their purpose in external communication and brand building). The use of these technology-dependent channels of communication certainly demonstrates the significance of technology to intra-organisational communication.

A slightly different notion is presented in the work of Jiménez-Castillo and Sánchez-Pérez (2013), who state that integrated information technology, coupled with efficient intra-organisational communication improves absorptive capacity and knowledge transfer among workers. While this paper seems to be related with knowledge management, it must be noted that the presence of integrated information technology is deemed necessary for positive influence of intra-organisational communication to be observed. Thus, this study posits information technology as an important potentiator of intra-organisational communication.

This means that integrated information technology may not have directly documentable impacts on intra-organisational communication, but its presence enhances the latter. The following figure sheds light on the nature of the relationship between technology and intra-organisational communication:

Figure 2.17: The Impacts of Technology on Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by Author

The above figure clearly shows that technology has a strong positive influence on intra-organisational communication. In a way, technology may even be considered to be necessary for efficient intra-organisational communication too (Guffey and Loewy, 2010). This significance that technology possesses can be used to explain the challenge that arises in the event that it is not easily available. For example, Men (2014) comments that while channels of communication that rely on technology are not replacements for face-to-face communication, they contribute to relationship building (both peer to peer and peer to management, because workers interact with other workers and the management over these channels of communication). Similarly, Young and Hinesly (2014) claim that reliance on social media for intra-organisational communication improves performance, coordination, collaboration and innovation. In the event that a firm fails to access such technologies, intra-organisational communication will be deprived of these benefits. Consequently, a lack of technology constitutes a significant challenge to intra-organisational communication.

Furthermore, the relevance of this challenge to the automotive sector can be illustrated with the help of examples from other organisations. Companies in the automotive sector rely on digital technologies to enhance intra-organisational communication, as evident from examples of Volkswagen (Porsiel, 2008), as well as Rolls-Royce (McGrattan, 2015). The fact that these leading firms of the global automotive sector rely on technology to support intra-organisational communication reinforces the idea that technology is, indeed, essential for intra-organisational

communication in the automotive sector. Also, in the absence of such supportive technologies as communication platforms, applications or social media, intra-organisational communication is likely to remain weak (Guffey and Loewy, 2010).

Going further in the discussion, it is important to remember that the Pakistani automobile sector is considerably underdeveloped when compared to those of the UK, the USA, Germany or even India (which is a developing country). This is because all these regions capitalize upon their resource base to engage their employees and enhance the level of information transmission within the organisation. In addition to that, they also use this technology to develop various platforms, such as mobile apps and employee communication portal so as to ensure that intra-organisational communication is facilitated and the organisations benefit from them (Sarwar et al, 2015). It further indicates that the country's automobile sector requires several improvements before it can function at the same level as those of its international peers.

As the automotive sector of Pakistan is weaker than developed countries like the UK, the USA or Germany (and even some under-developed countries like India), there is a paucity of resources. This factor is likely involved in the creation of a lack of technology, which then goes on to negatively impact intra-organisational communication. Indeed, in Lipiäinen, Karjaluoto and Nevalainen (2014), as well as Conrad and Newberry (2012) the need for technological competence and skills for intra-organisational communication has been mentioned. Moreover, Young and Hinesly (2014) state that the benefits offered by social media in intra-organisational communication can be realized only if the technology is implemented appropriately. Such assertions imply that the deployment of technology in intra-organisational communication is a complex task involving infrastructure development, as well as improvements to human capital. These processes can be costly, putting burden on resource-poor organisations.

There are other reasons behind the lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan too. For instance, in Ahmed et al. (2010), it has been revealed that companies in Pakistan rarely rely on software or technology for communication (without any mention of the expense or resource-consumption involved), indicating there are other variables in action. Considering the fact that advancements in information systems and technology have contributed to the seamlessness of communication within companies, Adisa, Gbadamosi and Osabutey (2017) show that the use of mobile information technology devices improves the effectiveness of intra-

organisational communication), their lack in Pakistani organisations presents a significant challenge to the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication.

Based on the aforementioned discussion, the following hypothesis has been drawn out:

H6: Lack of technology has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.9.7. Ineffective Payment and Reward Systems

Again, automotive sector companies in Pakistan can work on developing effective reward, recognition and communication systems that engage and acknowledge workers, while simultaneously allowing them to express their views (Saleem, 2015). This can be helpful in improving the quality of internal communications, as well as operations. However, the progress in this case is also very limited, which also acts as a major challenge for the intra-organisation communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

According to Amah, Nwuche and Chukwuigwe (2013), an effective payment and reward system consists of a high-quality intra-organisational communication framework, because the latter is a determinant of employee satisfaction. If payment and reward systems remain ineffective and organisations do not take measures to improve them, the quality of communication frameworks underpinning them remains poor too (Shields et al., 2015). Consequently, ineffective payment and reward systems, coupled with absence of organisational reforms for their improvement, act as barriers to effective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

This notion can be extended further with the help of other works too. Sievert and Scholz (2017), for instance, comment that intra-organisational communication tools serve to improve transparency in transmission of information within an organisation. This is in line with the needs of workers, who require greater transparency to understand their role, performance and organisational operations. From the perspective of rewards, payments and performance appraisals, transparency has been deemed to be crucial by Prasad (2015) and Ciobanu and Ristea (2015). Furthermore, Wenzel, Krause and Vogel (2019) identify transparency in performance management to be a key construct for improving employee motivation. So, it can

be said that intra-organisational communication improves transparency in organisational processes (including performance appraisal and management), which is necessary for the normal functioning of payment and reward systems. In this way, the role of intra-organisational communication is extremely critical in payment and reward systems.

Apart from that, Subari and Riady (2015) point out that performance management is, in fact, a form of communication between employees and the management on an ongoing basis. This reaffirms the idea that intra-organisational communication (particularly of the peer to management variety) is crucial to performance management in organisations. Moreover, Decramer, Smolders and Vanderstraeten (2013), as well as De Waal (2013) outline the fact that intra-organisational communication is essential for effective performance management in an organisation. As performance management involves payment and reward systems, this implies that intra-organisational communication is needed for the development of effective payment and reward systems. This is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.18: Intra-organisational Communication and its Role in Payment and Reward

Source: Developed by Author

The important role that intra-organisational communication plays in ensuring the effectiveness of payment and reward systems is clearly demonstrated in the above figure. Another important factor that is illustrated in the figure is that an organisation can resort to the improvement of intra-organisational communication as a tool for improving performance management and hence, reward systems. This assertion is true to the work of Subari and Riady (2015), who claim that performance management requires prolonged and regular communication between workers and the management. Therefore, if payment and reward systems are not to be improved, intra-organisational communication is not enhanced either, making the prevalence of ineffective payment and reward systems another important challenge here. This is demonstrated in the figure below:

Figure 2.19: The Intra-organisational Communication Issues Stemming from Low Significance of Employee Engagement

Source: (De Waal, 2013; Guffey and Loewy, 2010)

The above figure clearly shows that the prevalence of ineffective payment and reward systems is a limiting factor for intra-organisational communication because the focus that companies place on the latter is reduced. This is based on the assumption that due to the importance of intra-organisational communication to performance management and reward systems (acknowledged in the works of Subari and Riady (2015), as well as Decramer, Smolders and Vanderstraeten (2013)), a major motivation for the management to work on intra-organisational communication stems from the need for developing strong reward systems. The absence of this need can result in lower need and reduced effectiveness of intra-organisational communication.

Even though the challenge that has been described to this extent applies to all automotive sector organisations (including those in Pakistan), it is critical to identify any factors that may potentially increase its significance in the said country, as compared to automotive sector companies in other developed and developing nations. Inderyas et al. (2015)'s findings regarding the power distance in Pakistan are of relevance here too. As per the study, Pakistan's culture is one that features high power density, implying that distribution of power is uneven, with well-defined hierarchical power relationships in most settings. Gul et al. (2015)'s findings are relevant in this section too because they link high power distance with the prevalence of hierarchies in organisational structure. In addition to that, high power distance has been linked with less importance given to freedom and involvement of workers too.

From the above discussion, it can be claimed that workplaces in Pakistan follow well-defined power relationships and hierarchies with a low focus on the preferences and involvement of workers. Performance management, as well as payment and reward systems, are unlikely to be subject to managerial interest in such settings. The primary reason behind this is that performance management and payment/ reward systems are looked upon as factors that improve employee engagement and motivation (Dewettinck and van Dijk, 2013; Lee and Raschke, 2016; Shields et al., 2015). In a workplace where employee involvement and motivation are not considered important at all, the use of tactics that enhance these factors is unlikely. This implies that companies in Pakistan are highly susceptible to the challenge posed by ineffective payment and reward systems because of the culture and workplace dynamics. As a consequence, the prevalence of ineffective payment and reward systems poses a significant challenge to intra-organisational communication in the country.

Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis drawn out:

H7: Ineffective payment and reward structures has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

2.10. Research Gap

The research on internal communication, as suggested by the above literature review, is an interdisciplinary topic that has been studied by other authors. All of these researchers agree on the fact that intra-organisational communication plays an important role in the success of the organisations (Men, 2014; Welch, 2012; Zhang et al., 2016; De Araujo et al., 2012; Elving et al., 2015) and the key element of this communication is to ensure that a transparent environment is maintained throughout the organisation so as to make sure that the employees are aware of the issues and opportunities that are confronted by the organisation (Welch, 2012). This, as a result, can enhance the employee productivity and reduce the rate of employee turnover as well as absenteeism (Karanges et al., 2015; Ruck and Welch, 2012).

In addition to that, it has also been indicated by the research that the development and management of effective internal communication channels is also imperative for the effective management of organisations (Men, 2014). To do so, it is necessary for organisations to ensure that specific channels are developed through which employees receive information that is

relevant to their jobs and that can help them in performing their tasks effectively (van Ruler, 2018). Similar to any other organisational activity, the organisational communication channels shall also be planned, constructed and managed in an organized manner. This means that the lines of communication, authority and responsibility shall be well defined. In addition to that, these channels should be easily accessible and holistic feedback loops shall be developed to ensure that any loopholes in these channels are identified and eliminated accordingly. This, as a result, helps the companies to transmit knowledge all across the organisation. In addition to that, it also allows for enhanced problem solving through wider integration. Furthermore, it also allows for the management of employee grievances in a more effective manner (Zhang et al., 2016; Mersham, 2016).

A large amount of research pertaining to this topic have focused majorly on the development of the intra-organisational communication channels as well as the formulation of the strategies that can help the organisations in managing these channels in an effective and appropriate manner (Jacobs, Yu and Chavez, 2016; Welch, 2012; Karanges et al., 2015; Mazzei and Ravazzani, 2017). It has been indicated that there is a need for additional research in the area of intra-organisational communication, specifically in regard to the communication that is mediated by technology, including the use of emails as well as the intranet (Palttala et al., 2012).

National economic growth is entirely reliant on effective performance of major industries. Global studies show that prosperous economies have a backbone of highly effective and well-developed industries, which include, among others, the automobiles sector (Law, 2017). This illustrates that the automotive industry has potential to become one of the leading industries of any country's economy (with considerable contributions in important areas like GDP and employment) (Zahoor Sarwar et al., 2011). The current corporate environment is extremely competitive and poses a number of challenges for the automobile sector, including strict regulation, strong pressure to maintain up-to-date technological infrastructure and constant variations in consumer requirements (Díaz-Garrido, Martín-Peña, and Sánchez-López, 2016).

Considering the importance of the automobile sector, several researchers and organisations have conducted studies to identify strategies which can allow companies to cope with these challenges and operate effectively. Law (2017), for example, studied Honda's operations,

reporting that the organisation had successfully cut down its production costs by introducing flexible, small volume operations.

Similar research has been conducted on other organisations, particularly Mercedes-Benz and BMW by McDermott, (2014) showing that these organisations possess effectiveness and prowess in relation to operations and quality. Similarly, Durai (2017) conducted research on how employee motivation, a clear allocation of tasks and job satisfaction influence performance of automotive organisations. In addition to that, the work of Ivanova, Kaeschel and Ivanov (2015) has focused on operations of Lexus, a subdivision of the Toyota Motor Company, commenting on the need for integrating different operations and functions to improve the quality of operations. Other than that, Anurit, Newman and Chansarkar (2011) have commented on techniques and strategies used by different company's luxury automobile companies that exist in the global markets to keep their customers satisfied.

While the relationship between internal communication, production management and its importance in automobile companies has been studied extensively in countries such as Germany and the UK, it has not been explored to a similar extent in Pakistan (Rawlinson and Wells, 2016). Moreover, literature review shows that automotive organisations in Pakistan do not adopt measures for improving internal communication and, therefore, can struggle with production integration, limiting their performance as compared to similar organisations based in developed nations like Germany, the UK, the USA or Japan (Butt, Katuse and Namada, 2018). In addition to that, the lack of research conducted in this area in Pakistan also presents an issue, limiting advancements in this field, as well as improvements of internal communication and subsequently, manufacturing effectiveness and overall organisational performance in the country's automobile sector (Sarwar et al., 2012). The lack of research in this area further hampers the assessment of how intra-organisational communication works within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

The concerned research focuses on targeting these gaps by emphasizing the automotive sector of Pakistan, which has remained neglected in existing studies. On the other hand, by focusing on specific aspects of intra-organisational communication that have remained neglected in existing studies, this study can allow for covering up gaps. For instance, by discussing the nature and onset of challenges, as well as the interplay of employee-related, management-

related, culture-related and region-related factors that give rise to them, the depth of understanding regarding this matter can be increased, while simultaneously increasing the likelihood of smarter solutions to the issues being identified and implemented. Not only can this facilitate the attainment of research goals and objectives, it can also cover some important gaps in the existing literature, which can be particularly beneficial from an academic, as well as practical viewpoint.

The review clearly indicates that automotive sectors or countries like Germany are much more advanced than that of Pakistan when it comes to intra-organisational communication (Butt and Katuse, 2017). The integration of ICT in intra-organisational communication, as well as the use of other innovative technologies like 3D printing and modern data analytics has allowed organisations to improve the status of communication, as well as level of performance (Rehnberg and Ponte, 2018). Although researchers have different views regarding the individual impact of each of these tools on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sectors of different countries, one implication can be drawn from studies conducted on other countries: Pakistan is lagging behind many developed, as well as developing nations in regard to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector (Sarwar et al., 2012). The country's lagging status is primarily attributable to the lack of research observed in Pakistan, along with the resistance shown by Pakistani automotive companies in the adoption of new and innovative techniques for bolstering intra-organisational communication (Khan, Lew and Akhtar, 2016; Qadir, 2016). This outlines a major gap in research pertaining to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector, which needs to be dealt with by future research. Moreover, this may or may not be indicative of the lack of importance of intra-organisational communication within this region. The concrete answer to this aspect will be developed in this study.

One of the key goals of this research thesis is to gain a better understanding of the intra-organisational communication issue that exists within the region of Pakistan, particularly the automobile sector. The paper will assess the common challenges that are confronted by the automobile sector of Pakistan when it comes to intra-organisational communication and what the impact of these challenges is on the performance of these companies. In this case, this thesis will conduct a detailed analysis on Atlas Honda, which is one of the leading organisations within the automobile sector of Pakistan. The intra-organisational communication channels of

the company will be examined, and the challenges and benefits associated with these channels will also be assessed in detail. In addition to that, this paper will also assess how the automobile companies strive to manage these challenges. As a result, this thesis will become one of the few papers that pertain to the intra-organisational communication challenges within the automobile sector of Pakistan.

As mentioned above, a large body of literature has established that intra-organisational communication plays an important role in enhancing the overall outcomes of the organisations. A large number of studies, including Ruck and Welch (2012), Verčič Verčič, and Sriramesh (2012), have assessed the impact of intra-organisational communication on the overall organisational effectiveness. The research conducted by Ruck and Welch (2012), on the other hand, indicates that the perceptions of the employees in relation to the intra-organisational communication are very important for the implementation of successful communication strategies within organisations, which in return have an influential and evident impact on the overall outcomes of the organisation. Verčič Verčič, and Sriramesh, (2012) have indicated that the influences of intra-organisational communication on the psychological aspects of the employees, such as trust, loyalty and commitment are quite evident and established. There is, however, limited research on role played by intra-organisational communication in the alignment of the personal goals of the employees with the strategic goals of the organisations through the alteration of the psychological beliefs of the employees (Mazzei, 2018).

To cater to the above issues, this thesis also addresses the research gap associated with limited information of how the challenges associated with the intra-organisational communication have an impact on the overall psychological beliefs of employees. The thesis will, therefore, analyze how the levels of the intra-organisational communication within an organisation (including internal peer, internal corporate communication, as well as internal line management) have an impact on the overall psychological beliefs and performance of the employees as well as the performance of the organisations.

Given the fact that inter-organisational communication has become imperative for the success of the organisations, there has been a consistent increase in the number of research conducted in this area (Ahmed et al., 2010; Hynes, 2012). An assessment of the literature, however, indicates that most of such research focus on the organisations having remote teams, with a

specific focus on the multi-national corporations, with minimal focus on the companies that operate in automobile sector. One of the aims for the development of this research is that the automobile sector of Pakistan includes large global players, as well as native organisations (Abbasi, Sheikh and Hassan, 2015). This can make the product development process complex, spanning multiple regions (Christopher, 2016). The integration of all the functions of such an organisation is critical for the enhancement of the business performance (Mackelprang et al., 2014). At the same time, as these organisations confront complex supply chains and support service processes, they confront a large number of barriers that can hinder intra-organisational communication. This thesis, therefore, aims to address this gap in the literature by conducting an in-depth analysis of the intra-organisational communication challenges that are confronted by the automobile sector of Pakistan.

2.11. Conceptual Framework

On the basis of the above analysis, the following conceptual framework is proposed for this study:

Figure 2.20: Conceptual Framework

Source: Developed by Author

A summary of themes observed across the literature is provided in the table below:

Table 2.4: Summary of Themes Observed Across the Literature

Authors	Themes
Yin and Kaynak (2015); Dremel et al. (2017)	Big data analytics and the insights that they provide to organisations can improve decision-making, making them crucial for the automotive sector in the future, especially due to the growing popularity of connected vehicles that communicate with other vehicles and the environment. The significance of big data in the automotive sector creates challenges in intra-organisational communication due to the sheer complexity associated with collection processing, management and interpretation of the large volumes of unstructured information.
Mazzei (2018); Quratulain et al. (2018); Dwyer and Hopwood (2019)	Pakistani culture is dominated by high power distance. This implies that well-defined hierarchies are prevalent in which organisational values and objectives may be imposed upon workers without significant importance being given to their own goals and objectives. This one-way emphasis can create barriers to the implementation of effective intra-organisational communication.
Karanges et al. (2015); Kang and Sung (2017); Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014)	Intra-organisational communication is closely related to employee engagement. Companies often rely on the enhancement of intra-organisational communication in order to improve employee engagement (which itself tends to have positive impacts on commitment and performance). Automotive sector companies are no different and, as they focus on the engagement of workers, they improve the quality of intra-organisational communication. The absence of emphasis on employee engagement, therefore, prevents companies from taking measures to improve intra-organisational communication.
De Medeiros, Ribeiro and Cortimiglia (2014); Saleem (2015); Sarwar et al. (2012)	Innovation represents change or unconventionality in organisational practices. Thus, innovation in communication implies the use of intra-organisational communication practices that are unconventional, focusing on the identification of new solutions to communication-related challenges. On the other hand, the absence of innovation in the Pakistani automotive sector has also been recognized. The lack of innovation in intra-organisational communication implies that communication-related needs remain relatively unattended, creating challenges in accomplishing effective intra-organisational communication.
Lee, Kim and Kim (2014); Butt and Katuse (2017)	Intra-organisational communication is a significant component of internal branding in organisations. An organisation boasting a strong internal branding platform consists of an effective intra-organisational communication framework to back it. If the internal branding framework is weak, as is the case in Pakistani organisations, the chances of intra-organisational communication being effective are limited. Moreover, if

*Ahmed et al. (2010);
Adisa, Gbadamosi and
Osabutey (2017)*

companies take negligible measures to improve internal branding, the extent to which intra-organisational communication can be improved also remains low.

Communication technologies are subject to literary and economic interest as they provide companies with an option to improve intra-organisational communication. The availability of information systems and communication technologies increases the quality of intra-organisational communication. At the same time, absence of these technologies or slow adoption on a company's part can limit the extent to which intra-organisational communication can be improved. Therefore, the absence or slow adoption of communication technologies can act as a challenge to intra-organisational communication

*Amah, Nwuche and
Chukwuigwe (2013);
Saleem (2015)*

Much like the notion of internal branding or employee engagement, intra-organisational communication is also closely related to payment and reward systems within an organisation. Companies focus on the development of strong payment and reward systems to improve employee satisfaction and, in the process, it is necessary for them to enhance intra-organisational communication. If reward and payment systems remain ineffective, it is highly likely that the quality of intra-organisational communication is poor.

2.12. Chapter Summary

In this chapter, a review of the existing literature relevant to intra-organisational communication and the challenges that automotive companies in Pakistan face in relation to it was conducted. Intra-organisational communication involves the transfer of information between workers and management, making it critical for coordination, innovation, and performance enhancement in organisations. Intra-organisational communication (both peer to peer and peer to management) has been found to be significant for the normal functioning of companies (irrespective of their industry). Among other benefits, intra-organisational communication allows for higher organisational performance, employee commitment and integration of operations.

Using examples from automotive sector organisations in the developed world (Germany, United States, UK, Italy and Japan), it has been demonstrated that the use of novel information technology and systems can improve intra-organisational performance. On the other hand, those from the developing world (India and South Africa) have been used to demonstrate the use of employee engagement-related techniques to bolster intra-organisational communication.

Considering the practices used by companies across the world, as well as distinct characteristics of the automotive sector of Pakistan, such as the lack of resources or absence of emphasis on important areas associated with intra-organisational communication, seven main challenges to intra-organisational communication have been identified. These are related to the complexity and lack of technology, absence of innovation and poor emphasis on internal branding, employee engagement, personal goals of workers and reward systems.

Specific characteristics of workplaces in Pakistan, such as the prevalence of hierarchies and control-centric managerial practices have been linked with the challenges to intra-organisational communication in an attempt to understand the susceptibility of companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan to these factors. Often, a challenge has been found to stem from low emphasis being placed on aspects that require effective intra-organisational communication (such as employee engagement and payment/ reward systems) because such a scenario can limit resources invested in intra-organisational communication (as it is not deemed necessary).

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1. Chapter Introduction

With reference to Gunasekare (2015) study, it is found that methodology is considered and referred as the prime pillar of the research as it helps in setting up the best means and methods so that the aim and objectives as well as questions and hypothesis can be answered. In addition, Bradt et al., (2013) has defined that the methodology is also referred as the system of methods that are cast-off in specific study or activity area to obtain quality results with minimal likelihood of risk and errors that could affect the scope and time of the study, supported by Khan (2014). In addition to this, Alavi and Habek (2016) has stated that the method or methodology in the research related work is considered as the contextual framework for research, which is also referred by some professionals such as Zhang and Creswell (2013) and Creswell and Clark (2017) as a coherent and logical framework based on ideas, beliefs and values that guides the researchers to passably complete the research. Hence, the researcher of the anticipated study has acted accordingly and therefore, have engrossed keenly on selecting suitable means and methods so that the end-goal of the entitled study can be accomplished.

The following chapter concentrates on tools and techniques adopted to conduct the research study. Exclusively outlining within its structure are the research approach, methods taken, as well as explaining the population and sampling techniques that were utilised and adopted throughout the research. Additionally, data collection methods and research instruments have been included, as well as a discussion of the validity and reliability of the research instruments. Finally, the chapter concludes with the discussion of ethical considerations. Therefore, below mentioned are the hypothesis, which have been designed in Chapter in accordance with the aim and objectives, as well as the literature and the conceptual framework that has been assimilated, designed, and reviewed from studies, which have been conducted by diversified professionals and experts.

- H1: Complexity of big data analysis has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- H2: Lack of focus on personal goals of the employees has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

- H3: Lack of focus on employee engagement has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- H4: Lack of innovative mechanisms has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- H5: Low levels of internal branding have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- H6: Lack of technology has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- H7: Ineffective payment and reward structures have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

3.2. Research Philosophy

3.2.1. Theory

According to Bryman and Bell (2015) study, it is found that the research theory is made up of a researcher's assumptions about the phenomenon or topic being studied. In general, epistemology information about the research object that is proven to be true and doxology information about the research object that is assumed to be true guide research philosophy (Zikmund et al., 2013).

The following are the key research philosophies:

- **Positivism:** the idea that knowledge is only that which can be proven using scientific means or logical proof. It is further argued that observation of natural phenomena is the only concrete manner of understanding them and moral considerations or perceptions are not to be taken into consideration during the knowledge creation process (Taylor and Medina, 2011).
- **Interpretivism:** integrates human interest and perceptions into the research process, calling upon researchers to look for meaning and reality in both the world, as well as associated consciousness (Bryman and Bell, 2015). As per this philosophy, reality and knowledge can only be attained via social constructs, such as shared meanings, language and consciousness.
- **Realism:** this philosophy draws boundaries between human imagination and reality, arguing that reality is that which is perceived by human senses (Zikmund et al., 2013). However, a branch of realism known as critical realism argues that humans may

perceive illusions and deceptions too and thus, researchers need to be careful when seeking the reality (Danermark, Esktrom and Karlsson, 2019).

- Pragmatism: from a philosophical viewpoint, pragmatism assesses knowledge and reality by the practicality of it. This implies that the viability of a theory or idea, under pragmatism, is evaluated on the basis of its practical outcomes (Biesta, 2010). In the context of research work, pragmatism calls for assessment of practical outcomes to create or assess knowledge.

3.2.2. Chosen Research Philosophy

Positivism is suited for this research because it allows for studies to be free from subjective influences and, hence, can allow for the attainment of objectives, which are related with the identification and analysis of intra-organisational communication's challenges (Ghauri, 2004). Since the objectives of this research are not concerned with subjective ideas regarding intra-organisational communication, this can be quite helpful. Furthermore, positivism may also make the research generalizable, adding to its value and usefulness (Zikmund et al., 2013).

Given the fact that this research is concerned with the identification of factors that can influence intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies in Pakistan, positivism's support for the formation and assessment of relationships and validation of hypotheses can be particularly helpful. Moreover, it has been mentioned that by encouraging the formation and assessment of relationships between phenomena, positivism lays down foundations for the prediction of social and natural phenomena (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Therefore, in this research's contexts, basing proceedings on a positivist philosophy can allow this paper to make sound predictions regarding which factors may impact intra-organisational communication in automotive sector organisations and the ways in which they might do so. Both these factors are quite closely related with this research's objectives, further bolstering the rationale behind using positivism (Quinlan et al., 2019).

Apart from that, studies on this topic (or on similar ones) are frequently conducted under the light of positivism. For instance, Zhang, Van Donk and van der Vaart (2016) base their study on the positivist approach, as evident from their choice of research methods and design (which closely comply with the philosophy, as the latter guides the overall research process). Much like the rationale presented here, positivism suited the said study's purpose and nature. Zhang,

Van Donk and van der Vaart (2016)'s study was concerned with the impacts of intra-organisational communication and ICT on supply chain performance, and hence, had to establish relationships and make predictions via empirical observation, which are processes that align closely with the core principle of knowledge creation as being possible via observation of natural phenomena using scientific means, thereby justifying the use of positivism.

In addition to that, two other studies discussed in this paper as part of the literature review also base their research process on the positivist paradigm, namely Zahoor Sarwar et al. (2012) and Yan et al. (2016). The former is concerned with identifying the level of productivity within the automotive sector of Pakistan, linking it with prevalent conditions and pointing out factors that may result in improvement. The latter, on the other hand, is focused on identifying factors that limit or enhance the extent and nature of knowledge sharing and communication.

Despite the presence of differences in the topics being studied by this research and the two mentioned earlier, it is evident that the nature and objectives are somewhat similar. All three are concerned with the identification of the relationships between a set of variables and how some factors may influence an entity of interest. The fact that these studies also make use of a research process based on positivism also adds to the rationale behind the selection of the concerned research philosophy for the purpose of this research (Hair et al., 2015). This is mainly attributable to the fact that these studies also probe somewhat related topics and, more importantly, have similar objectives and nature to the research under consideration.

3.3. Research Approach

3.3.1. Theory

Inductive and deductive approaches are the most frequently used research approaches, which align with the principles of inductive and deductive reasoning respectively. The inductive method aids in producing new theories and ideas derived from existing or new information obtained from data, while the deductive approach aids and benefits theory and hypotheses testing (Marschan-Piekkari and Welch, 2004). In addition to that, the abductive approach has also been identified by scholars. This approach looks for the simplest possible explanation for any observation or phenomenon. Hence, for research based on abductive reasoning, the process

involves the observation phase, where different observations are made, followed by inquiry into the reasons or explanations and culmination with the identification of the simplest explanation (Lipscomb, 2012). While there are similarities to the deductive approach, the abductive approach is different in that it does not seek verification of the conclusion made by it (Walton, 2014). That is, even though it suggests the simplest explanation, no empirical proof or evidence is provided to back this conclusion.

3.3.2. Chosen Research approach

The research under consideration makes use of the deductive research approach. In literal terms, deductive reasoning involves the use of existing facts and theories, in a logical manner to make arguments regarding existing problems and phenomena. Pfeifer and Kleiter (2010) argue that logic is of particular importance in deductive reasoning, implying that the arguments, evaluations or assertions presented within the research must be aligned with present knowledge and logic.

In addition to that, another cornerstone of studies based on the deductive approach is the formation and evaluation of hypotheses. Generally, existing literature is reviewed with regards to the topic or problem at hand to come up with hypotheses, which are then verified by accessing data- (usually quantitative) collected for the study (Saunders, 2011). The concerned research is not different; hypotheses pertaining to the factors affecting intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan have been developed and assessed to yield findings.

3.3.3. Rationale

The selection of the deductive research approach is justified by multiple factors. Most significantly, the purpose and objectives of this research can be attained quite conveniently via the use of such an approach (Zikmund et al., 2013). As this research focuses on identifying and discussing the factors that can impact intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan (and how it might benefit organisations in the said sector), the development and validation of hypotheses characteristic of deductive research can be quite helpful. This is because individual factors can be identified via existing research and hypotheses pertaining to their impacts on intra-organisational communication (Quinlan et al., 2019). Later, these

hypotheses can be tested using collected data and appropriate analytical tools, allowing for attainment of research objectives.

A similar approach can be observed in the work of Vander Elst et al. (2010), who assess the relationships shared by intra-organisational communication with job security and employee wellbeing. The researchers use existing facts contained within the literature on the topic to formulate hypotheses. This has been followed by the collection of data and its analysis to validate or reject the hypotheses. Given the fact that the work of Vander Elst et al. (2010) and the research under consideration both seek similar objectives of establishing relationships between intra-organisational communication and a chosen set of factors, the use of a deductive approach by the former justifies the latter's reliance on it.

In addition to that, another factor that supports the use of the deductive research approach is that it is in line with positivism, which is the chosen research philosophy in this case. Other approaches tend to work well with other research philosophies. For instance, interpretivism and the inductive approach are in line with one another. The importance of this factor lies in the definition of the research philosophy (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). As research philosophy is the belief or set of beliefs that guide the selection and use of research methods, it is critical that all choices made in relation to the research methodology be in line with the chosen philosophy. Hence, the use of a deductive approach can prevent any mismatch between research beliefs and methods (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Again, multiple examples of positivism and the deductive approach being paired with one another can be found in existing studies. Of the ones reviewed as part of this research, Yan et al. (2016), Zhang, Van Donk and van der Vaart (2016) and Zahoor Sarwar et al. (2012) have been cited as examples of those using positivism. All three of these studies make use of existing data and facts to make assertions regarding the problem at hand and then undertake analysis to verify said assertions.

Furthermore, deductive research mostly yields results that are objective and generalizable. The usefulness of these factors to this research and its objectives are profound, as the research's findings can be extended to automotive companies around the world, which can add to its literary value (and support decision-making, which is part of its scope) (Hair et al., 2015). Most

studies based on the deductive research approach tend to rely on quantitative data and methods of analysis. This is evident from studies like Vander Elst et al. (2010), as well as Yan et al. (2016), where quantitative data and methods have been used to achieve targets. The main benefit offered by this is that the research process remains objective and structured, which can allow for smooth completion. However, there are examples of studies on similar topics making use of the inductive approach. Therefore, study of Rynänen, Pekkarinen and Salminen (2012), for example, employ an inductive approach, exploring new concepts in the context of intra-organisational communication.

3.4. Research Design

3.4.1. Theory

The research design refers to the overall framework employed by a study for the completion of research processes and attainment of research objectives. Broadly, there are two major research designs, namely exploratory and conclusive. The conclusive design can also be split into two categories: descriptive and causal research designs (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Of the three major research designs identified here, descriptive and exploratory are most commonly used.

Exploratory research, as the name suggests, is concerned with identification and discovery of new ideas and perspectives pertaining to a problem. Resultantly, the research process under this design is relatively unstructured and quite open to change. On the other hand, the descriptive research design is more concerned with description, identification or discussion of existing problems (Saunders, 2011). The research process is less flexible than that associated with the exploratory research design, but more structured.

3.4.2. Chosen Research Design

The current research makes use of a descriptive research design compared to other designs as discussed in above-mentioned section. It is a conclusive-type research design, which focuses on description and discussion of the characteristics or factors relevant to a specific individual or group. In addition to that, studies that rely on the descriptive research design often make specific predictions regarding the chosen population (in relation to the chosen topic or problem at hand) (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

In addition to this, Siedlecki (2020) and Nassaji (2015) has explained that descriptive research design is a scientific method of describing and observing the behavior of a material without influencing it in any way. With reference to Johnson et al., (2017) study, it is stated that in the proposed study, descriptive research design is smart and an effective choice of obtaining the quality artefacts as it supports the quantitative method researches in a unique way and hence, the anticipated study has already adopted quantitative method, which is explained in the subsequent section with complete detail and rationale. The descriptive method supports in such a manner that the descriptive research results cannot in any way be used as a definitive answer or confirmation of a hypothesis, but if the limits are understood they can nonetheless be a useful tool in many areas of scientific research (Kim 2013). Apart from this, it can also be supported by Sahin et al., (2020) study that descriptive incorporation in quantitative studies, therefore, assists in the researcher to conduct the study in a completely an unchanged and natural way, which helps the readers in the process of developing relevant insights as well as knowledge about the area that is being examined and explored, supported by Leavy (2014) findings.

In addition to this, descriptive research design also supports the researcher of the anticipated study in such a way that descriptive research is habitually cast-off as the precursor to quantitative research designs, the overview that provides some valuable clues as to which variables are worth testing in a quantitative manner. Henceforth, descriptive research systematically and accurately describes a situation, population, and phenomena. It supports the researcher who have adopted the quantitative method to adequately answer when, how, where, and what quires. A descriptive research design can use a wide spectrum of research methods to examine one or more variables. In contrast to experimental research, the researcher does not manipulate or control any of the variables, researcher only observes and measures them to accomplish the aim and objectives as well as to answer the research questions and hypothesis, supported by Sreejesh et al., (2014).

Furthermore, there are some characteristic features of the descriptive research design that have also been incorporated in this study. Overall, the focus remains on the collection of accurate data and preparation of a detailed research framework that highlights all intricacies of the research process (Quinlan et al., 2019).

3.4.3. *Rationale*

One of the most important of these factors is that a descriptive research design allows the researcher to approach the research objectives and problem in a structured manner. As the use of a structured approach can facilitate the attainment of the research objectives, deploying the descriptive research design can allow the researcher to complete this study more successfully, presenting an extremely significant reason behind the suitability of the descriptive research design in this case (Zikmund et al., 2013).

As discussed on multiple occasions earlier, the research is concerned with identification and discussion of factors that can influence the quality and depth of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. The fulfillment of this objective depends upon the establishment and verification of a relationship between the quality of intra-organisational communication (Saunders, 2011). Development and assessment of relationships in research work generally requires a structured and specific process, which is characteristic of descriptive research designs.

In addition to that, another factor relevant to this research design is that it focuses on a specific population. As a result, it can be argued that the research under consideration is focused on describing and discussing a problem that pertains to a specific group of people (Quinlan et al., 2019). This closely resembles the characteristics of a descriptive research design outlined earlier.

Saleem (2013) utilizes a descriptive research design, whereby the problem and relationship at hand have been described and discussed via a structured, systematic and quantitative framework. As the context and nature of the work of Saleem (2013), as well as the research under consideration are quite similar, using synonymous research designs is justified. Apart from that, the principles and characteristics of a descriptive research design are aligned with those of the research philosophy and approach selected here. Therefore, the selection of a descriptive research design, in this case, is also supported by the fact that it can allow for coherence within the chosen research methodology (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Of the studies that have been reviewed and discussed in this research, Yan et al. (2016) and Vander Elst et al. (2010) are clear examples of descriptive studies. Both these studies rely on

similar philosophies and approaches to the concerned study and then follow a research design that is synonymous with the descriptive research design highlighted here. The presence of these examples justifies the use of a descriptive research design in the case of this research too, because of the similarities between their purpose and nature and those of the research under consideration (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

3.5. Research Strategy

3.5.1. Theory

The research strategy loosely translates to a plan to be used for the execution of research methods in order to achieve the targeted research objectives. Multiple different types of research strategies are available, including:

- Analytical research strategy: studies that use this strategy rely on existing facts and knowledge to explain problems at hand, frequently involving assessment of cause-effect relationships (Hair et al., 2015).
- Action research strategy; as its name suggests, the research strategy is characterized by its agility and is usually used for studying pressing research problems, such as the outbreak of a disease (Bryman and Bell, 2015)
- Fundamental research strategy: even though existing facts are relied upon (in synonymy with the analytical research strategy), the goal is not to solve problems or explain phenomena at a larger scale (Saunders, 2011)
- Critical research strategy: critical analyses are performed on existing ideas and claims, with the aim of revealing loopholes and potential aspects that lack proper explanation. This research strategy delves into the depths of the topic (Hair et al., 2015)
- Experimental strategies: these strategies tend to conduct practical experiments in order to measure concerned variables and present outcomes. Unlike other strategies outlined above, the researcher is not merely observing, but can control and vary variables to provide thorough results (Collis and Hussey, 2013).

3.5.2. Chosen Research Strategy

The research under consideration makes use of the analytical research strategy, which is also known as descriptive research strategy or descriptive design (Wendt 2020). In addition, Maes

et al., (2013) and Jung (2017) has stated that an analytical research strategy involves making use of information and facts that are already available. A researcher examines and analyses the available data to elucidate complex problems. It answers questions like “how it came about” and “why is it like this” and generally relates to cause-and-effect relationships, supported by (Hagiwara et al., 2014). Moreover, most types of science-based problem-solving approaches have been found to use analytical strategies to achieve research goals and objectives. This is for the reason that this strategy allows the researchers to search for critical data and new information to add insights to the information generated. Thus, this is the prime reason and smart quality behind the selection and incorporation of analytical research strategy into the entitled study.

The analytical strategy, as outlined earlier, lays emphasis on the discussion of a complex problem or phenomenon using actual data and existing knowledge. In this case, the phenomenon being observed is intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan, with emphasis on factors that can influence it (Collis and Hussey, 2013). Previously the importance of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector has been established using examples from other countries.

Moreover, the specific benefits offered by intra-organisational communication have also been highlighted for this purpose. Keeping this importance under consideration, this research sheds light on the factors that can influence intra-organisational communication, establishing relationships between them, thereby offering decision-makers a chance to control these factors and hence improve intra-organisational communication (Gray, 2019).

3.5.3. *Rationale*

The rationale to incorporate the analytical research strategy in the anticipated study has been discussed with the support of Saaeb et al., (2021) analysis that analytical research strategy has been considered and referred as a special research type that involves critical thinking and evaluating facts and information about the research being carried out. In addition, the rationale is further supported by professionals’ findings codified in Berton et al., (2014) and Chen et al., (2018) that analytical research is used by a variety of people, including doctors, students, and psychologists, while studying and investigating some facts and information to obtain the most relevant information. It also supports adequately in the process of exploring the area and

activities, which are not discussed on a massive scale and have the potential to investigate and elucidate some new findings and discoveries that assist in the process of obtaining quality results with novelty (Ibáñez et al., 2016). This technique is time-effective and assists the researcher to scrutinize the facts and findings profoundly and with minimal prospect of risks and uncertainties that could affect the overall timeline and scope of the planned study. Critical data are extracted after incorporating and using analytical research strategy and it aids in adding new ideas to the material being produced, supported by Hauff (2021) findings.

The core purpose of this research is to assess the factors that can affect intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan so that decision-makers and authorities can take measures to improve allowing companies to reap the benefits. Comparing this research's purpose with the characteristics of an analytical research design provides multiple similarities. Firstly, the fact that this research is using existing information to assess and discuss a complex problem is quite similar to the major objectives targeted by studies reliant on an analytical research design (Quinlan et al., 2019). In addition to that, another important source of similarity (and hence, marker of feasibility) is the fact that this research also targets the formation of relationships between intra-organisational communication and the different factors that are thought to affect it, followed by their evaluation using an analysis of collected data (Gray, 2019).

Isac and Badshah (2016), for instance, examined the relationship shared by motivation and job satisfaction (this article has also been assessed in the current study). In order to achieve this objective, the researchers have employed an analytical research strategy, which is marked by employing existing facts to approach the problem, as well as use collected data to assess the concerned relationships in an attempt to devise a solution.

On the other hand, coherence, which has been discussed previously, remains an important factor in this context too. The research philosophy, design and approach chosen for any research need to be compatible with the research strategy being used. Lack of compatibility, such as that between a descriptive research design and a critical research strategy (the first seeks shallow analysis and description, while the latter calls for in-depth exploration of topic), can hamper smooth progression of research and limit its effectiveness (Collis and Hussey, 2013).

Again, much like previous choices and arguments, this can be backed using examples from studies in the existing literature. For instance, Yan et al. (2016), as well as Zahoor Sarwar et al. (2012), two studies with similar research philosophies, designs and approaches as the current study, make use of the analytical research design. In addition to that, another factor that is similar here is the nature of objectives and research processes used, with both studies utilizing statistical significance of relationships between variables to achieve their targets.

3.6. Research methods

According to Lewis (2015), there are three kinds of research methods: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods. The positivist approach is often referred to as the quantitative approach for the reason that it is seen as a core component of the positivist model previously mentioned. Furthermore, the quantitative approach is linked to the realism paradigm, since it is a necessary component of triangulation (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). The quantitative method, as the name implies, is concerned with mathematical statistic data and numbers and is accumulated through surveys, questionnaires and statistical experiments generally accumulated in the masses. This method describes social, physiological, and empirical insights using numbers and phrases, so it uses numbers and statistical methods to produce very accurate results, making it the best method for evaluating and testing hypotheses (Zikmund et al., 2013).

Tables and charts that depict the interactions between various variables are often used to display quantitative and statistical data from research. Graphs can also be used to visualize and interpret statistical data. Methods such as these are particularly useful for studying large demographics, populations and putting scientific hypotheses to the test. Statistical methods and procedures may be used to interpret data in a quantifiable way in this form of analysis approach (Bryman and Bell 2015). Therefore, this research study has adopted a quantitative research method in order to examine the intra-organisational communication challenges under the automotive industry of Pakistan.

In addition to that, qualitative research methods differ in that they are focused on the extensive, in-depth evaluation of the topic at hand. The research questions that are generally explored by qualitative studies clearly seek out deeper details regarding a topic. Mostly, these are ‘why’ type questions, rather than ‘what’ targeted in studies that make use of quantitative approaches (Gray, 2019). The use of the qualitative research method allows for better understanding of the

research topic, but there are chances of the research becoming overly subjective and less generalizable than quantitative ones.

Finally, mixed research incorporates components of both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The use of these methods generally can allow for a combination of the benefits of both qualitative and quantitative research techniques, but the resources and efforts required for completion of the research can be increased considerably (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

The current research has made use of quantitative research methods for multiple reasons. Firstly, the research philosophy, design and approach chosen all support the use of quantitative research methods. For instance, positivism favors systematic, scientific and statistical methods, which are closely associated with quantitative research, supporting its use here (Hair et al., 2015). Similarly, a deductive approach and descriptive design are more suited for quantitative research methods, further justifying their use in this case. Lastly, it must be noted that the analytical strategy also better suits quantitative research methods.

Since the use of quantitative research methods can allow for maintenance of coherence within the research methodology used in this study, it can support achieving the research objectives. In this way, its use is justified in this research. The fact that other research making use of similar research designs, philosophies, approaches and strategies have relied primarily on quantitative research methods can also be used to bolster the rationale behind using these methods in this case. For instance, Isac and Badshah (2016), who make use of a descriptive research design and an analytical research strategy, make use of quantitative research methods to achieve their objectives.

In addition to that, the work of Yan et al. (2016) can also be used to support the use of quantitative research methods in this case. This is attributable to the fact that the study has used a research methodology quite similar to the one used here and has used quantitative research methods. Again, as a similar study has been successfully completed using quantitative research methods, it can be implied that using quantitative research methods can be helpful in completing the concerned research successfully too. This also justifies their use here.

In addition to that, this research has preferred the use of positivism, descriptive design and analytical strategy. These aspects favor a research structure where the literature is reviewed to

generate hypotheses/relationships relevant to the study, followed by collection and assessment of data to validate or neglect them. Quantitative research methods are useful for such evaluations of hypotheses and relationships. In this way, quantitative research methods are suited to this research's philosophy, approach, design and strategy (Quinlan et al., 2019)

Again, the discussion presented earlier can be supported using examples from the existing literature. Zahoor Sarwar et al. (2012) pursue the factors that limit productivity within the automotive sector of Pakistan. As part of the research process used in this study, relationships between factors and variables were probed using statistical analysis, which enabled the researchers to identify factors that can affect productivity in the automotive sector. Even though the topic pursued by this study and the one being presented as an example are not exactly the same, there are remarkable similarities between the research objectives and nature of both. Similarly, Zhang, Van Donk and van der Vaart (2016) can also be used as an example here due to the presence of similar objectives and research design to the research under consideration (and the use of quantitative research methods).

As both studies mentioned earlier were completed quite effectively and managed to achieve desired outcomes and they shared similarities with the research under consideration, it is possible that the research methods used can be successfully applied here. This presents yet another justification for the use of quantitative research methods in this case (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

3.7. Pilot Study

In order to thoroughly understand the different aspects of the quantitative research method, a pilot study has been conducted. This was useful in designing or development of the questionnaire for this research study (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Researchers also conducted discussion sessions with other researchers to examine the understandability of the questionnaire, and based on their feedback, several modifications were made in the questionnaire's length, language, sequencing, and questions to enhance its objectivity. It has been ensured that questions should remain unbiased, interactive, and will be effective to collect all required data for the research. In the end, a pilot study was conducted to finalize the design of the survey questionnaire.

3.8. Population of the research

In research work, a population is defined as the complete set of people (or even objects) that possess the characteristics that a researcher has used to define the sampling criteria (Yvonne Feilzer, 2010). In effect, the population may be described as the whole group of individuals in which a researcher is interested. Depending upon the topic being studied, a population may be small (or finite) or large and too complex to be counted (infinite). For this research, the population consists of workers and people affiliated with the automotive sector of Pakistan (Quinlan et al., 2019).

3.8.1. Selection of sampling technique

Bryman and Bell (2015) and Zikmund et al (2013) state there are two kinds of sampling techniques: probability and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling adopts the approach of systematic, random and stratified sampling techniques to target the entire population whereas non-probability sampling is non-random because it does not provide equal chance for the selection of each individual. This technique has been subdivided into further techniques such as Snowfall, convenience and judgment (Hair et al., 2015). Random sampling was used in this research project. This makes it easier for the researcher to reach selected samples from the target population. This technique does not require the researcher to obey any rules and allows them to collect primary data (Lewis, 2015).

The explanation and justification of selecting simple random sampling procedure is discussed with the support of studies conducted by diversified professionals and experts. For example, Quinlan et al., (2019) study has discussed and enlightened that a simple random sampling is considered an active technique, which involved the identification of all individuals in the target population, followed by the allotment of numbers and the random selection of numbers (to support random selection of corresponding individuals) was used here (Quinlan et al., 2019). Similarly, with reference to Meng (2013) study, it is found that a subset of individuals has been considered a simple random sample i.e., selected from a larger set, from which an individual's subset is randomly selected with the same probability. Random sampling is referred as the part of a sampling technique that is used in the researches and other mathematical and scientific work in which all samples are selected with equal probability (West 2016).

In addition to this, a random sample is an unbiased representation of the total population. An unbiased random sample is important for drawing conclusions and is also considered imperative in the process of obtaining high-quality results (Acharya et al., 2013). Random sampling certifies that outcomes attained from a sample should estimate what would have been gained if the entire populace had been measured (Yadav et al., 2014). The simplest random sample permits all the units in the populace to have an equivalent fortuitous of being selected (Gregoire 2018). Thus, selection of simple random sampling technique is further justified with the support of Pai (2018) study that a simple random sample has been considered as an organised statistical population subset in which all subset members have an equivalent chance of being selected. A simple random sample is an unbiased group representation (Ismail 2018).

Comparatively to other sampling techniques, for example, stratified random sampling, it is found from several studies conducted by domain experts and professionals such as Etikan and Bala (2017) and Ekpenyong (2015) that stratified random sampling is a sampling method that divides a population into smaller subgroups called strata. Stratified random sampling, which is also known as stratification is the process of forming strata grounded on common characteristics or attributes of members such as income or level of education. It is also known as quota and proportional random sampling (Al-Omari 2013). Moreover, the stratified random sample permits investigators to obtain a population sample that signifies the total population studied. In the stratified random sample, the entire population is divided into homogeneous groups, so-called strata (Stehman 2014). It also an effective random sampling technique and has its own value and importance; however, for the anticipated study, such tactic of sampling has not been considered an effective choice. For this, there are several reasons that are discussed with the support of Stehman (2014) study like stratified random sampling is different from simple random sampling, which randomly selects data from an entire population so that each possible sample is correspondingly likely to occur, which is not possible in stratified as strata focused on involving the population division into smaller sub-groups. In addition to this, Pirzadeh (2013) and Beri et al., (2020) study also supports inn justifying the proposed study researcher choice that strata sampling can make it difficult to choose the right sub-groups that is stated as strata to sample. The second disadvantage is that the results are more difficult to organise and interpret compared to a simple random sample and especially in the studies where descriptive nature with the combination of quantitative research method is integrated, supported by Etika and Bala (2017).

On the other hand, in the proposed study, systematic sampling was another option, which can be incorporated to accomplish the aim and objectives as well as to answer the research questions and hypothesis; however, it is not adopted for the reason that the systematic method assumes that the population size is available or can be approximated reasonably. For example, researchers are likely to want to study the size of rats in a particular area. If researcher have no idea how many rats there are, they cannot systematically choose a starting point or the number of intervals, which is opposite in simple random where the researcher exactly knows about the sample on which via applying suitable means and methods, the possibility of obtaining quality results is on higher level (Xu 2018). Hence, in systematic sampling technique there is another risk, which is why the researcher have not adopted such technique. This risk is entitled as data manipulation, which might affect the anticipated study validity, reliability, and generalisability. With the support of Aune (2014) study, it can be stated that systematic sampling increases the risk of data manipulation because researchers can build their systems to increase the likelihood of achieving a particular result, rather than allowing random data to give a representative answer. The resulting statistics cannot be trusted. Thus, the above-conducted comparative analysis between different sampling technique assists in the process of developing relevant insights and knowledge of the readers behind the selection of simple random sampling technique compared to others.

Moreover, the selection of random sampling is supported by a number of reasons that helps the researcher of the proposed study to justify why the research has not been based on previous studies completely. The first and foremost thing is to cover the research gap as discussed earlier in the projected study so that new results, findings, and discoveries can be made and attained. Secondly, random sampling significantly reduces the probability of selection bias as the researcher's preferences do not play any part whatsoever in sample selection (Quinlan et al., 2019). As a result, the selected sample is chosen purely by chance and has a greater likelihood of representing the entire targeted population than one selected under the influence of external factors or preferences (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

In addition to that, random sampling also makes the results of a study more generalizable. This is primarily attributable to the fact that a random sample tends to accurately represent the targeted population. Thus, by covering all factors and viewpoints, the random sample can generate more holistic results than one that has been selected via a non-probability sampling

method. In this way, the results can be extended to the entire population with high levels of reliability (Zikmund et al., 2013). This is particularly valuable to the concerned research, as it does not take all workers of the Pakistani automotive industry into consideration, but its results have to be extended to the entire population (Gray, 2019).

Another factor that is thought to support the use of random sampling in research work is its relative simplicity. That is, once the researcher has identified a criterion for sample selection, working out the sample becomes quite simple (but not exactly easy, because determination of a criterion that allows for the selection of a truly random sample remains a challenging task) (Collis and Hussey, 2014). However, sample selection is simple, in that no external factors or preferences have to be taken into consideration and the same process can be repeated to continuously select participants without altering their probability of being selected and hence the fairness of this procedure. In contrast, in non-probability sampling techniques, multiple external factors have to be taken into consideration that can make the process more complicated. This explains why random, rather than non-probability, sampling has been chosen for this research (Saunders, 2011).

The factors cited in favor of random sampling greatly outweigh the negative aspects associated with it. For instance, some scholars point out that random sampling can be difficult to attain and may require greater inputs as compared to non-probability sampling. Particularly, convenience sampling is quite easy to undertake, and it does not require similar efforts, costs or time (Bryman and Bell, 2015). However, the extra investments made in random sampling generate significant benefits that greatly impact the integrity of this research. That is, using a non-probability sampling technique may have reduced the cost, time and efforts required, but would have sacrificed the integrity of the research process and reliability of its results, presenting an unfeasible trade-off. This highlights the significance of the sampling technique used in this case (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

The process that was used for the selection of random sample in this research was based on employee numbers. Within the organisation, each employee is assigned with a number that represents them. For the selection of the respondents in this study, the researcher collected the data on the employee number. The range of these numbers was then used in Microsoft Excel to generate a random list of employee numbers without any duplicates using the RAND,

RANK, IF, INDEX, ROW, COLUMN and OFFSET formula. The combination of these formulas was used to ensure that the generated list of numbers does not contain duplicates and all individual employees get an equal opportunity of being selected as the part of the sample. This allows the researcher to make use of the random sampling method when it comes to sample selection.

3.8.2. *Sampling size*

In this research study, the researcher is unable to target the entire population. As a result, selecting a particular sample size that reflects the entire population is important. This sample serves to represent that entire targeted population so ideally needs to incorporate all characteristics of all people presented within the targeted population. For this study, 500 workers from Atlas Honda, an automotive sector company of Pakistan, were targeted. Atlas Honda is one of the largest players in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Additionally, even though Atlas Honda is headquartered in Karachi, it has operations across the country, with manufacturing and assembly taking place in other areas like Sheikhpura. Since workers from both these locations have been targeted, a decent representation of the entire workforce is ensured. As per the research studies conducted by Guest, Bunce, and Johnson (2006); De Ruyter and Scholl (1998), targeting 500 people is sufficient to get enough data from research participants for conducting a quantitative research study.

Selection of the sample size has been based on a balance between two factors; the accuracy with which the sample is represented and the possibility of handling, managing and storing collected data. As the sample size increases, the accuracy with which the targeted population is represented increases, making a larger sample size suitable for research conduction. However, increments in sample size also increase the volume of data collected, giving rise to challenges in data collection, handling, storage and analysis (Hair et al., 2015). It is evident that there are limitations to the sample size because of resource, time and effort constraints that are associated with any research.

It is important to note that while the number of individuals targeted initially was 500, the number of valid responses obtained in the study was 350. Thus, the final sample size for this study was 350. A sample of 350 individuals is suitable for two reasons: firstly, it is not too small to not represent the entire population; secondly, it is not too large to create issues in the

management, handling and analysis of data. The suitability of this sample size is justified further by the observation that other studies on intra-organisational communication collected similar number of responses. Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa (2019), for instance settled for 310 responses. Similarly, Iswanto and Marzuki (2020) also had a sample of 352 responses. Since a similar number of responses have been used by other studies on intra-organisational communication, the sample size chosen here is justified.

3.8.3. Random Sampling in the Current Study

The current research relied on the use of employee numbers and the random number generator function available in Microsoft Excel. Atlas Honda Pakistan has designated unique numbers (IDs) for each worker. The random number generator function on Microsoft Excel was used to generate 500 unique numbers within the range that encompassed all employee IDs at Atlas Honda Pakistan. As a random series of numbers (corresponding to employee IDs at Atlas Honda) was generated and then used to select the sample, the chances of any individual working at the organisation being selected remained equal. Thus, the sampling technique used here resembled simple random sampling.

3.9. Data Collection Methods and Procedures

3.9.1. Validity and Reliability

Reliability and validity are two major components to assure that the research instruments and methods used are appropriate. Along with this, reliability ensures consistency in the quantitative research study (Zikmund et al., 2013). According to Saunders (2011), there are different approaches to enhance reliability in a qualitative study that include the use of comprehensive data, comparison of data and the application of inclusion and exclusion criteria. The reliability can be tested through originality of sources and it must be ensured that the data that has been utilized is as per the research theme or topic (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

3.9.1.1. Pre-Testing Validity and Reliability

Pre-testing validity and reliability have pertained to questionnaire design and development. The content validity technique was deployed to ensure that collected data remained reliable and valid. Pre-testing validity relies on an evaluation of the extent to which the data collection instrument/ measure can support gathering of content that is necessary for the research (Bell,

Bryman and Harley, 2018). In this case, the content validity technique has been deployed by assessing the research questionnaire in accordance with two criteria, namely:

- Suitability with the sample and population; the length, complexity and composition of the questionnaire (if the questionnaire is overly technical, too long or composed of many open-ended questions, response rates, as well as response accuracy can decline, creating validity issues). Therefore, the question has been assessed for its length, complexity and composition, making sure that it can support high response rates, as well as generation of accurate responses
- Inclusiveness: whether or not the questionnaire covers all necessary areas associated with the topic/ issue that is being explored by the research under consideration.

3.9.1.2. Post-Testing Validity and Reliability

In the current research, post-testing reliability has been assessed via Cronbach's alpha, the reliability statistic that measures internal consistency. Generally, Cronbach's alpha measures the extent to which the items within a dataset are related to one another. It is important to note that Cronbach's alpha is strictly related to the internal consistency and reliability of the data, rather than the degree to which a variable is unidimensional. It provides the co-efficient of reliability, with a higher value (closer to one) reflective of higher reliability (Dowdy, Wearden and Chilko, 2011). The Cronbach's alpha calculated for this research is illustrated in Table 4.2: Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Analysis (present in the Reliability Analysis section).

3.9.2. Primary Sources of Data Gathering

As indicated by Zikmund et al (2013), raw data, or first data, are considered to be the same as primary data collected by researchers at the initial stages of research from participants for the purpose of analysis and evaluation. Primary data is generally accumulated through questionnaires, surveys, observations, interviews and other sources and methods that are at the researcher's disposal. However, collecting primary data comes with its own challenges in comparison to collecting secondary data. Researchers need to be fully aware that the process of collecting raw data, or primary data, is time consuming, requires effort and diligence and requires adequate financial resources. This study has acquired the usage of questionnaires as the source of primary data collection, as it seemed the best fit to collect a variant and vast range of raw data from a large sample pool.

For this study, data has been collected using a survey questionnaire. Questions within the survey corresponded to the factors affecting intra-organisational communication, its benefits or challenges associated with it. Questions in the survey were kept closed ended to ensure convenience and decrease the time required for respondents to complete. In addition to that, a simple language, without compromising on necessary technical details, was deployed to ensure that the survey yielded necessary information and non-response due to misunderstandings remained low (Hair et al., 2015).

In addition to that, the survey consisted of Likert-type and multiple-choice questions to allow the researcher to generate quantitative data that could then undergo statistical analysis. The survey was administered to the sample of 500 individuals from Atlas Honda Pakistan. Prior to survey administration, the questionnaire was reviewed in order to identify any mistakes and overly complicated language (Zikmund et al., 2013). Therefore, the questionnaire design based on Likert scales and multiple-choice questions and the rationale behind this is questionnaire composed of many open-ended questions and response rates may affect the data reliability and validity as well as accuracy (Ab Latiff et al., 2016). A combination of both techniques is considered to be prolific that assists in the process of attaining quality results as applicants have several options as well as rating scale to record a respond rather than having only a singular style to achieve the end-goal, supported by (Mellor and Moore 2014). The questions and the dimensions for both Likert scale and multiple-choice questions are designed as per the aim, objectives, questions, and hypothesis. Apart from this, the dimensions are incorporated and formulated with the help of Rensis Likert findings who is referred as the maker of Likert scale. in 1932 by Rensis Likert, the original Likert Scale was developed. He was a psychologist interested in measuring people's opinions or points of view on a variety of subjects. He developed a 7-point bipolar consensus scale (Kandlhofer 2016). Similarly, for multiple-choice question Benjamin D. Wood findings has been used so that all results can be evaluated and examined adequately as Benjamin D. Wood measured to be the prime player behind the proposal of multiple-choice questions and testing (Hill and Alexander 2017).

3.9.3. Responses

Overall, 500 questionnaires were administered (one to each individual in the selected sample). All responses had been gathered within 29 days of the start of survey administration. Even though all the administered surveys generated responses, item non-response remained a major

issue. That is, several participants did not respond to particular items on the survey, leading to incomplete responses. The exclusion of these incomplete responses, as well as those that were clearly inaccurate (with either '5' or '1' being marked for all questions with Likert Scales), led to a set of 350 usable responses (even though 500 individuals were targeted initially).

The researcher initially targeted 500 individuals in order to account for non-response and unacceptable responses. Studies conducted on similar topics (Suzuki, Ando and Nishikawa, 2019; Iswanto and Marzuki, 2020) have relied on samples consisting of 310-352 responses. Hence, the current study also targeted 500 responses. However, the response rate was not expected to be 100%. Thus, 500 individuals were targeted to make sure that the final number of usable responses remained close to 350.

3.10. Data analysis techniques

The current research relies on statistical analysis to assess the quantitative information generated after the data collection process. Various statistical analyses have been deployed here. Descriptive statistics have been used in this research to provide details regarding the data set and respondent body. In addition to that, regression and correlation analysis have been used to assess the relationships between intra-organisational communication, its benefits/ challenges and factors affecting it in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Regression and correlation analysis are suited to this study because both these methods allow for the identification of relationships that exist between a dependent variable and a set of independent variables (Hair et al., 2015). Moreover, they provide valuable information regarding the nature of the relationship (whether it is positive or negative, for instance).

Analysis has not been performed manually here. Instead, IBM SPSS, a software package, was used. This offers two benefits: accuracy (since the likelihood of human error is reduced) and efficiency (less time is required). The package has default modes to perform regression and correlation analysis and provides the user with an output that can be easily interpreted (Argyrous, 2011). Therefore, these statistical techniques incorporated in the entitled study are referred as parametric methods. It can be stated that parametric means can be used with studies who have incorporated Likert scale as it is much easier to interpret parametric inferences and allows for a wider range of analysis. Not only is it an option, it is even recommended that researcher use parametric statistical systems with Likert scale.

3.11. Ethics Approval

Hair et al (2015) state that ethical concerns are one of the most critical aspects of conducting a successful research project. It aids in the development of a comprehensive code of ethics while doing research. It is also helpful in identifying standards, behaviors, practices, and challenges that can occur during the testing process. An ethics form was submitted to the university's campus in this respect. Sharing the main aim of this research study with participants is one of the big ethical considerations that have been pursued. Participants' permission to participate in the survey for data collection was obtained, and the survey was performed with their approval and cooperation. Participants have indeed been assured that all data and information will be kept strictly private and will not be exchanged with other participants or third parties. This ensures the participants' anonymity and non-disclosure agreements are respected. Additionally, respondents' identifying information is kept private and confidential.

3.12 Summary

The research under consideration is based on a positivist paradigm, with a descriptive research design and analytical research strategy. Primarily, quantitative research methods were used to assess the factors that may influence intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan, as well as benefits and challenges associated with it. In this regard, a sample of 500 individuals from Atlas Honda, an automotive sector company in Pakistan, has been selected for survey administration. The collected data was analyzed via regression and correlation using IBM SPSS to support generation of results.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. Overview of the Chapter

This chapter focuses on assessing and interpreting the key results associated with the data analysis conducted on the primary data collected under this research. In this case, the chapter consists of three distinct analysis parts. The first part is associated with the reliability analysis, where Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the reliability of the data that has been collected in this research. The second part of this chapter entails descriptive analysis, which has been conducted to assess the key characteristics of the respondents as well as the overall nature of the data. The final part is based on inferential analysis, where correlation and regression analysis have been conducted on the collected data. In this case, the results of the regression analysis were used to accept or reject the following hypothesis:

- ⇒ H1: Complexity of big data analysis has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- ⇒ H2: Lack of focus on personal goals of the employees has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- ⇒ H3: Lack of focus on employee engagement has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- ⇒ H4: Lack of innovative mechanisms has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- ⇒ H5: Low levels of internal branding have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- ⇒ H6: Lack of technology has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.
- ⇒ H7: Ineffective payment and reward structures have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

4.2. Reliability Analysis

Table 4.1: Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	350	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	350	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 4.2: Reliability Analysis- Cronbach's Alpha

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.863	37

Cronbach's Alpha of 0.863 can be seen very evidently in the data shown in the above table, which is indicative of high levels of accuracy within the data. Since the levels of reliability within the data are quite high, it has the capacity to generate accurate and authentic conclusions for the purpose of the research under consideration.

4.3. Descriptive Analysis – Frequency Distribution

4.3.1. Gender of the Respondents

Table 4.3: Gender of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	300	85.7	85.7	85.7
	Female	50	14.3	14.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

The above table depicts that most of the respondents in the chosen sample were males (85.7%), with females accounting for only a minor portion of the entire respondent body (14.3%). The majority is indicative of the prevalence of males in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Since more males take up professions in the automotive sector than females in the country, a higher proportion of males were present in the sample.

4.3.2. Age of the Respondents

Table 4.4: Age of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20-30years	156	44.6	44.6	44.6
	30-40 years	124	35.4	35.4	80.0
	40-50 years	63	18.0	18.0	98.0
	50 years or above	7	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

People belonging to the age group 20-30 years accounted for the greatest proportion of the entire respondent body, closely followed by those belonging to the age group 30-40 years. Individuals aged 40-50 years ranked third, while people aged 50 years or above accounted for the smallest proportion of the respondent body. The age-wise distribution of the sample reflects the age-wise distribution of the workers at Atlas Honda Pakistan and, broadly, the automotive sector. Most workers belong to the age groups 20-30 and 30-40, accounting for the prevalence of these age groups in the sample.

4.3.3. Education of the Respondents

Table 4.5: Education of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Intermediate	91	26.0	26.0	26.0
	Bachelor	126	36.0	36.0	62.0
	Master	106	30.3	30.3	92.3
	MS/M. Phil	22	6.3	6.3	98.6
	PhD	5	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

The majority of the respondents had bachelor's level education, closely followed by those having master's level qualification and intermediate level education. Individuals with MS/ M. Phil or PhD accounted for minor proportions of the respondent body. The research shows that, on average, the respondents have a bachelor's degree with PhD education being an outlier as very few respondents had a PhD.

4.3.4. Department of the Respondents

Table 4.6: Department of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Finance	33	9.4	9.4	9.4
	IT	30	8.6	8.6	18.0
	Marketing	83	23.7	23.7	41.7
	Treasury	6	1.7	1.7	43.4
	Legal	12	3.4	3.4	46.9
	HR	31	8.9	8.9	55.7
	Operations	22	6.3	6.3	62.0
	Internal Audit	8	2.3	2.3	64.3
	Production	57	16.3	16.3	80.6
	Sales	60	17.1	17.1	97.7
	Compliance	8	2.3	2.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

As evident from the above table, workers from six departments, in the following order, had the greatest representation in the given sample: Marketing, Sales, Production, Finance, HR and IT. Workers from other departments only had minor representation in the sample. This distribution reflects the total number of workers in the organisation fairly closely. Production and sales, for instance, are among the departments with the highest number of workers, explaining their larger representation as compared to compliance, which is a smaller department.

4.3.5. Employment Status of the Respondents

Table 4.7: Employment status of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Permanent staff	329	94.0	94.0	94.0
	Temporary/Contract staff	21	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

A vast majority of the workers represented in the sample were accounted for by permanent staff with only a few workers being contract workers. When it comes to the general trend of employment among the respondents, most of them were permanent staff members. This is valuable for the research under consideration as the permanent staff members are well versed in the communication regime that exists within the organisation. Hence, they can provide insights into the overall quality of intra-communication infrastructures.

4.3.6. The company confronts no issues in the management of large amounts of employee related data

Table 4.8: The company confronts no issues in the management of large amounts of employee related data

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	27	7.7	7.7	8.0
	Neutral	27	7.7	7.7	15.7
	Disagree	227	64.9	64.9	80.6
	Strongly Disagree	68	19.4	19.4	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

As evident from the above, most respondents believed their organisation *did* face issues in management regarding large volumes of data pertaining to workers. Only a small proportion of workers were of the opinion that their company did not face any issues in this regard.

4.3.7. The company has the technology that can allow for the facilitation of data management

Table 4.9: The company has the technology that can allow for the facilitation of data management

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	24	6.9	6.9	7.1
	Neutral	46	13.1	13.1	20.3
	Disagree	149	42.6	42.6	62.9
	Strongly Disagree	130	37.1	37.1	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

In line with the previous discussion, most workers suggested that their company did not have the technology that is needed or can allow for the facilitation of data management, with only about 7 percent of respondents actually considering their companies to possess said technology.

4.3.8. Complexity of Data Analysis

Table 4.10: Complexity of Data Analysis

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0
	Agree	5	1.4	1.4	1.4
	Neutral	35	10.0	10.0	11.4
	Disagree	174	49.7	49.7	61.1
	Strongly Disagree	136	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Regarding the complexity of data analysis, most workers (nearly 89 percent) provided negative ideas, going against the statement. Only 1.4 percent of all workers provided positive responses in this regard with 10.0 percent maintaining a neutral stance. The above-mentioned

4.3.9. The company consults the employees at the time of creation of job descriptions

Table 4.11: The company consults the employees at the time of creation of job descriptions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	54	15.4	15.4	15.7
	Neutral	7	2.0	2.0	17.7
	Disagree	218	62.3	62.3	80.0
	Strongly Disagree	70	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Again, a major proportion of workers disagreed with the fact that organisational management or authorities consulted them when designing and creating job descriptions for them, with only 15.7 percent of workers offering their agreement in this regard.

4.3.10. There are ample opportunities for effective training and development of the employees

Table 4.12: There are ample opportunities for effective training and development of the employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	2	.6	.6	.6
	Agree	43	12.3	12.3	12.9
	Neutral	16	4.6	4.6	17.4
	Disagree	120	34.3	34.3	51.7
	Strongly Disagree	169	48.3	48.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Regarding the presence of ample opportunities for effective training and development, most of the respondents disagreed and only 12.9 percent agreed with the statement.

4.3.11. The company has a rigorous and prompt system for the management of employee grievances

Table 4.13: The company has a rigorous and prompt system for the management of employee grievances

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	3	.9	.9	.9
	Agree	41	11.7	11.7	12.6
	Neutral	20	5.7	5.7	18.3
	Disagree	70	20.0	20.0	38.3
	Strongly Disagree	216	61.7	61.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Much like the previous statement, the responses were mainly negative here. Only 12.6 percent suggested that their organisation *did have* a rigorous and prompt system for the management of employee grievances, with a significant majority of workers vehemently rejecting this idea.

4.3.12. Lack of Focus on Personal Goals

Table 4.14: Lack of Focus on Personal Goals

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	4	1.1	1.1	1.4
	Neutral	49	14.0	14.0	15.4
	Disagree	176	50.3	50.3	65.7
	Strongly Disagree	120	34.3	34.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Only 1.4 percent of all respondents provided positive responses in this regard. More than three-quarters of the respondents disagreed with the idea that there is a lack of focus on personal goals.

4.3.13. I have sufficient levels of liberty and autonomy when it comes to performing my job

Table 4.15: I have sufficient levels of liberty and autonomy when it comes to performing my job

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	75	21.4	21.4	21.4
	Neutral	7	2.0	2.0	23.4
	Disagree	210	60.0	60.0	83.4
	Strongly Disagree	58	16.6	16.6	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Again, most of the responses were of disagreement, rather than agreement. While 21.3 percent of the respondents did agree with the idea that they had sufficient levels of liberty and autonomy when performing their jobs, most of them stated that this notion was incorrect.

4.3.14. Each employee has the responsibility of ensuring the quality of his job

Table 4.16: Each employee has the responsibility of ensuring the quality of his job

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	43	12.3	12.3	12.6
	Neutral	18	5.1	5.1	17.7

Disagree	128	36.6	36.6	54.3
Strongly Disagree	160	45.7	45.7	100.0
Total	350	100.0	100.0	

As evident from the above table, most of the workers did not think that every worker has the responsibility for ensuring personal job quality and effectiveness. A mere 12.5 percent of respondents agreed with this statement.

4.3.15. I have sufficient information about the processes for communicating across the overall organisation

Table 4.17: I have sufficient information about the processes for communicating across the overall organisation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	3	.9	.9	.9
	Agree	41	11.7	11.7	12.6
	Neutral	19	5.4	5.4	18.0
	Disagree	70	20.0	20.0	38.0
	Strongly Disagree	217	62.0	62.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

It is clear from the above table that workers rarely had any idea regarding processes and protocols for communicating across the entire organisation.

4.3.16. Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement

Table 4.18: Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	6	1.7	1.7	2.0
	Neutral	69	19.7	19.7	21.7
	Disagree	157	44.9	44.9	66.6
	Strongly Disagree	117	33.4	33.4	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

A very strong negative response was obtained when workers were questioned about a lack of focus on employee engagement. As shown in the above table, most of the workers *did not agree* with the statement.

4.3.17. The company has online portal that connects all the employees

Table 4.19: The company has an online portal that connects all the employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	27	7.7	7.7	8.0
	Neutral	27	7.7	7.7	15.7
	Disagree	254	72.6	72.6	88.3
	Strongly Disagree	41	11.7	11.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Again, most of the workers disagreed that their company has an online portal to facilitate connectivity between workers, with less than 8.3 percent agreeing with this idea.

4.3.18. The company arranges events that allow for the socialization of the employees

Table 4.20: The company arranges events that allow for the socialization of the employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	26	7.4	7.4	7.7
	Neutral	15	4.3	4.3	12.0
	Disagree	174	49.7	49.7	61.7
	Strongly Disagree	134	38.3	38.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

It is clear from the above table that most of the workers (more than 85 percent) noted their company that did not arrange any events that allowed for socialization between employees. Less than 10 percent of respondents did experience such events.

4.3.19. Lack of Innovative Mechanisms

Table 4.21: Lack of Innovative Mechanisms

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	0	0	0	0.0
	Agree	6	1.7	1.7	1.7
	Neutral	35	10.0	10.0	11.7
	Disagree	173	49.4	49.4	61.1
	Strongly Disagree	136	38.9	38.9	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

A majority of the respondents disagreed with the idea that there was a lack of innovative mechanisms in their company, with fewer than 2 percent of workers agreeing.

4.3.20. The company allows for the development of career aspirations of the employees

Table 4.22: The company allows for the development of career aspirations of the employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	59	16.9	16.9	17.1
	Neutral	7	2.0	2.0	19.1
	Disagree	229	65.4	65.4	84.6
	Strongly Disagree	54	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

As evident, most of respondents did not consider their company allowed for development of their career aspirations and ambitions. Only 17.4 percent of workers, representing a minority, agreed with this idea.

4.3.21. The company has a sound and satisfactory internal environment

Table 4.23: The company has a sound and satisfactory internal environment

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	41	11.7	11.7	12.0
	Neutral	18	5.1	5.1	17.1
	Disagree	113	32.3	32.3	49.4
	Strongly Disagree	177	50.6	50.6	100.0

Total	350	100.0	100.0
-------	-----	-------	-------

Most of the workers disagreed with the idea that the company possessed health, sound and satisfactory internal environments. Again, only a minor proportion of respondents agreed that their company had a sound and satisfactory internal environment.

4.3.22. I am always recognized for my performance and hard work

Table 4.24: I am always recognized for my performance and hard work

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	3	.9	.9	.9
	Agree	42	12.0	12.0	12.9
	Neutral	20	5.7	5.7	18.6
	Disagree	78	22.3	22.3	40.9
	Strongly Disagree	207	59.1	59.1	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

In line with the results discussed earlier, most of the responses in this category were negative too. A significant proportion of all respondents did not think that they received proper recognition for their efforts or performance.

4.3.23. Low Levels of Internal Branding

Table 4.25: Low Levels of Internal Branding

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	2	.6	.6	.9
	Neutral	59	16.9	16.9	17.7
	Disagree	170	48.6	48.6	66.3
	Strongly Disagree	118	33.7	33.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

More than 80 percent of all workers disagreed with the idea that there were low levels of internal branding within the organisation. Only a few workers agreed with this statement.

4.3.24. The company is well equipped with the modern-day cloud technology

Table 4.26: The company is well equipped with the modern-day cloud technology

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	58	16.6	16.6	16.9
	Neutral	7	2.0	2.0	18.9
	Disagree	230	65.7	65.7	84.6
	Strongly Disagree	54	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

The responses obtained were similar to other questions pertaining to technology. A significant proportion of respondents did not think that their company is well-equipped with modern-day cloud technology.

4.3.25. The company has expertise in the advanced communication software

Table 4.27: The company has expertise in the advanced communication software

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	43	12.3	12.3	12.6
	Neutral	19	5.4	5.4	18.0
	Disagree	125	35.7	35.7	53.7
	Strongly Disagree	162	46.3	46.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Again, the results closely resembled those in other areas pertaining to technology. An overwhelming majority of workers did not agree with the idea that their company had expertise in advanced communication software, with only 12.9 percent agreeing.

4.3.26. The company keeps itself updated on the modern technologies used for internal organisational communication

Table 4.28: The company keeps itself updated on the modern technologies used for internal organisational communication

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	3	.9	.9	.9
	Agree	41	11.7	11.7	12.6
	Neutral	20	5.7	5.7	18.3
	Disagree	70	20.0	20.0	38.3
	Strongly Disagree	216	61.7	61.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Much like the results discussed earlier, most of the workers (more than 80 percent) did not agree with the assertion that their company remained up to date in relation to modern technologies for intra-organisational communication.

4.3.27. Lack of Technology

Table 4.29: Lack of Technology

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	4	1.1	1.1	1.4
	Neutral	58	16.6	16.6	18.0
	Disagree	168	48.0	48.0	66.0
	Strongly Disagree	119	34.0	34.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

As per the results illustrated in the table, it can clearly be deduced that nearly 90 percent of workers did not agree with the idea that there was a lack of technology in their company. Less than 2 percent of workers agreed with this statement.

4.3.28. I am provided with market competitive pay rates

Table 4.30: I am provided with market competitive pay rates

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	0	0	0	0.0
	Agree	60	17.1	17.1	17.1
	Neutral	7	2.0	2.0	19.1
	Disagree	230	65.7	65.7	84.9
	Strongly Disagree	53	15.1	15.1	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

It is evident from the table that most of the respondents were deprived of market competitive pay rates, with only 17 percent of workers agreeing with the idea being considered.

4.3.29. My bonuses are satisfactory and performance based

Table 4.31: My bonuses are satisfactory and performance based

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	43	12.3	12.3	12.6
	Neutral	18	5.1	5.1	17.7
	Disagree	128	36.6	36.6	54.3
	Strongly Disagree	160	45.7	45.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

In alignment with the previous results concerning salary and compensation, the above table also shows that most of the workers in the company do not receive bonuses that are satisfactory or performance based.

4.3.30. Good performance is always recognized through promotions

Table 4.32: Good performance is always recognized through promotions

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	3	.9	.9	.9
	Agree	41	11.7	11.7	12.6
	Neutral	19	5.4	5.4	18.0
	Disagree	70	20.0	20.0	38.0
	Strongly Disagree	217	62.0	62.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

The above table clearly illustrates that most of the workers in the organisation do not receive promotions in recognition of their good performance. Only one eighth of workers were found to receive promotions for acknowledgement of good performance.

4.3.31. Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure

Table 4.33: Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	1	.3	.3	.3
	Agree	5	1.4	1.4	1.7
	Neutral	59	16.9	16.9	18.6
	Disagree	165	47.1	47.1	65.7
	Strongly Disagree	120	34.3	34.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Overall, most of the responses regarding the payment and reward structure were found to be negative (disagreement). This illustrates that most workers in the organisation do not consider the payment and rewards system to be effective enough. Moreover, this shows that, in Pakistan, automotive sector organisations do not place emphasis on aspects such as performance and rewards, which are related with the overall quality of intra-organisational communication.

4.3.32. The company has an exhaustive communication system in place

Table 4.34: The company has an exhaustive communication system in place

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	2	.6	.6	.6
	Agree	92	26.3	26.3	26.9
	Disagree	19	5.4	5.4	32.3
	Strongly Disagree	237	67.7	67.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

It is evident from the above table that most of the respondents did not think that their company had an exhaustive communication system in place, with only a small proportion of workers agreeing with this idea.

4.3.33. All the information is transmitted to all the employees in a timely manner

Table 4.35: All the information is transmitted to all the employees in a timely manner

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	45	12.9	12.9	12.9
	Disagree	24	6.9	6.9	19.7
	Strongly Disagree	281	80.3	80.3	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Upon being probed further regarding the quality of communication, similar results were obtained. This is evident from the table, which clearly shows that most of the workers did not agree with the idea that information is transmitted to all employees in a timely manner.

4.3.34. The cross functional teams are provided with effective platforms of communications

Table 4.36: The cross functional teams are provided with effective platforms of communications

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	26	7.4	7.4	7.4
	Agree	49	14.0	14.0	21.4
	Neutral	11	3.1	3.1	24.6
	Disagree	177	50.6	50.6	75.1
	Strongly Disagree	87	24.9	24.9	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

More than 75 percent of the workers (a considerable majority) did not agree with the idea that cross-functional teams in the organisation are provided with effective platforms of communications, suggesting that the organisation does not have such platforms in place.

4.3.35. Overall, I know how to reach each and every relevant member of the company

Table 4.37: Overall I know how to reach each and every relevant member of the company

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	19	5.4	5.4	5.4
	Agree	44	12.6	12.6	18.0
	Neutral	0	0	0	0.0
	Disagree	21	6.0	6.0	24.0
	Strongly Disagree	266	76.0	76.0	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

It is quite clearly deducible from the table that most of the workers did not have any idea regarding ways of contacting or communicating with other workers of the organisation.

4.3.36. We have effective formal as well as informal chains of internal communication

Table 4.38: We have effective formal as well as informal chains of internal communication

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
--	--	-----------	---------	---------------	--------------------

Valid	Strongly Agree	38	10.9	10.9	10.9
	Agree	93	26.6	26.6	37.4
	Neutral	8	2.3	2.3	39.7
	Disagree	137	39.1	39.1	78.9
	Strongly Disagree	74	21.1	21.1	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Even though a difference in the proportion of workers agreeing and disagreeing with this statement is considerably less when compared to other aspects, a significant majority of respondents did not agree with the idea that the organisation possessed effective formal and information chains of internal communication.

4.3.37. Communication System

Table 4.39: Communication System

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	43	12.3	12.3	12.3
	Disagree	245	70.0	70.0	82.3
	Strongly Disagree	62	17.7	17.7	100.0
	Total	350	100.0	100.0	

Communication system means those platforms and methods via which workers communicate with each other with top, middle or lower hierarchy. It could be traditional means and methods that covers letters and reports, and new digitalised means and methods that include email, online sharing, and alike other systems. Therefore, in the proposed work the focus is mainly allied with new modernisation techniques as it has the ability to even present the traditional methods smartly and effectively as well as in ubiquitous manner (Radovic et al., 2018).

Overall, the responses obtained in relation to the communication system were either neutral or in disagreement, as evident from the table. Moreover, more than 85 percent of the individuals were found to be in disagreement.

4.4. Descriptive Analysis - Descriptive

Table 4.40: Descriptive Statistics

N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
---	---------	---------	------	----------------

Data Analysis	350	2.00	5.00	4.2600	.69245
Focus on Personal Goals	350	1.00	5.00	4.1714	.72554
Focus on Employee Engagement	350	1.00	5.00	4.0943	.78651
Innovative Mechanisms	350	2.00	5.00	4.2543	.70278
Internal Branding	350	1.00	5.00	4.1486	.73057
Technology	350	1.00	5.00	4.1429	.74721
Payment and Reward Structure	350	1.00	5.00	4.1371	.75969
Communication System	350	3.00	5.00	4.0543	.54581
Valid N (listwise)	350				

For all the key variables, the mean was above 4, which is indicative of the fact that most of the respondents disagreed with the presence of effective data analysis, internal branding, technology, payment and reward structure, innovative mechanisms, employee engagement and personal goals. This is because 4 pertained to the disagree category.

The minimum value in most of the cases was 1, which pertained strongly agree and the maximum value was 5, which pertained to strongly disagree. In some of the cases, however, these values were not found. This is due to the averaging of various categories to develop a score for these variables.

The standard deviation of the response was at most 0.78, which shows that the scores could either move to neutral or to strongly disagree but in no case was there a chance for them to move to the strongly agree, showing an overall prevalence of dissatisfaction among the respondents in relation to the overall intra-organisational communication.

4.5. Correlation Analysis

Table 4.41: correlation analysis

		Correlations							Communication System
		Complexity of Data Analysis	Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	Lack of Innovative Mechanisms	Low Levels of Internal Branding	Lack of Technology	Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	
Complexity of Data Analysis	Pearson Correlation	1	.670**	.707**	.947**	.626**	.687**	.684**	-.462**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	Pearson Correlation	.670**	1	.901**	.701**	.898**	.948**	.940**	-.400**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.707**	.901**	1	.724**	.903**	.947**	.957**	-.372**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Lack of Innovative Mechanisms	Pearson Correlation	.947**	.701**	.724**	1	.646**	.705**	.702**	-.566**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Low Levels of Internal Branding	Pearson Correlation	.626**	.898**	.903**	.646**	1	.953**	.944**	-.387**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Lack of Technology	Pearson Correlation	.687**	.948**	.947**	.705**	.953**	1	.990**	-.391**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	Pearson Correlation	.684**	.940**	.957**	.702**	.944**	.990**	1	-.398**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
Communication System	Pearson Correlation	-.462**	-.400**	-.372**	-.566**	-.387**	-.391**	-.398**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	350	350	350	350	350	350	350	350

The Pearson correlation analysis was used in this research as a tool for assessing the strength of statistical significance as well as the nature of the relationships that exist between the dependent and the independent variables. Since the research has two quantitative variables; therefore, to articulate the relationship and significance between them, the study has used the Pearson correlation for the analysis of the results. Moreover, in this case, the following table lists the coefficient of correlation as well as the significance level for the each of the independent variables, so as to define their relationship with the dependent variable.

Table 4.42: coefficients of correlation and significance level for the independent variables

Variable	Coefficient of Correlation	Significance Level
Complexity of Data Analysis	-.462**	0.000
Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	-.400**	0.000
Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	-.372**	0.000
Lack of Innovative Mechanisms	-.566**	0.000
Low Levels of Internal Branding	-.387**	0.000
Lack of Technology	-.391**	0.000
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	-.398**	0.000

The following key assertions can be made in this regard:

- ⇒ Complexity of Data Analysis shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.462 unit in the intra-organisational communication.
- ⇒ Lack of Focus on Personal Goals shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.400 unit in the intra-organisational communication.
- ⇒ Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.372 unit in the intra-organisational communication.
- ⇒ Lack of Innovative Mechanisms shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational

communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.566 unit in the intra-organisational communication.

- ⇒ Low Levels of Internal Branding shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.387 unit in the intra-organisational communication.
- ⇒ Lack of Technology shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.391 unit in the intra-organisational communication.
- ⇒ Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure shares a negative and statistically significant (as significance level is less than p-value of 0.01) relationship with intra-organisational communication, where a unit increase in this variable will lead to a decrease of 0.398 unit in the intra-organisational communication.

4.6. Regression Analysis

Table 4.43: model summary for regression analysis – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.634 ^a	.402	.390	.42641

a. Predictors: (Constant),
Complexity of Data Analysis,
Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement,
Lack of Focus on Personal Goals,
Lack of Technology,
Lack of Innovative Mechanisms,
Low Levels of Internal Branding,
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure

As can be seen from the above table, the multivariate regression analysis has been used. The use of multivariate regression analysis is to understand the relationship between the dependent and independent variable. Similarly, table 4.6 articulates the r-square for the model that is 0.402, which indicates that the model has the capacity to explain 40.2% of the variability that exists outside of the model. In this case, the adjusted R square, which can be referred to as a better measure of quality as it is adjusted for the change in the degrees of freedom, is also 0.390. This also indicates that the model has the capacity to define 39.0 percent of the variability that exists outside the model.

Table 4.44: ANOVA table for regression analysis – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

ANOVA has been used for the regression analysis. The rationale behind this is the unique property of ANOVA, which is considered as a framework that forms the source for significance tests and offers knowledge about the variability levels within a regression model (Kumar et al., 2013). This

helps in the course of obtaining high-quality results with the nominal likelihood of risks and issues that could affect the reliability and validity of the work.

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	41.783	7	5.969	32.827	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.186	342	.182		
	Total	103.969	349			

a. Dependent Variable: Communication System

b. Predictors: (Constant),
Complexity of Data Analysis,
Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement,
Lack of Focus on Personal Goals,
Lack of Technology,
Lack of Innovative Mechanisms,
Low Levels of Internal Branding,
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure

The relatively high F value with a significance level of 0.000 indicates that the model is fairly strong with a probability of error that is close to zero. Hence, the authenticity and reliability of the model can be established.

Table 4.45: coefficients of regression analysis – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

	Model	Non-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
1	(Constant)	5.903	.158		37.260	.000
	Complexity of Data Analysis	.544	.104	.690	5.228	.000
	Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	-.020	.101	-.027	-.198	.843
	Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	.310	.103	.447	3.007	.003
	Lack of Innovative Mechanisms	-.987	.106	-1.271	-9.327	.000

Low Levels of Internal Branding	-.220	.104	-.295	-2.113	.035
Lack of Technology	.556	.256	.761	2.171	.031
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	-.614	.236	-.855	-2.606	.010

a. Dependent Variable: Communication System

The analysis of the above regression model has led towards the following key assertions:

- ⇒ Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure has been observed to have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of -0.614. This indicates that a unit increase in the ineffective payment and reward structure will lead to a decrease of 0.614 in the intra-organisational communication. Since the significance range of 0.010 is less than the confidence interval of 0.05, this interaction is statistically important.
- ⇒ Lack of Technology has been observed to have a positive impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of 0.556. This indicates that a unit increase in the lack of technology will lead to an increase of 0.556 in the intra-organisational communication. The significance level of 0.031 is smaller than the confidence interval of 0.05, so this interaction is statistically important.
- ⇒ Low Levels of Internal Branding has been observed to have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of -0.220. This indicates that a unit increase in the low levels of internal branding will lead to a decrease of 0.220 in the intra-organisational communication. Since the significance amount of 0.035 is less than the confidence interval of 0.05, this association is statistically important.
- ⇒ Lack of Innovative Mechanisms has been observed to have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of -0.987. This indicates that a unit increase in the lack of innovative mechanisms will lead to a decrease of 0.987 in the intra-organisational communication. The significance level of 0.000 is smaller than the confidence interval of 0.05, indicating that this interaction is statistically meaningful.
- ⇒ Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement has been observed to have a positive impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of 0.310. This indicates that a unit increase in the lack of focus on employee engagement will lead to an

increase of 0.310 in the intra-organisational communication. Since the significance amount of 0.003 is less than the confidence interval of 0.05, this interaction is statistically important.

- ⇒ Lack of Focus on Personal Goals has been observed to have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of -0.20. This indicates that a unit increase in the lack of focus on personal goals will lead to a decrease of 0.20 in the intra-organisational communication. This relationship, however, is not statistically significant, as the significance level of 0.843 is greater than the confidence interval of 0.05.
- ⇒ Complexity of Data Analysis has been observed to have a positive impact on the intra-organisational communication, with a coefficient of regression of 0.544. This indicates that a unit increase in the complexity of data analysis will lead to an increase of 0.544 in the intra-organisational communication. This relationship is statistically significant, as the significance level of 0.000 is less than the confidence interval of 0.05.

4.7. Hypothesis Summary Table

Table 4.46: hypothesis summary table – challenges of intra-organisational communication challenges

The following table proposes the verdict in relation to the hypothesis assessed under this research:

Hypothesis	Coefficient	Significance Level	Verdict
H1: Complexity of big data analysis has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.	0.544	0.000	Accepted
H2: Lack of focus on personal goals of the employees has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.	-0.20	.843	Reject
H3: Lack of focus on employee engagement has a negative impact on the	0.301	.003	Accept

intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.			
H4: Lack of innovative mechanisms has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.	-0.987	.000	Accept
H5: Low levels of internal branding have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.	-0.220	.035	Accept
H6: Lack of technology has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.	0.556	.031	Accept
H7: Ineffective payment and reward structures have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.	0.544	0.000	Accept

As can be seen from the above table, six out of the seven hypotheses that were developed under this research have been accepted. Hence, the findings are somewhat in alignment with the arguments that have been proposed by the literature that has been reviewed in the current research. The results of the analysis show that intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan is faced with multiple barriers (six of the seven challenges to intra-organisational communication have been found to be important in the aftermath of this statistical analysis).

The complexity of data analytics is among the foremost factors that have been found to have negative impacts on the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector. Furthermore, the lack of technology and innovation has also been found to be major factors negatively influencing intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. In a similar context, the lack of focus on employee-related aspects in the industry, such as

employee engagement, internal branding, or the payment and reward systems are important factors that can negatively influence the quality of intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies in the country.

From the above statements, it may be argued that broadly, technological and employee-related factors account for key challenges associated with intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. These factors can be linked with the availability of resources, as well as culture and practice in the country. For instance, the generalized lack of resources in the country means that the automotive sector has remained deprived of technology, which amplified the concerns associated with complexity in data analytics too, because individuals are not comfortable with the use of these technologies.

Similarly, the culture and practices in automotive sector organisations are also to blame for the challenges associated with intra-organisational communication. This is because the culture does not place emphasis on the needs of workers, thereby reducing interest, efforts and resources devoted to employee engagement, payment and reward systems or internal branding. Since intra-organisational communication is closely related with these factors, the lack of emphasis limits improvements to intra-organisational communication too. This explains the nature of these challenges.

4.7 Summary

Data collected for the research was used to assess a total of seven hypotheses drawn out on the basis of the literature review conducted earlier. The descriptive analytics reflected the distribution of the target population, providing key insights regarding the workforce of the automotive sector of the country. For instance, the male-dominance in the workforce (presence of more males and females), as well as the presence of people in age-groups 20-30 and 30-40 were observed clearly in the sample, reflecting prominent characteristics of the workforce. Similarly, the analysis revealed the resource deprived nature of the automotive sector, as well as the poor emphasis on employee engagement, payment and reward systems and innovation very clearly, highlighting major problems associated with the country's automotive sector.

In addition, six of the seven hypotheses were accepted after the correlation and regression analysis. This meant that complexity of data analytics, lack of innovation, lack of technology, lack of emphasis on employee engagement, lack of effective payment and reward systems and lack of internal branding were all found to be key challenges associated with intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. These challenges related broadly to the corporate culture and scarcity of resources in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Lastly, the statistical techniques chosen in the proposed study to assess the quantitative information generated after the data collection process descriptive statistics have been used in this research to provide details regarding the data set and respondent body. In addition to that, regression and correlation analysis are used to assess the relationships amid intra-organisational communication, its benefits/ challenges and factors affecting it in the automotive sector of Pakistan, which has also been supported by ANOVA. Regression and correlation analysis are suited to this study because both these methods allow for the identification of relationships that exist between a dependent variable and a set of independent variables. In addition to this, it can be stated that the statistical techniques chosen are analytically valid to measure means and standard deviations with Likert data and the rationale behind this is discussed with the support of studies like Kumar et al., (2013) and Viswanathan et al., (2017) that descriptive statistics supports in performing standard deviation as descriptive statistics are broken down into central tendency measures and variability measures. Central tendency measures include the mean, mode, and media, which further supports the readers in justifying the choice behind integrating the descriptive statics in the entitled study. Moreover, variability measures include standard deviation, minimum, variance, and allied others techniques to examine and evaluate the assimilated data (Hossain et al., 2019). Hence, descriptive statistical technique is considered prolific for the entitled study. On the other hand, with respect to regression and correlation, it can be stated with the support of Kannan et al., (2016) study that correlation can be used with Likert scale and according to some professionals like Kabashi et al., (2021) and Ratnam et al., (2016), it is also called Summeted scale. For regression, the support of ANOVA has been taken so that the end-results can be obtained. This is for the reason that regression is a statistical way to create the rapport amid variables sets to predict the dependent variable using independent variables. Rather, ANOVA is a statistical tool that is applied to unrelated groups to ascertain whether they have a shared mean.

Moreover, the data incorporated in the entitled study is of interval nature. Interval data is measured on a numeric scale with equal distances between adjacent values and Likert scale is considered an active and smart choice to obtain the aim and objectives of the entitled study. There is no true zero on an interval scale, which distinguishes it from a ratio scale. Interval variables are data measured on a scale whose intervals are equal. In fact, the Likert scale refers to giving qualitative data a quantitative value so that it can be used for statistical analysis. Therefore, it makes sense to use the Likert scale as interval data (Wu and Leung 2017). Therefore, based on the analysis, the choice of analytical methods is deemed to be appropriate for the entitled study. The analytical methods integrated in the entitled study is also referred as parametric methods. Hence, with the support of Emerson (2017) study, it can be stated that parametric means can be used with studies who have incorporated Likert scale as it is much easier to interpret parametric inferences and allows for a wider range of analysis. Not only is it an option, it is even recommended that researcher use parametric statistical systems with Likert scale.

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION

5.1. Chapter Introduction

This chapter is concerned with the discussion of results obtained from the statistical analysis. In this regard, the results and findings have been elaborated and compared with the existing literature to improve our understanding. Overall, this section discusses each of the challenges associated with intra-organisational communication in the Pakistani automotive sector organisations in detail, providing explanations regarding the impacts observed in each case. Where findings do not align with the wide literature on the topic, other explanations and propositions have been provided.

5.2. Key Factors Affecting Intra-Organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

It has been observed that the challenges relevant to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan are rooted in either one of the two broad concerns illustrated in the following figure:

Source: Developed by author

Examples from the analysis conducted earlier can be used to support this notion. In the quantitative analysis, it was found that the wide majority of workers at Atlas Honda Pakistan did not consider

the organisation to have technology and infrastructure for the management of data on a large-scale. This is representative of a lack of resources needed to support complex communications. Similarly, the absence of such resources also manifests as the organisation's inability to manage employee-related data. The lack of resources, therefore, has been found to expose the organisation to tackle complexity of data analytics and communication, while simultaneously hindering the adoption of technology. Since both of these factors were identified as challenges to intra-organisational communication, the idea that the paucity of funds and resources in Pakistan creates challenges in intra-organisational communication is reinforced. This is clarified further in the figure below:

Figure 5.2: Lack of Resources and Ineffectiveness of Communication

Source: Developed by author

The assertions made about this point are supported by existing literature on the topic. Indeed, Sarwar et al. (2012) and Saleem et al. (2015) point out that the automotive sector of Pakistan is underdeveloped and lacks resources (particularly in terms of technology). These studies also support the fact that the absence of necessary technological infrastructure in the industry negatively influences innovation, as well as intra-organisational communication. Effectively, the two studies establish a clear link between the absence of financial and technical resources and poor standards of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. The idea that the absence of financial and technological resources in Pakistan underpins intra-organisational communication issues can be used to imply that while challenges to intra-organisational communication may take various forms, the absence of financial resources can be found at their root.

On the other hand, the other 'broad' factor mentioned here was cultural. Culture has a prominent influence on social behavior and interactions, making it a key variable influencing workplace dynamics, managerial practice and organisational strategy. Indeed, in a culture marked by power distance, such as that of Pakistan, hierarchies are considered important and power relationships are well defined. The central management holds decision-making authority, creating barriers to the participation of workers in decision-making processes. This also gives rise to the popularity of management practices that do not favor employee freedom or involvement. Hence, a power distant culture reduces the significance of employee engagement and involvement (which can have extended negative impacts on the importance of payment and reward systems, or the value placed in employees' interests). The literature review conducted in this study, as well as the research's own findings reveal that a lack of focus on employee engagement is an important factor underpinning challenges to intra-organisational communication. The observation that, in Pakistan, preference exists for managerial practices that do not support employee engagement supports the idea that companies in the country suffer from a lack of emphasis on employee engagement. From this perspective, the managerial practices and cultural influences that hinder employee engagement can be considered to be important in relation to challenges experienced in intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Moreover, process workers work in industrial, manufacturing, and warehouse locations where they perform routine tasks, often as part of a production line and in automobile sector either in the UK, Europe, Pakistan, the role of process workers has been considered an active facet from initiation to closure of a particular automobile project (Shaju and Subhashini 2017). Process workers ensure that the machines are kept in good condition, work on schedule and follow strict safety guidelines. In addition, they take delivery of vehicle parts and prepare them for the production line. Ready-to-fit add-on parts on the vehicle. Forming of metal sheets that form the frame of the vehicle. Attach parts for the frame and several other tasks and processes are executed and completed by process workers, supported by (Jons et al., 2013). Therefore, they have been considered an essential role and character in the success of entire automobile project. So, in this regard, with the support of Deyo (2016) study, it can be stated that they the key players in the completion of the automobile project and if they are engaged and involved in the project with enthusiasm and interest, the possibility of obtaining the quality results would be on higher level. Hence, it can be stated further

that in automobile organisations, for example, Atlas Honda of Pakistan, it is necessary that there must be suitable means and methods that are validated and verified must be adopted for the employee engagement which covers personnel from well educated, middle management, white collar staff, to process workers. This action, eventually, aids in attaining the quality artefacts such as sustainability, productivity, and profitability.

A reduction in the importance of these factors can limit the perceived need for intra-organisational communication (as intra-organisational communication adds to these factors, its contributions make up its total need). With these factors being eliminated, the perceived need of intra-organisational communication may become less. Eventually, this can reduce the resources devoted to intra-organisational communication, creating barriers to its improvement. These ideas draw upon the results of this study, as well as the existing literature and are summarized in the figure illustrated below:

Figure 5.3: The Role of Cultural Factors in Challenges to Intra-organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by Author

The ideas presented in the abovementioned figure are supported by studies that consider the culture of Pakistan and its potential impacts on workplace dynamics. For example, in the work of Inderyas et al. (2015), the power distant nature of Pakistani culture, which lies at the heart of changes to workplace dynamics shown in the above figure, has been clearly outlined. The study claims that Pakistani culture is highly power distant and attributes great importance to hierarchies and power

relationships. Moreover, according to Gul et al. (2018), such a power distant culture has been linked with management practices that disregard the importance of employee freedom, preferences and involvement. As a result, these studies show that the workplace dynamics emerging from power distance in the culture of Pakistan with less emphasis on employee engagement or involvement tend to create barriers in the development of intra-organisational communication.

Extending this notion further, quite a few studies link intra-organisational communication with factors influenced by these altered workplace dynamics. For instance, the significance of intra-organisational communication in employee engagement is acknowledged by Karanges et al. (2015), Kang and Sung (2017) and Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014). On the other hand, Hrehova (2010) and Femi (2014) are examples of studies that link intra-organisational communication with personal goals and development of workers. Finally, Liu, Ko and Chapleo (2017) state that intra-organisational communication is important for internal branding too. With reference to Kushwaha and Sharma (2016) study, it can be stated that it is important in such a way that internal branding has been considered and referred as a corporate strategy metric that helps in motivating and enabling employees not matter from which department they belong, either higher, lower, or middle to not only keep the brand promise but to live it. This is strengthened and can be done in more productive manner when intra-organisation communication means and methods are integrated and practiced adequately and smartly. Thus, the more fortified intra-organisational communication is present, the more effective internal branding will be reflected, supported by (Piehler et al., 2015). This, as well as the current research findings, shows intra-organisational communication can support employee engagement, freedom and empowerment. Such studies also indicate that intra-organisational communication is a tool for companies that seek to enhance employee engagement, motivation or involvement. Therefore, the need to develop in these areas underpins the significance of intra-organisational communication.

Strong internal branding strengthens the company externally and offers employees to continuously communicate effectively with the market. An effective internal branding strategy strengthens the overall brand in many different and productive ways, which is considered to be key reason behind the success, sustainability, productivity, profitability, and competitive edge. For example, it helps ensure consistent customer experiences especially via interactions with employees; Encourages

employees to embrace brand values and build on brand engagement, thereby working more effectively towards the same goals; and creates strong brand ambassadors from within, who do not know the corporate culture but survive (Eilert et al., 2017). For car workers or it can be stated that for automobile industry, internal branding has been considered an active and smart facet that helps the company to obtain quality results via formulating effective strategies that assists in attaining the trust of end-users (Löhndorf and Diamantopoulos 2014). Kale (2017) has further stated that internal branding is extremely vital in the automotive industry as some consumers in this industry are utterly loyal to a company. Others will discover a new brand when they have a more competitive product or when someone they trust recommends it. Hence, it is also recognised as one of the key steps for the workers and automotive firm in accomplishing success, in engaging more employees with the company, and similar others benefits.

In Pakistan, these aspects are not important, and the management does not seek to work on them. Resultantly, the importance of intra-organisational communication drops, creating barriers to its development. Therefore, some important challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan are also rooted in the country's culture and its influence on workplace dynamics. It is important to mention that while these broad variables (a lack of resources and cultural considerations) have not been directly considered as challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan, they have been highlighted here due to their close association with the seven challenges that correspond to the hypotheses tested in the quantitative analysis performed earlier.

The factors that have been mentioned to this point are not part of the analysis but have been found to be associated with the main variables explored in the study. For instance, while the analysis conducted here shows that a lack of employee engagement has a negative impact on intra-organisational communication, it does not explain why or how companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan experience a lack of employee engagement. Existing literature relevant to the topic has been used to identify explanatory factors, which have then been termed as the 'broad factors' that are associated with the findings of this study. Again, the broad factors are not part of the quantitative analysis conducted earlier, but a review of the findings, coupled with analysis of the existing literature shows that they are closely associated and may play important roles in explaining

findings. Hence, they have been mentioned here to broaden understanding. These factors correspond only to the variables incorporated within the hypotheses of the concerned study and no other variables, such as age, gender or education that were discussed in the descriptive analysis conducted in Chapter Four.

5.3. Barriers and Challenges Associated with Intra-organisational Communication

Previously, a brief overview of the broad factors that underpin the challenges to intra-organisational communication has been provided in light of the results of this study. In this research, a total of seven challenges associated with intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan were identified, as illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.4: The factors underpinning barriers and challenges associated with intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by author

It was proposed that each of the aforementioned factors separately account for barriers to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Based on results of the regression and correlation analysis conducted on data collected from workers in Atlas Honda, it

has been identified that besides a “lack of focus on personal goals of workers”, all six factors negatively influence the quality of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Each of the seven factors has been discussed separately in this section to provide detailed explanations regarding the nature and influence of each factor:

5.3.1. Complexity of Big Data Analytics

The complexity of big data analytics was identified as a potential barrier to the development of effective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. It corresponded to the hypothesis “H1” in the quantitative analysis conducted earlier. Since H1 was validated after the analysis, the relationship between the complexities of big data analytics can be termed as statistically significant. As a negative relationship was proposed between the complexity of big data analytics and the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan, it can be said that the complexity of big data analytics is one of the key factors negatively influencing the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication in the country’s automotive sector.

The significance of this challenge stems from the fact that connectivity and networking have become notions of immense importance in the automobile sector. Most importantly, the rise of connected vehicles is a crucial factor here, since such vehicles are connected with their surroundings like other vehicles on the roads, as well as buildings, roads and other objects. A connected system of vehicles, roads, buildings and other devices constitutes a large communication network, which generates significant volumes of data. This information is critical for organisations because it contains insights regarding customer behavior and demands, which may be used to improve product development and strategy.

Indeed, Fan, Lau and Zhao (2015) point out that large, unstructured data (big data) can reshape business intelligence, providing support for the assertions made to this point. Furthermore, literary support for the prevalence and usefulness of connected vehicles, as well as big data analytics in automotive sector companies can also be found. In Hoseinzadeh et al. (2020), for instance, the possibility of using connected vehicles and, subsequently, big data to enhance safety and mobility has been explored. On the other hand, Syafrudin et al. (2018) clearly highlights the utility of big

data analytics for improving manufacturing processes in the automotive industry. Similarly, Johanson et al. (2014) highlight the importance of big data analytics in product development processes in the automotive sector. Such studies support the idea that connected vehicles and big data are technologies that can promote enhanced performance in the automotive sector and hence are bound to be extensively used. Also, some findings from these studies, such as the potential of big data to generate competitive advantage, also support the idea that big data is necessary for organisational survival and success.

Nevertheless, the notion of business intelligence in and of itself is not relevant to the study. However, the need for processing and interpreting this information and communicating this with the right area in an organisation is. This means that while this study is not concerned with the possibility of big data offering competitive benefits, it is definitely concerned with the need of an intra-organisational communication system capable enough to handle the complexity of the application. Simply put, big data analytics are crucial for organisational survival and success in the contemporary automotive industry but introduces complex communication-related requirements that pose challenges to intra-organisational communication. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.5: The major issues surrounding big data analytics in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by author

From the aforementioned figure, it is evident that two distinct types of complexities (pertaining to communication) originate from big data analytics. One is concerned with management of the data

originated from the network of connected devices, while the other is related with transfer of knowledge and insights generated from the data. Difficulties in data transfer stem mainly from the nature of big data. Information collected by a network of sensors implanted in connected vehicles, other objects in their surroundings or organisational machinery is unstructured, dynamic, real-time and in very large volumes. Prior to its use for generation of business intelligence (as stated in the work of Fan, Lau and Zhao (2015), the information needs to be transferred, processed, compiled and stored. Difficulties encountered in all these processes can contribute to the challenge that is posed to intra-organisational communication.

The assertion that transfer, processing, compilation and handing of big data are complex activities is supported by studies that highlight its properties. In Ghasemaghaei and Calic (2019), volume, veracity, variety and volume are identified as four important characteristics of big data. This idea is supported in the work of Kepner et al. (2014) too, who identify the same four characteristics of big data. These characteristics imply that information that classifies as a big data change rapidly, consists of multiple forms and often is in large volumes. Such characteristics make the handling, management and transfer of big data complicated processes, creating challenges in communication (indeed, transfer of information from devices within the company to the internal network and servers can constitute internal communication). Therefore, the complexity of constituent activities in management of big data accounts for challenges faced in intra-organisational communication.

On the other hand, it can be argued that the resources required for a fully functional big data system present a far more crucial challenge to intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies of Pakistan. Considering the complexity associated with activities involved in the management and communication of data, it is evident that well-developed computing capabilities are required. The development of such infrastructure requires substantial investments in information technology, which may create resource-related challenges for organisations in the automotive sector. Particularly, in the automotive sector of Pakistan, which has been found to be resource-poor when compared with the automotive sector in developed countries like USA, UK or Germany, as well as under-developed ones like India, this might present an extremely significant challenge.

The fact that management of data and communication in relation to a big data system requires advanced information technology infrastructure is supported by quite a few studies in the existing literature. Yang et al. (2017), for instance, point out that the computing resources required for the transmission and processing of big data are much more advanced than the conventional computing resources owned by organisations. Furthermore, Liu (2013) comment that management and communication of big data within an organisation requires advanced computing infrastructure and resources. When combines with Ahmed et al. (2010)'s revelation that companies in Pakistan do not actively engage in adoption of advanced technology, this implies that the country's automotive sector lacks the resources required to handle big data, thereby posing challenges to intra-organisational communication. This is summarized in the following figure:

Figure 5.6: Big data analytics and challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by author

As evident from the aforementioned figure, the complexity of big data analytics presents a significant challenge to intra-organisational communication because of the need for big data in the

automotive industry, but the absence of resources required to support it. With communication requirements left unmet, intra-organisational communication suffers.

In addition to that, another interesting aspect here is the need for human capital, as well as training. Seamless intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies that have deployed big data analytics (or any other advanced information technology, for that part) necessitates presence of specific skills. The development of such skills requires training, which gives rise to training expenses. Again, as the automotive sector of Pakistan is resource-poor, it is unlikely to possess a workforce that is already equipped with skills needed to cater to the communication-related complexities associated with big data analytics. In addition to that, companies in the automotive sector may also find the significant training-related expense to be a concern. Both these factors are illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.7: Complexity of big data analytics and challenges to intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

The assertions presented in the above-mentioned figure (and the discussion preceding it) are supported in the existing literature on this topic. Conrad and Newberry (2012), when identifying the traits that are critical for communication competence in an individual point out information

technology competence, suggesting that skills concerned with the handling, management and transmission of data are crucial for communication (both external, as well as intra-organisational communication). Similarly, Debortoli, Muller and vom Brocke (2014) point out that apart from business and technical skills, communication skills are needed for the development of an effective big data system.

Such studies clearly support the fact that effective intra-organisational communication is essential for the normal functioning of a big data system and that certain skills are needed to ensure that intra-organisational communication remains effective enough to fulfill this role. The main challenge arises from the fact that if human resource is not skilled enough and training is not conducted, the complexity of big data cannot be managed, and the intra-organisational communication system ceases to be effective. This means that the complexity of big data negatively affects intra-organisational communication if the skill-requirements are not met. Sarwar et al. (2012)'s claim that the automotive sector of Pakistan is short on resources is relevant here, because it shows that the industry does not have resources needed to meet skill requirements. Consequently, another 'pathway' by which the complexity of big data analytics hampers intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan involves the need for skills and training, which may exacerbate the situation of the under-developed industry.

A clearer representation of the challenge posed by complexity of big data analytics to intra-organisational communication is presented in the following figure:

Figure 5.8: Complexity of big data analytics and ineffective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by author

It is extremely interesting to note that the challenge posed by complexity of big data analytics has so far remained concerned with the nexus of “lack of funds and resources in the automotive sector of Pakistan”, rather than “cultural considerations” (these two broad factors have been mentioned above and linked with the study’s findings, as well as literature in an attempt to improve understanding of challenges). However, this challenge also has its roots in the power distant culture of Pakistan, as well as its impacts on managerial practices and workplace dynamics. Quratulain et al. (2018), Mazzei et al. (2018), Inderyas et al. (2015) and Gul et al. (2018) are studies that completely support the idea that the culture of Pakistan is power distant, and this promotes hierarchies in workplaces. In addition to that, these studies also support the idea that such a culture reduces the importance given to employees’ freedom and preferences in the workplace, implying that managerial practices are concerned with control, rather than involvement of workers.

All these factors are closely related with the complexity of big data and the challenge that this complexity poses for intra-organisational communication. For example, to benefit from insights generated by big-data analytics, information needs to be transferred across different functions within an organisation. Such transmission of information necessitates presence of seamless intra-organisational communication, as well as employee involvement. If employees' involvement and freedom are not valued in the workplace, communication across different functions of a company is subjected to hindrances. So, the complexity of big data analytics can weaken the intra-organisational communication system by placing pressure on it (especially if the system cannot respond due to workplace dynamics that do not support involvement of workers).

The assertions made above are supported by Yang et al. (2017) and Debortoli, Muller and vom Brocke (2014) who identify the need for superior communication to support big data analytics and the transmission of insights within an organisation. Such studies reveal that deployment of big data places pressure on the intra-organisational communication system and only an effective one can support implementation of the technology. In addition to that, studies that are concerned with knowledge management may also be used to support the assertion made here. Lee et al. (2016) identifies that transmission of knowledge from the point of origination to the point where it needed as a critical capability for knowledge management. When applied to the context of big data analytics, this means that insights generated from such a system have to be transmitted to decision-making authorities, placing pressure on the intra-organisational communication system within the company (Fuller, 2012). As the culture and workplace dynamics in Pakistan do not support involvement of workers, the complexity of big data analytics creates extra issues in intra-organisational communication, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 5.9: Big Data Analytics and Pressure on the Intra-organisational Communication System

Source: Developed by author

It is clear from the above-mentioned figure that the need for knowledge transfer associated with a big data system, coupled with consequent complexity in communication puts extra pressure on the intra-organisational communication system. The added complexity and pressure are potent challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector. In Pakistan, however, the lack of significance given to workers' freedom and involvement aggravate the extent to which intra-organisational system is weakened by this complexity and pressure. Consequently, the challenge posed by complexity of big data to intra-organisational communication possibly draws from workplace dynamics in Pakistan too.

So far, discussion has revealed that big data analytics is important to automotive sector companies in that it promises competitive benefits over rivals. The main issue is that big data systems require advanced information technology infrastructure (Liu, 2013), a wide array of communication skills (Debortoli, Muller and vom Brocke, 2014) and swift transmission of information within the organisation (Yang et al., 2017). These factors are related to intra-organisational communication and create challenges for companies in the automotive sector because of resource constraints (Saleem et al., 2015; Sarwar et al., 2012) and workplace/ cultural dynamics (Inderyas et al., 2015; Gul et al., 2018). Therefore, complexity of big data analytics has potent negative impacts on intra-

organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan and these impacts are worsened by resource-constraints, as well as power-centric workplace dynamics of companies in the industry.

5.3.2. Lack of Focus on the Personal Goals of Workers

The second challenge corresponded with H2: “lack of focus on personal goals of the employees has a negative impact on intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”. Analysis conducted on data obtained from workers at Atlas Honda showed that the relationship between “lack of focus on the personal goals of employees” and “intra-organisational communication” was found to be statistically insignificant. Consequently, H2 was not validated by the statistical analysis conducted earlier and the proposition that intra-organisational communication is affected negatively if personal goals of workers are not taken into consideration remains invalid. This is a surprising result, given that the existing literature on the topic provided ample support for the existence of such a relationship.

The role that intra-organisational communication plays in recognition of personal goals of workers and career development is acknowledged by Femi (2014) and Markaki, Sakas and Chadjipantelis (2013). These studies posit intra-organisational communication as an essential pre-requisite to two-way communication of goals and objectives in an organisation (the assertions made here are considered with peer to management communication in the organisation only). It is implied that focusing on the personal goals of workers would require the management to enhance two-way intra-organisational communication because information regarding personal goals and career aspirations cannot be transferred to the management otherwise (Dwyer and Hopwood, 2019).

Similarly, Hrehova (2010) identifies communication skills of workers to be very important for fulfillment of their personal goals. This also supports the idea that two-way intra-organisational communication is quite essential for improving the management’s awareness regarding personal goals and objectives of workers. Furthermore, in Buzzenell and Lucas (2013), other aspects related to intra-organisational communication, such as dignity and respect, have been identified as critical to the realization of personal goals and career aspirations of workers. These studies firmly establish the idea that intra-organisational communication is necessary for realization of personal goals of workers. Using this point, it has been argued that a company that focuses on personal goals of

workers has to engage in improvement of intra-organisational communication (because the realization of personal goals is not possible in its absence).

These studies propose that intra-organisational communication is a significant driver of personal development and realization of career aspirations of workers, as evident from the figure illustrated below:

Figure 5.10: Two-way communication between workers and the management in an organisation

Source: Developed by author

Even more so, studies even provide a motivation for companies to look into the career aspirations of workers, study their personal goals and improve intra-organisational communication in the process. For example, Merchant Jr (2010) shows that career development and realization of personal goals can improve workers' commitment to the organisation and enhance their performance. Rizwan et al. (2014) also comments that gaining information regarding personal goals of workers can allow organisations to support their fulfillment, thereby motivating workers and improving their performance. Other than that, this view is supported by Becker, Hartmann and Miller (2014) too, who identify personal development and career building to be key factors that motivate workers.

In line with the views presented by such studies, companies pursue high employee performance. Acknowledging the fact that focusing on personal goals of workers may motivate them, companies look to improve intra-organisational communication, because it is necessary for improving fulfillment of personal goals. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.11: The role of intra-organisational communication in fulfillment of personal goals

Source: Developed by author

The above-mentioned figure also shows that in line with the existing literature, focus on personal goals of workers has positive impacts on intra-organisational communication because companies improve communication infrastructure to support realization of these goals. In the absence of such focus, intra-organisational communication is not needed for realization of goals, making it relatively unimportant to a company. Theoretically, this implies that the lack of focus on personal goals of workers is a challenge to intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies of Pakistan.

However, as mentioned earlier, the result obtained here is the exact opposite. The relationship between lack of focus on personal goals and intra-organisational communication has been found to be insignificant. This means that despite presence of supportive literary arguments, lack of focus on personal goals is not a challenge to intra-organisational communication in automotive sector companies of Pakistan. A possible explanation to this is that automotive sector companies of Pakistan do not rely on intra-organisational communication to improve realization of personal goals of workers. This means that instead of improving their communication system to facilitate achievement of career and personal development among workers, companies could focus on other influential factors, such as training or performance evaluation. If intra-organisational communication is not considered to be an option for enhancing career development and realization

of personal benefits at all, lack of focus on these areas will not negatively influence it. The following figure shed light on this idea:

Figure 5.12: The role of training and performance evaluation in fulfillment of personal goals

Source: Developed by author

As evident from the figure presented earlier, a possible reason behind the lack of a significant relationship between lack of focus on personal goals and intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan is that other factors (that may replace intra-organisation communication) are involved. These factors include training of workers, as well as performance evaluation; both are tools that enable organisations to emphasize on attainment of personal objectives and support career development. Consequently, if focus on personal goals is low, managerial emphasis on these factors, rather than intra-organisational communication decreases. In this way, lack of focus on personal goals may not influence intra-organisational communication at all.

Some literary support can also be found for the assertions made here. Indeed, Tahir et al. (2014) points out that training and development initiatives allow employees to make better decisions. This supports their development and confidence, allowing them to attain personal goals. Similarly, Zha et al. (2017) reveals that while the training initiatives introduced by companies are focused on improving performance (to benefit the organisation), employees' personal goals- such as the desire to improve or move further in their careers- are also incorporated. Such studies imply that training and development definitely has a part to play in the attainment of personal goals. It can, therefore, be argued that intra-organisational communication possibly does not play a part here and hence, remains unaffected by lack of focus on personal goals.

Similarly, performance evaluation is another factor that can add to personal development of workers. In Kondrasuk (2011), it is argued that an ideal performance appraisal needs to incorporate the personal goals of workers to enhance motivation. Moreover, Goksoy and Alayoglu (2013) mention the significance of conflicts between organisational and personal goals in performance appraisals, indicating that both are part of the evaluation process. The point here is that instead of working on intra-organisational communication to enhance attainment of personal goals (as was assumed earlier), a company may be more concerned with training initiatives or enhancement of performance evaluation frameworks. In this way, if the focus on personal goals of workers is low, intra-organisational communication would not be affected at all, because its development or improvement were never linked with personal goals of workers in the first place.

It is important to clarify here that the predominant viewpoint across the literature is that intra-organisational communication is an important facilitator when it comes to attainment of workers' personal goals. Using this, it was hypothesized that low focus on personal goals in the automotive sector of Pakistan acts as a barrier to intra-organisational communication because companies have one less reason to improve it. However, since this relationship was found to be statistically insignificant, other factors can be taken into account. That is, companies may not even consider intra-organisational communication to improve attainment of personal goals and focus on other areas, such as training and development or performance evaluation. In such a situation, lack of focus on personal goals will negatively influence these other factors, but not intra-organisational communication. This is a possible explanation for the insignificant relationship observed here.

5.3.3. Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement

The third challenge to intra-organisational communication considered in this research was “lack of focus on employee engagement”. It corresponded to the third hypothesis, H3: Lack of focus on employee engagement has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan. Statistical analysis performed on data collected from individuals working at Atlas Honda, Pakistan validated that said hypothesis. Thus, the negative relationship between “lack of focus on employee engagement” and “intra-organisational communication” is statistically significant.

A straightforward implication of this is that companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan do not place emphasis on employee engagement and this, in turn, contributes to the ineffectiveness of intra-organisational communication. For the most part, this finding is rooted in the intimate relationship between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication. Intra-organisational communication is a significant driver of employee engagement in any organisation (including those in the automotive sector). The main reason behind this is that improved communication within the organisation allows workers to engage in meaningful interactions with their superiors and managers, bolstering their confidence. This is an example of peer to management communication within the company.

On the other hand, peer to peer communication, whereby workers communicate with other non-managerial staff across the organisation is also significant in terms of employee engagement. This is because improved intra-organisational communication (peer to peer) translates to better transmission of information between workers. Eventually, this can increase the extent to which workers are informed, thereby adding to their confidence, motivation and commitment. Essentially, this is reflective of improved employee engagement.

This can be tied back to the rational choice theory, where it has been indicated by Paternoster, Jaynes and Wilson (2017) that the overall organisational communication efficiency and productivity is the consequence and sum of the efforts taken by the individual employees. In case of lack of employee engagement, the employees are not provided with the chances or opportunities that may allow them to play their role in developing the overall intra-organisational communication within the company.

Numerous studies in the existing literature support the idea that intra-organisational communication is crucial to employee engagement or has positive impacts on it. Kang and Sung (2017) clearly state that intra-organisational communication sets the stage for employee engagement, while Karanges et al. (2015) point out that intra-organisational communication needs to be effective for workers to be engaged. Ruck and Welch (2012) also support the idea that employee engagement is positively influenced by intra-organisational communication. Such studies clearly indicate that intra-organisational communication is a factor that has a strong

positive influence on employee engagement. An organisation seeking to improve employee engagement, therefore, would be targeting intra-organisational communication, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 5.13: Focus on employee engagement and the need for stronger intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

The point being made here is that focusing on employee engagement drives managerial interest in intra-organisational communication too. This means that a company that intends to improve employee engagement will work on its communication system, improving intra-organisational communication. Literary support exists for this notion. An example is the work of Balakrishnan and Masthan (2013), which reveals that the management considers intra-organisational communication to be an important area with respect to employee engagement. Thus, when the need to improve employee engagement arises, managerial interest in intra-organisational communication increases. Alternatively, if focus on employee engagement dwindles, the management's interest in intra-organisational communication is bound to decrease as well. Resultantly, lack of focus on employee engagement negatively influences intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Having established that presence of focus on employee engagement drives interest in and improvements to intra-organisational communication, it can be said that the absence thereof will have the opposite effect. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.14: Lack of focus on employee engagement and its negative impact on the need for intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

As evident from the above-mentioned figure, lack of focus on employee engagement negatively results in lack of focus on intra-organisational communication. This is attributable to the fact that the need to improve employee engagement is one of the reasons behind company interest in intra-organisational communication. If companies do not hold employee engagement in high regard, they have one less reason to focus on intra-organisational communication, negatively influencing total interest in it. Again, the work of Balakrishnan and Masthan (2013) provides literary support here. The study states that managers work on intra-organisational communication to improve employee engagement. Similarly, Karanges et al. (2015) states that intra-organisational communication positively impacts employee engagement, posing it's as a tool to enhance the latter. Ruck and Welch (2012) also suggest that improvements to intra-organisational communication result in better engagement of workers, hinting at its usefulness as a tool to improve the latter.

Extending this notion, low focus on employee engagement can result in low focus on intra-organisational communication, limiting efforts made for its improvement. Consequently, the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication remains low. Hence, the negative impact of lack of focus on employee engagement on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan can be attributed to the fact that focus on employee engagement drives focus on intra-organisational communication (because of the latter's utility in improving the former).

In addition to that is important to discuss the significance of Pakistani culture and workplace dynamics in the regard. The power distance of Pakistani culture, in particular, can prove to be explanatory here. High power distance promotes hierarchical organisations that emphasize upon

control of workers, rather than involvement. This means that in Pakistani automotive companies, hierarchies and chains of command are considered to be very important. Significance given to workers' involvement remains quite low. Consequently, there is lack of focus on the engagement of workers in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Studies conducted on cultural dimensions in Pakistan support this idea. Inderyas et al. (2015), for instance, points out that the culture of Pakistan is power distant, with Gul et al. (2018) arguing that this promotes use of management practices that favour structure and control over engagement and freedom of workers. All these factors point in the direction that Pakistani culture contributes to the lack of focus on employee engagement in the country's automotive sector. As a result, the negative impacts of this factor on intra-organisational communication are felt strongly.

Moreover, it is interesting to note that of the two 'broad' factors that were observed to be closely related with challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector in Pakistan, "cultural considerations and workplace dynamics" is more important here. This is because the lack of focus on employee engagement stems not from the paucity of resources, but rather the culture and workplace dynamics that do not value involvement and freedom of workers. The following figure summarizes this idea:

Figure 5.15: The lack of focus on employee engagement and challenges to intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

While the discussion so far has been focused on the observation that intra-organisational communication draws its importance from the role it plays in improving employee engagement,

there is another possible explanation for the relationship that has been observed here. That is, employee engagement can be thought of as a factor that influences intra-organisational communication (rather than being affected by it). If this holds true, the following bi-directional relationship can be observed between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication:

Figure 5.16: The bi-directional relationship between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

As clearly illustrated in the aforementioned figure, employee engagement positively impacts intra-organisational communication because of its value in supporting two-way communication within the company. Therefore, the higher the levels of employee engagement are in an organisation, the better intra-organisational communication will be. Moreover, employee engagement also improves confidence and commitment. This is supported in the work of Ashraf et al. (2012), who point out that improving employee engagement results in enhanced organisational commitment, as well as confidence. These factors, in turn, go on to improve the quality of communication within the organisation.

Apart from that, further literary support for the assertion made here can be drawn from Vercic and Vokic (2017). The authors state that employee engagement and intra-organisational communication share a two-way relationship. While intra-organisational communication is certainly necessary for engagement of workers, an improvement in employee engagement induces positive changes in effectiveness of communication within the organisation. Therefore, the lack of focus on employee engagement in Pakistani automotive companies could deprive intra-organisational communication from these benefits, acting as a challenge to it. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.17: Lack of focus on employee engagement and ineffective intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

The idea that lack of focus on employee engagement can negatively impact intra-organisational communication in an organisation is a theme found in some studies. Mishra, Boynton and Mishra (2014), for instance, point out that an intra-organisational communication model that does not focus on employee engagement is unlikely to generate good results, because the engagement of workers is critical for seamless communication. In this way, the study appreciates the essential nature of employee engagement for effective intra-organisational communication. It is also implied that if employee engagement in an organisation is weak, intra-organisational communication will also suffer. This explains the negative relationship between “lack of focus on employee engagement” and “intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan”.

Again, it is quite necessary to consider the fact that this interplay between employee engagement and intra-organisational communication is not unique to the automotive sector or companies in Pakistan. What makes this challenge significant in the country’s automotive sector is the inherent lack of emphasis on employee involvement. As discussed previously, this lack of interest is rooted in the highly power distant culture of the country. Indeed, studies like Quratulain et al. (2018) and Mazzei (2018) show that the high level of power distance in the country and the prevalence of hierarchies create barriers to employee engagement and two-way communication (particularly between workers and the management, giving an example of peer to management communication). So, in the automotive sector of Pakistan, the lack of employee engagement emerges as a key challenge to intra-organisational communication not only because of the inter-linkages between

employee engagement and intra-organisational communication but also because of barriers to involvement created by the country's culture. This is clarified further in the following figure:

Figure 5.18: The Interplay between employee engagement, intra-organisational communication and cultural considerations in Pakistan

Source: Developed by author

Thus, the negative relationship between lack of focus on employee engagement and intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan stems from the close relationship that employee engagement and intra-organisational communication share. For one, intra-organisational communication is a factor that is known to improve employee engagement. It is, therefore, not uncommon for companies to improve intra-organisational communication when they are faced with low levels of engagement. In this sense, focus on employee engagement drives

focus on intra-organisational communication. Secondly, employee engagement independently casts positive impacts on intra-organisational communication. Lack of focus on employee engagement, therefore, can deprive intra-organisational communication of the focus, as well as positive benefits that it receives when a company emphasizes employee engagement.

Also, the challenge is quite relevant for the automotive sector of Pakistan because the country's culture creates barriers to employee engagement and communication. With companies already being less keen to improve engagement, as well as communication, negative impacts can be felt more strongly. As a result, this challenge can be identified as particularly significant for intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

5.3.4. Lack of Innovative Mechanisms

The fourth challenge to intra-organisational communication considered in this research was the lack of innovative mechanisms. This corresponded with H4: "A lack of innovative mechanisms has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan". Upon being subject to statistical analysis using data collected from workers at Atlas Honda, Pakistan, H4 was validated. Thus, the negative relationship between "lack of innovative mechanisms" and "intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan" was statistically significant.

Results of the analysis conducted earlier show that a lack of innovative mechanisms negatively influences intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Simply put, this shows that the automotive sector of Pakistan does not have an innovation-driven strategy to support communication, which negatively impacts frameworks and infrastructures devoted to communication. The net outcome is weak intra-organisational communication. In this way, the absence of innovation-driven strategy or innovative mechanisms acts as a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the country's automotive sector.

The result obtained here has multiple explanations and implications. Firstly, it is critical to appreciate the relationship between innovation and intra-organisational communication here. Even though the study focused on the negative impacts of the lack of innovative mechanisms, this relationship is ultimately rooted in the association between innovative mechanisms and intra-organisational communication. That is, if there is a lack of innovative mechanisms, intra-

organisational communication in a company is influenced negatively (which is in reality the loss of positive impacts that it could have enjoyed in the presence of innovative mechanisms). This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.19: The Impact of Innovative Mechanism on Effectiveness of Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

The positive relationship illustrated in the above figure is associated with the concept of innovation. Innovative mechanisms are related to novelty. That is, if a company has innovative mechanisms in place, it possesses the capability to look for new, unique and highly effective solutions to any problems that it may encounter. In the context of communication, particularly in the automotive sector of Pakistan, this means that the presence of innovative mechanisms can allow for tackling communication-related challenges. This is particularly important in the automotive sector where the transfer and sharing of information can become quite complicated. Muniz et al. (2019) support this assertion, commenting that in the automotive sector, the transfer and sharing of information is a complex task. Therefore, the requirement for innovative mechanisms is high in the automotive sector (as a unique way of intra-organisational communication that facilitates the transfer of information to help counter the complexity).

This assertion is cemented further by the work of De Medeiros, Ribeiro and Cortimiglia (2014), who acknowledge the idea that innovation is equivalent to novelty and unconventionality in operations. In the context of intra-organisational communication, innovation implies the use of unconventional tools and media to enhance the transfer of information across the organisation (this covers both peer to peer and peer to management communication, as both are affected by communication systems, channels and media in an organisation) (Quirke, 2012). Also, Zerfass et al. (2018) comment that an innovation-driven communication strategy is necessary for organisations because of the unique challenges they face in the contemporary era. Thus, the importance of innovative mechanisms to intra-organisational communication draws from three different aspects, as illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.20: The Three Facets of Innovative Mechanisms' Impact upon Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

In the above figure, the important role those innovative mechanisms play in the improvement of intra-organisational communication is clearly illustrated. It is clear that the significance of innovative mechanisms stems not only from their positive impacts on intra-organisational communication, but also from factors that create the need for unique tools and media for

communication. For instance, the complexity of information transfer and sharing in the automotive sector, as identified by Muniz et al. (2019), intensifies the importance of innovative mechanisms for communication (because the complexity has to be overcome using new and unconventional tools). Similarly, the unique challenges to communication found in the contemporary era, such as cultural, lingual or geographic barriers (Quirke, 2012), also necessitates the presence of innovative mechanisms for intra-organisational communication.

Having highlighted the importance of innovative mechanisms to intra-organisational communication, it can be stated that the lack of innovative mechanisms is a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan because the complexity and needs associated with communication remain unchecked. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.21: The Negative Influence of a Lack of Innovative Mechanisms on Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

It is quite clear from the above figure that the lack of innovative mechanisms exposes organisations in the automotive sector to the complexity and challenges associated with communication. With no unique approaches available to curb these issues, intra-organisational communication received a negative blow. Hence, the lack of innovative mechanisms assumes the role of a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

So far, the discussion has focused on the role those innovative mechanisms play in intra-organisational communication and how their absence acts as a challenge. This is one way to look at things. Another line of reasoning for the established lack of innovative mechanisms as a challenge to intra-organisational communication considers the influence of intra-organisational communication on innovative mechanisms (rather than the converse relationship that has been discussed so far). The point being made here is that intra-organisational communication also positively influences innovative mechanisms in an organisation.

A number of researchers support this point of view. Bruhn and Ahlers (2017) and Suh, Harrington and Goodman (2018) clearly state that intra-organisational communication is important for innovation in an organisation. These studies imply that improvements to intra-organisational communication result in improvements to innovative mechanisms (and the converse is also true). Verčič and Vokić (2017) also suggest that intra-organisational communication is the cause of innovation in a company. From this, it follows that in an organisation with weak intra-organisational communication, the level of innovation is low and hence there is a lack of innovative mechanisms. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.22: The Impacts of Intra-organisational Communication on Innovation within the Company

Source: Developed by author

The critical nature of intra-organisational communication and innovation in companies can be explained via knowledge management perspective too. As intra-organisational communication is concerned with the transfer and sharing of information, it facilitates knowledge management in

organisations. Knowledge management, in turn, bolsters innovative mechanisms, presenting another pathway by which intra-organisational communication is important to innovation in companies. Lee et al. (2016) and Mahdi, Nassar and Almsafir (2019) support this idea, suggesting that knowledge management is the source of innovation, and offers a competitive advantage to an organisation. Again, because intra-organisational communication facilitates knowledge transfer, it can be considered to be very important for innovation and innovative mechanisms in companies (Quirke, 2012). Moreover, Muniz et al. (2019)'s idea that knowledge transfer and sharing are marred by complexity in the automotive sector intensifies the importance of intra-organisational communication in this regard. These assertions imply that intra-organisational communication is invaluable to innovative mechanisms in the automotive sector because of its contributions to knowledge transfer and sharing. This is shown in the following figure:

Figure 5.23: Intra-organisational communication, knowledge transfer and innovation in the company

Source: Developed by author

It is clear from the above figure that intra-organisational communication has an important role to play in supporting innovation in organisations via its facilitation of knowledge management. The lack of innovative mechanisms in the automotive sector of Pakistan presents a challenge to intra-organisational communication because it reflects the low perceived need for innovative mechanisms in companies. This, in turn, limits improvements made to intra-organisational communication, highlighting the nature of this challenge. Therefore, the lack of innovative

mechanisms acts as a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan in two ways:

Figure 5.24: The Two-Way Impact of a Lack of Innovative Mechanisms on Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

To this point, two mechanisms that explain the negative relationship between a lack of innovative mechanisms and intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan have been discussed. Both these mechanisms have been summarized in the above figure. It is also important to shed light on factors that account for the lack of innovative mechanisms in the automotive sector of Pakistan because this may explain why the reasoning presented earlier applies to companies in operating in this specific industry.

In Section 5.2, it was pointed out that the challenges to intra-organisational communication are related broadly to two factors: the paucity of resources and cultural considerations. Both these factors can be used to explain the results obtained here. The paucity of resources in the automotive sector of Pakistan has been established by researchers like Saleem et al. (2015) and Sarwar et al. (2012). Such studies suggest that companies in the automotive sector are often bound by resource constraints. Using unconventional and innovative media for communication becomes difficult for these companies due to the lack of resources. Firstly, the direct cost associated with technological

innovation in communication may hinder progress (Quirke, 2012). Secondly, skills and capabilities required to work with unconventional communication media may result in increased training requirements, incurring further expenditure (DeCenzo, Robbins and Verhulst, 2016). As companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan experience shortages of resources, their progress in relation to innovative mechanisms is limited, creating challenges to intra-organisational communication.

On the other hand, cultural considerations are important too. Among the dimensions of culture outlined in Hofstede's model, uncertainty avoidance is related closely to innovative mechanisms. This is because uncertainty avoidance represents the extent to which people resist change. Innovation, being supportive of novelty and unconventionality, goes against uncertainty avoidance. Therefore, in a region with high uncertainty avoidance, the lack of innovative mechanisms is likely to be more pronounced than in one with relatively low uncertainty avoidance. Zeng and Hao (2016) reveal that Pakistan is rated quite high in the uncertainty avoidance index provided by Hofstede. Bashir et al. (2012) also support this idea, stating that Pakistani culture is marked by high uncertainty avoidance. Therefore, companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan have a high chance of facing a lack of innovative mechanisms because of the inherent resistance to change and unconventionality.

This assertion is supported by the work of Kaasa and Vadi (2010), who point out that uncertainty avoidance in a region shares a negative relationship with the propensity to change. A culture with high uncertainty avoidance is reflective of resistance to change. As innovation is closely related to novelty and change, uncertainty avoidance counters the propensity to innovate. Moreover, regions with high uncertainty avoidance generally have regulations to promote uniformity and prevent ambiguity. Thus, high uncertainty avoidance in Pakistan also explains the low propensity to innovate in automotive companies of the country. Eventually, this signifies the challenge that is presented by the lack of innovative mechanisms to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

The following figure illustrates the ways in which this negative relationship between lack of innovative mechanisms and intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan draws from the paucity of resources and high uncertainty avoidance in the country:

Figure 5.25: The Negative Impacts of Lack of Innovative Mechanisms on Intra-organisational Communication in the Automotive Sector of Pakistan

Source: Developed by author

To sum it up, the lack of innovative mechanisms in Pakistan negatively impacts intra-organisational communication in the country. This can be explained via the direct impacts of innovative mechanisms on communication, as well as the perceived importance of intra-organisational communication (which stems from its positive impacts on innovation, among other things). Either way, the lack of innovative mechanisms limits the quality of intra-organisational communication, as well as efforts made for its improvement. This relationship is associated with a lack of resources in the automotive sector of Pakistan, as well as high uncertainty avoidance. Both these factors aggravate the lack of innovative mechanisms. Therefore, Pakistani automotive sector companies face an extremely significant lack of innovative mechanisms, which poses a major threat to the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication.

5.3.5. *Low Levels of Internal Branding*

Another challenge associated with intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan was the persistently low level of internal branding. This challenge corresponded to the

fifth hypothesis, H5: “Low levels of internal branding have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, which was tested using regression and correlation analysis. Results obtained from the statistical analysis show that the hypothesis is valid. Hence, it can be said that a statistically significant relationship exists between low levels of internal branding and intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

The exact nature of this challenge can be explained using the relationship between intra-organisational communication and internal branding. Internal branding refers to the process of promoting the company’s brand, culture and values within the organisation. Unsurprisingly, this requires transmission of information regarding the values and characteristics of the brand. Indeed, Sharma and Kamalanabhan (2012) argued that enhancements to the flow of information to internal stakeholders are necessary for internal branding in an organisation. Effective transmission of information to internal stakeholders, in turn, depends on the quality of intra-organisational communication. Thus, the relationship between intra-organisational communication and internal branding is as follows:

Figure 5.26: The Relationship between Internal Branding and Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

The above figure shows that there exists a positive relationship between internal branding and intra-organisational communication. As intra-organisational communication is necessary for internal branding success, high levels of internal branding increase the need for intra-organisational communication. On the other hand, low levels of internal branding can result in a decreased need for intra-organisational communication. This can decrease the resources devoted to improvements in intra-organisational communication. Consequently, the quality of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan remains low because of low levels of internal branding.

A link between the acceptance of this hypothesis and the social exchange theory can be developed. As indicated by the research of Thibaut (2017), Yan et al. (2016), Mortensen (2017), the interactions that exist between employers, employees and the organisation play an important role in enhancing the effectiveness of the overall communication systems. As the company lacks the internal branding processes, which could allow the employees to better interact with the organisation, the overall intra-organisational communication system of the organisation is not very strong, which is proven by the overall results of this dissertation.

Support for this assertion can be found in the existing literature. For instance, a number of studies make mention of the important role of intra-organisational communication in internal branding. Lee, Kim and Kim (2014) state that intra-organisational communication is an essential component of internal branding in an organisation. Low levels of internal branding, thus, reflect a low quality of intra-organisational communication. Moreover, this also implies that in a company with low levels of internal branding, the overall requirement for improving intra-organisational communication is low. Therefore, low levels of internal branding in the automotive sector of Pakistan present a challenge to intra-organisational communication.

Other studies also provide support for this notion. Punjaisri and Wilson (2017) reveal that intra-organisational communication is necessary for the success of internal branding tactics used by an organisation. In the presence of low levels of internal branding, few tactics are introduced, implying that the overall need for intra-organisational communication is low. This hinders development of intra-organisational communication infrastructure and capabilities. Furthermore,

Liu, Ko and Chapleo (2017) suggest that in order to increase the chances of success of their internal branding initiatives, companies need to improve the transmission of information between different departments. This clearly shows that if the levels of internal branding are high, numerous initiatives are used and the measures taken to improve communication are higher in number as compared to situations where the levels of internal branding are low, and few initiatives are introduced.

On the other hand, some studies provide even greater support for the point being made here, suggesting that intra-organisational communication is part of internal branding. It is important to clarify this. Previously, the findings of studies like Punjaisri and Wilson (2017) and Liu, Ko and Chapleo (2017) showed that intra-organisational communication is important for internal branding (it increases effectiveness and chances of success). Matanda and Ndubisi (2013), in contrast, suggest that intra-organisational communication is part of internal branding. This means that internal branding is incomplete without intra-organisational communication. Moreover, this also means that the higher the level of internal branding will be, the stronger intra-organisational communication will have to be to support transmission of information as part of internal branding. Dryl (2017) also supports this latter notion, suggesting that intra-organisational communication is a necessary part of internal branding. The following figure further clarifies the difference of academic opinions obtained in this regard:

Figure 5.27: The Varying Roles of Intra-organisational Communication in Internal Branding

As evident from the figure, intra-organisational communication is related to internal branding in two major ways. In either way, it makes important contributions to internal branding and serves as a mode to realize the benefits offered by it. Therefore, it can be implied that intra-organisational communication provides a possible target for improvement when companies seek to improve internal branding. Also, in companies with low levels of internal branding, the overall requirement

for intra-organisational communication is low, because information does not have to be transmitted to internal stakeholders. This may also limit actions taken to improve the quality of intra-organisational communication. These factors that link low levels of internal branding with ineffective intra-organisational communication are illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.28: The Factors Linking Low Levels of Internal Branding with Ineffective Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

From the above figure, it is clear that low levels of internal branding in automotive sector organisations can contribute to ineffective intra-organisational communication. There are two possible explanations for this. The first one considers intra-organisational communication's status as a part of internal branding. Under this perspective, internal branding receives less interest (and its levels are low), its components (including intra-organisational communication) are likely to follow suit. This implies that in an automotive sector organisation with low levels of internal branding, the focus on intra-organisational communication is low, causing it to remain relatively underdeveloped. This yields ineffective intra-organisational communication.

On the other hand, the second explanation provided here considers the role played by intra-organisational communication in internal branding. This is centred around Sharma and Kamalanabhan (2012)'s idea that internal branding necessitates a transfer of information to internal stakeholders. To support this requirement, an effective intra-organisational communication framework is necessary. Consequently, in an automotive sector organisation where high levels of internal branding are present, the frequency and volume of internal information transfer are high and an effective intra-organisational communication system is developed to cater to those needs. Conversely, in an automotive sector organisation with little to no internal branding, the flow of information to internal stakeholders is minimal and intra-organisational communication remains underdeveloped.

The assertions made up to this point explain why low levels of internal branding negatively influence intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. However, it is critical to discuss factors specific to Pakistan that contribute to this issue because the research question is concerned with automotive sector companies in Pakistan and not elsewhere. These factors have not been subject to analysis but play only an explanatory role here. That is, discussing factors specific to Pakistan can show why the challenge posed by low levels of internal branding is important to automotive sector companies in the country.

With this caveat being addressed, the significance of this challenge for Pakistani companies can be linked to the culture of Pakistan. Earlier on, it was pointed out that an interesting finding of this study is that all the challenges identified here are related to either one or both of the 'broad' factors, namely paucity of resources and cultural considerations. These factors were not part of the data analysis but were observed to be important when reviewing the findings and hence have been discussed here. In case of this challenge, the culture of Pakistan and its impacts on internal branding are crucial. Most importantly, the high power-distance of Pakistani culture has been discussed previously. Indeed, Bashir et al. (2012) suggest that Pakistani culture is marked by high power-distance (assessed using Hofstede's cultural insights model). This shows that in the country, the ideas, preferences and involvement of workers are not valued. As internal branding focuses on informing workers regarding the brand and its characteristics, its use is set to be low in a workplace with high power-distance and low emphasis on worker involvement.

Therefore, it is important to note here that the automotive sector of Pakistan is particularly exposed to challenges created by low levels of internal branding in relation to intra-organisational communication. Again, it must be highlighted here that culture or high power-distance were not variables in the analysis or part of the research question. They have been used here to explain why low level of internal branding constitutes a significant challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

5.3.6. Lack of Technology

The lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan was identified as another challenge to intra-organisational communication. It corresponds to H6: “Lack of technology has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, which was subject to statistical analysis in the previous section. Results obtained using data from workers of Atlas Honda, Pakistan show that the hypothesis is statistically valid. This means that a significant negative relationship exists between a lack of technology and the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

The result obtained here has a few straightforward implications. Firstly, it points to a lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Results of the descriptive analysis show that employees at Atlas Honda did not consider the organisation to be equipped with technology that is needed to manage data and communications. This supports the idea that companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan do not possess the necessary technology to support intra-organisational communication. The second implication here is that this lack of technology negatively impacts intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector, as clearly illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.29: Lack of Technology and Ineffective Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

As evident from the figure (and the preceding discussion), the relationship sheds light on two important areas: the lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan and its negative influence on the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication. Starting with the first part of the assertion, the lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan has been discussed by some researchers. Ahmed et al. (2010), for instance, reveals that automotive sector companies in the country do not rely on technology to support communications.

Furthermore, in the work of Sarwar et al. (2012) and Saleem et al. (2015), it has been pointed out that intra-organisational in the automotive sector of Pakistan lags behind those of developed countries in terms of technology and resources. These studies indicate that apart from a general problem with the accessibility to technology in the country, automotive sector organisations also have to tackle the resource-related constraints and their negative impact on the ability to utilize technology. The results of these studies show that in the automotive sector of Pakistan, reliance on technology is low because of a paucity of resources and poor accessibility to technology.

On the other hand, it may also be argued that cultural factors and workplace conditions account for the lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Earlier it was pointed out that Pakistani culture created barriers to innovation and the adoption of innovative technologies. The same notion can be raised here, implying that a lack of technology presents a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan because companies in the country are fairly resistant to adopting new technologies. This means that they are highly exposed to the negative impacts of a lack of technology to intra-organisational communication.

The notion presented above is supported by the work of Bashir et al. (2012) who show that Pakistan's culture is dominated by high levels of uncertainty avoidance. Uncertainty avoidance is a cultural dimension proposed by Hofstede, which shows the extent to which people in a region are open to change. High uncertainty avoidance means that change is not met positively. Therefore, in Pakistani companies (including those in the automotive sector), readiness to adopt new technologies for communication is low. Moreover, Abbasi et al. (2015) show that intention to use, accept or adopt technology at the individual level is influenced by norms and culture. This implies that the high level of uncertainty avoidance in individuals of Pakistan is likely to decrease their

propensity to adopt and use technology. As a result, it can be argued that the culture of Pakistan is not supportive of technology adoption or use.

It is important to highlight here that the factors discussed up to this point—the lack of resources in automotive sector of Pakistan or the high uncertainty avoidance—are not independent variables in the analysis and this research does not seek to explore their impacts on intra-organisational communication. They have been discussed here to show why the lack of technology is a relevant challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. That is, the impacts of a lack of technology on intra-organisational communication have been assessed and verified in this study, but their relevance to the automotive sector of Pakistan stems from the fact that automotive sector companies lack resources to invest in technology and resist adoption due to the high uncertainty avoidance that prevails in Pakistani culture.

To this point, it has been established that lack of technology is a relevant issue for companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan. It is now necessary to discuss the nature of its impacts on intra-organisational communication. Results from the quantitative analysis show that a lack of technology negatively influences communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. This is most probably because of the significance of technology, such as new communication media, to intra-organisational communication. A multi-modal communication strategy improves the quality of intra-organisational communication. The lack of technology can limit the adoption of such a strategy, resulting in ineffective communication. Therefore, the fact that technology has positive impacts on the quality of intra-organisational communication can be used to suggest that its absence can result in ineffective intra-organisational communication.

The significance and role of technology to intra-organisational communication is accepted widely across the existing literature on the topic. Agnihotri et al. (2016), for instance, suggest that technology is extremely important to intra-organisational communication. In a similar context, Nguyen, Newby and Macaulay (2015) comment that intra-organisational communication is affected positively by the presence of supportive technology. Moreover, Jussila, Karkkainen and Aramo-Immonen (2014) clearly reveal that communication technology plays an important part in supporting intra-organisational communication. These studies implicate that the presence of

supportive technology within an organisation improves the quality of intra-organisational communication. From this, the converse implication can also be made. That is, if supportive technologies are not present, the positive impacts that they impart are absent, resulting in a low quality of intra-organisational communication. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.30: Lack of Technology and Low Quality of Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

In addition to that, the significance of technology to intra-organisational communication is supported in academic works concerning more specific communication media too. For instance, Young and Hinesly (2014) comment on the benefits that are offered by social media as a channel of intra-organisational communication. The study shows that companies are becoming increasingly reliant on social media to support intra-organisational communication, revealing the extent to which technology has become involved in communication. On the other hand, Men (2014) reveals that intra-organisational communication is supported by multiple media, such as enhanced video/audio, webcams and online chat platforms. These technologies support communication within the organisation.

Earlier, it was shown that automotive companies in Pakistan are faced with the dual concern of lack of resources and resistance to change when it comes to adoption of technology. Lack of technology, therefore, was observed to be a relevant issue for the automotive sector of the country. Considering the fact that modern technologies are adopted actively by companies and play an important role in intra-organisational communication, it is clear that companies operating in the automotive sector of Pakistan are deprived of the benefits on offer. This means that the lack of technology is a significant and relevant challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Apart from that, another dimension to the effects that technology has on intra-organisational communication is that it potentiates the positive impacts of the latter. Up to this point, it was suggested that technology is necessary for intra-organisational communication or that its presence improves the quality of communication within the organisation. Here, the possible role of technology as a factor that enhances the positive impacts of intra-organisational communication is being considered. This means that the positive impacts of intra-organisational communication exist regardless of the presence or absence of supportive technology but are more pronounced if it is present. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.31: Supportive technology and the effects of intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

The possible role of supportive technology as a potentiator for intra-organisational communication is clearly illustrated above. Some literary support can be found for this type of relationship too. Jiménez-Castillo and Sánchez-Pérez (2013), for instance, show that the positive influence of intra-organisational communication on knowledge management is enhanced in the presence of

integrated information technology. Considering the fact that supportive technology acts as a potentiator of intra-organisational communication, it can be stated that the lack of such technology can result in a reduction in the positive effects on intra-organisational communication. This can be considered as decreased effectiveness of intra-organisational communication. Thus, the lack of technology in automotive sector of Pakistan acts as a challenge to intra-organisational communication.

However, it must be noted that not all studies consider supportive technology to be totally advantageous for communication within the organisation. A common argument that is raised against the positive nature of technology (with respect to communication) is that employees are not experienced in the use of new communication channels, which can result in a mismatch of skills and poor realization of benefits. Indeed, Lipiäinen, Karjaluoto and Nevalainen (2014) suggest that the benefits that technology has to offer for intra-organisational communication are commendable, but it also introduces unique skill requirements that can prove to be quite problematic.

Similarly, Young and Hinesly (2014) suggest that the realization of benefits offered by technologies in communication depends on the effectiveness of implementation and use. Since continued use requires the necessary skills from workers, this does support the idea that a lack of skills may convert technology into a disadvantageous rather than advantageous tool in terms of communication. While these studies certainly point out that the adoption of technology to support intra-organisational communication can introduce challenges, rather than smoothening communication within the company, this can be viewed from a different perspective. That is, the adoption of technology requires new skills, which encourages companies to train workers, resulting in improved intra-organisational communication competence in the long run (Guffey and Loewy, 2010). This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.32: Supportive technology and the improvement of intra-organisational communication

Source: Developed by author

As illustrated above, the new training requirements introduced by adoption of technology in companies result in better communication skills among workers when fulfilled. This can have positive rather than negative impacts on intra-organisational communication in the long run. Now, since companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan face a lack of technology, they do not experience unique skill requirements. As a result, workers do not receive additional training for intra-organisational communication. The net result is that their communication skill set remains relatively underdeveloped (as compared to what it could be if technology had been implemented to support intra-organisational communication). This results in weaker intra-organisational communication in the long run.

To sum it up, a lack of technology is a significant issue in the automotive sector of Pakistan. It has been observed to be associated with both of the broad issues that were identified earlier (paucity of resources and cultural considerations). As mentioned earlier, these are not variables discussed in the study, but the findings show that they are involved and serve important explanatory purposes. The lack of resources in the automotive sector of Pakistan prevents firms from adopting

technology. On the other hand, the country's high uncertainty avoidance means that readiness to adopt technology is low. This also makes the lack of technology a relevant and significant challenge for automotive sector companies operating in Pakistan.

The impact of lack of technology on intra-organisational communication is negative. This is attributable to the fact that supportive technology, such as communication media, has positive impacts on intra-organisational communication. These impacts may include supplementation of direct communication, improving information transfer or increasing the extent to which intra-organisational communication casts its positive influence over organisational operations. Nevertheless, a lack of technology eliminates these positive impacts, resulting in ineffective intra-organisational communication. Also, while the skill requirements associated with technology adoption have been considered to be concerning for companies, they drive training and development initiatives. Resultantly, an organisation that adopts technology trains its workers in intra-organisational communication, which contributes to improved competence. Lack of technology eliminates the need for such training, resulting in low communication competence among workers and hence ineffective intra-organisational communication. This makes the lack of technology a significant challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

5.3.7. Ineffective Payment and Reward Structures

The final challenge to intra-organisational communication identified in this research was ineffective payment and reward structures and their continued prevalence. Payment and reward structures are ineffective, and the absence of any corrective measures to improve them was part of the challenge. The challenge corresponded to H7: "Ineffective payment and reward structures have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan" and was subject to statistical analysis where it turned out to be valid. The main result here is that ineffective payment and reward structures constitute a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

The ineffectiveness of payment and reward structures does not apparently influence intra-organisational communication or its outcomes. However, it exerts its influence via the measures taken to improve intra-organisational communication. That is, if payment and reward structures

are ineffective, the extent to which intra-organisational communication is improved is negatively influenced. The main reason behind this is that intra-organisational communication is needed to support an efficient payment and reward system in an organisation. This means that a highly effective payment and reward structure involves voluminous and frequent flows of information across the organisation. The capacity of intra-organisational communication has to be increased accordingly to meet this requirement, resulting in improvements to intra-organisational communication. If the payment and reward structure is ineffective, it will not require excessive communication, meaning that the intra-organisational communication infrastructure will not be developed. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.33: Ineffective Payment and Reward Structures and Ineffective Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

The assertion made in the above figure and preceding discussion can be supported using arguments from studies on the concerned topic. Amah, Nwuche and Chukwuigwe (2013) clearly point out that seamless intra-organisational communication is an important component of an effective payment and reward structure. This implies that if the payment and reward structure is allowed to remain ineffective, the intra-organisational communication system that backs it will remain ignored too. With negligible improvements being made to the underlying system, intra-organisational communication becomes ineffective too (Shields et al., 2015).

Other studies also support this notion. Prasad (2015), for example, comments that transparency is an extremely important determinant of the effectiveness of a payment and reward system. Wenzel,

Krause and Vogel (2019) also support this idea, stating that transparency helps to improve employee motivation and satisfaction with respect to payment and reward structures. Sievert and Scholtz (2017) point out that intra-organisational communication serves to improve transparency in payment and reward structures. These studies show that in order to create an effective payment and reward structure, organisations have to improve transparency. Also, in order to improve transparency, an organisation has to enhance intra-organisational communication. In contrast, if the payment and reward system is ineffective, it can be said that the organisation has not taken any efforts to improve transparency. This means that the importance being given to intra-organisational communication is low too. Moreover, it was identified earlier that this challenge is not limited to the ineffectiveness of payment and reward structures, but also includes a persistent lack of action to counter it. This means that the presence of an ineffective payment and reward system indicates negligible interest devoted to intra-organisational communication. Resultantly, intra-organisational communication is influenced negatively.

Another interesting aspect here is that intra-organisational communication occupies a central position in performance management. Performance management, in turn, includes payment and reward structures. Therefore, intra-organisational communication is considered to be central to payment and reward structures. If these structures remain ineffective, intra-organisational communication remains ineffective too. The main reason behind this is that persistent ineffectiveness of payment and reward structures shows lack of action being taken to improve them. Given the strong association of intra-organisational communication with performance management and payment and reward structures, this translates to a lack of action being taken to improve intra-organisational communication. Consequently, ineffective payment and reward structures are reflective of restricted improvement to intra-organisational communication.

The assertion that intra-organisational communication is strongly associated with performance management is supported by Subari and Riady (2015), who consider performance management to be a form of communication. From this perspective, ineffective payment and reward systems, being part of performance management, negatively impact it. Since performance management is a form of communication within the organisation, this negative impact is translated to intra-organisational communication. This is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5.34: The Negative Impacts of Ineffective Payment and Reward Structures on Intra-organisational Communication

Source: Developed by author

As evident from the # figure, the negative impacts of ineffective payment and reward systems on intra-organisational communication stem from the latter's relationship with performance management. Performance management includes payment and reward systems and has been referred to as a form of communication within the organisation. Ineffective payment and reward systems in the automotive sector of Pakistan imply that the quality of performance management is low. As performance management has been termed as a form of communication within the organisation, this means that the quality of intra-organisational communication is decreased too. This highlights the challenge that ineffective payment and reward systems present to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

Apart from that, the effects that payment and reward systems have on other aspects, such as employee motivation, commitment and confidence are of importance too. An effective payment/reward structure is unbiased and manages to attain its purpose of satisfying, motivating

and engaging workers. Effectively, such a payment/reward structure encourages workers to participate in communication with the management (this is associated with peer-to-management communication and not peer-to-peer communication, where workers interact with one another). From this perspective, effective payment and reward structures encourage intra-organisational communication. From this, it follows that in the absence of effective payment and reward structures, intra-organisational communication is negatively impacted. This is attributable to the fact that employee commitment and confidence remain low. Poor incentive is present to encourage communication with the management, impeding the flow of information between workers and managerial staff. This can cripple intra-organisational communication.

Academic support can be found for this notion. Yousaf et al. (2014), for instance, point out that fair and impartial rewards positively influence the commitment, confidence and motivation of workers. In a similar context, Al-Madi et al. (2017) also comment that employee motivation and confidence can be increased by offering them rewards. Since an effective payment and reward system ensures that rewards are indeed fair and equitable, these studies support the idea that such a system positively influences employee confidence, motivation and commitment. This notion can be extended further using the argument that trust in management is an important construct associated with employee confidence and commitment. Indeed, studies like Shagholi et al. (2010) and Oh and Park (2011) identify trust to be an important factor associated with employee commitment and confidence.

This is in alignment with the theories of motivation, as well as the results of the research done by Mangi, Kanasro and Burdi (2015) and Lunenburg (2011). Here, the researchers indicated that motivation is extracted from various sources, including effective organisational culture, work life balance as well as pay and benefits, the better the communication within the organisation, the better employee contribution to the organisational communication. The absence of an effective payment structure indicates that the employees may not be effectively motivated, which can lead towards a weak overall intra-organisational communication structure.

As effective payment and reward systems improve employee commitment, motivation, confidence and trust in management, it can be suggested that such systems positively impact trust in management too. Trust in management, on the other hand, promotes exchange of information

between workers and the management. This constitutes effective intra-organisational communication (of the peer to peer variety) (Guffey and Loewy, 2010). While effective payment and reward systems positively influence trust, ineffective ones are likely to cast negative influences on it. Resultantly, the presence of ineffective payment and reward systems in the automotive sector of Pakistan can have negative impacts on trust and exchange of information. This can limit the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication. In this way, ineffective payment and reward systems constitute a significant challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

It is also critical here to explore the relevance of this challenge to the automotive sector of Pakistan. So far, the discussion shows that ineffective payment and reward structures restrict improvement to intra-organisational communication or reduce its effectiveness. It is necessary to consider factors that make this challenge relevant and significant for the automotive sector of Pakistan. The key factor here is a lack of interest in payment and reward structures. This reduced focus stems from the culture of Pakistan. Bashir et al. (2012), as well as Inderyas et al. (2015) show that the culture of Pakistan is characterised by high power distance. This means that the automotive sector companies in the country do not consider employee freedom and preferences to be of importance. As a result, the development of payment and reward structures that are aimed at engaging and motivating workers is not considered to be significant enough.

Given the culture and workplace dynamics in the automotive sector of Pakistan, the development of effective payment and reward systems is not deemed important. This reduces the need for intra-organisational communication because the flows of information originating from payment and reward systems are eliminated. In addition to that, the motivation, commitment, and confidence of workers are negatively impacted too. This results in low trust in management, which further limits the extent to which exchange of information between workers and management occurs. The net result is ineffective intra-organisational communication. It is worth noting here that this challenge is associated with 'cultural considerations', which was one of the two factors that were found to be related to the challenges identified and assessed here. It is also important to point out that as with other challenges, this factor was not part of the analysis and is used for explanatory purposes

only as it helps answer the research question regarding intra-organisational communication challenges in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

The results obtained here have shown that intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan is influenced negatively by the presence of ineffective payment and reward systems. For one, the presence of ineffective payment and reward system implies that actions being taken to improve them are limited. As intra-organisational communication is improved to support payment and reward systems, this limited action means that intra-organisational communication is devoid of improvements. This explains its low quality. On the other hand, an ineffective payment and reward system does not involve significant flows of information and hence effective intra-organisational communication is not necessary. This also limits the quality of intra-organisational communication. Finally, ineffective payment and reward structures negatively influence trust and information exchange, reducing the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication. Overall, this shows that the presence of ineffective payment and reward structures is indeed a key challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

5.4. Chapter Summary

Intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan is faced with a number of challenges. These challenges stem from characteristics of the industry and their relationships with intra-organisational communication. In addition to that, broader factors like the generalized lack of resources in Pakistan or impacts of the country's culture on managerial practices often signify the challenges at hand. The findings of this study show that the challenges to intra-organisational communication are often associated with them.

The complexity of big data analytics and lack of technology have been found to be important variables that negatively impact intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. The former is a significant challenge because of the complex data transfer and knowledge sharing requirements it gives rise to. These complex requirements cannot be fulfilled easily, pressurizing the intra-organisational communication system and impacting it negatively. On the other hand, the lack of supportive technology implies that intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan is deprived of unconventional communication channels, limiting its effectiveness. In addition to that, the lack of technology also implies that training requirements

for workers are reduced, meaning that less training initiatives are introduced and hence, overall communication competence remains low. This also imparts a negative influence on intra-organisational communication.

Other than that, factors pertaining to workers and their motivation were also found to impart negative impacts on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. For example, the lack of employee engagement was observed to decrease the perceived need for intra-organisational communication, thereby limiting improvement. In addition to that, a lack of employee engagement decreased the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication too. Similarly, low levels of internal branding had negative impacts on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan too. Low levels of internal branding lead towards a decreased need for intra-organisational communication, halting its development. In addition to that, the absence of internal branding negatively influences the flow of information within the organisation, leading towards ineffective intra-organisational communication. Similarly, the presence of ineffective payment and reward structures negatively influences the need for intra-organisational communication too, presenting an important challenge here.

Finally, the lack of innovative mechanisms for communication is another factor that negatively influences intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Innovative mechanisms have been deemed necessary to support communication within the organisation because of cultural, geographic and lingual barriers. Absence of an innovation-driven intra-organisational communication strategy can result in complex communication requirements being unmet. Unmet requirements, in turn, could result in poor quality of intra-organisational communications. Therefore, the lack of innovative mechanisms limits the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

CHAPTER SIX: CONCLUSION, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND CONTRIBUTIONS

6.1. Chapter Introduction

This chapter is concerned with the concluding remarks, as well as recommendations on the basis of the study's findings. In this regard, the premise and scope of the study has been summarized. Similarly, findings of the study and the extent to which research questions could be answered have been outlined in this chapter too. Moreover, the measures that can be introduced for the improvement of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan have been highlighted. Apart from that, the limitations of this study have been pointed out, with recommendations for future studies being presented too.

6.2. Overview of the Research

Communication within organisations is an interesting and a much-needed topic to be considered. As many businesses focus on improvements that have direct and visual improvements, such as 5S which is a tool for making workstations look clean and in order. One of the unseen factors that have impact on the organisational effectiveness is communication. Communication is a subject which has been studied for a long time and there is a comprehensive amount of literature available on it. Communication in organisations is to us a vital aspect to consider. There are three reasons on why organisations should consider it, first it can be beneficial for the social aspect of the organisation. Secondly it can have good outcome of the financial aspect of the organisation. Third, it can increase the production of better-quality items with lower production cost. However, what was found in this master's thesis was that not many researches or studies have been conducted looking at the causes of communication problems between departments in organisations. Most of the literature regarding communication concerned on how to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of communication between departments in organisation and within the whole organisation to increase productivity. Further, communication literature covering employee empowerment and satisfaction was also apparent in our search for relevant theory for this case study. Improvements on communication are important and this master's thesis has shed light on communication problems between departments within a manufacturing organisation. The findings will be of interest to automotive organisations that have communication problems internally.

The automotive sector occupies a critical role in the economy of any region. Its significant contributions to the economy involve generation of income, exports and employment (which can contribute to economic stability). Such significance of the automotive sector has led towards extensive research on policies, issues, practices and development (with the aim of improving operational effectiveness). A review of the literature shows that research on the automotive sector tends to be focused mainly on developed economies, such as the United States or those in the European Union. With regards to Pakistan, very few studies discuss the details of the automotive sector, presenting a gap in the literature.

Intra-organisational communication remains a key entity for firms in the automotive sector, owing to the fact that it improves performance and innovativeness. Despite the presence of these obvious benefits, companies in the automotive sector have struggled to enhance intra-organisational communication. This inability stems from the presence of multiple issues. Most importantly, organisations often lack resources to develop an effective intra-organisational communication system and often fail to harness the systems and capabilities that they possess. Similarly, deficient workplace practices and cultural barriers also prevent automotive sector organisations from improving the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication.

In view of these issues, the research set out to explore the intra-organisational communication challenges faced by automotive sector of Pakistan. The main aim of the research under consideration is the identification and assessment of main intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan. This involves a detailed discussion and elaboration of the factors that are involved in intra-organisational communication. To help attain this key aim, the research targets attainment of the following specific research objectives:

To identify the key barriers to intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan; the research intended to identify the main factors that hinder development of effective intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. The challenges were broadly found to be related to the culture and workplace practices of automotive companies (the prevalence of high power-distance or lack of engagement of workers, for instance, were found to limit intra-organisational communication). Also, the lack of resources or infrastructure for

communication was also found to be a key challenge to intra-organisational communication for automotive sector companies in Pakistan.

To propose strategies that can facilitate effective intra-organisational communication sector within the auto mobile sector of Pakistan; in light of the analysis on challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan, the research intended to formulate strategies and recommend measures that could enable organisations to counter said challenges, thereby improving the standards of intra-organisational communication. This objective is concerned with the recommendations of the study, which are presented below.

The literature review laid down the foundations for this research's hypotheses, which relate to the objectives outlined earlier. Seven hypotheses were developed, with the research aiming to conduct hypotheses testing to attain its objectives. This was achieved via the use of primary quantitative research methods, backed by theoretical underpinnings from the literature review. Data collected from a sample of 350 workers of Atlas Honda, Pakistan was subject to statistical analysis, followed by interpretation of results and discussion of findings.

6.3. Outcomes of Hypotheses Tested

The research tested seven hypotheses, each pertaining to a challenge to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Outcomes of each hypothesis tested coupled with a brief discussion of the result are presented below:

The first hypothesis, "Complexity of big data analysis has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan" was **accepted**. The main implication of this is that while big data analytics present a source of opportunity for companies in the automotive sector, they are linked with challenges in internal communication. For one, the efficient deployment of such systems requires advanced communication tools and infrastructure, which cannot be obtained by companies in the resource-poor automotive sector of Pakistan. The absence of necessary infrastructure, in turn, sabotages the quality of intra-organisational communication. Additionally, effective big data and analytics systems generate large volumes of information, which can pressurize existing communication systems. Since the automotive sector of Pakistan remains resource-poor, communication systems cannot be upgraded to meet these extra communication requirements. Hence, the complexity of big data and its communication

requirements imparts negative impacts on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

On the other hand, the second hypothesis, “Lack of focus on personal goals of the employees has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, was **rejected**. This hypothesis was rooted in the observation that personal goals and career development are dependent on intra-organisational communication. In a workplace where personal goals are not focused upon, the need for intra-organisational communication is felt to a lesser extent. This, in turn, limits efforts made for its improvement. However, as the hypothesis has been rejected, this relationship does not hold true. An alternate explanation here is that intra-organisational communication is not the only factor that positively impacts career development and hence it is not necessary for emphasis on personal goals to be tied to intra-organisational communication. Other factors, such as training and development or performance management, are also relied on to support attainment of personal goals. Hence, the absence of a statistically significant relationship here is most likely due to the influence of these other factors.

Moreover, the third hypothesis, “Lack of focus on employee engagement has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan” was **accepted**. Employee engagement shares a two-way association with intra-organisational communication. On one hand, employee engagement positively impacts intra-organisational communication; from this perspective, any reduction in focus on employee engagement will lead to a low quality of intra-organisational communication. On the other hand, intra-organisational communication has been poised to have positive impacts on employee engagement too. This makes intra-organisational communication a ‘go to area’ for management when it seeks improvements to employee engagement. Under this perspective, a reduction in focus on employee engagement is likely to decrease the importance of intra-organisational communication, leading towards negative impacts on the latter.

The fourth hypothesis, “Lack of innovative mechanisms has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, was **accepted**. The lack of innovative mechanisms implies that companies do not have innovation-driven communication strategies. The absence of such strategies, in turn, leads towards a poor quality of communication

(as innovation supports the generation of novel and creative solutions to communication-related challenges faced by companies). In addition to that, another important point here is that intra-organisational communication is deemed necessary for innovation. The absence of innovative mechanisms, in this context, reflects a low focus on innovativeness. This, in turn, limits the significance given to intra-organisational communication as a factor that boosts creativity and innovation within the company. Either way, the lack of innovative mechanisms creates barriers to intra-organisational communication.

The fifth hypothesis, “Low levels of internal branding have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, was **accepted**. This is explained by the fact that internal branding demands a flow of information across the organisation (because workers have to be exposed to the characteristics and nature of the organisation). In a company with high levels of internal branding, high volumes of information are generated and hence improved intra-organisational communication is needed to support the flow of this information. This drives improvements to intra-organisational communication. As the levels of internal branding are low in the automotive sector of Pakistan, the need for high volume information transfer is not felt and resultantly, intra-organisational communication remains underdeveloped.

In addition, the sixth hypothesis, “Lack of technology has a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, was **accepted**. Technology is directly related with the quality of intra-organisational communication, with advanced information systems and networking being tied to highly effective communication systems. In addition to that, the implementation of advanced technology pushes companies to train and develop workers. Communication and interpersonal skills are covered in these training initiatives. Either way, intra-organisational communication is positively impacted by technology. The lack of technology in the automotive sector of Pakistan, therefore, results in negative impacts on intra-organisational communication.

Finally, the seventh hypothesis, “Ineffective payment and reward structures have a negative impact on the intra-organisational communication within the automotive sector of Pakistan”, was

accepted. This is explained by the fact that payment and reward systems are components of performance management within the organisation. Since performance management has been deemed to be a form of communication within the organisation, the lack of effective payment and reward system is equivalent to the absence of effective communication within the organisation (hence leading towards ineffective intra-organisational communication). At the same time, the lack of effective payment and reward systems also decreases trust among workers, limiting the extent to which they engage in communication with the management and other workers. This also limits the efficacy of intra-organisational communication. Either way, the prevalence of ineffective payment and reward systems has negative impacts on intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

6.4. Contributions of the Study

The current research remained focused on the challenges of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. In this regard, the main aim of the research under consideration was the identification and assessment of main intra-organisational communication challenges that are faced by the automotive sector of Pakistan. The research has made important contributions on theoretical, practical, as well as policy grounds. From the theoretical perspective, for instance, the research is among the first to provide an integrated analysis of the challenges to intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan. On the other hand, with the automotive sector being a key industry for Pakistan (accounting for 2.8% of the GDP, as per Invest Pakistan (2020)), providing details of the challenges to intra-organisational communication may have important implications from practical and policy perspectives (that is, the research can enable companies and policymakers to improve intra-organisational communication and offer support to automotive sector companies, respectively). The contributions of this study have been summarized in the upcoming sub-sections.

6.4.1. Theoretical Contributions

The study is among the earliest to address intra-organisational communication challenges in the automotive sector of Pakistan. Even though earlier studies have explored this topic, it has been mostly limited to developed countries, such as the United States, United Kingdom or Germany. Thus, the foremost theoretical contribution of this study is that it lays the foundations for a model illustrating factors that could limit the effectiveness of intra-organisational communication in the

automotive sector of Pakistan. Factors specific to this sector, such as the prevalence of workplace practices that limit emphasis on employee engagement or cultural barriers to communication within the firm have been linked to intra-organisational communication. This study has presented a series of factors unique to companies and workplaces in Pakistan that can explain the barriers that organisations face when they seek to develop intra-organisational communication.

In addition, the study also serves to integrate various variables and factors in explaining challenges to intra-organisational communication. For instance, the interplay between employee engagement or internal branding and intra-organisational communication has not been targeted in the context of the automotive sector in earlier studies. Approaching the topic from multiple aspects has also assisted in integrating several concepts relevant to the topic, addressing areas that were not targeted previously. For instance, exploring ways in which intra-organisational communication affects or is affected by innovation within the organisation has allowed for a deeper understanding regarding the challenges that emerge from the lack of innovative mechanisms.

Furthermore, in spite of the fact that broad factors like culture or paucity of resources (and their impacts on workplace dynamics) were not part of the core analysis, the study has used them for explanatory purposes. Again, this has opened up new avenues for study in the field of intra-organisational communication, marking another critical theoretical contribution.

6.4.2. Practical Contributions

The research has identified and assessed intra-organisational communication challenges at Atlas Honda in Pakistan. The foremost practical contribution of the study is that it has shed light on major issues that are limiting the company's intra-organisational communication framework. In this way, it has created a platform for improvement. Furthermore, the study has provided recommendations for the organisation too, reinforcing the idea that it holds practical value for the concerned organisation in that the recommendations may allow the company to improve intra-organisational communication and hence, performance.

The issues raised in this study (in the context of Atlas Honda Pakistan) may also be relevant (to some extent) for other automotive sector organisations of the country. Therefore, the study

provides other companies with areas to look to if they are seeking improvements in their intra-organisational communication framework. Therefore, if the organisation implements what is suggested, it will potentially affect the sustainability of the organisation. It affects the social side of the organisation by reducing stress amongst employees and thus employees have less days off work, due to stress related sickness. It can also affect the cooperation and communication within the organisation, so that the organisation has increased chances of having the correct material for production at the correct time. Thus, decreasing the need of special transports such as material or low utilisation of space and by that decreasing the environmental effect. This can also in turn lead to that product are correctly produced and put together. In general terms it means improved management that potentially affects the bottom line positively.

6.4.3. Policy Contributions

As outlined earlier, the automotive sector of Pakistan is one of the most important contributors to the country's economy. Recent statistics have revealed that the sector accounts for 2.8% of the country's GDP (Invest Pakistan, 2020). This research has revealed that a major factor that contributes to challenges faced by companies in the automotive sector (with respect to intra-organisational communication) is the low availability of resources and infrastructure in Pakistan.

This shows that the presence of a supportive IT and communication policy that facilitates growth in availability of communication technology and infrastructure is the need of the day in Pakistan. The research shows that the government needs to take important policy initiatives, including tax benefits for local and international IT companies or dedicated subsidies for technology development, to improve the availability of information and communication technology in the country. Resultantly, automotive sector companies may find it easier to obtain advanced information technology and infrastructure to support improvements to intra-organisational communication.

As a result, the current research has paved the way for policy initiatives directed at reducing the technology and infrastructure gaps that exist in Pakistan and have prevented the country's automotive sector from attaining highly effective intra-organisational communication.

6.5. Recommendations of the Study

In light of the analysis conducted in the research, quite a few recommendations have been made here. These recommendations are targeted primarily at the case organisation, Atlas Honda (and broadly, other automotive sector companies in Pakistan), as well as the policy-making authorities in Pakistan.

6.5.1. Recommendations for Atlas Honda Pakistan and Other Automotive Sector Companies

Atlas Honda Pakistan, as well as other companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan, needs to take measures to counter the challenges to intra-organisational communication faced by them. Developing a multi-modal intra-organisational communication system harnessing modern technology is required. It can involve an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system, social media platforms, internal dashboards designed by IT personnel, and real-time chat applications for workers. It is critical that all elements of the system are integrated to ensure real-time collection and transfer of data. Doing so can ensure that information within the organisation is distributed effectively and remains accessible for all concerned stakeholders.

Resource Allocation: Devoting resources to intra-organisational communication means a sizeable proportion of the financial resources at the organisation is essential. It should be used for the development of communication infrastructures or holding training programmes. Either way, the improvements to the communication system will increase the quality of intra-organisational communication.

Training and Development: Managers need to organize proper and frequent training programs for workers. The areas targeted by these programs should include communication and interpersonal skills, as well as IT and managerial capabilities. Conducting training initiatives can ensure that workers are equipped with the skills to effectively communicate with one another. At the same time, IT and managerial competencies can allow for better use of new multimodal communication systems, as well as enhanced involvement of workers. Such changes can assist the management in creating an environment where information can be transferred seamlessly, indicating improved intra-organisational communication.

Boost Engagement: Managers need to focus on employee engagement as it will allow for improved motivation and performance, which is inherently beneficial for the organisation. At the same time, involving workers and allowing them to participate in decision-making activities can drive improvements to intra-organisational communication too.

6.5.2. Recommendations for Policy-Making Authorities in Pakistan

It has been seen earlier that the challenges the automotive sector companies of Pakistan face in relation to intra-organisational communication can be linked with the absence of funds, resources and infrastructure. In particular, the availability of an information technology infrastructure in Pakistan and depriving automotive sector companies from the benefits that it has to offer remains a key concern. Policy makers in the country can take steps to counter this challenge, with an emphasis on supporting the development of the technology and IT sectors. A strong IT sector, including both local and international organisations, could help support enhancements to the availability of technology infrastructure, as well as services required by companies in the automotive sector and other industries. As a result, the introduction of subsidies, tax reduction and economic stimulus to foster the development of IT sector organisations is essential for Pakistan to ensure that its automotive sector companies can have access to state-of-the-art technology and hence, improve intra-organisational communication.

6.6. Limitations of the Study

The methods and scope of this study account for limitations associated with it. For one, the research was focused on a single organisation (Atlas Honda) in a single sector (automotive) in a single country (Pakistan). Intra-organisational communication depends on a wide array of factors, including culture (at the national and organisational level), availability of resources (at the national and organisational level) and best practices (at the industrial level). Since the current research focused only on Atlas Honda and the automotive sector of Pakistan, it must have missed a number of country-specific, sector-specific and organisation-specific variables that influence intra-organisational communication (or could act as challenges to it) in the context of other companies, industries and countries. From this perspective, the decision to limit the scope of this research to single a organisation, sector and country limited our understanding, thus presenting a major limitation.

In addition to that, the research was based solely on quantitative methods. While these methods are extremely useful for the validation of hypotheses or evaluation of relationships, they do not allow for in-depth analysis of phenomena. As a result, this study was limited in the extent to which it could explore the nature of the challenges to intra-organisational communication. Moreover, by neglecting qualitative research methods, the study remained incapable of gaining a deeper understanding of why specific factors, such as the complexity of big data, lack of technology, lack of focus on employee engagement or low levels of internal branding act as barriers to the development of intra-organisational communication in the automotive sector of Pakistan.

6.7. Recommendations for Future Research

Future research needs to explore and study the challenges to intra-organisational communication in a greater variety of contexts. This can include studies that focus on multiple countries at once or those that study multiple organisations and industries within a single country at the same time. In particular, future studies can:

- Build on the platform created by the current study to explore the challenges to intra-organisational communication in other important sectors in Pakistan, such as agriculture and banking
- Explore the issues in other automotive sector companies, with comparative analysis being conducted involving Suzuki, Toyota and Honda (the three main companies in the automotive sector of Pakistan)

There is further needed to widen the context of the topic when studying it in future studies. For instance, studies can focus on the development of models and frameworks that link challenges to intra-organisational communication with measures for improvement, allowing companies with opportunities to evaluate major challenges and options that are available for them to improve intra-organisational communication.

Taking these measures can ensure that research takes into account the variety of company-specific, sector-specific and country-specific challenges to intra-organisational communication. This, in turn, may provide a better understanding of the issue at hand, while simultaneously increasing the theoretical, practical and policy implications of the research.

Apart from that, in order to improve generalization of the results, the study can include separate analysis for developed and developing countries. In doing so, future research will be able to present distinct results for each type of economy. In addition, this will also incorporate the factors that are not considered in one type of economy and increase the breadth of the research.

In addition to that, future research can also explore the topic using a different methodology. A qualitative methodology with multiple countries or sectors being considered could, for instance, yield better understanding of the ways in which specific factors give rise to barriers to intra-organisational communication. In this way, our overall understanding of the challenges to intra-organisational communication can be broadened, leading towards better decision-making at the organisational level.

6.8. Managerial Implications

This proposed study suggests that leadership and organisational planning have the greatest impact on employee engagement and intra-organisational communication. One of the management implications of the findings and discussions is that the organization needs to provide better leadership and planning to its people. Managers in the process of setting up the means and methods allied with intra-organisational communication do play a key role in improving employee engagement and need to take care of the wellbeing of employees by providing adequate feedback on employee contributions and suggesting some ideas for career advancement by taking advantage of opportunities within the company. Managers should also evaluate their level of performance and introduce some incentives and bonuses for top performers so that they can continue this long-term endeavour.

Managers must help create an environment in which employees are emotionally and cognitively engaged, which ultimately reflects on robust intra-organisational communication. Managers can engage emotionally with employees by building strong bonds with colleagues, managers, and work. Employees can participate cognitively by understanding the clear mission and purpose of the automobile organisation, and soliciting relevant information and comments. When employees have a strong bond with executives, they feel respected by their superiors and their opinions are taken into account. This allows them to develop an internal emotional bond that will help the

organization achieve its goals. Likewise, employees who understand the long-term goals of the organisation and the importance of their professional role in the success of the organisation will always have greater cognitive engagement.

REFERENCES

- Ab Latif, R., Mohamed, R., Dahlan, A. and Nor, M.Z.M., 2016. Using Delphi technique: making sense of consensus in concept mapping structure and multiple choice questions (MCQ). *Education in Medicine Journal*, 8(3).
- Abbasi, M.N., Sheikh, M.R. and Hassan, N.M., 2015. Supplier Selection: Insight from Automotive Industry of Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences (PJSS)*, 35(1).
- Abbasi, M.S., Tarhini, A., Elyas, T. and Shah, F., 2015. Impact of individualism and collectivism over the individual's technology acceptance behaviour. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 28(6), pp.747-768.
- Abomhara, M., 2015. Cyber security and the internet of things: vulnerabilities, threats, intruders and attacks. *Journal of Cyber Security and Mobility*, 4(1), pp.65-88.
- Acharya, A.S., Prakash, A., Saxena, P. and Nigam, A., 2013. Sampling: Why and how of it. *Indian Journal of Medical Specialties*, 4(2), pp.330-333.
- Adisa, T.A., Gbadamosi, G. and Osabutey, E.L., 2017. What happened to the border? The role of mobile information technology devices on employees' work-life balance. *Personnel Review*, 46(8), pp.1651-1671.
- Afzal, M. and Awais, S., 2014. Population and poverty nexus in Pakistan. *Journal of Independent Studies and Research*, 12(2), pp.63-75.
- AG, D.B., 2018. Automotive industry.
- Agnihotri, R., Dingus, R., Hu, M.Y. and Krush, M.T., 2016. Social media: Influencing customer satisfaction in B2B sales. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 53, pp.172-180.
- Ahmed, I., Shahzad, A., Umar, M. and Khilji, B.A., 2010. Information technology and SMEs in Pakistan. *International Business Research*, 3(4), p.237.
- Ahmed, Z., Shields, F., White, R. and Wilbert, J., 2010. Managerial communication: The link between frontline leadership and organisational performance. In *First Annual General Business Conference Conference Proceedings* (p. 69).
- Ahmet, A.Y.I.K., 2015. An analysis of the relationship between organisational communication and organisational cynicism according to teachers' perceptions in Turkey. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 10(5), p.547.

- Alavi, H. and Habek, P., 2016. Addressing research design problem in mixed methods research. *Management Systems in Production Engineering*.
- Ali, I., Jiménez-Zarco, A.I. and Bicho, M., 2015. Using social media for CSR communication and engaging stakeholders. *Corporate Social Responsibility in the Digital Age (Developments in Corporate Governance and Responsibility)*, 7, pp.165-185.
- Ali, M., Kan, K.A.S. and Sarstedt, M., 2016. Direct and configurational paths of absorptive capacity and organisational innovation to successful organisational performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(11), pp.5317-5323.
- Al-Madi, F.N., Assal, H., Shrafat, F. and Zeglat, D., 2017. The impact of employee motivation on organisational commitment. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 9(15), pp.134-145.
- Almaiah, M.A. and Al Mulhem, A., 2019. Analysis of the essential factors affecting of intention to use of mobile learning applications: A comparison between universities adopters and non-adopters. *Education and Information Technologies*, 24(2), pp.1433-1468.
- Al-Omari, A.I., Jemain, A.A. and Ibrahim, K., 2013. New ratio estimators of the mean using simple random sampling and ranked set sampling methods. *Investigación Operacional*, 30(2), pp.97-108.
- Amah, E., Nwuche, C. and Chukwuigwe, N., 2013. Effective reward and incentive scheme for effective organisations. *Research Journal of finance and Accounting*, 4(13), pp.73-79.
- Angouri, J. and Miglbauer, M., 2013. 12 Local Languages and Communication Challenges in the Multinational Workplace. *Language and intercultural communication in the new era*, p.225.
- Anurit, J., Newman, K. and Chansarkar, B.A., 2011. Consumer Behaviour of Luxury Automobiles: A Comparative Study between Thai and UK Customers' Perceptions, 1999. *Marketing Series*, pp.1-17.
- Argyrous, G., 2011. *Statistics for research: With a guide to SPSS*. Sage Publications.
- Ashraf, Z., Jaffri, A.M., Sharif, M.T. and Khan, A., 2012. Increasing employee organisational commitment by correlating goal setting, employee engagement and optimism at workplace. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(2), pp.71-77.
- Aula, P. and Siira, K., 2010. Organisational communication and conflict management systems. *Nordicom Review*, 31(1), pp.125-141.

- Aune-Lundberg, L. and Strand, G.H., 2014. Comparison of variance estimation methods for use with two-dimensional systematic sampling of land use/land cover data. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 61, pp.87-97.
- Bakanauskienė, I., Bendaravičienė, R. and Krikštolaitis, R., 2010. Empirical evidence on employees' communication satisfaction and job satisfaction: Lithuania's university case. *Organizacijų vadyba: sisteminiai tyrimai*, 2010, nr. 54, p. 21-36.
- Balakrishnan, C. and Masthan, D., 2013. Impact of internal communication on employee engagement—A study at Delhi International Airport. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 3(8), pp.1-13.
- Bashir, M., Jianqiao, L., Abrar, M. and Ghazanfar, F., 2012. The organisations cultural values: A study of public sector universities in Pakistan. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(10), pp.3686-3693.
- Bassi, L., 2017, September. Industry 4.0: Hope, hype or revolution?. In *2017 IEEE 3rd International Forum on Research and Technologies for Society and Industry (RTSI)*(pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Becker, K., Hartmann, B.L. and Miller, J.M., 2014. Fostering successful career paths in construction: Motivation, evaluation, feedback. *Practice Periodical on Structural Design and Construction*, 19(1), pp.159-167.
- Bedarkar, M. and Pandita, D., 2014. A study on the drivers of employee engagement impacting employee performance. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 133, pp.106-115.
- Benish, K.D., 2015. Pennoyer's Ghost: Consent, Registration Statutes, and General Jurisdiction after Daimler AG v. Bauman. *NYUL Rev.*, 90, p.1609.
- Beri, Á., Martínez-Blanco, X., Varela, L., di Pasquo, M. and de Souza, P.A., 2020. Sampling biases and Paleozoic sporomorphs diversity dynamics in Western Gondwana strata. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences*, 98, p.102457.
- Berton, T., Mayhoub, F., Chardon, K., Duca, R.C., Lestremau, F., Bach, V. and Tack, K., 2014. Development of an analytical strategy based on LC–MS/MS for the measurement of different classes of pesticides and their metabolites in meconium: application and characterisation of foetal exposure in France. *Environmental research*, 132, pp.311-320.
- Biesta, G., 2010. Pragmatism and the philosophical foundations of mixed methods research. *Sage handbook of mixed methods in social and behavioral research*, 2, pp.95-118.

- Bloom, N., Garicano, L., Sadun, R. and Van Reenen, J., 2014. The distinct effects of information technology and communication technology on firm organisation. *Management Science*, 60(12), pp.2859-2885.
- Bolay, C., Essig, P., Kaminsky, C., Hol, J., Naegele, P. and Schmidt, R., 2019, November. Friction modelling in sheet metal forming simulations for aluminium body parts at Daimler AG. In *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* (Vol. 651, No. 1, p. 012104). IOP Publishing.
- Bolman, L.G. and Deal, T.E., 2015. Think—or sink: Leading in a VUCA world. *Leader to Leader*, 2015(76), pp.35-40.
- Borca, C. and Baesu, V., 2014. A possible managerial approach for internal organisational communication characterization. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 124, pp.496-503.
- Boxall, P. and Purcell, J., 2011. *Strategy and human resource management*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Bradt, J., Burns, D.S. and Creswell, J.W., 2013. Mixed methods research in music therapy research. *Journal of Music Therapy*, 50(2), pp.123-148.
- Bratton, J. and Gold, J., 2017. *Human resource management: theory and practice*. Palgrave.
- Bruhn, M. and Ahlers, G.M., 2017. Integrated communication in the innovation process—An approach to integrated innovation communication. In *Strategy and Communication for Innovation* (pp. 205-225). Springer, Cham.
- Bryman, A. and Bell, E., 2015. *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Bučko, A., Protecting Reputation in Crisis: Case Study of Strategic Reputational Risk Management at Tesla Inc.
- Buerke, A., Straatmann, T., Lin-Hi, N. and Müller, K., 2017. Consumer awareness and sustainability-focused value orientation as motivating factors of responsible consumer behavior. *Review of Managerial Science*, 11(4), pp.959-991.
- Burton, K., Grates, G. and Learch, C., 2013. *Best-In-Class Practices In Employee Communication: Through The Lens Of 10 Global Leaders*. Institute for Public Relations.
- Butt, M.A. and Katuse, P., 2017. International Human Resource Management Practices in Automotive Industry in Pakistan: Implications for Economic Growth. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 12(2), p.136.

- Butt, M.A., Katuse, P. and Namada, J.M., 2018. On Green Strategy: Effect on Automotive Industry of Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 13(2), p.221.
- Buzzenell, P.M. and Lucas, K., 2013. Constrained and constructed choices in career: An examination of communication pathways to dignity. *Annals of the International Communication Association*, 37(1), pp.1-31.
- Caluschi, C., 2013. Improving a Car Dealership's Communications through the Comunicom Direct Active Communication System. *Revista de Management Comparat International*, 14(3), p.473.
- Cătălin, M.C., Andreea, P. and Adina, C., 2014. A holistic approach on internal marketing implementation. *Business Management Dynamics*, pp.09-17.
- Charlier, S.D., Stewart, G.L., Greco, L.M. and Reeves, C.J., 2016. Emergent leadership in virtual teams: A multilevel investigation of individual communication and team dispersion antecedents. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 27(5), pp.745-764.
- Chaturvedi, P.D., 2011. *Business communication: Concepts, cases, and applications*. Pearson Education India.
- Chen, R., Qiao, J., Bai, R., Zhao, Y. and Chen, C., 2018. Intelligent testing strategy and analytical techniques for the safety assessment of nanomaterials. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 410(24), pp.6051-6066.
- Christopher, M., 2016. *Logistics & supply chain management*. 5th Edition Pearson UK.
- Ciobanu, A. and Ristea, B., 2015. The Relationship Between Performance Appraisal And Civil Servants' motivation. *Management research and practice*, 7(2), p.5.
- Coffelt, T.A., Baker, M.J. and Corey, R.C., 2016. Business communication practices from employers' perspectives. *Business and Professional Communication Quarterly*, 79(3), pp.300-316.
- Cojuharenco, I., Cornelissen, G. and Karelaia, N., 2016. Yes, I can: Feeling connected to others increases perceived effectiveness and socially responsible behavior. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 48, pp.75-86.
- Collis, J. and Hussey, R., 2013. *Business research: A practical guide for undergraduate and postgraduate students*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Comin, D., Licht, G., Pellens, M. and Schubert, T., 2018. *Do Companies Benefit from Public Research Organisations? The Impact of the Fraunhofer Society in Germany* (No. 2018/7).

- Lund University, CIRCLE-Center for Innovation, Research and Competences in the Learning Economy.
- Conrad, D. and Newberry, R., 2012. Identification and instruction of important business communication skills for graduate business education. *Journal of Education for Business*, 87(2), pp.112-120.
- Coombs, W.T., Falkheimer, J., Heide, M. and Young, P. eds., 2015. *Strategic Communication, Social Media and Democracy: the challenge of the digital natives*. Routledge.
- Cooren, F. and Martine, T., 2016. Communicative Constitution of Organisations. *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy*, pp.1-9.
- Cooren, F., Kuhn, T., Cornelissen, J.P. and Clark, T., 2011. Communication, organizing and organisation: An overview and introduction to the special issue. *Organisation Studies*, 32(9), pp.1149-1170.
- Cornelissen, J.P., 2016. 12 Shifting the Figure of Organisation as Communication. *Organisation as Communication: Perspectives in Dialogue*, p.213.
- Cornett, J.M. and Hoffheimer, M.H., 2015. Good-Bye Significant Contacts: General Personal Jurisdiction after Daimler AG v. Bauman. *Ohio St. LJ*, 76, p.101.
- Creswell, J.W. and Clark, V.L.P., 2017. *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. Sage publications.
- Daimler, A.G. and Stuttgart, A., 2013. *Daimler Sustainability Report 2012*. Daimler AG.
- Dalal, R.S., Baysinger, M., Brummel, B.J. and LeBreton, J.M., 2012. The relative importance of employee engagement, other job attitudes, and trait affect as predictors of job performance. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 42, pp.E295-E325.
- Danermark, B., Ekström, M. and Karlsson, J.C., 2019. *Explaining society: Critical realism in the social sciences*. Routledge.
- Davison, R.M., Ou, C.X. and Martinsons, M.G., 2013. Information technology to support informal knowledge sharing. *Information Systems Journal*, 23(1), pp.89-109.
- De Araujo, D.C, Simanski, E.S.S. & de Quevedo, D.M. 2012. Internal communication: relationship between company and workers, a case study. *Brazilian Business Review*, 9(1): 43-59.

- De Medeiros, J.F., Ribeiro, J.L.D. and Cortimiglia, M.N., 2014. Success factors for environmentally sustainable product innovation: a systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 65, pp.76-86.
- De Ruyter, K. and Scholl, N., 1998. Positioning qualitative market research: reflections from theory and practice. *Qualitative market research: An international journal*, 1(1), pp.7-14.
- De Stefano, M.C., Montes-Sancho, M.J. and Busch, T., 2016. A natural resource-based view of climate change: Innovation challenges in the automobile industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 139, pp.1436-1448.
- De Waal, A., 2013. *Strategic Performance Management: A managerial and behavioral approach*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- Debattista, J., Lange, C., Scerri, S. and Auer, S., 2015, December. Linked'Big'Data: towards a manifold increase in big data value and veracity. In *2015 IEEE/ACM 2nd International Symposium on Big Data Computing (BDC)* (pp. 92-98). IEEE.
- Debortoli, S., Müller, O. and vom Brocke, J., 2014. Comparing business intelligence and big data skills. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 6(5), pp.289-300.
- DeCenzo, D.A., Robbins, S.P. and Verhulst, S.L., 2016. *Fundamentals of human resource management*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Decramer, A., Smolders, C. and Vanderstraeten, A., 2013. Employee performance management culture and system features in higher education: relationship with employee performance management satisfaction. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(2), pp.352-371.
- Delia, L., Thomas, P., Corbalan, L., Sosa, J.F., Cuitiño, A., Cáseres, G. and Pesado, P., 2018, July. Development approaches for mobile applications: comparative analysis of features. In *Science and Information Conference* (pp. 470-484). Springer, Cham.
- Denker, S., 2014. The Future of General Jurisdiction: The Effects of Daimler Ag v. Bauman. *Fordham J. Corp. & Fin. L.*, 20, p.145.
- Dewettinck, K. and van Dijk, H., 2013. Linking Belgian employee performance management system characteristics with performance management system effectiveness: exploring the mediating role of fairness. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(4), pp.806-825.

- Deyo, F.C. ed., 2016. *Social reconstructions of the world automobile industry: Competition, power and industrial flexibility*. Springer.
- Dhawan, P. and Prior, D., 2017, June. Internal branding and leader-member exchange: role of cultural capital in employee's service delivery behaviour in healthcare sector: an abstract. In *Academy of Marketing Science World Marketing Congress* (pp. 259-259). Springer, Cham.
- Díaz-Garrido, E., Martín-Peña, M.L. and Sánchez-López, J.M., 2016. Determinants of environmental strategy in the automotive sector: Analysis of key factors. *International Journal of Sustainable Transportation*, 10(5), pp.430-440.
- Dobusch, L. and Schoeneborn, D., 2015. Fluidity, identity, and organisationality: The communicative constitution of Anonymous. *Journal of Management Studies*, 52(8), pp.1005-1035.
- Dowdy, S., Wearden, S. and Chilko, D., 2011. *Statistics for research*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Dremel, C., Wulf, J., Herterich, M.M., Waizmann, J.C. and Brenner, W., 2017. How AUDI AG Established Big Data Analytics in Its Digital Transformation. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 16(2).
- Dryl, T., 2017. Internal branding in organisation in the context of internal corporate communication. *Handel Wewnętrzny*, 367(2), pp.56-68.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Childe, S.J., Blome, C. and Papadopoulos, T., 2019. Big data and predictive analytics and manufacturing performance: integrating institutional theory, resource-based view and big data culture. *British Journal of Management*, 30(2), pp.341-361.
- Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Childe, S.J., Wamba, S.F. and Papadopoulos, T., 2016. The impact of big data on world-class sustainable manufacturing. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 84(1-4), pp.631-645.
- Dulye, L., 2008. Using communication to drive change at Rolls-Royce. *Strategic Communication Management*, 13(1), p.32.
- Durai, S., 2017. A study on the impact of Job Satisfaction on Job Performance of Employees working in Automobile Industry, Punjab, India. *Journal of Management Research*, 9(1), pp.117-130.

- Duthler, G. and Dhanesh, G.S., 2018. The role of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and internal CSR communication in predicting employee engagement: Perspectives from the United Arab Emirates (UAE). *Public relations review*, 44(4), pp.453-462.
- Dweiri, F., Kumar, S., Khan, S.A. and Jain, V., 2016. Designing an integrated AHP based decision support system for supplier selection in automotive industry. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 62, pp.273-283.
- Dwyer, J. and Hopwood, N., 2019. *The business communication handbook*. Cengage AU.
- Eilert, M., Jayachandran, S., Kalaignanam, K. and Swartz, T.A., 2017. Does it pay to recall your product early? An empirical investigation in the automobile industry. *Journal of Marketing*, 81(3), pp.111-129.
- Ekpenyong, E.J. and Enang, E.I., 2015. Efficient exponential ratio estimator for estimating the population mean in simple random sampling. *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 44(3), pp.689-705.
- Ell, T., 2016. New Workplace Design to Business® Evolution–Fallstudie Daimler AG. In *Arbeitsplatz der Zukunft* (pp. 231-250). Springer Gabler, Wiesbaden.
- Elving, W.J., Golob, U., Podnar, K., Ellerup-Nielsen, A. and Thomson, C., 2015. The bad, the ugly and the good: new challenges for CSR communication. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 20(2), pp.118-127.
- Emerson, R.W., 2017. Likert scales. *Journal of Visual Impairment & Blindness (Online)*, 111(5), pp.488-488.
- Erevelles, S., Fukawa, N. and Swayne, L., 2016. Big Data consumer analytics and the transformation of marketing. *Journal of business research*, 69(2), pp.897-904.
- Erez, M., Lisak, A., Harush, R., Glikson, E., Nouri, R. and Shokef, E., 2013. Going global: Developing management students' cultural intelligence and global identity in culturally diverse virtual teams. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 12(3), pp.330-355.
- Estell, P. and Davidson, E.J., 2019, January. Employee Engagement, Voice Mechanisms, and Enterprise Social Network Sites (ESNS). In *Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.
- Etikan, I. and Bala, K., 2017. Sampling and sampling methods. *Biometrics & Biostatistics International Journal*, 5(6), p.00149.

- Fan, S., Lau, R.Y. and Zhao, J.L., 2015. Demystifying big data analytics for business intelligence through the lens of marketing mix. *Big Data Research*, 2(1), pp.28-32.
- Femi, A.F., 2014. The impact of communication on workers' performance in selected organisations in Lagos State, Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of humanities and Social Science*, 19(8), pp.75-82.
- Freitag, A. and Trebecki, J., 2012. Impact of a lingering crisis on the perception of internal communication by employees: A case in the automotive sector. *Comunicação Pública*, 7(n12), pp.43-55.
- Friedl, J. and Verčič, A.T., 2011. Media preferences of digital natives' internal communication: A pilot study. *Public Relations Review*, 37(1), pp.84-86.
- Fuller, S., 2012. *Knowledge management foundations*. Routledge.
- Galluccio, L., Melodia, T., Palazzo, S. and Santagati, G.E., 2012, January. Challenges and implications of using ultrasonic communications in intra-body area networks. In *Wireless On-demand Network Systems and Services (WONS), 2012 9th Annual Conference on* (pp. 182-189). IEEE.
- Gao, H., Hu, J., Huang, T., Wang, J. and Chen, Y., 2011. Security issues in online social networks. *IEEE Internet Computing*, 15(4), pp.56-63.
- García-Morales, V.J., Jiménez-Barrionuevo, M.M. and Gutiérrez-Gutiérrez, L., 2012. Transformational leadership influence on organisational performance through organisational learning and innovation. *Journal of business research*, 65(7), pp.1040-1050.
- García-Morales, V.J., Matías-Reche, F. and Verdú-Jover, A.J., 2011. Influence of internal communication on technological proactivity, organisational learning, and organisational innovation in the pharmaceutical sector. *Journal of Communication*, 61(1), pp.150-177.
- Gardiner, A., Aasheim, C., Rutner, P. and Williams, S., 2018. Skill requirements in big data: A content analysis of job advertisements. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 58(4), pp.374-384.
- German Trade and Invest, 2018. *The Automotive Industry in Germany*. [Online]. Available at: https://www.gtai.de/GTAI/Content/EN/Invest/_SharedDocs/Downloads/GTAI/Industry-overviews/industry-overview-automotive-industry-en.pdf [Accessed 2 December 2018].
- Ghasemaghaei, M. and Calic, G., 2019. Does big data enhance firm innovation competency? The mediating role of data-driven insights. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, pp.69-84.

- Ghauri, P., 2004. Designing and conducting case studies in international business research. *Handbook of qualitative research methods for international business*, pp.109-124.
- Goksoy, A. and Alayoglu, N., 2013. The impact of perception of performance appraisal and distributive justice fairness on employees' ethical decision making in paternalist organisational culture. *Performance improvement quarterly*, 26(1), pp.57-79.
- Gopal, P.R.C. and Thakkar, J., 2016. Sustainable supply chain practices: an empirical investigation on Indian automobile industry. *Production Planning & Control*, 27(1), pp.49-64.
- Goraya, M., 2017. Robust production & sale, automobile industry on course. *Business Recorder*. [online]. Available at: <https://fp.brecorder.com/2017/09/20170919219135/> [Accessed 2 December 2018].
- Grant, A.E. and Meadows, J.H., 2016. *Communication technology update and fundamentals*. Routledge.
- Gray, D.E., 2019. *Doing research in the business world*. Sage Publications Limited.
- Gregoire, T.G. and Affleck, D.L., 2018. Estimating desired sample size for simple random sampling of a skewed population. *The American Statistician*, 72(2), pp.184-190.
- Grigoriou, K. and Rothaermel, F.T., 2017. Organizing for knowledge generation: Internal knowledge networks and the contingent effect of external knowledge sourcing. *Strategic Management Journal*, 38(2), pp.395-414.
- Gritzalis, D., Kandias, M., Stavrou, V. and Mitrou, L., 2014. History of information: the case of privacy and security in social media. In *Proc. of the History of Information Conference*(pp. 283-310).
- Guest, G., Bunce, A. and Johnson, L., 2006. How many interviews are enough? An experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field methods*, 18(1), pp.59-82.
- Guffey, M.E. and Loewy, D., 2010. *Business communication: Process and product*. Cengage Learning.
- Gul, H., Usman, M., Liu, Y., Rehman, Z. and Jebran, K., 2018. Does the effect of power distance moderate the relation between person environment fit and job satisfaction leading to job performance? Evidence from Afghanistan and Pakistan. *Future Business Journal*, 4(1), pp.68-83.

- Gunasekare, D.U., 2015. Mixed research method as the third research paradigm: a literature review. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*.
- Hagiwara, N., Kashy, D.A. and Penner, L.A., 2014. A novel analytical strategy for patient–physician communication research: The one-with-many design. *Patient education and counseling*, 95(3), pp.325-331.
- Hair Jr, J.F., Wolfinbarger, M., Money, A.H., Samouel, P. and Page, M.J., 2015. *Essentials of business research methods*. Routledge.
- Hanigan, K., 2014. A Blunder of Supreme Proportions: General Jurisdiction after Daimler AG v. Bauman. *Loy. LAL Rev.*, 48, p.291.
- Hauff, S., 2021. Analytical strategies in HRM systems research: a comparative analysis and some recommendations. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(9), pp.1923-1952.
- Hill, N. and Alexander, J., 2017. *The handbook of customer satisfaction and loyalty measurement*. Routledge.
- Hoseinzadeh, N., Arvin, R., Khattak, A.J. and Han, L.D., 2020. Integrating safety and mobility for pathfinding using big data generated by connected vehicles. *Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp.1-17.
- Hossain, M.S., Rahim, N.A., Aman, M.M. and Selvaraj, J., 2019. Application of ANOVA method to study solar energy for hydrogen production. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 44(29), pp.14571-14579.
- Hrehova, D., 2010. The Significance of Communication and Language Competences for Employment and Career Development. *Human Resources Management & Ergonomics Journal*, 4(2).
- Hume, J. and Leonard, A., 2014. Exploring the strategic potential of internal communication in international non-governmental organisations. *Public relations review*, 40(2), pp.294-304.
- Hynes, G.E., 2012. Improving employees' interpersonal communication competencies: A qualitative study. *Business communication quarterly*, 75(4), pp.466-475.
- Iannaccone, L.R., 2016. Rational choice. *Rational choice theory and religion: summary and assessment*.
- Ibáñez, M., Pozo, Ó.J., Sancho, J.V., Orengo, T., Haro, G. and Hernández, F., 2016. Analytical strategy to investigate 3, 4-methylenedioxypyrovalerone (MDPV) metabolites in

- consumers' urine by high-resolution mass spectrometry. *Analytical and bioanalytical chemistry*, 408(1), pp.151-164.
- IHS Market Ltd., 2014. *Five Critical Challenges Facing the Automotive Industry: A Guide for Strategic Planners*. IHS Market LTD.
- Inderyas, S., Khattak, K., Raza, A.A., Hassan, Z. and Mohammad, A.N., 2015. The Moderating role of power distance on the relationship between leadership styles and employees job performance on public health care sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 5(1), pp.1-8.
- Invernizzi, E., Biraghi, S. and Romenti, S., 2012. Entrepreneurial communication and the strategic role of internal communication. *Sinergie rivista di studi e ricerche*, (87).
- Invest Pakistan (2020). *Automobiles: Sector Brief*. Invest Pakistan. Available at: [https://invest.gov.pk/automobiles#:~:text=Pakistan's%20Automobile%20industry%20contributes%20\(2.8,terms%20of%20taxes%20and%20duties.](https://invest.gov.pk/automobiles#:~:text=Pakistan's%20Automobile%20industry%20contributes%20(2.8,terms%20of%20taxes%20and%20duties.)
- Isac, N. and Badshah, M.W., 2016. Motivation and job satisfaction of Human Resources within an organisation. *Scientific Bulletin- Economic sciences*, 15 (1).
- Ismail, M., Kawnal, N. and Shahbaz, M.Q., 2018. Generalized ratio-product-type estimator for variance using auxiliary information in simple random sampling. *Kuwait Journal of Science*, 45(1).
- Iswanto, A.H. and Marzuki, F., 2020. Can Corporate Character Dimensions Act as Bridge between Leader-Member Exchange and Employee Organisation Relationship: An Empirical Study of Indonesian Pharmaceutical Firms. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(2), pp.535-544.
- Ivanova, M., Kaeschel, J. and Ivanov, D., 2015. Analysis of the order recovery point location in the supply chain. *International Journal of Integrated Supply Management*, 9(4), pp.329-342.
- Iyer, P., Davari, A. and Paswan, A., 2018. Determinants of brand performance: the role of internal branding. *Journal of brand Management*, 25(3), pp.202-216.
- Jacobides, M. G., MacDuffie, J. P., and Tae, C. J., 2016. Agency, structure, and the dominance of OEMs: Change and stability in the automotive sector. *Strategic Management Journal*, 37(9), pp.1942-1967.

- Jacobs, M.A., Yu, W. and Chavez, R., 2016. The effect of internal communication and employee satisfaction on supply chain integration. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 171, pp.60-70.
- Jacobsen, L.F., Grunert, K.G., Søndergaard, H.A., Steenbekkers, B., Dekker, M. and Lähteenmäki, L., 2014. Improving internal communication between marketing and technology functions for successful new food product development. *Trends in food science & technology*, 37(2), pp.106-114.
- Japan International Cooperation Agency and UNICO International Corporation, 2011. *Project For Automobile Industry Development Policy In The Islamic Republic Of Pakistan*. [online]. Available at: <http://spearheadresearch.org/index.php/researchopinions/growth-trajectory-pakistan-automotive-sector> [Accessed 2 December 2018].
- Jiménez-Castillo, D. and Sánchez-Pérez, M., 2013. Nurturing employee market knowledge absorptive capacity through unified internal communication and integrated information technology. *Information & Management*, 50(2-3), pp.76-86.
- Jiménez-Jiménez, D. and Sanz-Valle, R., 2011. Innovation, organisational learning, and performance. *Journal of business research*, 64(4), pp.408-417.
- Johanson, M., Belenki, S., Jalminger, J., Fant, M. and Gjertz, M., 2014, October. Big automotive data: Leveraging large volumes of data for knowledge-driven product development. In *2014 IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)* (pp. 736-741). IEEE.
- Johnson, T., Sanderson, B., Wang, C.H. and Parker, F., 2017. Factors associated with first-time NCLEX-RN success: A descriptive research study. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 56(9), pp.542-545.
- Jones, R., Latham, J. and Betta, M., 2013. Creating the illusion of employee empowerment: lean production in the international automobile industry. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(8), pp.1629-1645.
- Jung, D., 2017. The Formation of Modern Muslim Subjectivities: Research Project and Analytical Strategy. *Tidsskrift for Islamforskning*, 11(1), pp.11-29.
- Jussila, J.J., Kärkkäinen, H. and Aramo-Immonen, H., 2014. Social media utilization in business-to-business relationships of technology industry firms. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 30, pp.606-613.

- Kaasa, A. and Vadi, M., 2010. How does culture contribute to innovation? Evidence from European countries. *Economics of innovation and new technology*, 19(7), pp.583-604.
- Kabashi, F., Snopçe, H., Abazi-Bexheti, L. and Shkurti, L., 2021, August. Analysis of the Cases of Coronavirus in Prizren Region by using ANOVA and regression analysis. In *2021 International Conference on INnovations in Intelligent SysTems and Applications (INISTA)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Kale, D., 2017. Sources of innovation and technology capability development in the Indian automobile industry. *Institutions and Economies*, pp.121-150.
- Kandlhofer, M. and Steinbauer, G., 2016. Evaluating the impact of educational robotics on pupils' technical-and social-skills and science related attitudes. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 75, pp.679-685.
- Kang, M. and Sung, M., 2017. How symmetrical employee communication leads to employee engagement and positive employee communication behaviors. *Journal of Communication Management*, 21(1), pp.82-102.
- Kannan, S., Kumaran, S.S. and Kumaraswamidhas, L.A., 2016. Optimization of friction welding by taguchi and ANOVA method on commercial aluminium tube to Al 2025 tube plate with backing block using an external tool. *Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology*, 30(5), pp.2225-2235.
- Kanyurhi, E.B. and Bugandwa Mungu Akonkwa, D., 2016. Internal marketing, employee job satisfaction, and perceived organisational performance in microfinance institutions. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(5), pp.773-796.
- Karachi Chamber of Commerce & Industry, 2019. *KCCI- eBulletin*. Karachi Chamber of Commerce & Industry.
- Karamat, F., 2017. *Growth Trajectory: Pakistan Automotive Sector – Spearhead Research – Pakistan*. [online] Spearheadresearch.org. Available at: <http://spearheadresearch.org/index.php/researchopinions/growth-trajectory-pakistan-automotive-sector> [Accessed 2 December 2018].
- Karanges, E., Johnston, K., Beatson, A. and Lings, I., 2015. The influence of internal communication on employee engagement: A pilot study. *Public relations review*, 41(1), pp.129-131.

- Kepner, J., Gadepally, V., Michaleas, P., Schear, N., Varia, M., Yerukhimovich, A. and Cunningham, R.K., 2014, September. Computing on masked data: a high performance method for improving big data veracity. In *2014 IEEE High Performance Extreme Computing Conference (HPEC)* (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- Khan, M.Q., Masood, S.A. and Qureshi, S.N., 2019. Analysis of Low Productivity in Public Sector Automobile. *Technical Journal*, 24(01), pp.51-62.
- Khan, S. Z. A., 2011. *Technology transfer effectiveness through international joint ventures (IJVs) to their component suppliers: a study of the automotive industry of Pakistan*. University of Birmingham.
- Khan, S., 2019. 'Automobile Industry Survey 2018: Honda Civic & Suzuki GD 110S declared biggest winners', *Business Recorder*, April 30. Available at: <https://www.brecorder.com/2019/04/30/493649/automobile-industry-survey-2018-honda-civic-suzuki-gd-110s-declared-biggest-winners/>
- Khan, S.N., 2014. Qualitative research method: Grounded theory. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 9(11), pp.224-233.
- Khan, Z., Lew, Y.K. and Akhtar, P., 2016. The influence of industrial policy and national systems of innovation on emerging economy suppliers' learning capability. *Industry and innovation*, 23(6), pp.512-530.
- Kianto, A., 2011. The influence of knowledge management on continuous innovation. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 55(1/2), pp.110-121.
- Kim, H.W., Kankanhalli, A. and Lee, H.L., 2016. Investigating decision factors in mobile application purchase: A mixed-methods approach. *Information & Management*, 53(6), pp.727-739.
- Kim, S., 2013. Compassion fatigue in liver and kidney transplant nurse coordinators: A descriptive research study. *Progress in Transplantation*, 23(4), pp.329-335.
- Kondrasuk, J.N., 2011. So what would an ideal performance appraisal look like?. *Journal of Applied Business and Economics*, 12(1), pp.57-71.
- Kumar, R., Sahoo, A., Satyanarayana, K. and Rao, G., 2013. Some studies on cutting force and temperature in machining Ti-6Al-4V alloy using regression analysis and ANOVA. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering Computations*, 4(3), pp.427-436.

- Kupritz, V.W. and Cowell, E., 2011. Productive management communication: Online and face-to-face. *The Journal of Business Communication (1973)*, 48(1), pp.54-82.
- Kushwaha, G.S. and Sharma, N.K., 2016. Green initiatives: a step towards sustainable development and firm's performance in the automobile industry. *Journal of cleaner production*, 121, pp.116-129.
- Law, C.M., 2017. Motor vehicle manufacturing: the representative industry. In *Restructuring the Global Automobile Industry* (pp. 1-18). Routledge.
- Law, C.M., 2017. *Restructuring the global automobile industry* (Vol. 4). Taylor & Francis.
- Law, C.M., 2017. *Restructuring the global automobile industry*. Routledge.
- Lazaroiu, G., 2015. Employee motivation and job performance. *Linguistic and Philosophical Investigations*, 14, p.97.
- Leary, M.R., 2014. *Introduction to behavioral research methods*. Pearson, © 2014..
- Lee, C.E., 2010. Face-to-face versus computer-mediated communication: Exploring employees' preference of effective employee communication channel. *International journal for the advancement of science & arts*, 1(2), pp.38-48.
- Lee, M.T. and Raschke, R.L., 2016. Understanding employee motivation and organisational performance: Arguments for a set-theoretic approach. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 1(3), pp.162-169.
- Lee, V.H., Foo, A.T.L., Leong, L.Y. and Ooi, K.B., 2016. Can competitive advantage be achieved through knowledge management? A case study on SMEs. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 65, pp.136-151.
- Lee, Y.K., Kim, S. and Kim, S.Y., 2014. The impact of internal branding on employee engagement and outcome variables in the hotel industry. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 19(12), pp.1359-1380.
- Leonardi, P.M., Huysman, M. and Steinfield, C., 2013. Enterprise social media: Definition, history, and prospects for the study of social technologies in organisations. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 19(1), pp.1-19.
- Leung, L., 2015. Validity, reliability, and generalizability in qualitative research. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 4(3), p.324.
- Lewis, S., 2015. Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches. *Health promotion practice*, 16(4), pp.473-475.

- Liebel, G., Tichy, M., Knauss, E., Ljungkrantz, O. and Stieglbauer, G., 2018. Organisation and communication problems in automotive requirements engineering. *Requirements Engineering*, 23(1), pp.145-167.
- Liebowitz, J. ed., 2013. *Big data and business analytics*. CRC press.
- Lipiäinen, H.S.M., Karjaluoto, H.E. and Nevalainen, M., 2014. Digital channels in the internal communication of a multinational corporation. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 19(3), pp.275-286.
- Lipscomb, M., 2012. Abductive reasoning and qualitative research. *Nursing Philosophy*, 13(4), pp.244-256.
- Liu, G., Ko, W.W. and Chapleo, C., 2017. Managing employee attention and internal branding. *Journal of Business Research*, 79, pp.1-11.
- Liu, L., 2013. Computing infrastructure for big data processing. *Frontiers of Computer Science*, 7(2), pp.165-170.
- Lockley, S. K., 2018. *An Employee App: "Advancement through Technology"*, Staffbase, <<https://insights.staffbase.com/blog/mobile-first-internal-communication-at-audi>>
- Löhndorf, B. and Diamantopoulos, A., 2014. Internal branding: Social identity and social exchange perspectives on turning employees into brand champions. *Journal of Service Research*, 17(3), pp.310-325.
- López-Nicolás, C. and Meroño-Cerdán, Á.L., 2011. Strategic knowledge management, innovation and performance. *International journal of information management*, 31(6), pp.502-509.
- Lubin, D.A. and Esty, D.C., 2010. The sustainability imperative. *Harvard business review*, 88(5), pp.42-50.
- Lunenburg, F.C., 2010. Formal communication channels: Upward, downward, horizontal, and external. *Focus on Colleges, Universities, and Schools*, 4(1), pp.1-7.
- Lunenburg, F.C., 2011. Organisational culture-performance relationships: Views of excellence and theory Z. In *National Forum of Educational Administration and Supervision Journal*(Vol. 29, No. 4, pp. 1-10).
- Luthra, S. and Haleem, A., 2015. Hurdles in implementing sustainable supply chain management: An analysis of Indian automobile sector. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 189, pp.175-183.

- Luthra, S., Garg, D. and Haleem, A., 2015. Critical success factors of green supply chain management for achieving sustainability in Indian automobile industry. *Production Planning & Control*, 26(5), pp.339-362.
- Luthra, S., Garg, D. and Haleem, A., 2016. The impacts of critical success factors for implementing green supply chain management towards sustainability: an empirical investigation of Indian automobile industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 121, pp.142-158.
- Mackelprang, A.W., Robinson, J.L., Bernardes, E. and Webb, G.S., 2014. The relationship between strategic supply chain integration and performance: a meta-analytic evaluation and implications for supply chain management research. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 35(1), pp.71-96.
- Maes, J., Teller, A., Erhard, M., Liqueste, C., Braat, L., Berry, P., Egoh, B., Puydarrieux, P., Fiorina, C., Santos, F. and Paracchini, M.L., 2013. Mapping and assessment of ecosystems and their services: an analytical framework for ecosystem assessments under action 5 of the EU biodiversity strategy to 2020.
- Mahdi, O.R., Nassar, I.A. and Almsafir, M.K., 2019. Knowledge management processes and sustainable competitive advantage: An empirical examination in private universities. *Journal of Business Research*, 94, pp.320-334.
- Mahmood, K., Ilyas, M. and Rehman, C.A., 2014. Impact of knowledge management and decentralization on supply chain performance: A study of automobile sector of Pakistan. *International Journal of Operations and Logistics Management*, 3(2), pp.124-139.
- Mangi, A.A., Kanasro, H.A. and Burdi, M.B., 2015. Motivation tools and organisational success: A critical analysis of motivational theories. *The Government-Annual Research Journal of Political Science.*, 4(4).
- Mani, V., Agrawal, R. and Sharma, V., 2015. Supply chain social sustainability: A comparative case analysis in Indian manufacturing industries. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 189, pp.234-251.
- Mannan, Z., 2013. *Business communication: Strategies for success in business and professions*. University Grants Commission.

- Markaki, E.N., Sakas, D.P. and Chadjipantelis, T., 2013. Communication management in business. The latent power for career development. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 73, pp.319-326.
- Marlow, S.L., Lacerenza, C.N. and Salas, E., 2017. Communication in virtual teams: A conceptual framework and research agenda. *Human Resource Management Review*, 27(4), pp.575-589.
- Marschan-Piekkari, R. and Welch, C., 2004. Qualitative research methods in international business: The state of the art. *Handbook of qualitative research methods for international business*, pp.5-24.
- Martin, K., 2015. What Remains of Vicarious Jurisdiction for Establishing General Jurisdiction over Corporate Defendants after Daimler AG v. Bauman. *Seton Hall Cir. Rev.*, 12, p.1.
- Masondo, D., 2018. South African business nanny state: the case of the automotive industrial policy post-apartheid, 1995–2010. *Review of African Political Economy*, 45(156), pp.203-222.
- Matanda, M.J. and Ndubisi, N.O., 2013. Internal marketing, internal branding, and organisational outcomes: The moderating role of perceived goal congruence. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 29(9-10), pp.1030-1055.
- Maule-ffinch, B., 2015. Key trends in information security. *Network Security*, 2015(11), pp.18-20.
- Mazzei, A. and Ravazzani, S., 2015. Internal crisis communication strategies to protect trust relationships: A study of Italian companies. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 52(3), pp.319-337.
- Mazzei, A. and Ravazzani, S., 2017. Internal branding and employee brand consistent behaviours: The role of enablement-oriented communication. *MERCATI & COMPETITIVITÀ*.
- Mazzei, A., 2010. Promoting active communication behaviours through internal communication. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 15(3), pp.221-234.
- Mazzei, A., 2018. Employee Engagement. *Encyclopedia of Strategic Communication*, pp.1-6.
- Mazzei, M.J. and Noble, D., 2017. Big data dreams: A framework for corporate strategy. *Business Horizons*, 60(3), pp.405-414.

- McDermott, M.C., 2014. BMW and Mercedes-Benz first international plant location decision: the site selection and negotiation process in the USA. *International Journal of Automotive Technology and Management* 20, 14(2), pp.172-193.
- McGrattan, G., 2015. *Exploring Purpose: the Best Bits of the Melcrum Summit*. Synergy.
- Meier, C., 2016. Digital supply chain management. In *Digital Enterprise Transformation* (pp. 255-286). Routledge.
- Mello, J.A., 2014. *Strategic human resource management*. Nelson Education.
- Mellor, D. and Moore, K.A., 2014. The use of Likert scales with children. *Journal of pediatric psychology*, 39(3), pp.369-379.
- Men, L.R., 2014. Strategic internal communication: Transformational leadership, communication channels, and employee satisfaction. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 28(2), pp.264-284.
- Meng, X., 2013, May. Scalable simple random sampling and stratified sampling. In *International Conference on Machine Learning* (pp. 531-539). PMLR.
- Merchant Jr, R.C., 2010. The role of career development in improving organisational effectiveness and employee development. *Florida Department of Law Enforcement*.
- Merrilees, B. and Frazer, L., 2013. Internal branding: Franchisor leadership as a critical determinant. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(2), pp.158-164.
- Mersham, G., 2016. The communication challenges of issue management in a postmodern world: a case study of the South Durban Industrial Basin. *Communitas*, 21(1), pp.165-177.
- Meshi, D., Tamir, D.I. and Heekeren, H.R., 2015. The emerging neuroscience of social media. *Trends in cognitive sciences*, 19(12), pp.771-782.
- Miller, V.D., Poole, M.S., Seibold, D.R., Myers, K.K., Park, H.S., Monge, P., Fulk, J., Frank, L.B., Margolin, D.B., Schultz, C.M. and Shen, C., 2011. Advancing research in organisational communication through quantitative methodology. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 25(1), pp.4-58.
- Mishra, K., Boynton, L. and Mishra, A., 2014. Driving employee engagement: The expanded role of internal communications. *International Journal of Business Communication*, 51(2), pp.183-202.

- Mohr, D., Muller, N., Krieg, A., Gao, P., Kaas, H., Krieger, A. and Hensley, A., 2013. *The road to 2020 and beyond: What's driving the global automotive industry?* McKinsey & Company.
- Mortensen, C.D., 2017. *Communication theory*. Routledge.
- Muniz Jr, J., Hong, J., Oliveira, S., Wintersberger, D. and Popadiuk, S., 2019. Knowledge sharing in the automotive sector: a comparative study of chinese and brazilian firms. *Production*, 29.
- Mustafa, S., Begum, R., Nisar, S. K., and Osama, A., 2018. Impact of New 5 Year Automobile Policy (2016-21) on the Profitability of Major Players in the Automobile Industry of Pakistan. *Eur Sci J*, 14(16), pp.1857-1881.
- Naeem, M., 2017. *Product Brand Loyalty And Purchase Decision: A Comparative Study Of Automobile Industry Of Pakistan*. National University Of Modern Languages.
- Nassaji, H., 2015. Qualitative and descriptive research: Data type versus data analysis.
- Nayebi, F., Desharnais, J.M. and Abran, A., 2012, April. The state of the art of mobile application usability evaluation. In *Electrical & Computer Engineering (CCECE), 2012 25th IEEE Canadian Conference on* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- Nazir, O. and Islam, J.U., 2017. Enhancing organisational commitment and employee performance through employee engagement. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 6(1), pp.98-114.
- Neto, M.T.R., da Silva, L.C.F. and Ferreira, C.A.A., 2018. Influence of internal communication on the organisations' performance: proposition of model. *Future Studies Research Journal: Trends and Strategies*, 10(2).
- Neves, P. and Eisenberger, R., 2012. Management communication and employee performance: The contribution of perceived organisational support. *Human Performance*, 25(5), pp.452-464.
- Next Capital Limited, 2015. *Automobile Manufacturing Sector*. Karachi: Next Capital Limited, pp.1-9
- Nguyen, T.H., Newby, M. and Macaulay, M.J., 2015. Information technology adoption in small business: Confirmation of a proposed framework. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 53(1), pp.207-227.

- Nicoleta, I.S.A.C. and Badshah, M.W., 2016. Motivation And Job Satisfaction Of Human Resources Within An Organisation. *Scientific Bulletin: Economic Sciences*, 15(1), pp.33-40.
- Niebel, T., Rasel, F. and Viete, S., 2019. BIG data–BIG gains? Understanding the link between big data analytics and innovation. *Economics of Innovation and New Technology*, 28(3), pp.296-316.
- Obeidat, B.Y., Al-Suradi, M.M., Masa'deh, R.E. and Tarhini, A., 2016. The impact of knowledge management on innovation: An empirical study on Jordanian consultancy firms. *Management Research Review*, 39(10), pp.1214-1238.
- Oh, Y. and Park, J., 2011. New link between administrative reforms and job attitude: The role of interpersonal trust in peers as a mediator on organisational commitment. *International Review of Public Administration*, 16(3), pp.65-87.
- Pal, S.K., Singh, H.P., Kumar, S. and Chatterjee, K., 2018. A family of efficient estimators of the finite population mean in simple random sampling. *Journal of Statistical Computation and Simulation*, 88(5), pp.920-934.
- Palttala, P., Boano, C., Lund, R. and Vos, M., 2012. Communication gaps in disaster management: Perceptions by experts from governmental and non-governmental organisations. *Journal of Contingencies and Crisis Management*, 20(1), pp.2-12.
- PAMA, 2020. 'Monthly Production & Sales of Vehicles', PAMA. Available at: <https://www.pama.org.pk/statistical-information/sales-production/monthly-sales-production>
- PAMA, 2020. *Product and Sales Data of Vehicles*. PAMA.
- Papasolomou, I. and Kitchen, P.J., 2011. Cause related marketing: Developing a tripartite approach with BMW. *Corporate Reputation Review*, 14(1), pp.63-75.
- Paternoster, R., Jaynes, C.M. and Wilson, T., 2017. Rational choice theory and interest in the "Fortune of Others". *Journal of research in crime and delinquency*, 54(6), pp.847-868.
- Pfeffermann, N., Minshall, T. and Mortara, L. eds., 2013. *Strategy and communication for innovation*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Pfeifer, N. and Kleiter, G.D., 2010. Uncertain deductive reasoning. In *The science of reason* (pp. 161-182). Psychology Press.

- Piehler, R., Hanisch, S. and Burmann, C., 2015. Internal branding—Relevance, management and challenges. *Marketing Review St. Gallen*, 32(1), pp.52-61.
- Piehler, R., Hanisch, S. and Burmann, C., 2015. Internal branding—Relevance, management and challenges. *Marketing Review St. Gallen*, 32(1), pp.52-61.
- Pirzadeh, H., Shanian, S., Hamou-Lhadj, A., Alawneh, L. and Shafiee, A., 2013. Stratified sampling of execution traces: Execution phases serving as strata. *Science of Computer Programming*, 78(8), pp.1099-1118.
- Plale, B., 2013, October. Big data opportunities and challenges for IR, text mining and NLP. In *Proceedings of the 2013 international workshop on Mining unstructured big data using natural language processing* (pp. 1-2).
- Pokorný, J., 2015, June. Database technologies in the world of big data. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computer Systems and Technologies* (pp. 1-12).
- Pongolini, M., Lundin, J. and Svensson, L., 2011, June. Global online meetings in virtual teams: from media choice to interaction negotiation. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Communities and Technologies* (pp. 108-117). ACM.
- Porsiel, J., 2008. Machine translation at Volkswagen: a case study. *Multilingual Computing & Technology*, 100.
- Prasad, P., 2015. Performance appraisal: An empirical study to understand job satisfaction and motivation of personnel through the system. *International journal of engineering and applied sciences*, 2(4).
- Pryke, S., Badi, S., Almadhoob, H., Soundararaj, B. and Addyman, S., 2018. Self-organizing networks in complex infrastructure projects. *Project management journal*, 49(2), pp.18-41.
- Punjaisri, K. and Wilson, A., 2017. The role of internal branding in the delivery of employee brand promise. In *Advances in corporate branding* (pp. 91-108). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Qadir, U., 2016. *Pakistan's Automotive Industry: A Case of Stalled Development* (No. 2016: 137). Pakistan Institute of Development Economics.
- Qadir, U., 2016. *Technology Acquisition, Catching Up and Competitiveness in Pakistan*. Pakistan Institute of Development Economics.

- Qadir, U., 2017. Technological capabilities development in Pakistan's automotive industry: a case of stalled development. *International Journal of Technological Learning, Innovation and Development*, 9(2), pp.114-136.
- Qatawneh, H., 2018. Hybrid communication strategies and tools as a strategic lever to improve supply chain performance. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 13(3), p.181.
- Quinlan, C., Babin, B., Carr, J. and Griffin, M., 2019. *Business research methods*. South Western Cengage.
- Quirke, B., 2017. *Making the connections: using internal communication to turn strategy into action*. Routledge.
- Quirke, M.B., 2012. *Making the connections: Using internal communication to turn strategy into action*. Gower Publishing, Ltd.
- Quratulain, S., Khan, A.K., Crawshaw, J.R., Arain, G.A. and Hameed, I., 2018. A study of employee affective organisational commitment and retention in Pakistan: The roles of psychological contract breach and norms of reciprocity. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 29(17), pp.2552-2579.
- Radovic Markovic, M. and Salamzadeh, A., 2018. The importance of communication in business management. In *Radovic Markovic, M., & Salamzadeh, A.(2018). The Importance of Communication in Business Management, The 7th International Scientific Conference on Employment, Education and Entrepreneurship, Belgrade, Serbia*.
- Ratnam, C., Vikram, K.A., Ben, B.S. and Murthy, B.S.N., 2016. Process monitoring and effects of process parameters on responses in turn-milling operations based on SN ratio and ANOVA. *Measurement*, 94, pp.221-232.
- Rawlinson, M. and Wells, P., 2016. *The new European automobile industry*. Springer.
- Razmerita, L., Kirchner, K. and Nielsen, P., 2016. What factors influence knowledge sharing in organisations? A social dilemma perspective of social media communication. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 20(6), pp.1225-1246.
- Rehnberg, M. and Ponte, S., 2018. From smiling to smirking? 3D printing, upgrading and the restructuring of global value chains. *Global Networks*, 18(1), pp.57-80.

- Rizwan, M., Tariq, M., Hassan, R. and Sultan, A., 2014. A comparative analysis of the factors effecting the employee motivation and employee performance in Pakistan. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), p.35.
- Rodriquez, A., Tavares, B., Silva, I., Brito, M. and Au-Yong-Oliveira, M., 2018, September. Social Networks and Internal Corporate Communication: Help or Hindrance?. In *European Conference on Innovation and Entrepreneurship* (pp. 659-XIX). Academic Conferences International Limited.
- Ruck, K. and Welch, M., 2012. Valuing internal communication; management and employee perspectives. *Public Relations Review*, 38(2), pp.294-302.
- Ruesch, J., Bateson, G., Pinsker, E.C. and Combs, G., 2017. *Communication: The social matrix of psychiatry*. Routledge.
- Ryynänen, H., Pekkarinen, O. and Salminen, R.T., 2012. Supplier's internal communication in change process to solution business: Challenges and tentative research agenda. *jbm- Journal of Business Market Management*, 5(3), pp.154-172.
- Saaeb, R.R. and Al-Saidi, M., 2021. The Practical Reality Of Green Human Resources Management Strategies (Descriptive Analytical Research Of The Opinions Of A Sample Of Faculty In The Al-Furat Al-Awsatuniversities Area). *Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation*, 32(3).
- Şahin, F., 2012. The mediating effect of leader–member exchange on the relationship between Theory X and Y management styles and affective commitment: A multilevel analysis. *Journal of Management & Organisation*, 18(2), pp.159-174.
- Sahin, S. and Mete, J., 2021. A Brief Study on Descriptive Research:: Its Nature and Application in Social Science. *International Journal of Research and Analysis in Humanities*, 1(1), pp.11-11.
- Saleem, M., 2015. *Analysis of Key Factors Affecting Kaizen and Development of a Framework for its Effective Implementation in Automobile Sector of Pakistan*. Islamabad: National University of Sciences and Technology.
- Sarkar, A., 2016. We live in a VUCA World: The importance of responsible leadership. *Development and Learning in Organisations: An International Journal*, 30(3), pp.9-12.

- Sarwar, S. Z., Ishaque, A., Ehsan, N., Pirzada, D. S. and Nasir, Z. M. (2012). Identifying productivity blemishes in Pakistan automotive industry: a case study. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 61(2), pp.173-193.
- Saunders, M.N., 2011. *Research methods for business students*, 5/e. Pearson Education India.
- Schoeneborn, D. and Vasquez, C., 2017. Communication Constitution of Organisations. *The International Encyclopedia of Organisational Communication*, pp.1-18.
- Schoeneborn, D., Blaschke, S., Cooren, F., McPhee, R.D., Seidl, D. and Taylor, J.R., 2014. The three schools of CCO thinking: Interactive dialogue and systematic comparison. *Management communication quarterly*, 28(2), pp.285-316.
- Schoeneborn, D., Kuhn, T.R. and Kärreman, D., 2018. The communicative constitution of organisation, organizing, and organisationality. *Organisation Studies*, p.0170840618782284.
- Schoenherr, T. and Speier-Pero, C., 2015. Data science, predictive analytics, and big data in supply chain management: Current state and future potential. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 36(1), pp.120-132.
- Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R., 2016. *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Shagholi, R., Hussin, S., Siraj, S., Naimie, Z., Assadzadeh, F. and Moayedi, F., 2010. Value creation through trust, decision making and teamwork in educational environment. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2), pp.255-259.
- Shaju, M. and Subhashini, D., 2017. A study on the impact of job satisfaction on job performance of employees working in automobile industry. *Journal of Management Research*, 17(2), pp.74-83.
- Sharma, N. and Kamalanabhan, T.J., 2012. Internal corporate communication and its impact on internal branding: Perception of Indian public sector employees. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 17(3), pp.300-322.
- Shields, J., Brown, M., Kaine, S. and North-Samardzic, A., 2015. *Managing employee performance & reward: Concepts, practices, strategies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Siedlecki, S.L., 2020. Understanding descriptive research designs and methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 34(1), pp.8-12.

- Sievert, H. and Scholz, C., 2017. Engaging employees in (at least partly) disengaged companies. Results of an interview survey within about 500 German corporations on the growing importance of digital engagement via internal social media. *Public relations review*, 43(5), pp.894-903.
- Singh, T., Veron-Jackson, L. and Cullinane, J., 2008. Blogging: A new play in your marketing game plan. *Business horizons*, 51(4), pp.281-292.
- Soliman, E.M., 2013. The relationship between internal marketing orientation and employee job satisfaction in public sector. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 3(5), pp.111-120.
- Spaho, K., 2013. Organisational communication and conflict management. *Management: journal of contemporary management issues*, 18(1), pp.103-118.
- Sreejesh, S., Mohapatra, S. and Anusree, M.R., 2014. Business research design: Exploratory, descriptive and causal designs. In *Business Research Methods* (pp. 25-103). Springer, Cham.
- Srivastava, A., Ramachandran, K. and Suresh, A., 2014. Status of employee engagement in India: A time for reflection. *International Journal of Education and Management Studies*, 4(4), p.316.
- Stehman, S.V., 2014. Estimating area and map accuracy for stratified random sampling when the strata are different from the map classes. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 35(13), pp.4923-4939.
- Steyn, E., Steyn, T.F.J. and van Rooyen, M., 2011. Internal communication at DaimlerChrysler South Africa: A qualitative perspective on two-way symmetrical communication and internal marketing. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 5(4), pp.131-144.
- Stieglitz, S. and Brockmann, T., 2012. Increasing organisational performance by transforming into a mobile enterprise. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 11(4).
- Straub, B. and Daimler, A.G., 2018, July. Automotive Displays-Increasing and Challenging Market. In *2018 25th International Workshop on Active-Matrix Flatpanel Displays and Devices (AM-FPD)* (pp. 1-4). IEEE.

- Subari, S. and Riady, H., 2015. Influence of training, competence and motivation on employee performance, moderated by internal communications. *American Journal of Business and Management*, 4(3), pp.133-145.
- Suh, J., Harrington, J. and Goodman, D., 2018. Understanding the link between organisational communication and innovation: An examination of public, nonprofit, and for-profit organisations in South Korea. *Public Personnel Management*, 47(2), pp.217-244.
- Suzuki, M., Ando, N. and Nishikawa, H., 2019. Intra-organisational communication and its consequences. *Management Decision*.
- Syafrudin, M., Alfian, G., Fitriyani, N.L. and Rhee, J., 2018. Performance analysis of IoT-based sensor, big data processing, and machine learning model for real-time monitoring system in automotive manufacturing. *Sensors*, 18(9), p.2946.
- Szmelter, A., 2015. Communication in global supply chains in automotive industry. *Information Systems in Management*, 4(3), pp.205-218.
- Szymańska, O., Adamczak, M. and Cyplik, P., 2017. Logistics 4.0-a new paradigm or set of known solutions?. *Research in Logistics & Production*, 7.
- Taherparvar, N., Esmailpour, R. and Dostar, M., 2014. Customer knowledge management, innovation capability and business performance: a case study of the banking industry. *Journal of knowledge management*.
- Tahir, N., Yousafzai, I.K., Jan, S. and Hashim, M., 2014. The Impact of Training and Development on Employees Performance and Productivity A case study of United Bank Limited Peshawar City, KPK, Pakistan. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(4), p.86.
- Tata Motors, 2018. *Connecting Aspirations*, Tata Motors, <<https://www.tatamotors.com/connecting-aspirations/>>
- Tatoglu, E., Bayraktar, E., Golgeci, I., Koh, S.L., Demirbag, M. and Zaim, S., 2016. How do supply chain management and information systems practices influence operational performance? Evidence from emerging country SMEs. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 19(3), pp.181-199.
- Taylor, P.C. and Medina, M., 2011. Educational research paradigms: From positivism to pluralism. *College Research Journal*, 1(1), pp.1-16.

- Terglav, K., 2017. *Employees as brand builders: a multilevel approach to internal branding* (Doctoral dissertation, Univerza v Ljubljani, Ekonomska fakulteta).
- Thibaut, J.W., 2017. *The social psychology of groups*. Routledge.
- Torres, A.I., Ferraz, S.S. and Santos-Rodrigues, H., 2018. The impact of knowledge management factors in organisational sustainable competitive advantage. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 19(2), pp.453-472.
- Turner, M.D., Ayantunde, A.A., Patterson, K.P. and Patterson III, E.D., 2012. Conflict management, decentralization and agropastoralism in dryland West Africa. *World Development*, 40(4), pp.745-757.
- van Ruler, B., 2018. Communication theory: An underrated pillar on which strategic communication rests. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 12(4), pp.367-381.
- Vander Elst, T., Baillien, E., De Cuyper, N. and De Witte, H., 2010. The role of organisational communication and participation in reducing job insecurity and its negative association with work-related well-being. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 31(2), pp.249-264.
- Verčič, A.T. and Vokić, N.P., 2017. Engaging employees through internal communication. *Public Relations Review*, 43(5), pp.885-893.
- Verčič, A.T., Verčič, D. and Sriramesh, K., 2012. Internal communication: Definition, parameters, and the future. *Public relations review*, 38(2), pp.223-230.
- Veres, C., Marian, L., Moica, S. and Al-Akel, K., 2018. Case study concerning 5S method impact in an automotive company. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 22, pp.900-905.
- Verghese, A.K., 2012. *Internal communications: insights, practices and models*. SAGE Publications India.
- Vermeir, P., Blot, S., Degroote, S., Vandijck, D., Mariman, A., Vanacker, T., Peleman, R., Verhaeghe, R. and Vogelaers, D., 2018. Communication satisfaction and job satisfaction among critical care nurses and their impact on burnout and intention to leave: A questionnaire study. *Intensive and Critical Care Nursing*, 48, pp.21-27.
- Vermeir, P., Downs, C., Degroote, S., Vandijck, D., Tobback, E., Delesie, L., Mariman, A., De Veugele, M., Verhaeghe, R., Cambré, B. and Vogelaers, D., 2018. Intra-organisational communication and job satisfaction among flemish hospital nurses: an exploratory study. *Workplace health & safety*, 66(1), pp.16-23.

- Viqar, S. and Welch, J.L., 2013. Deterministic collision free communication despite continuous motion. *Ad Hoc Networks*, 11(1), pp.508-521.
- Viswanathan, R., Ramesh, S., Elango, N. and Kamesh Kumar, D., 2017. Temperature Measurement and Optimisation in Machining Magnesium Alloy Using RSM and ANOVA. *Pertanika Journal of Science & Technology*, 25(1).
- Vošta, M. and Kocourek, A., 2017. Competitiveness of the European automobile industry in the global context. *Politics in Central Europe*, 13(1), pp.69-86.
- Walker, R.M., Damanpour, F. and Devece, C.A., 2011. Management innovation and organisational performance: The mediating effect of performance management. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 21(2), pp.367-386.
- Walton, D., 2014. *Abductive reasoning*. University of Alabama Press.
- Wang, G., Gunasekaran, A., Ngai, E.W. and Papadopoulos, T., 2016. Big data analytics in logistics and supply chain management: Certain investigations for research and applications. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 176, pp.98-110.
- Welch, M., 2011. The evolution of the employee engagement concept: communication implications. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 16(4), pp.328-346.
- Welch, M., 2011. The evolution of the employee engagement concept: communication implications. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 16(4), pp.328-346.
- Welch, M., 2012. Appropriateness and acceptability: Employee perspectives of internal communication. *Public Relations Review*, 38(2), pp.246-254.
- Wendt, M., 2020. Comparing 'deep' insider knowledge: Developing analytical strategies for cross-national qualitative studies. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 23(3), pp.241-254.
- Wenzel, A.K., Krause, T.A. and Vogel, D., 2019. Making performance pay work: The impact of transparency, participation, and fairness on controlling perception and intrinsic motivation. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 39(2), pp.232-255.
- Werth, O., Guhr, N. and Breitner, M.H., 2019, January. Successful Mobile Application Development: Towards a Taxonomy of Domain-Specific Process Models and Methodologies. In *Proceedings of the 52nd Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*.

- West, P.W., 2016. Simple random sampling of individual items in the absence of a sampling frame that lists the individuals. *New Zealand Journal of Forestry Science*, 46(1), pp.1-7.
- Williams, C., 2007. Research methods. *Journal of Business & Economic Research*, 5(3), pp.65-72.
- World Bank Group, 2020. 'GDP per capita (current US\$) – Pakistan', *World Bank Group*. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD?locations=PK>
- Wright, M. ed., 2016. *Gower handbook of internal communication*. CRC Press.
- Wu, H. and Leung, S.O., 2017. Can Likert scales be treated as interval scales?—A Simulation study. *Journal of Social Service Research*, 43(4), pp.527-532.
- Xu, Y. and Goodacre, R., 2018. On splitting training and validation set: a comparative study of cross-validation, bootstrap and systematic sampling for estimating the generalization performance of supervised learning. *Journal of Analysis and Testing*, 2(3), pp.249-262.
- Yadav, S.K., Kadilar, C., Shabbir, J. and Gupta, S., 2015. Improved family of estimators of population variance in simple random sampling. *Journal of Statistical Theory and Practice*, 9(2), pp.219-226.
- Yan, Z., Wang, T., Chen, Y. and Zhang, H., 2016. Knowledge sharing in online health communities: A social exchange theory perspective. *Information & Management*, 53(5), pp.643-653.
- Yang, C., Huang, Q., Li, Z., Liu, K. and Hu, F., 2017. Big Data and cloud computing: innovation opportunities and challenges. *International Journal of Digital Earth*, 10(1), pp.13-53.
- Yildirim, O., 2014. The Impact of organisational communication on organisational citizenship behavior: research findings. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 150, pp.1095-1100.
- Yin, S. and Kaynak, O., 2015. Big data for modern industry: challenges and trends [point of view]. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 103(2), pp.143-146.
- Young, A.M. and Hinesly, M.D., 2014. Social media use to enhance internal communication: Course design for business students. *Business and Professional Communication Quarterly*, 77(4), pp.426-439.
- Yousaf, S., Latif, M., Aslam, S. and Saddiqui, A., 2014. Impact of financial and non financial rewards on employee motivation. *Middle-East journal of scientific research*, 21(10), pp.1776-1786.

- Yvonne Feilzer, M., 2010. Doing mixed methods research pragmatically: Implications for the rediscovery of pragmatism as a research paradigm. *Journal of mixed methods research*, 4(1), pp.6-16.
- Zahoor Sarwar, S., Ishaque, A., Ehsan, N., Saeed Pirzada, D. and Moeen Nasir, Z., 2012. Identifying productivity blemishes in Pakistan automotive industry: a case study. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 61(2), pp.173-193.
- Zamora Cabot, F.J., 2014. Decision of the Supreme Court of the United States in the Daimler AG v. Bauman Et Al Case: Closing the Golden Door. *Bauman Et Al Case: Closing the Golden Door (March 3, 2014). Papeles el Tiempo de los Derechos*, (2).
- Zeng, H. and Hao, L., 2016. Cross-cultural examination of the effects of promotional framing on consumers' responses: a comparison of China and Pakistan. *International Business Review*, 25(5), pp.1020-1029.
- Zerfass, A. and Viertmann, C., 2017. Creating business value through corporate communication. *Journal of Communication Management*, 21(1), pp.68-81.
- Zerfass, A., Verčič, D., Nothhaft, H. and Werder, K.P., 2018. Strategic communication: Defining the field and its contribution to research and practice. *International Journal of Strategic Communication*, 12(4), pp.487-505.
- Zha, S., Adams, A.H., Calcagno-Roach, J.M. and Stringham, D.A., 2017. An examination on the effect of prior knowledge, personal goals, and incentive in an online employee training program. *New Horizons in Adult Education and Human Resource Development*, 29(4), pp.35-46.
- Zhang, W. and Creswell, J., 2013. The use of "mixing" procedure of mixed methods in health services research. *Medical care*, 51(8), pp.e51-e57.
- Zhang, X., Van Donk, D.P. and van der Vaart, T., 2016. The different impact of inter-organisational and intra-organisational ICT on supply chain performance. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, 36(7), pp.803-824.
- Zhang, Z. and Gupta, B.B., 2018. Social media security and trustworthiness: overview and new direction. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 86, pp.914-925.
- Zikmund, W.G., Babin, B.J., Carr, J.C. and Griffin, M., 2013. *Business research methods*. Cengage Learning.

APPENDIX A

Participant Information Sheet

Title:

**INTRA-ORGANISATIONAL COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES IN THE
AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY: THE CASE OF ATLAS HONDA, PAKISTAN**

Dear Participant,

I would like to extend an invitation to you to participate in this research project. Before you make a decision, you should be aware why this study is being conducted and what it would entail. Please give yourself plenty of time to read the following document below before you consider whether or not you would be interested to participate. Your inclusion in the study is entirely optional, and you can opt out at any time.

Who I am and what is the purpose of study?

My Name is Muhammad Shoaib and I am a student at the University of West Scotland, currently studying Doctor of Business Administration. This research study is part of the prerequisite of the degree of Doctor of Business Administration, hence why I am conducting this research.

The study focuses on the key obstacles that an automobile company faces as a result of inadequate communication strategies used by the company, as well as how they can solve these issues. As a result, the emphasis of this analysis will be on the various factors that influence intra-organisational communication, and a conceptual structure for intra-organisational communication for the automotive sector in Pakistan will be established based on the findings. This research is solely for academic reasons, with the intention of obtaining a Doctor of Business Administration degree. This study's findings are intended to be used by the automotive industry, employees, customers, government policymakers, and academics.

What will participation involve?

The participant will be required to fill out a survey questionnaire, which has 25 questions that must be answered. The length is estimated to be about 10-15 minutes. Questionnaires will be submitted by email or in person, depending on the participant's preference and convenience.

Why have you been invited to take part (Participant recruitment criteria)

Participant selection and assortment has been made on the basis of the fulfilment of the criteria,
-Current employees of the Automobile industry

Do you have to take part?

Participation is entirely optional, and you have the freedom to decline participation, reject any question, and withdraw at any time with no repercussions.

What will happen if you take part?

You will be asked to complete a survey questionnaire, via email or post. This should take no longer than 10-15 minutes to complete. The time and date of the survey will be accommodated to your preference and convenience.

What are the possible risks and benefits of taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or, any physical or psychological discomfort or harm. Hence, there are no immediate benefits for taking part in the research, however, it is hoped that this research will provide a strategic framework which will help in understanding the areas and factors of improvement needed in Intra-organisational communication challenges in Automobile sector. The research will provide better understanding of employee needs and the issues they are facing. This research can help Automobile sector for growth and sustainability.

Will my participation in this project be kept confidential?

The participants' personal details will always be kept private and confidential. In any study, the subjects will not be named or known, and the results will be analysed anonymously. Any survey data will be covered by appropriate authentication processes and technologies. The research does not have any direct or indirect impact or influence on the participant's personal or professional life. Any data collected from the questionnaires will be the sole responsibility of the researcher and not used by any third parties under any circumstances.

How will information you provide be recorded, stored and protected?

The information and data obtained would not be analysed or saved on a server, website, or network available to the public. The information will be held for testing purposes only and will be used to support staff, customers, and the industry.

What will happen to the results of the study?

The researcher plans to present his findings at conferences. The key goal is to complete the dissertation prerequisite for the DBA.

Who should you contact for further information?

For more information or any concerns in regard to the research, please feel to contact me at your own convenience.

Researcher: **Muhammad Shoaib**
[Redacted]

Director of study: **Christos Athanasoulis**
[Redacted]

Thank you

APPENDIX B

CONSENT FORM

Title of Project:

**INTRA-ORGANISATIONAL COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES IN THE
AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY: THE CASE OF ATLAS HONDA, PAKISTAN**

Name of Researcher: **Muhammad Shoaib**

Please initial all boxes

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
3. I understand that relevant sections of my survey notes and data collected during the study, may be looked at by individuals from **the University of the West of the Scotland**, where it is relevant to my taking part in this research. I give permission for these individuals to have access to my records.
4. I understand the data you are collecting from me, will only be used in UWS for academic purpose. But if you need to disclose outside the UWS you need to take my permission.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Email or phone no. (if applicable)

Name of Researcher

Date

Signature

Email or phone no. (if applicable)

APPENDIX C

Questionnaire

Section A: Background Information

1. Gender
 - Male
 - Female

2. Age
 - 20-30years
 - 30-40 years
 - 40-50 years
 - 50 years or above

3. Education
 - Intermediate
 - Bachelor
 - Master
 - MS/M. Phil
 - PhD

4. Department
 - Finance
 - IT,
 - Marketing,
 - Treasury,
 - Legal
 - HR
 - Operations
 - Internal Audit
 - Production
 - Sales
 - Compliance

5. Employment Status
 - Permanent staff
 - Temporary/Contract staff

Section B: Intra-Organisational Challenges Faced by the Company

1 Strongly Agree	2 Agree	3 Neutra l	4 Disagree	5 Strongly Disagree
----------------------------	-------------------	-------------------------	----------------------	-------------------------------

Complexity of Data Analysis					
The company confronts no issues in the management of large amounts of employee related data	1	2	3	4	5
The company has the technology that can allow for the facilitation of data management	1	2	3	4	5
Lack of Focus on Personal Goals					
The company consults the employees at the time of creation of job descriptions.	1	2	3	4	5
There are ample opportunities for effective training and development of the employees	1	2	3	4	5
The company has a rigorous and prompt system for the management of employee grievances	1	2	3	4	5
Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement					
I have sufficient levels of liberty and autonomy when it comes to performing my job.	1	2	3	4	5
Each employee has the responsibility of ensuring the quality of his job	1	2	3	4	5
I have sufficient information about the processes for communicating across the overall organization	1	2	3	4	5
Lack of Innovative Mechanisms					
The company has online portal that connects all the employees	1	2	3	4	5
The company arranges events that allow for the socialization of the employees	1	2	3	4	5
Low Levels of Internal Branding					
The company allows for the development of career aspirations of the employees	1	2	3	4	5
The company has a sound and satisfactory internal environment	1	2	3	4	5
I am always recognized for my performance and hard work	1	2	3	4	5
Lack of Technology					
The company is well equipped with the modern-day cloud technology					
The company has expertise in the advanced communication software	1	2	3	4	5
The company keeps itself updated on the modern technologies used for internal organisational communication	1	2	3	4	5
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure					
I am provided with market competitive pay rates	1	2	3	4	5
My bonuses are satisfactory and performance based	1	2	3	4	5

Good performance is always recognized through promotions	1	2	3	4	5
--	---	---	---	---	---

Section C: Intra-Organisational Communication

Innovation capability and firm performance					
The company has an exhaustive communication system in place	1	2	3	4	5
All the information is transmitted to all the employees in a timely manner	1	2	3	4	5
The cross functional teams are provided with effective platforms of communications	1	2	3	4	5
Overall I know how to reach each and every relevant member of the company	1	2	3	4	5
We have effective formal as well as informal chains of internal communication	1	2	3	4	5

APPENDIX D

Pilot Testing Results

Reliability Test

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	25	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	25	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.835	37

As can be seen from the above-mentioned table, the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.835. This is indicative of high levels of reliability, showing that the collecting data will generate accurate results. Thereby, ensuring that the regression estimates will be closely similar to the population parameters.

Correlations

		Complexity of Data Analysis	Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	Lack of Innovative Mechanisms	Low Levels of Internal Branding	Lack of Technology	Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	Intra-Organisational Communication
Complexity of Data Analysis	Pearson Correlation	1	.889**	.880**	.841**	.810**	.868**	.878**	.861**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Lack of Focus on Personal Goals	Pearson Correlation	.889**	1	.817**	.700**	.881**	.881**	.771**	.865**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Lack of Focus on Employee Engagement	Pearson Correlation	.880**	.817**	1	.903**	.886**	.812**	.911**	.872**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Lack of Innovative Mechanisms	Pearson Correlation	.841**	.700**	.903**	1	.779**	.627**	.938**	.730**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Low Levels of Internal Branding	Pearson Correlation	.810**	.881**	.886**	.779**	1	.814**	.786**	.812**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Lack of Technology	Pearson Correlation	.868**	.881**	.812**	.627**	.814**	1	.730**	.913**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.001	.000		.000	.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Ineffective Payment and Reward Structure	Pearson Correlation	.878**	.771**	.911**	.938**	.786**	.730**	1	.818**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Intra-Organisational Communication	Pearson Correlation	.861**	.865**	.872**	.730**	.812**	.913**	.818**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

The correlation analysis conducted on the pilot data also indicates that all of the independent variables share a positive and significant correlation with the selected independent variable. In this case, most of the responses were negative, showing that the selected challenges had a negative impact on the overall communication mechanisms of the selected organisation.

Summary of the Pilot Testing

	Yes	No
The questions were well targeted	23	2
The phrasing of the questions was easy to understand	25	0
The questions measured what they aimed at measuring	22	3
The questions were redundant	2	23
The questionnaire was succinct and precise	25	0
The questionnaire kept the convenience of the respondents under consideration	21	4
Unnecessary jargons were used	0	25
The questionnaire had the right number of questions	20	5
There was a right mix of open and closed ended questions	24	1
Right types of scales were used to measure the responses	25	0

As can be seen from the above-mentioned table and graphs, most of the responses generated in the pilot test were positive. This is indicative of the appropriateness of the instrument to measure the research variables. In addition to that, it is also indicative of how well the questionnaire was understood by the respondents and how effectively it kept the convenience of the respondents under consideration.